

HERON (No: 649690): Deliverable D.1.1

LANDSCAPE OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICY PACKAGES IN A MULTI-LEVEL GOVERNMENT SYSTEM

PART OF WORK PACKAGE 1: MAPPING OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICY INSTRUMENTS AND
AVAILABLE TECHNOLOGIES IN BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT

NATIONAL REPORT FOR BELGIUM

SEPTEMBER 2015

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HERON: Forward – looking socio-economic research on Energy Efficiency in EU countries

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649690. The content of this document reflects only the authors' views and the EASME is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Contents

ACRONYMS	6
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	9
1. THE ROLE OF GOVERNANCE AND ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICY PACKAGES ON THE NATIONAL LEVEL	10
1.1 Policy Packages and Policy Governance in Belgium	10
1.1.1 Competences in Belgium	10
1.1.2 Governance framework in Belgium	11
1.1.3 Targets	25
1.2 National Programmes and Initiatives.....	29
1.2.1 Buildings sector	29
1.2.2 Transport sector	34
1.3 Conclusions and Lessons Learned of other Projects about the Performance of the National Policy Packages for Energy Efficiency	37
1.3.1 The lack of a national (or regional) energy efficiency “strategy”	37
1.3.2 The lack of monitoring and evaluation in Belgium.....	40
2. INTERACTION BETWEEN THE NATIONAL AND THE SUB-NATIONAL LEVELS	44
REFERENCES.....	46

List of Figures

Figure 1 Regions, Communities, language areas and provinces of Belgium 10
Figure 2 Organisation of the Flemish Energy Agency (VEA) 15
Figure 3 Section Energy, air, climate and sustainable buildings of Brussels Environment..... 19
Figure 2 Department for Energy and Sustainable Building of DGO4 in Wallonia 22
Figure 5 Primary energy consumption and energy efficiency objective in Belgium. 42

List of Tables

Table 1 Division of energy policy responsibilities in Belgium (simplified)	11
Table 2 Targets and estimate <i>final</i> energy savings in Belgium ^(a) (in GWh)	26
Table 3 Target groups at the Federal level	27
Table 4 Target groups in the Flemish Region	27
Table 5 Target groups in the Walloon Region	28
Table 5 Target groups in the Brussels-Capital Region	28
Table 3 Implementation of the Ecodesign Directive - estimated annual energy savings compared to the baseline for the EU-27 by 2020 (in TWh)	29
Table 4 Achieved and expected final energy savings in GWh of the Flemish Public Service Obligation (PSO) on Distribution System Operators (DSO)	30
Table 5 Achieved and expected final energy savings (in GWh) in the Walloon Region	32
Table 6 Achieved and expected energy savings in GWh in the Brussels-Capital Region	33
Table 7 Achieved and expected energy savings in GWh in the transport sector in the Flemish Region	35
Table 8 Achieved and expected energy savings in GWh in the transport sector in the Walloon Region	36
Table 9 Achieved and expected energy savings in GWh in transport sector in the Brussels-Capital Region	37

ACRONYMS

ANB	Agency for Nature and Forest (Agentschap voor Natuur en Bos)
AEE	Energy Employment Alliance (Alliance Emploi-Environnement)
AWAC	Walloon Air and Climate Agency (Agence wallonne de l'Air et du Climat)
BatEx	Model (“Exemplary”) Building (Bâtiment Exemplaire)
BAU	Business As Usual
BBRI	Belgian Building Research Institute
BGL	Brussels Green Loan
CDM	Clean Development Mechanism
CELINE	Cellule Interrégionale de l’Environnement
CHP	Combined Heat and Power, cogeneration
CO	carbon monoxide
CO ₂	carbon dioxide
COBRACE	Brussels Code for Air, Climate and Energy management (Code Bruxellois de l’air, du climat et de la maîtrise de l’énergie)
CONCERE/ENOVER	Energy Consultation Group (Concertation Etat-Régions pour l’Energie”/Energieoverleg)
DIV	Department for Registration of Vehicles (Dienst Inschrijvingen Voertuigen)
DG	Directorate General
EE	Energy Efficiency
EED	Energy Efficiency Directive (Directive 2012/27/EU)
EP	Energy Performance
EPB	Energy Performane of Buildings
EPBD	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (Directive 2010/31/ZU)
EPC	Energy Performance Certificate
ESD	Energy Services Directive (Directive 2006/32/EC)
ETS	Energy Trading Scheme
EU	European Union
Fedesco	Federal Energy Services Company
FPS	Federal Public Service
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GHG	Greenhouse Gases
GWh	Gigawatt hour
HC	Hydrocarbons

IBGE/BIM	Brussels Environment
IEE	Intelligent Energy Europe
INBO	Research Institute for Nature and Forest (Instituut voor Natuur en Bosonderzoek)
IRCEL/CELINE	Interregional Environmental Agency
IRCEL	Intergewestelijke Cel voor het Leefmilieu
LNE	Environment, Nature and Energy Department (Leefmilieu, Natuur en Energie)
LNG	Liquid Natural Gas
MAM	Maximum Authorised Mass
MEPS	Mandatory Energy Performance Standard
MIVB/STIB	public transport operator of Brussels
MIVB	Maatschappij voor het Intercommunaal Vervoer te Brussel
MMD	Monitoring Mechanism Decision
MMR	Monitoring Mechanism Regulation
Mtoe	Million tons of oil equivalent
MW	Megawatt
NEEAP	National Energy Efficiency Action Plan
NMBS/SNCB	national (Belgian) railway operator
NMBS	Nationale Maatschappij van de Belgische Spoorwegen
NO _x	Nitrogen Oxides
NRP	National Reform Programme
nZEB	nearly Zero-Energy Building
PACE	Air-Climate-Energy Plan (Plan Air Climat Energie)
PAM	Policies And Measures
PEB	Energy Performance of Buildings (performance énergétique des bâtiments)
PM	Particulate Matter
PIT	Personal Income Tax
PIVERT	Green Investments Plan (Plan d'Investissements Verts)
pkm	passenger kilometre
PAEE	Action Plan on Energy Efficiency (Plan d'Action en Efficacité Énergétique)
PACE	Air Climate Energy Plan (Plan Air Climat Energie)
PLAGE	Local Action Plan for the Use of Energy (Plan local d'actions de gestion de l'énergie)
PMR	Persons with Reduced Mobility (Personnes à Mobilité Réduite)
PSO	Public Service Obligations
PV	Photovoltaic

RES	Renewable Energy Sources
R&D	Research & Development
SDRB	Brussels Regional Development Agency (Société de Développement pour la Région de Bruxelles-Capitale)
SLRB	Brussels Regional Housing Authority (Société du Logement de la Région de Bruxelles-Capital)
REHA	Rehabilitation premium for owners (prime à la Réhabilitation en faveur des propriétaires)
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
ReTiBo	Registration Ticket On-board computer
SERV	Flanders Social and Economic Council (Sociaal Economische Raad Vlaanderen)
SISP	Public Service Housing Company
SME	Small and Medium Enterprises
SPW	Walloon Public Service (Service Public de Wallonie)
SRWT	Walloon Regional Transport Company (Société régionale wallonne du Transport)
SWL	Walloon Housing Corporation (Société Wallonne du Logement)
TEC	Walloon public transport operator (Transport En Commun)
TEP	Tradable Emissions Permit
TWh	Terawatt hour
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
URE	Rational Use of Energy (Utilisation Rationnelle de l'Energie)
UREBA	Rational Use of Energy in Public Buildings (Utilisation Rationnelle de l'Énergie dans les Bâtiments publics et Assimilés)
VEA	Flemish Energy Agency (Vlaams Energieagentschap)
VAP	Flemish Adaptation Plan (Vlaams adaptatieplan)
VMP	Flemish Mitigation Plan (Vlaams mitigatieplan)
VITO	Flemish Institute for Technological Research (Vlaame Instelling voor Technologisch Onderzoek)
VMSW	Flemish Association for Social Housing (Vlaamse Maatschappij voor Sociaal Wonen)
VORA	Progress Report (Vooruitgangrapport)
WTCB	Belgian Building Research Institute (Wetenschappelijk & Technisch Centrum voor het Bouwbedrijf)

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

It is impossible to describe the energy efficiency (EE) and climate policies of Belgium, simply because Belgium is not a country in the ordinary sense of the word. EE and climate policies and measures (PAMs) are almost entirely designed and implemented at the level of the three (3) Regions: the Flemish Region, the Walloon Region and the Brussels-Capital Region. The Regions do this independently and without any cooperation to speak of, except perhaps where the Energy Performance of Buildings (EPB) Directive is concerned. After five (5) so-called “state-reforms”, there are few competences left at the Federal Level, mainly product design and standards, and travel by rail (the national railway company NMBS/SNCB is an autonomous Federal company). After the sixth state reform, currently in progress, the Federal Level will become even less relevant.

The cooperation between the Federal Level and the three Regions and in particular between the Regions is such that they cannot even agree to Regional energy savings targets for 2020. In other words, there is an *indicative* (national) energy savings target for Belgium in 2020, but the relative contributions of the Regions are still unknown. Burden-sharing between the Regions to attain the Belgian (national) climate policy target is just as problematic.

Therefore, due to “lack of a country”, D1.1 of WP.1 is for Belgium without object. We give a general overview of the targets and policy packages of the three Regions, and will describe their most relevant policy instruments in more detail in D1.2. Wherever (still) relevant, we dedicate a few words to the policies and measures at the Federal Level.

Whether or not related to the above mentioned complex institutional structure, quantitative and even qualitative evaluations and monitoring of energy and climate policies in Belgium are dismal, certainly at the level of the Regions. That explains why we can show so few quantitative targets and results. The only exception is the Federal Level in the area of climate policies and measures (PAMs).

The remainder of this report is devoted to trying to explain the inane governance of Belgium, which in fact is an unmanageable task, and certainly cannot be summarized in a few words.

1. THE ROLE OF GOVERNANCE AND ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICY PACKAGES ON THE NATIONAL LEVEL

1.1 POLICY PACKAGES AND POLICY GOVERNANCE IN BELGIUM

1.1.1 Competences in Belgium

The Kingdom of Belgium is a federal parliamentary democracy under a constitutional monarchy. Five successive revisions to Belgium's constitution since the 1970s established the country as a unique federal state with political power and competences (areas of responsibility) divided between the federal government, three regions, and three communities. This complex system distributes policy responsibilities, including energy and climate policy, throughout these three levels. Belgium's three regions — Flanders, Wallonia, and Brussels-Capital — are defined on a territorial basis. The regions have powers in fields connected to their land in the widest meaning of the term, including public works and transport, land use and development planning, environmental and water policy, and housing. Belgium's three communities — the Flemish community, the Wallonia-Brussels community, and the German-speaking community — are defined based on concepts of culture and language. Last but not least, Belgium has seven Parliaments, with (sometimes unclear) competences¹.

Figure 1 Regions, Communities, language areas and provinces of Belgium

Source: Wikipedia, retrieved 31.07.2015.

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Communities,_regions_and_language_areas_of_Belgium

Belgium is currently in the process of a new institutional reform (the so-called “sixth state reform”) with large transfers of competences from the federal to the regional level.

Belgium has a complex internal institutional structure and its energy policy commitments are shared by the federal government and the country's three regional governments [Deloitte, 2015, p. 11], with only occasional input from the communities regarding issues of education and public health

¹ “Central government” in Belgium refers to Federal state and the federated entities that are the Brussels-Capital Region, the Walloon Region, the Flemish Region, the French Community and the Germanspeaking Community, the Flemish Community, the Common Community Commission, the French Community Commission and the Flemish Community Commission.

[Schenk, 2008, p. 99]. Each level in Belgium has a distinct set of responsibilities and can operate (semi-)autonomously from the other, which distinguishes Belgium from systems of ‘cooperative’ federalism such as Germany (Happaerts, 2013, p. 8). Also, the federal government cannot impose anything on the subnational governments, and the latter cannot be bound by federal legislation (id., ibid., p. 8). *Energy and climate change policies are foremost a regional competence* which leads to an **unclear division of competences within the regions and between the federal and the regional authorities** [Ecologic, 2014, p. 4]. The division of competences, although divided on a strictly exclusive basis, is **very fragmented** within policy domains, such as energy or climate change policies (Happaerts, 2013, p. 8).

Table 1 Division of energy policy responsibilities in Belgium (simplified)

Federal government	Regional governments
Nuclear	Energy efficiency
Offshore renewables	Renewables except offshore renewables
Security of supply	Non-nuclear energy R&D
Large storage infrastructure	Energy from waste
Energy transmission / transport	Energy distribution

To assess where Belgian policies aiming at improving energy efficiency stand, including in the building and transport sectors, it is essential to recognize that, to a large extent, *these policies are driven by guidelines decided at the EU level* [Estache & Kaufman, 2011, p. 140]. The EU has traditionally had a high normative authority in Belgium, meaning that what the EU says or does is rarely criticised by Belgian politicians (Happaerts, 2013, p. 9).

Belgium stands out among EU members in that it is the only country for which quantitative targets are made at the regional level (Flanders, Wallonia and Brussels-Capital) rather than at the national level. There are de facto four (4) Energy Efficiency Plans in Belgium, a national one and three regional. *“For all practical purposes, the main drivers of Belgium’s contribution to the EU effort to improve energy efficiency are thus designed at the subnational level.”* [Estache & Kaufman, 2011, p. 141]. Consistent with the autonomy given to each region, the types of commitments and the policy instruments adopted vary across plans. The federal government also intervenes in setting standards and financing. Moreover local authorities (municipalities) have taken the initiative to contribute to the promotion of energy efficiency as well, *even if it is not part of their mandate* [id. Ibid, p. 141].

Most energy-climate initiatives are thus undertaken at the regional level. The Federal government has only limited responsibilities for climate change. The Regions matter for climate governance, and they control the main powers that are needed to conduct climate policies (Happaerts, 2013, p. 8). The Regions have each adopted particular energy and climate policy plans or strategies, as well as other specific legislation [Nachmany et al, 2015, p. 3].

1.1.2 Governance framework in Belgium

The federal government and the three regions and the appointed their own bodies to control the reporting and monitoring of the overall energy savings framework and supervision to ensure the exemplary role of the public sector (NEEAP Belgium, 2014).

1.1.2.1 Federal level

1.1.2.1.1 Directorate General of Energy (DG Energy)

The [Federal Public Service \(FPS\) of Economy, S.M.E.'s, Self-employed and Energy](#), more specifically the Directorate General of Energy (DG Energy), is charged with overall control and responsibility for overseeing the framework set up in connection with the implementation of the Directive 2006/32/EC and the Directive 2012/27/EG within the federal government. The DG Energy is also responsible for the coordination of the transposition of the Directive 2012/27/EG and the reporting on the implemented energy efficiency measures. In this context, the DG Energy maintains contacts with the other competent Federal Public Services ([NEEAP Belgium, 2014](#)).

The relevant website is [DG Energy](#) (Dutch) or [DG Energy](#) (French). There are [German](#) and [English](#) versions, but with minimal information.

In terms of energy policy, there is a short (energy) [policy memorandum](#) (in Dutch and French) from the current federal Minister of Energy. The mission of the Directorate General for Energy is described as creating the conditions so that a sustainable energy supply as well as a reliable infrastructure, appliances and products are available to both companies and citizens (p. 7). In terms of energy efficiency, the main competence of DG Energy is *energy labeling*. DG Energy closely monitors the proper implementation of the energy labeling on Belgian territory and actively participates in the negotiations on the revision of the framework directive at European level (p. 9). DG Energy is also responsible for checking the (product) quality of fossil fuels and blended biofuels, although this is less relevant for energy efficiency.

1.1.2.1.2 Directorate General of Environment (DG Environment)

With the reorganization of the federal government and the abolition of the former ministries, the [Federal Public Service Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment](#) (FPS VVVL) was established in 2001. This FPS is composed of several Directorates General (DGs), including [DG Environment](#). Although most of the environmental responsibilities in Belgium are exercised by the regions, there are still a number of tasks reserved for the federal government. The DG Environment retains a number of key competencies. DG Environment has - in addition to an operational service - four thematic services, namely *Multilateral and strategic matters, Marine Environment, Inspection, Climate Change*; and a *Department of Product Management and Chemicals*. A list of what DG environment does is available at their website [What does DG Environment do?](#)

The Department of Product Management and Chemicals and the thematic service Inspection are relevant in terms of energy efficiency for their role in product policy, more in particular *energy labeling* and *Ecodesign*. The DG Environment website provides very little information on these matters. There is a list of control areas [here](#).

The federal thematic service Climate Change is responsible for the federal or national climate policy. Because of the complex internal structure of Belgium, the Belgian climate policy is very complicated. The powers are divided between the federal level and the regions, and there are multiple decision-makers and decision-making processes involved (see also Chapter 2).

The relevant website for the thematic service Climate Change is [www.klimaat.be](#) (Dutch) or [www.climat.be](#) (French). There is no English version.

The communication of information is one of the fundamental commitments of the Parties to the Convention of the United Nations (UNFCCC). The main reporting obligations include the National greenhouse gas inventory (annually); the National Communication; the Biannual report, the Report on demonstrable progress; and the Report for the calculation of the quantity allocated. In particular, [Belgium's first biennial report on Climate Change](#) (2014) and the [6th National Communication](#) of December 2013 (both available in English) contain relevant information on Belgian energy efficiency policies. At the European level the "Monitoring mechanism" also provides a range of reporting requirements. Belgium has set up a number of structures and procedures to meet the above obligations. The National Climate Commission ensures coordination during the preparation of the reports

to facilitate the exchange of information and harmonizing the methods and procedures to the relevant parties (the regions and the federal government). The reports (in Dutch and French) are available on the website of the [National Climate Commission](#). The English version of the website contains minimal information.

1.1.2.1.3 The Belgian Buildings Agency

The Belgian Buildings Agency ([buildingsagency.be](#)) is the real estate specialist of the federal state. It manages approximately 7.5 million square meters spread over some 1,200 buildings that are either owned or leased by the federal government. Its mission includes managing large offices; designing sustainable buildings and maintaining public buildings (courthouses, prisons, etc.).

Fedesco, the federal Energy Services Company (ESCO) will be abolished by the end of 2015 ([press release 17/07/2015](#)), and its responsibilities (and staff) will be transferred to the Belgian Buildings Agency. The existing service “Energy and Sustainable Development” of the Belgian Buildings Agency will thus become responsible for the optimization of the energy performance of the federal public buildings.

1.1.2.1.4 Directorate “Public Enterprises and Rail Policy” (DOS / DEPPF)

The [Federal Public Service Mobility and Transport](#) consists of the Directorate General Maritime Transport; the Directorate General Road Transport and Road Safety; the Directorate-General for Sustainable Mobility and Rail Administration; and the Directorate General Aviation.

In terms of energy (efficiency) policy, it is relevant that rail transport largely remains a federal responsibility. In this context, the Federal Public Service Mobility and Transport has the custody over the Belgian (national) railway company, in particular the [NMBS/SNCB](#) group. The Directorate “Public Enterprises and Rail Policy” (DOS/DEPPF) - formerly known as the Directorate Railway Transport – is one of the three directorates of the Directorate-General for Sustainable Mobility and Rail Administration of the FPS Mobility and Transport. The other two directorates are the Directorate Mobility and the Directorate Intermodal Transport. The official website of the Directorate “Public Enterprises and Rail Policy” is [DOS](#) (Dutch) or [DEPPF](#) (French). There are (outdated) annual reports, but none relevant to energy efficiency policy.

1.1.2.1.5 The national (Belgian) railway company NMBS/SNCB

[NMBS/SNCB](#) is the national (Belgian) railway operator.

The [management contracts 2008-2012](#) of the three companies of the NMBS/SNCB group impose a 3,8% annual growth in the number of passengers transported, to be reached through investments in infrastructure, the strengthening of the transport capacity and the quality of service (enhancing timeliness, safety, accessibility and information to travellers), the further development of an attractive pricing policy, the promotion of combinations between railway and other soft transport modes through specific investments (parking spaces for cars and bicycles with safety cameras, lighting...) and awareness raising campaigns ([VITO & ECONOTEC, 2015, p. 49](#)). The management contracts came to an end by 31/12/2012, and no new management contracts have been signed yet. However, the previous contracts have been extended.

1.1.2.1.6 Department for Registration of Vehicles (DIV)

The DIV is the [Department for Registration of Vehicles](#) of the Federal Public Service Mobility and Transport. The DIV is mostly relevant in relation to the vehicle registration tax, for which the regions are responsible. DIV is also connected to the [“Brussel’Air premium”](#).

1.1.2.1.7 The Federal Public Service Finance

The [FPS Finance](#) is the Federal Public Service (FPS) of Belgium that deals with the finances of the federal government, in particular taxation and treasury. It is responsible to the current federal Minister of Finance.

The FPS Finance website has a page dedicated to the so-called “[green fiscality](#)”. However, in 2015 this page is (nearly) empty, as competences have shifted to the regions. In 2014 (income year 2013), there still was a federal (individual or personal income) tax deduction for expenses (paid in 2013) related to roof insulation for own dwellings. From income year 2014 (i.e. tax year or assessment year 2015), *federal* tax deductions for energy saving measures are no longer relevant. There are a few “transitional systems” for expenses made in earlier years; but these systems will soon end.

With the execution of the Sixth State Reform, a substantial number of federal individual income tax measures have become regional (e.g. the tax reductions for energy saving expenses and renovation expenses for residences in urban development zones or those leased at a moderate rate). The Law of 8 May 2014 modifying the income tax code and introducing the partial regionalisation of personal income tax was published on 28 May 2014 in the Belgian Official Journal ([Dutch](#)) ([French](#)). This law introduces the regionalisation of 25.99% of personal income tax. The regions’ fiscal autonomy increases with a new regional personal income tax surcharge in addition to the federal income tax.

From 2015, as a result of the Sixth State Reform, the tax deductibility for the expenses for energy saving measures; as well as for burglary protection and fire protection systems, and the contributions to the maintenance and renovation of protected monuments and buildings has become a regional responsibility. The regions decided to abolish the tax credit for burglary protection and fire protection systems, but to retain (for now) the tax credit for roof insulation expenses. Due to the (extremely) complex internal workings of the Belgian federal state, the individual or personal income taxes (PIT) are still collected by the Federal Public Service (FPS) Finance, even though from 2015 certain personal income tax credits (e.g. for roof insulation expenses) are set by the regions. The taxation rules after the Sixth State Reform have become gruesomely complex. The tax form of 2015 counts a total of 772 codes, split over 21 pages. It is expected that the complexity of preparing a personal income tax return will continue to increase with the number of additional regional decrees implemented. Personal income tax may thus differ significantly depending on whether the taxpayer resides in Flanders, Wallonia or Brussels. The FPS Finances also has to perform two parallel calculations for every Belgian taxpayer, one federal and one regional.

In 2015 (income year 2014), there was still a federal tax credit for purchases (in 2014) of new motorcycles, tricycles and quadricycles, exclusively powered by an electric motor and suitable for the transport of two persons at least. The tax credit for electric cars had already been abolished in 2014.

Although the annual road tax, the registration tax (for vehicles) and the Eurovignette are a regional competence, the Federal Public Service Finances (still) collects them on behalf of the Brussels-Capital Region. For the Flemish region, we refer to the Flemish Tax Authority; for the Walloon region we refer to the Department of Taxation of Vehicles.

The Federal Public Service Finance, Staff Service Expertise and Strategic Support, published a Tax Survey in 2015 ([Haulotte S., Valenduc Ch. And Deloddere E., 2015](#)).

1.1.2.2 Flemish region

1.1.2.2.1 The Flemish Ministry of Environment, Nature and Energy

For the policy area “Environment, Nature and Energy” the Flemish Ministry of Environment, Nature and Energy was established, consisting of a department with the same name (Environment, Nature and Energy Department) and three autonomous agencies without legal identity:

- The Flemish Energy Agency (VEA);

- The Agency for Nature and Forest ([ANB](#)). ANB is responsible for the sustainable management of nature in Flanders.
- The Research Institute for Nature and Forest ([INBO](#)). INBO is the Flemish research and knowledge centre for nature and its sustainable management and use.

For energy (efficiency) policies only the Environment, Nature and Energy (LNE) department and the Flemish Energy Agency (VEA) are relevant.

The Flemish energy policy memorandum contains the major strategic choices in terms of energy policy of the Flemish Government for the period 2014-2019, and represents the views of the current minister. The memorandum (in Dutch only) is available [here](#).

1.1.2.2.2 The Flemish Energy Agency (VEA)

The Flemish Energy Agency, abbreviated VEA, was founded by the Flemish Government Decree of 16 April 2004. VEA is an internal autonomous agency without legal identity of the Flemish Ministry of Environment, Nature and Energy. The VEA has been operational since 1 April 2006. In order to bring all executive decisions on energy together in a single act, the above-mentioned decree of April 16, 2004 was dissolved and integrated into the [Energy Decree of 19 November 2010](#).² This latter decision came into effect on January 1, 2011.

Figure 2 Organisation of the Flemish Energy Agency (VEA)

The Flemish Energy Agency's mission is to implement a sustainable energy policy by means of implementing policy instruments in a cost-effective and qualitative manner. Tasks include:

- Promoting the rational use of energy and managing the appropriate resources and funds;
- Promoting environmentally friendly energy production and managing the appropriate resources and funds;
- Executing awareness and communication actions on environmentally friendly energy production and rational use of energy;
- Implementing regulation in relation to management and expansion of the distribution of electricity, gas and heat;
- Research in support of (energy) policy implementation. This may also be outsourced (e.g. to universities or research institutes);
- Processing information acquired from the policy implementation with the aim of supplying the department (LNE) with policy-based inputs;
- Contributing to the implementation of the Flemish climate policy plan.

The VEA is also partner of [ManagEnergy](#), where the following areas of expertise are mentioned: energy efficiency in buildings, subsidies to promote energy efficiency, energy labelling of buildings,

² Oddly, the Belgian (federal) NEEAP 2014 does not seem to be aware of this fact, and only mentions the Decree of 16 April 2004.

changing citizens's behaviour, dissemination of information, promotion of technology (solar energy, wind energy, CHP, insulation), promotion campaigns on the rational use of energy and sustainable energy.

The VEA is headquartered in Brussels and has subsidiaries in Hasselt and Ghent. The VEA currently employs 67 staff. The VEA is structured into six cells (see organisation chart).

The official website of the VEA is www.energiesparen.be. Relevant documents (only available in Dutch) on the internal workings of VEA are the annual reports (e.g. [annual report 2014](#)) and the business plans (e.g. [business plan 2015](#)), downloadable at the [VEA website](#).

The VEA website www.energiesparen.be is the official portal of everything related to energy efficiency (savings) and renewable energy sources in Flanders. The website has a [tab](#) dedicated to (Flemish) energy policy, including energy-efficiency. Extensive information is available on the energy performance of buildings ([EPB](#)); the energy performance certificates (EPC) for [residential](#) and [public](#) buildings; the [energy efficiency directive](#); the “[Energy Renovation Programme 2020](#)”; nearly Zero Energy Buildings ([BEN](#)); and on energy efficiency policies [for companies](#). Next to energy efficiency, information is also provided on “[green energy and CHP](#)”, as well as on the “[public service obligations](#)”. There are simply too many documents to list them all, and they are only available in Dutch. The “[Third Flemish Energy Efficiency Action Plan](#)” [[NEEAP Flanders 2014](#)] is available in English from the [EU website](#).

1.1.2.2.3 The Environment, Nature and Energy (LNE) department

The Environment, Nature and Energy (LNE) Department is responsible for planning and evaluating the Flemish environmental policy in compliance with economic and social demands. LNE is also responsible for the co-ordination of all environmental actors as well as the implementation and enforcement of the environmental legislation in Flanders.

The most relevant department of LNE in terms of energy efficiency is the Air, Nuisance, Risk Management, Environment and Health department, in particular the service “[Climate](#)”. This LNE service is responsible for the theme “Climate Change”. Flanders tries to meet its Kyoto targets with the implementation of the [Flemish Climate Plan 2013-2020](#), approved by the Flemish Government on June 28, 2013. This plan consists of two sub-plans: the Flemish Mitigation [Plan](#) (VMP) to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, and the Flemish Adaptation Plan ([VAP](#)) to mitigate the effects of climate change in Flanders. Those plans are made available by LNE [here](#), but only in Dutch. The Flemish Mitigation Plan describes a large number of measures which are also related to energy efficiency (although the targets are only given in terms of CO₂-eq. reductions), including measures for the buildings and transport sectors. The Progress Report 2012 ([VORA12](#)) (in Dutch) of the Flemish Climate Policy Plan 2006-2012 was communicated to the Flemish Government on October 24th, 2014.

LNE has an English version of its website, but with a minimum of information <http://www.lne.be/en>. All information on the Flemish Climate Plan 2013-2020 is available from the [Climate Change theme](#) at the LNE website. All documents are in Dutch, with the exception of two obsolete documents related to the former Flemish Climate Policy Plan 2006-2012, namely the [Climate Policy Plan 2006-2012](#) and the Flemish Climate Policy Plan - [Progress Report](#) (May 2009) which gives an account of the state of affairs on the 8th of May 2009.

1.1.2.2.4 The Housing Agency-Flanders

The policy domain “[Planning, Housing Policy and Heritage](#)” is an administrative service of the Flemish government. The [Housing Agency - Flanders](#) is one of its underlying entities. It consists of a staff service; and three departments: the department of Financial Instruments, the department of Housing policy, and the Housing department.

The Housing Agency-Flanders is responsible for the implementation of an integrated housing policy in Flanders, with a view to affordable and good quality housing for everyone. The Housing Agency – Flanders does so by providing financial incentives to individuals; ensuring that the living standards are respected; encouraging, promoting and supporting a local housing policy; advising social housing projects and municipal spatial plans; monitoring the approved rental services, social rental and tenant organizations; monitoring of terminated systems, such as miners loans, rent compensation, alternative financing and the urgency plan; monitoring of social loans and guaranteed dwelling insurance; encouraging affordable housing, even in the private rental market; and formulating proposals to improve housing policy from field experience.

The Housing Agency – Flanders, more in particular the Housing department, is responsible for the [home improvement grant](#). Improvements include renovation work carried out on the dwelling (e.g. roof, façade, windows, heating system and humidity control).

1.1.2.2.5 The Facility Company (“Het Facilitair Bedrijf”)

Concerning the [exemplary role of the Flemish government buildings](#), the Flemish Government adopted the following decisions. All entities of the Flemish government must supply the “property database” of the ‘Facility Company’ with the following information: the total useful floor area (regardless of whether or not the area is heated and/or cooled); the energy performance; and other useful data on energy. On the basis of this information, it is decided whether it is necessary to impose additional obligations or not. For renovation works, the entities must always comply with the (energy performance) standards that are applicable to renovations which require a (building) permit, even for those (small) renovations that legally do not require a permit. All entities are also required to report annually on the implemented and planned energy-saving activities and compliance with the energy performance requirements.

The “property database” is managed by the “Facility Company” ([facilpunt.be](#)). But although it is the Facility Company that offers professional support to the entities of the Flemish Government; it is the Flemish Energy Agency (VEA, cells energy performance regulations and energy performance certification) that oversees compliance with the energy performance requirements. In other words, the entities report to the VEA, and the VEA decides whether additional obligations have to be imposed.

1.1.2.2.6 The Mobility and Road Safety Policy Department

The [Department of Mobility and Public Works](#) has more than 900 staff in 13 departments. There are four types of units:

- The policy departments (General Affairs and Mobility and Road Safety Policy, Ports and Water and Airport Policy);
- The technical support services (Expertise Concrete and Steel, Geotechnical, General Technical Support, Hydraulics Research and Communications Center);
- One executive department (Maritime Access)
- The management support departments (Human Resources, Budget and Accounting and Legal Services).

A complete list of competences and which unit or department is responsible for what is available on a dedicated webpage ([departement-mow.vlaanderen.be/afdelingen/bevoegdheden](#)).

In terms of energy (efficiency) policy, the most important department is the [Mobility and Road Safety Policy department](#). The department prepares the mobility policy for freight and passenger transport as well as for road safety. The department refers to a number of its most relevant websites. The [hot-line bicycle path](#) allows reporting bottlenecks (“abnormal situations”) for cyclists to the relevant road authorities in Flanders. The website [Mobile Flanders](#) contains all possible information about traffic, transport and public works in Flanders, Belgium and Europe. The website [Mobile Flanders for local](#)

[authorities](#) provides information specifically aimed at local authorities. The website [Commuter Fund](#) refers to the Commuter Fund policy instrument, that aims to promote sustainable commuting in Flanders. The website "[Just bigger](#)" refers to trucks or heavy duty vehicles, and gives hints to truckers plus information on mirror adjustments sites, as well as references to information campaigns. There is also a [traffic signs database](#), and the "[Toepark](#)" website showing reserved parking spaces for the disabled near a destination as well as directions to the selected parking.

The official website of the Mobility and Road Safety Policy Department is [mobielvlaanderen.be](#), which acts as a portal website for everything related to mobility in Flanders. Extensive information on Flemish mobility policy (in Dutch only) is provided at the Mobile Flanders website, in particular [here](#). It contains – amongst others – the [Policy memorandum Mobility and Public Works 2014-2019](#) that represents the views of the current Flemish minister of Mobility and Public Works; the [road safety plan](#) (2008); and the [Commuter plan](#) (2005). The Mobility plan Flanders is still **work in progress**, and a final version is not expected before 2016. Information on the public inquiry of the Mobility plan Flanders is available at a dedicated website, [www.mobiliteitsplanvlaanderen.be](#). The site contains documents on the results of the mobility survey in 2011; advice from consultative bodies; a [draft version](#) (350 pp) of the mobility plan; and a [brochure](#). In the draft version of the Mobility plan, paragraph 4.1.5.3 Energy-efficiency is dedicated to energy efficiency of vehicles (p. 137-138); paragraph 6.1.2.1 Efficiency of transport deals with transport efficiency (p. 226-228); and paragraph 6.1.2.2 Modal choice elaborates on modal choice (p. 228-231). None of this means much in terms of concrete policy instruments.

1.1.2.2.7 The Flemish transport company De Lijn

The Flemish transport company [De Lijn](#) (in English: "The Line") is a public association with legal personality run by the Flemish government to provide public transport in Flanders. The "[Decree of 31 July 1990 setting up the Flemish Transport Company \(VMM\)](#)" regulates the foundation, the structure, the capital, the governing body, the operation, the control, the budget and the entry into force of the VMM. On 31 December 1990 the VMM merged with three other transport companies in Flanders and was renamed "De Lijn". From 1 January 1991, De Lijn has the monopoly of urban and regional public transport (tram, bus, premetro) in Flanders.

The [management contract](#) 1/1/2011-31/12/2015 with De Lijn can be downloaded [here](#). One of the annexes in the management contract 2011-2015 covers a [memorandum](#) which describes the intentions and targets of De Lijn in the area of "green transport in 2015". Paramount are the reduction of the emissions of its vehicles.

1.1.2.2.8 The Flanders Social and Economic Council (SERV)

In the Flanders Social and Economic Council ([SERV](#)), Flemish employers and employees discuss and consult about issues falling within the scope of Flemish authority. SERV is made up of ten representatives of employers' organisations; and ten representatives of employees' organisations. A [brochure](#) (in English) introducing SERV can be downloaded at the SERV website.

SERV is mentioned here mainly because it plays an important role in the steering committee of the [Commuter Fund](#).

1.1.2.2.9 The Flemish Tax Authority

The [Flemish Tax Authority](#) is responsible to the current Flemish Minister for the Budget, Finance and Energy. The Flemish Tax Authority implements the Flemish taxation policy. It is responsible for the collection and recovery of Flemish taxes; the exercise of tax audits; the recovery of tax claims; the collection of fees and special (sector) contributions; the delivery of policy-oriented inputs to the [Department of Finance and Budget](#); and the issuing of certificates for tax exemptions and reductions. It consists of five (5) departments: client management; coordination of taxation; collection and regulations; dossier handling; and real estate transactions.

The Flemish Tax Authority automatically assigns [property tax reductions](#) for newly built energy efficient residential and non-residential buildings. The property tax reductions are decided by the Flemish Government.

Since January 1, 2011, the Flemish Tax Authority collects a number of transport related taxes in Flanders. The [annual road tax](#) is payable for vehicles used for the transport of persons or freight on public roads. The [registration tax](#) (BIV) applies to each entry into service of a car, aircraft or craft. It also applies to second-hand vehicles that are registered by the new owner for the first time. The [Eurovignette](#) is a charge for road use by trucks of minimum 12 tons.

1.1.2.3 Brussels-Capital region

A word in advance. All relevant detailed information is only available in Dutch or French. However, there is a website, Brussels Sustainable City ([sustainablecity.be](#)), which does provide some information in English. The site [themas/sustainable-building](#) gives an overview of policy measures for the building sector; and [themas/mobility](#) for the transport sector.

1.1.2.3.1 Brussels Environment

Brussels Environment, before 2006 and until today also known as “the Brussels Institute for Environmental Management (IBGE-BIM)” has expertise in environment and energy of the Brussels-Capital Region. The [NEEAP \(2014\)](#) for Belgium describes the IBGE-BIM³ as a public interest organization Class A instituted by the [Royal Decree of 8 March 1989](#). One of the initial missions of the Brussels Institute for Environmental Management, specified in the Royal Decree, is to study the application and implementation of the rules of the European Union on the environment. A skill of the Brussels Institute in the field of energy includes ([Decree of January 20, 1994 - 21/04/94 MB](#)) the rational use of energy (RUE) ([NEEAP Belgium, 2014](#)). The [Belgian Earth Observation Platform](#) describes the Brussels Institute for Management of the Environment, or IBGE-BIM, as the environmental and energy watchdog of the Brussels Capital Region. Since 1989, the Belgian regions have had authority over such important matters as the economy, employment, public works, transport, urban planning and the environment. IBGE-BIM was created in 1989 to be the spokesman of the people of Brussels for everything relating to their “living environment”. IBGE-BIM acts, from the regulatory standpoint, as a research, planning, advisory and information body, as well as an issuer of permits, and a surveillance and control agency. From the sectoral standpoint, it has authority in the areas of waste, air quality, noise, parks and forests, water, soil and energy.

Figure 3 Section Energy, air, climate and sustainable buildings of Brussels Environment

We reproduce the most relevant part of the Brussels Environment [organisation chart](#), namely the Section of Energy, air, climate and sustainable buildings.

³ The Belgian NEEAP (2014) does not mention the name “Brussels Environment”, although this (new) name was already introduced in 2006.

The subsection Promotion of sustainable buildings includes a department for the assistance of private persons; a department for the assistance of (building) professionals; and a department for energy subsidies (or “energy premiums”). The subsection Planning Energy, Air & Climate and stimulation of buildings consists of a department for the technical stimulation of sustainable buildings; a department for the economic stimulation of sustainable buildings; and a department for planning energy, air and climate. Finally, the subsection Energy Performance of Buildings (EPB) consists of a department EPB works; a department EPB calculation methods and instruments; a department EPB certificates; and a department EPB heating and air-conditioning.

Annual reports of Brussels Environment, e.g. the Annual Report (2014) are available in ([Dutch](#)) or ([French](#)).

The official website of Brussels Environment is www.ibgebim.be (only in Dutch or French).

The “Energy” theme on the website contains a lot of relevant information on energy efficiency policy in the Brussels-Capital region, albeit only in Dutch or French. There is information on financial incentives (“[energy premiums and support](#)”) including the Brussels “[green loan](#)” and other support such as the “[facilitator sustainable buildings](#)”; on the energy performance of buildings, including the energy performance certificate ([EPB](#)); on the Local Action Plan for the Use of Energy ([PLAGE](#)); and on the “Energy House” ([Energy house](#)).

1.1.2.3.2 The Energy House

The Energy House offers all citizens of Brussels free of charge coaching (dissemination of information, home visits, assistance in making decisions, realization of small interventions, and assistance in finding the necessary funding) by a team of (energy) experts. The Energy House is an initiative of the Brussels Capital Region. It consists of a coordination structure which is housed at Brussels Environment and local offices that provide the field work and are responsible for direct contact with the households within the region. Brussels Environment coordinates the assignments of the Energy House and is responsible for the framework, the funding (through subsidies) and the overall organization of the local branches. The local branches are themselves independent and separately managed associations. The six existing associations are active in each one of the six geographical areas in which the Brussels-Capital Region is divided and cover all 19 municipalities.

The Energy House has a dedicated website, <http://www.maisonenergiehuis.be> (Dutch and French only).

1.1.2.3.3 Other actors in the buildings sector (Citydev.brussels and SLRB)

In the area of construction and renovation of housing and eco-construction, Brussels Environment cooperates regularly with the Citydev.brussels (formerly known as the Brussels Regional Housing Authority SLRB) and the Brussels Regional Development Agency (SDRB).

[Citydev.brussels](#) is the new name of what was until recently known as the Brussels Regional Development Agency (SDRB). Citydev.brussels is the regional [public institution](#) active in the area of economic expansion and urban renovation. It constructs in a public-private partnership housing for residents with moderate incomes in neighbourhoods characterised by a shortage of residential constructions. The energy performance (EP) of new construction has to comply with the passive standard; and the EP of renovation with very low energy standards. SDRB also implements ecological criteria concerning e.g. water management or the selection of materials.

The Brussels Regional Housing Authority ([SLRB](#)) is in charge of low-cost housing. The local companies, called Public Service Housing Companies (SISP), are under its supervision. The SLRB has made sustainable development a priority of its 2010–2014 strategic plan. Since 2010, all SLRB projects strive to be exemplary with regard to energy. All new construction must comply at a minimum with the pas-

sive standard, and any major renovation with a very low energy standard. The SLRB also works on an “energy cadastre” of its assets to improve their management and maintenance over the years.

1.1.2.3.4 Brussels Mobility – Policy Directorate

[Brussels Mobility](#) is one of six administrations of the Ministry of the Brussels-Capital Region⁴. The other five administrations are Local Authorities⁵; Finances and Budget; Taxation; Urban Development; and Economy and Employment. The general secretariat “Brussels Regional Coordination” acts as the link between the administration and the Regional Government.

Brussels Mobility is the administration of the Brussels-Capital Region responsible for equipment, infrastructure and mobility issues. Brussels Mobility defines the mobility strategies of the Brussels-Capital Region; and manages development projects, the renewal and maintenance of public spaces and regional roads, as well as transport infrastructure and taxis. In doing so, it fulfils essential tasks to protect the quality of life and sustainable development in the region, sometimes in partnership with other bodies.

Brussels Mobility is split into ten (10) directorates, and one “Mobility Centre” which manages traffic flows in the Brussels-Capital Region in real time 24/7. In terms of energy (efficiency) policy, the most relevant directorate is the [Policy Directorate](#). The Policy Directorate defines and proposes the main strategic options. It draws up proposals for sustainable mobility in which the various modes of transport play a role, and organizes awareness campaigns and training for schools, businesses and citizens (such as “Car Free Sunday”, the “[Satchel Action](#)”, “[To Work Without a Car](#)”, and many other initiatives. This Directorate is also responsible for monitoring the implementation and application of the transport plan Iris 2, the Bicycle Plan, the Pedestrian Plan, the Freight Transport Plan, the Road Safety Plan and the Parking Policy Plan.

The official website of Brussels Mobility is mobielbrussel.irisnet.be (Dutch); or bruxellesmobilitate.irisnet.be (French), which acts as the portal website for everything related to mobility in the Brussels-Capital Region. The website also contains extensive information (in Dutch or French only) on the transport [Iris 2 Plan](#), the [Bicycle Plan](#), the [Pedestrian Plan](#), the [Freight Transport Plan](#), the [Road Safety Plan](#) and the [Parking Policy Plan](#). All these plans can be downloaded, but are available in Dutch or French only. The most important plan is the [Iris 2-mobiliteitsplan](#) (2011) (146 pp) (Dutch) or [Plan Iris 2](#) (French).

There is also a link to the [Municipal Mobility Policy Plans](#). Each municipality in the Brussels-Capital Region has its own Mobility Plan that explains in detail the mobility component of the Municipal Development Plan and takes into account the Iris 2 plan.

As far as policy instruments are concerned, the most relevant information concerns the “[Company Travel Plan](#)” which consists of the study, implementation, evaluation and updating of the actions undertaken by one or more enterprises to manage in a sustainable manner all transport movements associated with their business. Another relevant policy instrument is the “[Brussel’Air premium](#)” (“Bruxell’air Bonus”), granted to residents who decide to turn in their licence plate and switch to other, less polluting, means of transport.

1.1.2.3.5 The Society for Intercommunal Transport in Brussels (MIVB / STIB)

The [Society for Intercommunal Transport in Brussels](#) (MIVB / STIB) is a [public entity](#) responsible by [ordinance of November 22, 1990](#) with the operation of the public transportation system in the Brussels Capital Region.

⁴ The Brussels-Capital Region only has one Ministry.

⁵ The Brussels-Capital Region consists of 19 municipalities, where each municipality is responsible for handling local duties, such as the upkeep of roads within its borders.

A management contract links the MIVB / STIB with her supervisory authority, the Brussels Capital Region. This agreement defines the tasks and obligations of the parties with the common goal of ensuring the sustainability of a quality transport system serving the customer. The Board of Directors of the MIVB / STIB is in charge of monitoring the proper implementation of the management contract.

1.1.2.4 Walloon region

1.1.2.4.1 Department for Energy and Sustainable Building

The [Operational Directorate General \(DGO4\) for Spatial Planning, Housing, Heritage and Energy](#) has four departments:

- Department of Planning and Urban Development.
- Department of Housing.
- Department of Heritage.
- Department of Energy and Sustainable Building.

A complete organisation chart of DGO4 is available [at the website of DGO4](#). We only reproduce the most relevant part, namely the Department for Energy and Sustainable Building.

Figure 4 Department for Energy and Sustainable Building of DGO4 in Wallonia

In terms of energy efficiency policy, the most relevant is the Department for Energy and Sustainable Building. The Department for Energy and Sustainable Building from the Operational Directorate General (DGO4) for Spatial Planning, Housing, Heritage and Energy of the Walloon Public Service is the department of the Walloon administration in charge of implementing the competencies allocated to Wallonia with regard to energy matters according to the [Special Law for Institutional Reform dated August 8th 1980](#) (art 6, VII) (NEEAP Belgium, 2014).

The Department for Energy and Sustainable Building aims to reduce energy consumption, promote the use of renewable energy sources (RES) and to ensure the proper organization of the energy market in Wallonia. The Department participates in the definition and development of policies in these matters and coordinates actions to encourage best practices, both in the residential sector (with a particular focus on youngsters), in industry and in the services sectors, including in the public sector. Support for research and development (R&D) and innovation also aims to reduce energy consumption and to develop cost-effective energy sources. The Department ensures the proper organization of the regional energy markets by drafting and implementing legislative acts, but also by contributing to the implementation of social measures for the benefit of the customers in the regional energy markets.

The department has three branches:

- Sustainable Building
- Management of Promotion of sustainable energy
- The direction of the Organization of regional markets of energy.

The official website of the Department for Energy and Sustainable Building is energie.wallonie.be, which acts as a portal website ("Portail de l'Énergie") for everything related to energy (efficiency) in Wallonia; and very similar to energiesparen.be in Flanders or ibgebim.be in the Brussels-Capital Region. Part of the site is dedicated to private persons, and contains extensive information on policy instruments to stimulate energy savings. The most relevant information in this area concerns application of the energy performance for buildings regulations ([PEB](#)); on financial incentives and other support, including the "[Primes Énergie](#)", "[tax certificates](#)" for low energy, passive or zero-energy buildings to be used in the framework of fiscal reductions; obtaining a "[loan](#)" from the Walloon region; or [aid specifically targeted at low-income households](#).

There is also information on the "Walloon Energy Desks" or rather "[Guichets Énergie Wallonie](#)". The Energy Desks are 16 locations spread over the Walloon Region, where a team of in total 40 consultants welcome and guide the Walloon citizens with everything related to energy in the home. The consultants are experts in the service of the Walloon Region (Department for Energy and Sustainable Building). They provide personalized technical advice, free of charge, and they also inform citizens on the regulations in force and the financial and other support available in Wallonia.

Another part of the site is dedicated to [tertiary buildings and collective housings](#), again with relevant and extensive information on policy instruments, such as the energy performance of buildings ([PEB](#)); financial and other support including "[Primes Énergie](#)" and the "[UREBA](#)" subsidies (which are aimed specifically at non-commercial services); and the "[URE](#)" facilitators (where "URE" stands for rational use of energy").

1.1.2.4.2 Walloon Housing Corporation (SWL)

The Walloon Housing Corporation or "Société Wallonne du Logement" ([SWL](#)) is a public interest organisation and the main institutional operator of the public social housing policy in Wallonia. It ensures, on behalf of the Walloon Government, guardianship of and provides advice and assistance to 64 public social housing societies. It coordinates the development and rental management of 101,000 social dwellings.

SWL is involved in the Green Investments Plan (PIVERT), related to the thermal renovation of social dwellings in Wallonia. The second installment of the program ([PIVERT2](#)) focuses on innovative and sustainable renovation work. The energy performance target is an annual energy consumption of maximum 90 kWh/m².

1.1.2.4.3 Walloon Air and Climate Agency (AWAC)

The Walloon Air and Climate Agency (AWAC) is an independent public service established by the [Decree of 5 March 2008 on the constitution of the Walloon Air and Climate Agency](#) and the [Order of the Walloon Government of 3 July 2008 on the organization of the Walloon air and climate agency](#). The Agency was created in 2008 from the Air Unit of the former General Directorate of Natural Resources and Environment (DGRNE), now the [Public Service of the Walloon region - Operational Directorate-General \(DGO3\) for Natural Resources and the Environment](#). There remains a close link between the Agency and the DGO3, due to the cross-participation of leading officials in decision-making bodies. The number of staff members of AWAC is about thirty. AWAC is located in Jambes since November 2011.

The Agency represents the Walloon Region at the national level and in international organizations in all matters related to air and climate. AWAC coordinates the monitoring of the negotiations, trans-

poses decisions in the Walloon legislation and ensures their implementation. It prepares, on behalf of the Walloon Region, in collaboration with the Walloon Government and the departments of the Walloon Public Service (SPW), the overall strategy for improving air quality, climate change abatement and protection of the ozone layer.

The official website of the Air and Climate Agency is www.awac.be. In terms of energy (efficiency), the most relevant information concerns the so-called “Air Climate Energy Plan” or in French “Plan Air Climat Energie”, abbreviated [PACE](#). However, **work on this plan is still in progress**. There is some information on the former “[Walloon Plan of Air and Climate 2008-2012](#)”. Documents (in French only) of the former plan can be downloaded, [here](#), [here](#) and [here](#). They contain descriptions of a number of measures, including energy efficiency in both the buildings and transport sectors.

1.1.2.4.4 Directorate of Mobility Planning

The [Operational Directorate General for Mobility and Waterways](#) (DGO2) initiates and coordinates all policies related to transport (road, rail, air and water) and mobility in the Walloon region. DGO2 has – amongst others – a Waterways Management Directorate; three Waterways Departments (one for each of the three main basins in Wallonia); a Department of Transportation Operations; and a Department of Mobility Strategy.

The [Department of Mobility Strategy](#) consists of the Directorate for Certification and Homologation; the Directorate of Mobility Planning; the Directorate of Transport Regulations; the Directorate of Environmental and Economic Impacts; and the Directorate for the Promotion of Waterways and Inter-modal transport.

In terms of energy (efficiency) policy, the most relevant department is the Directorate of Mobility Planning. The department develops and implements planning tools and incentives in function of a coherent and effective mobility management for the Walloon region. Planning tools include (municipal, urban and provincial) mobility plans with the intent of organizing multimodal accessibility; school surveys to diagnose student behavior in terms of mobility; and corporate travel plans designed to optimize travel related to the activities of one or more businesses. The department ensures the implementation of the results of mobility studies and grants so-called “pulse credits” to municipalities for creating amenities for pedestrians, cyclists and PMRs (“Personnes à Mobilité Réduite”, i.e. persons with reduced mobility).⁶ The Directorate is responsible for the training of “Mobility Advisors” and manages a documentation center on mobility. Finally, it coordinates cycling policy and supports projects to promote cycling, including awareness campaigns such as the Mobility Week which takes place every year from September 16 to 22.

The official website of the Directorate of Mobility Planning is the Mobility portal or “Portail de la mobilité” (mobilite.wallonie.be), which acts as a portal website for everything related to mobility in Wallonia. The site contains some information on the Walloon [Mobility policy](#); the [Walloon Rail policy](#); the [Wallonia Bicycle Plan](#); and “[Rural mobility](#)”. The information is fairly limited. There is a reference to the chapter on Mobility of the Walloon regional policy statement “[OSER, INNOVER, RASSEMBLER 2014-2019](#)”. More importantly, it does have a dedicated [page](#) that allows the visitor to search for the mobility plans of the different cities and municipalities; the school and business travel plans; and the “pulse credits”.

1.1.2.4.5 The Walloon Regional Transport Company (SRWT) and TEC

The [Walloon Regional Transport Company](#) (SRWT) was established as a [legal entity of public law](#) in 1989 following the transfer of mobility competences to the regions. The goals of SRWT are the study, design, promotion and coordination of public transport services. It proposes to the Walloon government the tariff structures applicable to public (passenger) transport; as well as the regional allocation

⁶ The “pulse credits” plans or “crédits d’impulsion” in French are also called “plan Escargot”, where Escargot is an (edible) snail.

of subsidies to the (public transport) operating companies. SRWT defines the commercial (public transport) policy of the Walloon government. It realizes the investment programs adopted by the Walloon government. SWRT coordinates the actions of the operating companies, including orders and bulk purchases of rolling stock and equipment (as well as financing those actions); actions to promote the creation of services common to all operating companies; harmonizing the individual and collective labour relations of said operating companies; and settling disputes between the operating companies. SRWT is also responsible for the relations with the national (Belgian) railway operator NMBS/SNCB and with international public transport organisations.

SWRT consists of seven (7) directorates, Study-Safety-Services; Finances, IT, Technical Services, General Services, Sustainable Mobility and Internal Audit. In terms of energy efficiency (policy), the most relevant directorate is the Directorate of Sustainable Mobility.

SWRT also comprises the five (5) different Public Transport Companies, abbreviated TEC (“sociétés de Transport en commun”). TEC are associations of public law whose acts are deemed commercial. TEC or "Transport En Commun" thus refers to the 5 public transport companies active on the territory of the Walloon Region: TEC Walloon Brabant, TEC Charleroi, TEC Hainaut, TEC Liege-Verviers and TEC Namur-Luxembourg. These five entities are headed by the parent company: the Walloon Regional Transport Company (SRWT), responsible for the strategic and commercial management.

The Walloon government is currently (september 2015) considering a “rationalization” (merging) of the SRWT and the five TECs.

1.1.2.4.6 The Department of Taxation of Vehicles

The [Operational Directorate General \(DGO7\) of Taxation](#) of the Walloon Public Service is responsible to the current Walloon Minister of Budget, Public Service and Administrative Simplification.

The [Department of Taxation of Vehicles](#) of the Operational Directorate General (DGO7) of Taxation is responsible for the [annual road tax](#), the [registration tax](#) and the [Eurovignette](#).

1.1.3 Targets

1.1.3.1 EU 2020 targets for Belgium

As stated earlier, **Belgium’s energy and climate policy design is strongly influenced by EU objectives** [ENTRACTE, 2012, p. 24]. The energy and climate change topic of the Europe 2020 strategy encompasses the following three targets for Belgium [NRP, 2015]:

- (1) an indicative target of reducing primary energy consumption by 18% compared to the projected gross inland energy consumption (excluding non-energy uses) for 2020;
- (2) a 15% reduction in greenhouse gas emissions by 2020 compared to 2005 in sectors not covered by the EU Emission Trading System (i.e. non-ETS sectors), according to a linear declining emission reduction programme between 2013 and 2020. For the 2013-2020 period, Europe only imposes a Belgian objective for the non-ETS sectors and no longer for the ETS emissions;
- (3) a 13% share of gross final energy consumption from renewable energy sources by 2020.

Since 2013, Belgium’s 2020 energy efficiency target is 43.7 Mtoe expressed in primary energy consumption, or 32.5 Mtoe expressed in final energy consumption. [NEEAP, 2014, p. 9][Towards an Energy Union Belgium, 2015, p. 6] [Nachmany et al, 2015, p. 4]. The overall targeted primary energy savings fostered by existing and planned policies amount to 9.6 Mtoe by 2020 (calculated as the dif-

ference between projected gross inland consumption in 2010, without and with energy savings measures [NEEAP, 2014, p. 9] [Deloitte, 2014, p. 14].

Table 2 Targets and estimate final energy savings in Belgium^(a) (in GWh)

	Wallonia		Brussels		Flanders	
	Target	Results	Target	Results	Target	Results
2012 (realized)	4 643	5 385	..	851	..	16 499
2016 (expected)	8 358	9 076	2 199	2 465	16 959	27 416
2020 (expected)	^(b)	12 014	^(b)	4 617	^(b)	36 044

^(a) The Federal Government did not state any targets or results in the NEEAP

^(b) The distribution between the Federal Level and the Regions of energy-climate targets and the corresponding opportunities is still being discussed.

Source [NEEAP Belgium, 2014]

The Flemish Region achieved savings of 16 499 GWh final in the non-TEP sectors in 2012, an increase of 52% on the savings achieved in 2010. The new calculations show that the final savings expected at the end of 2016 are 162% of the final target. The estimated savings in 2016 given in the first action plan (2007) were only 107% of the target and the expected savings in the second action plan (2011) were 148% of the target. The most recent study of potential dates from 2009, so a number of parameters are out of date. A thorough, new study of potential will be carried out by the end of 2015 [NEEAP, 2014, p. 9]. The Walloon Region expects final energy savings to be 109% of the target in 2016. The Brussels-Capital Region expects final energy savings to be 120% of the target in 2016.

The intra-Belgian burden sharing concerning the climate and energy package is not yet decided [NRP, 2015, p. 18]. Since 2013 the National Climate Commission has been engaged in extending the National Climate Plan (2009-2012) until 2020, but the process has been slowed down by the lack of agreement among the Regions and the Federal Level on burden-sharing of non-ETS targets for 2013–2020 and determination of the share of renewables per region [Nachmany et al, 2015, p3]. In 2015 a climate responsibility mechanism among regions has started. *The mechanism consists in determining a multiannual reference trajectory for the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions for each region until 2030 for the residential and tertiary building sector (excluding industrial buildings).* [Towards an Energy Union Belgium, 2015 p. 11].

Belgium has not yet established a strategy for energy and climate covering the post-2020 period. In 2012 the federal government published a long term policy vision on sustainable development, covering *improved energy efficiency; greater accessibility of energy services; greenhouse gas emission reduction by 80-95% by 2050 compared to 1990; decarbonisation of electricity; increased share of renewable energies and increased energy security.* Strategies in the different regions focus on achieving the 2020 targets, while also referring to the 2050 long-term objectives. *“The federal government plans to establish an ‘energy pact’, underpinned by a common energy vision with the regions. The overarching goal of the pact would be to guarantee the supply of clean and affordable energy for the next 20-25 years.”* [Towards an Energy Union Belgium, 2015 p. 11]

The policy packages defined at or approved at the different levels may help achieve several objectives. This is particularly so with regard to improvements of energy efficiency and GHG reduction targets, for which many common measures exist. [NRP, 2014, p. 34]

1.1.3.2 Target groups

The competences of the federal level are mostly limited to product standards and the national (Belgian) railway company NMBS/SNCB. The Federal level also has important responsibilities concerning taxation in Belgium. The Federal authorities of course remain responsible for their buildings and their personnel (including the work-related mobility of their staff).

Table 3 Target groups at the Federal level

Policy	Target group
Implementation of the Ecodesign Directive	Products. Energy related products (ErP) excluding means of transport
Energy labelling	Products. Refrigerators, dishwashers, washing machines, air-conditioners, tumble dryers, lamps, luminaires & light-bulbs, televisions, vacuum cleaners, space and water heaters, ovens, range hoods and residential ventilation.
Sustainable procurement	Products. The Federal Public Services and other federal government agencies. Other Belgian public authorities.
Tax deduction for roof insulation	Residential buildings (dwellings)
Federal Energy Services Company FEDESCO (*)	Non-residential (public) buildings. ±1800 federal public buildings
Management contract with NMBS/SNCB	Passenger and freight railway transport.
Ecodriving (regulatory)	Freight road transport (truck drivers) and passenger public road transport (bus drivers)
Free public transport for commuters (third party agreement TPA)	Passenger public transport. Federal employees (who commute by public transport) and employees of private companies (who commute by train)
Tax deduction environmentally friendly vehicles	Passenger transport. Electric motorcycle, tricycle or quadricycle.
Tax deduction for home work travel by bicycle	Passenger transport. Employees of private companies. Modal shift to bicycles.
Energy guzzlers website (informative)	Products and Passenger road transport (energy efficient and environmentally friendly cars) (50/50)

(*) Responsibilities will be taken over by Belgian Building Agency in 2015.

At the regional level multiple policies regarding the support of energy efficiency are in place. The Regions have introduced building energy performance standards (EPB) and certificates (EPC) [Nachmany et al, 2015, p. 4]. The measures mainly fall within the scope of the implementation of European directives regarding energy efficiency and energy performance of buildings. In Wallonia and the Brussels-Capital Region, some of the measures are part of multi-annual "Employment-Environment Alliance" programmes [NRP, 2014].

Table 4 Target groups in the Flemish Region

Policy	Target group
Implementation of the EPBD (EPB & EPC)	Residential and non-residential buildings
Audit of heating equipment (regulatory)	Heating systems.
Public Service Obligation for DSOs (grants)	Residential and non-residential (existing) buildings.
Property tax reduction	Residential buildings (newly built dwellings)
Home improvement grant	Residential buildings (existing dwellings)
Management contract with "De Lijn"	Passenger public transport. Vehicle efficiency. Travel efficiency.
Blue bike (financial support)	Passenger transport. Modal shift to bicycles.
Green car registration tax (green BIV)	Transport. Environmentally friendly vehicles.
Commuter fund (financial support).	Passenger transport (home-work travel of employees of private & public companies). Modal shift to more environmentally friendly modes of transport.
Ecoscore (informative)	Passenger and freight road transport. Energy efficient and environmentally friendly vehicles.
ReTiBo (registration ticket on-board computer)	Passenger public transport. Travel efficiency.
The "energy savings" website (informative)	Buildings and Renewable Energy Sources (RES)
Energy consultants	Residential and non-residential buildings. Households (with special attention to low income households); owners of

	heritage buildings; operators of tourism businesses and accommodations; SMEs; building sector professionals; and farmers
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EPB = Energy Performance Buildings. EPC = Energy Performance Certificate. DSO = Distribution System Operator (electricity grid manager).

The Walloon Region focuses on buildings, in particular the implementation of the EPBD and the renovation of existing dwellings through financial incentives.

Table 5 Target groups in the Walloon Region

Policy	Target group
Implementation of the EPBD (EPB & EPC)	Residential and non-residential buildings
ECOPACK (soft loan)	Residential buildings (existing dwellings)
Energy premiums (“primes énergie”)	Residential buildings (existing dwellings)
PIVERT (green investments program)	Residential buildings. Low income households in public social housing
REHA (subsidies)	Residential buildings (existing dwellings) Energy efficient glazing.
UREBA (subsidies)	Existing non-residential, non-commercial & public buildings
Model buildings BATEX (subsidies)	Residential buildings (dwellings) in 2012. Non-residential buildings (schools, offices, services) in 2013.
Management contract with SRWT-TEC	Passenger public transport. Vehicle efficiency. Travel efficiency.
Ecomalus (additional vehicle registration tax)	Transport. Environmentally friendly vehicles.
Ecoscore (informative)	Passenger and freight road transport. Energy efficient and environmentally friendly vehicles.
ReTiBo (registration ticket on-board computer)	Passenger public transport. Travel efficiency.
The energy portal website	Buildings. Everything energy-related.
Energy information desks (informative)	Residential buildings. (all energy efficiency related measures such as thermal insulation, heating systems, solar boilers, lighting, appliances, ...).
RUE Facilitators (informative)	Non-residential buildings.

EPB = Energy Performance Buildings. EPC = Energy Performance Certificate. RUE = Rational Use of Energy

The Brussels-Capital Region also focuses on buildings.

Table 6 Target groups in the Brussels-Capital Region

Policy	Target group
Implementation of the EPBD (EPB & EPC)	Residential and non-residential buildings
Mandatory energy audit (regulatory)	Non-residential buildings.
Local Action Plans for Demand-side Management P.L.A.G.E. (voluntary / regulatory)	Residential and non-residential (private and public buildings. Hospitals, schools, public and social housing communities. For the non-voluntary part: private owners with a building floor area of more than 100 000 m ² of building stock and public owners with a building floor area of more than 50 000 m ²
The Brussels Green Loan (BGL)	Residential buildings (existing dwellings). Focus on low income households.
Energy premiums (“primes énergie”)	Existing residential and non-residential (including industrial) buildings.
Model buildings “BatEx”	Residential and non-residential buildings.
Iris 2 Plan	Transport. Mobility plan.
Management contract with MIVB/STIB	Passenger public transport. Vehicle efficiency. Travel efficiency.
Company Transport Plan (BVP/PDE)	Passenger transport. Employees of large private & public

(Regulatory)	companies working in Brussels. Modal shift to more environmentally friendly modes of transport.
BRUXEL'AIR premium	Passenger transport. Modal shift from car to more environmentally friendly modes of transport.
Ecoscore (informative)	Passenger and freight road transport. Energy efficient and environmentally friendly vehicles.
ReTiBo (registration ticket on-board computer)	Passenger public transport. Travel efficiency.
Brussels Environment portal website	Buildings. Transport.
The Energy House (informative / aid in implementation)	Residential buildings (dwellings)
Sustainable building facilitator network (informative / aid in implementation)	Residential and non-residential buildings. Corporate bodies and institutions. Multifamily dwellings and the tertiary sector (including industrial facilities).

EPB = Energy Performance Buildings. EPC = Energy Performance Certificate

1.2 NATIONAL PROGRAMMES AND INITIATIVES

1.2.1 Buildings sector

1.2.1.1 Federal level

The federal government maintains the existing policies regarding the reduction of GHG emissions in the key non-ETS sectors (transport and buildings), aiming at supporting and completing regional measures. Additional measures in the field of transport and product standards are likely to be adopted as a result of the cooperation agreement with the Regions on the distribution of the non-ETS target [NRP, 2014, p. 23].

The Federal Level has adopted the following instruments to meet energy savings targets:

- Implementation of the EU Ecodesign and Ecolabelling (energy labelling) Directives in the residential and services sectors to promote more energy efficient products (for building, heating, boiler, isolation, materials, etc.) and related incentives [Deloitte, 2015, p. 14-15];
- Organisation of consumer information programmes;
- Creation of buildings standards. Federal and regional governments share policy responsibility in the areas of energy performance in buildings.

The Federal Level provided fiscal incentives to households, who could deduct up to 40% of the energy efficiency improvement costs [ENTRACTE, 2012, p. 28]. In 2014 only roof insulation was still supported by a tax cut of 30%. Federal support for energy efficiency (tax reductions for low-/zero-energy houses, green loans) has been reduced over 2012-2013, as responsibility for energy savings has shifted to the regions [Nachmany et al, 2015, p. 4].

Table 7 Implementation of the Ecodesign Directive - estimated annual energy savings compared to the baseline for the EU-27 by 2020 (in TWh)

Implemented measure	Annual saving (TWh)
Standby and off-mode losses of electrical and electronic equipment	35
Simple set top boxes	6
Domestic lighting	39
Tertiary sector lighting	38
External power supplies	9
Televisions	28
Electric motors	135

Circulators	23
Domestic refrigeration	4
Domestic dishwashers	2
Domestic washing machines	1.5
Fans (driven by motors with an electric input power between 125-500 kW)	34
Air conditioners and comfort fans	11
Total	365

Source: [VITO & ECONOTEC, 2015, p. 27]

The Federal Energy Services Company (FEDESCO) was created to improve energy efficiency and install photovoltaic panels in public buildings [ENTRACTE, 2012, p. 28].

1.2.1.2 Flemish region

Flanders focuses on energy savings in buildings by offering investment support and setting energy performance (EP) obligations.

The Flemish Parliament approved the introduction of energy performance of buildings (EPB) regulations as a matter of principle in a building code decree in 1999, before the European EPBD was planned. Work on the establishment of EPB-calculation methods had already started at the beginning of 1998 [ASIEPI, 2009, p. 1].

Flemish Action Plan on Energy Efficiency (“Energierenovatieprogramma 2020”).

The Action Plan on Energy Efficiency aims to ensure that by 2020 all existing homes (in Flanders) have insulated roofs and that all single glazing and outdated boilers have been replaced with high efficiency ones. The plan combines existing and new actions in the field of energy efficiency, such as premi-ums and tax deductions for investments in energy efficiency, energy consultancy and audits, and the dissemination of technical and financial information on energy efficiency measures. The Flemish government aims to introduce *additional* policies to improve the energy efficiency performance of heat boilers and the replacement of old heating systems.

Table 8 Achieved and expected final energy savings in GWh of the Flemish Public Service Obligation (PSO) on Distribution System Operators (DSO)

Instrument		2012	2016	2020
Grant - roof insulation		2698	4630	6524
Grant - boiler replacement	(a)	2773	2807	2843
Grant - glazing replacement		800	1218	1668
Grant - wall insulation		343	877	1486
Grant - floor & cellar insulation		18	86	151
Grant - solar thermal & heat pump	(b)	251	472	676
Grant - new build below EP standard		93	190	257
Grant - EE lighting non-residential		193	322	403
Grant - frequency transformer	[c]	639	589	415
Grant - ventilation with heat recovery	(d)	125	125	125
Energy scans of dwellings		50	88	81
Discount voucher for EE refrigerators & washing machines	[e]	0.4	0.6	0.9
		7983.4	11404.6	14629.9

(a) from 2012 „protected customers“ (vulnerable households) only

- (b) Including obligatory minimum proportion of renewable energy in new dwellings from 214
 - [c] until the end of 2011
 - (d) Saving from fitting energy saving light bulbs and shower heads
 - [e] for „protected customers“ only.
- Source: NEEAP (2014)

The Flemish Region also sets an additional target of 10% nearly Zero-Energy Buildings in 2015 as a percentage of all new builds, and of 75 % nZEBs as a percentage of new builds in 2020. It does not say how much final energy it hopes to save with this measure.

In 2014, new or planned initiatives included launching a long-term strategy for an in-depth renovation of the building stock (consultation of stakeholders, information session, inventory of buildings); measures of the Flemish Government regarding the commitment to renovate public buildings, consolidation of financial instruments for energy-efficiency renovations, and launching of a regulatory development process to finalize the transposition of the EU directive on the energy performance of buildings (EPBD).

In 2015, the Flemish Government is resolved to solidify the first step towards a long-term vision of the thorough renovation of the existing housing stock. The Energy Renovation Programme 2020 will be evaluated and adjusted to 2030 in consultation with stakeholders. The premium system for roof insulation and high efficiency glazing will be revised, by including a clear phasing out scenario, thus accelerating the investment decision. Extra stimuli will be included for thorough energetic renovation towards nearly zero-energy (nZE) performance level for existing houses. Other measures concern raising the quality of the EPC for residential buildings and the EPC for non-residential buildings [NRP, 2015, p. 62].

Flemish 2013-2020 Climate Policy Plan.

The Flemish government adopted the Flemish 2013-2020 climate policy plan on 28 June 2013. The Flemish Climate policy plan contains a mitigation and an adaptation policy plan covering the sectors buildings, mobility, agriculture, non-ETS industries, non-ETS energy sectors as well as waste [ECOLOGIC, 2014, p. 11]. The provisional indicative goal is to **reduce greenhouse gas emissions by 15% between 2013 and 2020** (Vlaamse Regering 2013). The Flemish mitigation plan contains concrete measures for non-ETS sectors, paying particular attention to the transport and building sectors, which are the most non-ETS greenhouse gas-intensive in Flanders [NRP, 2014, p. 23]. Flanders aims to reduce its non-ETS emissions by 15% by 2020 compared to 2005. The target of 15% emissions reductions is provisional [Nachmany et al, 2015, p. 3] [NRP, 2015, p. 18], given that no internal burden sharing in Belgium has been decided yet [ECOLOGIC, 2014, p. 4-5] [NRP, 2015, p. 64]. Most climate-related measures that are integrated in the plan are funded by the political domains responsible for their implementation [NRP, 2015, p. 18]. A new financing arrangement has been created for the period 2015-2020 in order to support, with the newly established Flemish Climate Fund, projects or measures according to their greenhouse gas emission reduction potential and cost-efficiency. The Flanders Spatial Policy Plan strives, among other things, to set up solid open-space networks for the purpose of climate mitigation and adaptation. [NRP, 2014, p. 23];

Flemish Climate Fund (Vlaams Klimaatfonds).

The Climate Fund was passed by the Flemish government on 27 April 2012. The Fund is financed through the auctioning of EU emission permits. The generated revenues are used to finance the effective and cost efficient implementation of Flemish climate policy with a focus on mitigation. For 2013 and 2014 the budget was € 36.5 million [ECOLOGIC, 2014, p. 12] The Climate Fund was used to finance the first series of measures for the period 2013-2014. These measures included increased premium for those who have their walls insulated and their windows replaced at the same time, an acceleration in making social dwellings energy-saving, the deployment of energy consultants in the

farming sector, for national heritage sites and for tourist infrastructure, etc. . [NRP, 2015, p. 62]. The 2014-2019 government agreement states that the Climate Fund resources will first and foremost be allocated to energy saving measures for buildings [NRP, 2015, p. 18].

1.2.1.3 Walloon region

Wallonia mostly concentrates on the residential buildings, through the granting of loans and energy subsidies to encourage energy efficiency upgrades in housing. Wallonia was the first Belgian Region to adopt a thermal regulation for buildings in 1984, which was implemented in 1985 [Morfils & Hauglustaine, 2014, p. 17].

Employment-Environment Alliance (AEE). The “Alliance” was launched in March 2011. The main goals are to stimulate demand for sustainable renovation and construction of private and public buildings; to increase the availability and capacity of the construction sector; and to develop skills through an extensive green training programme [ECOLOGIC, 2014, p. 14]. It involves social partners and actors in the field of public, voluntary, and private bodies.

Table 9 Achieved and expected final energy savings (in GWh) in the Walloon Region

Instrument	2014	2020
Model buildings BATEX	123.358	370.075
Commerce Enlightened	0.781	0.871
ECOPACK soft loans	67.523	267.120
EPB (energy performance buildings)	185.027	673.128
PIVERT (green investments program)	43.224	172.895
Energy premiums – “primes énergie”	1,467.000	3,348.642
Energy subsidies – “REHAbilitation”	192.383	580.695
Renovation SPW	0.043	0.278
Heating networks for public housing	2.140	2.140
Subsidies UREBA 2013	-	74.067
	2,081.479	5,489.914

Decimal point notation.

Source: NEEAP (2014)

The AEE contains a number of measures, including new ones. For example, the Walloon Region launched “Ecopack” in 2012, interest-free loans and energy subsidies („primes énergie“) to stimulate energy efficiency upgrades in housing [Nachmany et al, 2015, p. 4]. The interest-free loans scheme for the financing of energy efficiency works in housing was extended in 2014. Other new measures and initiatives include the upgrade of standards concerning the energy performance of new buildings (EPB); a call for projects on the construction and renovation of non-residential model buildings (BATEX in 2013); financing arrangements for the renovation of high energy-consuming public buildings (PIVERT2), and additional subsidies for the renovation of school, municipal and voluntary sector buildings (special UREBA 2013). The Rehabilitation premiums are subsidies for replacing single glazing with energy efficient double glazing in existing dwellings. Commerce Enlightened offers free advice on energy efficient lighting in the commercial (trade) sector. Collective boilers plants with heating networks for public housing in Wallonia is another AEE measure. Renovation SPW refers to renovation of the public buildings of the Walloon Public Services (SPW).

The interim evaluations of the first Employment-Environment Alliance (AEE) lead to a first estimate of the economic, social and environmental impact of the first AEE measures, The AEE has led to a significant increase in private and public demand for sustainable renovation, and helped to create/maintain jobs in the construction sector. The Ecopack measure (zero interest loan for renova-

tions, associated with bonuses) benefitted households with low and modest incomes. The AEE has reduced energy consumption (2 million MWh in 2014, or 1.6% of total final consumption and 4.6% in the domestic sector - 5,5 million MWh in 2020, representing 4.3% of total final consumption and 12.1% of the consumption of the domestic sector). The AEE has also reduced CO₂ emissions (from 500 000 T in 2014 and 1.3 million T in 2020).

The Marshall Plan 4.0 will focus on the energy efficiency of buildings based on the experience of the first Employment-Environment Alliance for sustainable construction, which will be reoriented and reinforced. [NRP, 2015, p. 100].

The Walloon Government approved the Action Plan on Energy Efficiency (PAEE) in March 2014. It aims to promote rational use energy (RUE), but also focuses on tracking energy, from production via transport and distribution to end-use. PAEE includes subsidy mechanism (such as UREBA) to renovate the existing building stock, and contains a long-term strategy to mobilize investments for the renovation of both residential and non-residential (private and public) buildings. PAEE is also a tool to assess the impacts of the existing measures and to compare them with the European energy saving targets.

The PEB decree of 28.11.2013 and the Walloon Government decree of 15.05.2014 introduce requirements for achieving near Zero Energy Buildings (nZEBs) with regard to new construction. As of 1 January 2015, all advertisements for the sale or lease of a building must mention the energy performance indicator. The energy subsidies („primes“) are also being reformed. The energy premiums will focus more on the most effective energy efficiency measures, and the amounts will depend on the beneficiary's income level. The procedures will also be simplified. The overall budget dedicated to these premiums will be reduced to 40 million EUR (-25 million EUR), but the budget for the zero or reduced loan rate (including Ecopack) will increase from 75 million EUR to 85 million EUR in 2015 and aims at 100 million EUR in 2019. The Fund for the reduction of the global regionalized energy cost will be merged with Ecopack.

The Walloon region will provide a single point of contact to locally access the various support tools available.

Air-Climate-Energy Plan. The Walloon Parliament adopted the Climate Decree in February 2013. This should enable Wallonia to meet its commitments to **cut GHG emissions (ETS and non-ETS) by 30% by 2020 and by 80-95% by 2050 compared to 1990 levels**. The decree establishes the framework in order to reach these objectives. The GHG emission reduction path is determined by the implementation of an „emission budget“ mechanism, whereby the Walloon government will be responsible for setting the emission budgets for a period of five years [ECOLOGIC, 2014, p. 13] [NRP, 2014, p. 23]. The Climate Decree also introduces an Air-Climate-Energy Plan listing the specific measures for achieving the targets.

1.2.1.4 Brussels-Capital region

Brussels focuses on all types of buildings.

Brussels Code for Air, Climate and Energy (COBRACE).

COBRACE was adopted on 2 May 2013. The code contains measures regarding energy efficiency, climate, renewables, sustainable transport and air quality [Nachmany et al, 2015, p. 3], focussing on the major energy consuming and greenhouse gas and air pollutant emitting sectors [NRP, 2014, p. 23], in order to meet the objectives of the Brussels-Capital region, namely the **reduction of GHG emissions by 30% (40% per capita) by 2025 compared to 1990**.

Table 10 Achieved and expected energy savings in GWh in the Brussels-Capital Region

Instrument	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2020
The Energy House					5	12	18	..

Mandatory energy audits			16	31	47	62	78	..
EPB heating systems			111	186	260	325	367	..
PLAGE - regulatory							24	..
PLAGE - voluntary	38	47	54	62	62	62	62	..
Model buildings BatEx	90	11	19	28	38	48	57	..
Energy bonuses	270	391	460	562	684	807	929	..
Obligation oil suppliers						19	37	..
Minimize occupancy costs						1	9	..
	398	449	660	868	1.095	1.335	1.581	-

Source: NEEAP (2014)

The Brussels-Capital Government adopted in first reading the Regional Air-Climate-Energy Plan PACE (“plan Air Climat Energie”) in September 2014. This plan allows for the implementation of the Air, Climate and Energy Management Code (COBRACE) of the Brussels Capital Region, defining regional 10-year targets on energy (including renewables), climate change and air quality.

The plan provides for the creation of an Energy House („Maison de l’énergie“), a support service for households which aims at promoting the rational use of energy as well as „eco-construction“. The Brussels-Capital Region provides subsidies called “Energy bonuses” (“primes énergie”) for residential, services and industrial sector buildings [Nachmany et al, 2015, p. 4]. The Plan includes an increase in the funds allocated to energy bonuses, as well as a fund for the renovation of public buildings. PLAGE are voluntary Local Action Plans for Demand-side Management, some of which will become obligatory from 2016. An energy audit has to be undertaken for any non-residential building with a floor area above 3500 m² when renewing the environmental permit. A periodic inspection of heating systems is mandatory (EPB-heating system). The plan also strengthens the regulation on the energy performance of buildings, in particular a compulsory passive standard for all new buildings from 2015. The plan foresees renewed calls for projects on “model buildings” (BatEx). “Minimize occupancy costs” refers to the construction and renovations of buildings by the Brussels Regional Housing Authority (SLRB). The energy performance of those buildings should guarantee minimum costs of living for the future occupants.

Finally, the Code COBRACE sets specific standards in terms of air quality and greenhouse gas emissions.

1.2.2 Transport sector

1.2.2.1 Federal level

“Federal and regional initiatives mainly focus on shifting road traffic growth towards rail or waterways and improving public transport provision, promoting car-sharing and upgrading infrastructure. Drivers are also encouraged to use low-energy vehicles (information, tax incentives) and use them in moderation (eco-driving).” [Nachmany et al, 2015, p. 5]

The Federal government promotes public transportation, car-sharing and car-pooling. A tax rebate is granted to household to purchase more efficient vehicles [ENTRACTE, 2012, p. 27].

The transport sector was formerly mainly under federal competency, but most responsibilities were transferred to the regional level in 2011, e.g. taxation on registration and ownership of cars, environmental incentives, and speed limits [ECOLOGIC, 2014, p. 23].

Federal green car support granting a 3-15% sales price equivalent reduction were abolished in 2012 and tax deductions for investment in electric cars were phased out by the end of 2010. There is still a tax deductions for companies with low fuel consuming car fleet [Nachmany et al, 2015, p. 5].

From 1 January 2014, the competences for environmental taxation (in the transport sector) of the Regions also include the entry into traffic service („Belasting op de inverkeerstelling“ / “Tax de mise en circulation”); the road tax („Verkeersbelasting”); and the “Eurovignette”.

The Federal state carries on with measures on the basis of its remaining competences, which mainly include biofuels, the tax system and rail transport [NRP, 2015, p. 19].

The regions have adopted several policy instrument to decrease GHG emission from transport, such as the Flemish and Walloon car registration tax reflecting CO₂ emissions) [Nachmany et al, 2015, p. 5], but significant differences prevail between regions. The regions keep on working toward the setting up of a kilometre-based charging system for trucks heavier than 3.5 ton. The system should enter into force in the first half of 2016 to replace the present Eurovignette system [NRP, 2015, p. 19].

1.2.2.2 Flemish region

“Mobility policy in Flanders lacks a clear discourse on implementing the policy objectives for 2020 and beyond” (Van Brussel S. et al, 2015, p. 281).

Draft Flemish mobility plan

The draft Flemish mobility plan aims to reduce GHG emissions by 16% by 2030 compared to 2005 in the transport sector [Towards an Energy Union Belgium, 2015 p. 11]. It will be implemented in conjunction with the policy plans concerning spatial planning and the environment. The final approval of the Plan is expected in the Spring of 2016 [NRP, 2015, p. 63].

Table 11 Achieved and expected energy savings in GWh in the transport sector in the Flemish Region

Instruments	2012	2016	2020
Manage mobility & improve environmental performance of transport	1863	6558	9239

Source: NEEAP (2014)

To reduce emissions in the transport sector, Flanders introduces the following policies and measures [NRP, 2014, p. 23] [NRP, 2015, p. 63]:

- Variable congestion charge, to reduce the number of vehicle-kilometres;
- Integrated public transport policy, to enhance the environmental characteristics of transport modes and fuels;
- More environmentally friendly mobility and logistic chains, to promote environmentally-friendly transport modes.

Variable congestion charge. The Eurovignette will be replaced in the first half of 2016 by a “kilometer charge for heavy vehicles” (variable congestion charge) from 3.5 ton Maximum Authorised Mass (MAM). The kilometer charge will be collected using special measuring equipment built into the trucks and control gates on toll read able to identify the trucks.

Integrated public transport policy. The alignment of the transport plans of the public transport operators will improve connections of city and suburban transport to the railway. The integrated ticket system based on the MoBIB card norm, part of ReTiBo (Registration and Ticket System with On-board computer) will be further implemented, allowing to chart travel streams and to better coordinate supply and demand. Smart traffic lights will guarantee better traffic flow of public transport. The fleet of hybrid buses of De Lijn will be expanded and deployed on inner city and suburban routes. In the longer term, De Lijn will focus on fully electric (city) and hydrogen (inter-city) powered buses.

More environmentally friendly mobility and logistic chains. For passenger transport, nodes where transport systems meet (Park & Rides, public transport, carpool parkings) will be developed and

made accessible for pedestrians and cyclists. Integrated bicycle rout networks are developed to stimulate the use of bicycles for home-school and home-work traffic. The Super local Functional Bicycle Route Network ("Bovenlokaal Functioneel Fietsroutenetwerk") and bicycle free-ways will be extended in regions sensitive to congestion. For freight transport, the inland waterway shipping will be stimulated by completing and optimizing the network. The focus is on facilitating onshore power supply, the use of hydrogen and LNG as a shipping fuel, and the provision of a range of waterside industrial estates.

Implementation of infrastructure for electric vehicles. The first phase of the implementation of charging points at carpool parking and Park & Rides by the Road & Traffic administration is up and running.

The Climate Fund was used to finance the first series of measures for the period 2013-2014. These measures include the expansion of the number of electric charging points on parking lots in the Flemish Region (i.e. carpool parking and Park & Rides), expansion of the quay-side energy inland waterway infrastructure for inland waterway shipping, etc. [NRP, 2015, p. 62].

1.2.2.3 Walloon region

The Walloon region launched a regional mobility programme in 2009, covering the period from 2009 to 2014. The measures of the programme focused on two key aspects [ECOLOGIC, 2014, p. 13]:

- environmental protection (reduction of energy consumption and of polluting emissions);
- the development of alternatives to the car, including public transport and cycle transport.

Table 12 Achieved and expected energy savings in GWh in the transport sector in the Walloon Region

		2012	2016	2020
Management contract	SRWT - vehicle efficiency	2	2	2
SRWT	Car sharing - Interoperability of tickets	4	4	4
Public transport - outside SRWT	Public transport – vehicle efficiency	216	216	216
	Teleworking civil servants	0	0	0
Financial instruments	Public transport	26	26	26
	Roads	349	62	..
	Inland navigation	163	163	163
		759	474	412

Source: NEEAP, 2014.

The Walloon Climate Decree targets a reduction of GHG emissions of 16% by 2030 compared to 2005 in the transport sector.

The environmental penalty scheme aiming at promoting the purchase of vehicles emitting less CO₂ has been extended to company cars since 1 January 2014.

Regarding public transport, consultation between the operators will be strengthened to improve complementarity.

Investments in multimodal transport are being maintained in order to encourage the shift to green alternatives. For example, the building of the multimodal platform Trilogiport (Liège) began in June 2013 and is scheduled to become operational in the second half of 2015 [NRP, 2014, p. 23]

The "Transport and Logistics" strategy aims to enhance the coordination between the Walloon ports and to provide multimodal platforms. The adoption of management contracts in December 2014 will allow each of the 4 autonomous Walloon ports to receive a budget of 5 million EUR for 5 years, pro-

vided that they present a five-year investment plan, a business plan and scorecard indicator. A coordination platform for ports will be set up.

The Walloon Region plans to develop a global approach reconciling accessibility, environment and energy efficiency [NRP, 2015, p. 19].

1.2.2.4 Brussels-Capital region

The Brussels-Capital Region targets to decrease GHG emissions from private cars by 50% by 2050 compared to 2001.

Table 13 Achieved and expected energy savings in GWh in transport sector in the Brussels-Capital Region

Instrument	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2020
Transport	32	96	191	317	475	664	884	..

Source: NEEAP (2014)

The aforementioned COBRACE code also provides for the improvement of air quality through measures promoting a higher environmental performance of vehicles.

The Integrated Plan for Air, Climate and Energy (“plan Air Climat Energie – PACE”) supports and completes the measures taken in the framework of the IRIS 2 plan. It includes in particular an overhaul of transport taxation according to environmental criteria. A provision of COBRACE aiming at reducing car use by acting on free car parking available at the workplace came into force on 5 February 2014. [NRP, 2014, p. 23]

The Air-Climate-Energy Plan reinforces the Regional Iris 2 plan which establishes guidelines in term of mobility. Some of the measures include:

- A study on the development potential of electric cars and LNG vehicles in an urban context was started in January 2015;
- Regional and local services can no longer purchase diesel vehicles. Ambitious environmental performance criteria are defined for all public authority vehicles (cars, vans, trucks). Regional and local vehicle fleets will be analysed to streamline their size and usage. For new cars quota are imposed: 25% in 2015 to 40% in 2020 electric vehicles for regional bodies; and 15% in 2015 tot 25% in 2020 electric vehicles for local authorities.

The replacement of the Eurovignette by a kilometre levy for heavy-goods vehicles should come into force early 2016.

The Air-Climate-Energy plan also provides for the adaptation of regional car taxation according to environmental criteria, particularly the vehicle's type of fuel and CO₂, PM10 and NO_x emissions. Other emissions (CO, HC) as well as noise may be added [NRP, 2015, p. 130].

1.3 CONCLUSIONS AND LESSONS LEARNED OF OTHER PROJECTS ABOUT THE PERFORMANCE OF THE NATIONAL POLICY PACKAGES FOR ENERGY EFFICIENCY

1.3.1 The lack of a national (or regional) energy efficiency “strategy”

As should have become clear from reading chapter 1.1 Policy packages and policy governance in Belgium, Belgium does **not** have a *national* energy (efficiency) or climate change policy, due to the exclusivity of competences. Hence, there are **no** “other projects” that evaluate Belgian (national) pol-

icies for energy efficiency (or for any other policy, for that matter); and from which one can “learn lessons”. As stated repeatedly in chapter 1.1, the only lesson that one can learn is that Belgium accepts the normative authority of the EU. A Belgian strategy would almost by definition be the EU strategy.

This lack of a strategy also applies to the regional levels. There are no real “strategies” or “policy packages” in terms of energy efficiency. This should likewise have become clear after reading chapter 1.2 National programmes and initiatives. Nevertheless, the National Reform Program report for Belgium (NRP, 2015) tries to keep a positive outlook. Policy instruments that are outlined and decided at different levels of governance can contribute to achieve several goals, which is particularly so with regard to improvement of energy efficiency and GHG reduction targets in the non-ETS sector, for which numerous *common* measures exist [NRP, 2015 p. 29]. Happaerts (2013) is somewhat more pessimistic in the perspective of multi-level governance of climate change in Belgium. His analysis of subnational climate policies in Belgium shows “... *how a multi-level system, besides offering multiple opportunities to subnational governments, can also have a inhibiting effect and be conducive to policy failures. It indicates a need to avoid blind optimism with respect to multi-level solutions, and urges both scholars and policy-makers to consider other and additional ways to deal with climate change in a complex political landscape*” (Happaerts, 2013, p. 22).

In actual fact, there is a severe fragmentation of policy instruments. This is the case for the buildings sector, but even more so for the transport sector. If there is such a thing as a regional energy efficiency “strategy”, the unauthorized version would be this. All three regions in Belgium focus on buildings, both residential and non-residential (although dwellings appear to receive somewhat more attention). The regions expect significant final energy savings by imposing mandatory energy building performance standards (MEPS), including the gradual introduction of near Zero Energy Buildings. This is not a surprise, given the low energetic quality of the housing stock in Belgium. In spite of its importance, the Flemish Region and the Brussels-Capital Region fail to give a quantitative 2020 energy savings target for this particular measure in their respective NEEAPs. The Walloon Region does provide a target in the NEEAP for this specific policy instrument, but the expected final energy savings in 2020 are fairly modest. The renovation of the existing building stock is encouraged by a plethora of subsidies (often called “premiums” or “bonuses”) in all three Regions and / or soft loans in the Walloon and Brussels-Capital Region. The Flemish Region is unique in that it relies on the Public Service Obligation (PSO) of the Distribution System Operators (DSOs) or “electricity grid managers”. This policy instrument is the only one the Flemish Region gives a clear target for in terms of final energy savings in 2020. All three regions pay particular attention to “vulnerable households”, who often get additional support in the form of subsidies, soft loans and / or energy audits. Also striking in the Walloon Region and the Brussels-Capital Region is the combination of energy and climate policies with social policies, whereby the authorities vigorously try to stimulate “green jobs” in the construction sector. Informative and awareness raising initiatives are to be found at all levels (Federal, Regional). Again, most of the policy instruments concerning information and education are very fragmented, but particularly so in the Walloon Region. In fact, the fragmentation of policy instruments can be considered a major “institutional barrier” both at the federal and the regional level. The energy efficiency policies and measures for the transport sector are weak, if not to say very weak. Basically, transport policies are limited to either agreements with the federal and regional public transport operators on improving vehicle fleet efficiencies and travel efficiency including interconnectivity; financial support for alternative modes of transport (bicycles in particular); and informative measures combined with financial / fiscal instruments to promote purchasing cars that emit less CO₂. The promotion of electric mobility is generally speaking lacklustre. In the Flemish Region and the Walloon Region ambitious mobility plans are still in the making. The expected (and long overdue) mobility plans intend to integrate mobility with spatial planning (land use).

The fragmentation of authority applies to other policy domains as well, including climate change policies but also energy and environmental policies in general. This fragmentation has not gone unnoticed by authors both inside and outside of Belgium. The most relevant sources in that respect are Schenk (2008), who gives a broad but by now somewhat outdated view of energy (efficiency) policies in Belgium; Wuppertal Institut, Ecofys and O.Ö. Energiesparverband ([Energy Efficiency Watch, 2013](#)) who attempt to evaluate the (previous) Belgian NEEAP; Deloitte (2015) who give a country profile of the European energy market reform; and last but not least the climate experts from the federal thematic service Climate Change of the Federal Public service Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment ([UNFCC, 2015](#)).

1.3.1.1 Observations by Schenk (2008)

The Martindale Center of Lehigh University in 2008 published a series of articles on the "[Benelux: Integration and Individuality](#)" (Volume 26). One of those articles was written by Caitlin M. Schenk, on "[The Belgian Energy Landscape, Security Efficiency and Sustainability](#)".

Schenk (2008) observes that the institutional complexity of Belgium hinders the implementation of comprehensive energy and climate policies. It is challenging to achieve national energy policy goals under a complex division of responsibilities between the federal and regional governments [[Schenk, 2008, p. 108](#)].

She furthermore adds that although federal and regional governments share policy responsibilities in the area of energy efficiency and climate change, in particular for buildings, their articulation and implementation differ significantly. "*Federal and regional policies lack coordination, making it difficult for a cohesive national approach to energy efficiency to emerge.*" [[Schenk, 2008, p. 103](#)]

1.3.1.2 Observations by Energy Efficiency Watch (2013)

Energy Efficiency Watch is an Intelligent Energy Europe project that tries to portray the progress made in implementation of energy efficiency policies via screening of the NEEAP's and extensive EU wide expert surveys. The Country Report Belgium For Energy Efficiency in Europe, Assessment of Energy Efficiency Action Plans and Policies in EU Member States 2013 ([Energy Efficiency Watch, 2013](#)) is already outdated, as it does not cover the most recent NEEAPs (2014) for the federal and regional level.

The authors of the Energy Efficiency Watch report do recognize that the Belgian NEEAP is composed of the measures outlined in three distinct energy efficiency action plans of the three Belgian regions. "*As one specific measure typically applies only to one region, it is **difficult to assess the Belgian NEEAP as a whole***" [[Energy Efficiency Watch, 2013, p. 2](#)]. In other words, the institutional complexity of Belgium is even reflected in the NEEAPs, with separate action plans for the Federal level and the Regions. It is not clear however if the authors of the Energy Efficiency Watch report are aware that the multi-level governance in Belgium is at the heart of the problem.

1.3.1.3 Observations by Deloitte (2015)

Deloitte Conseil in 2015 wrote a country profile for Belgium concerning the European energy market reform.

Although the report does not have much to say about energy efficiency policy in Belgium, it does comment that Belgium has a complex internal institutional structure and its energy policy commitments are shared by the federal level and the country's three regions. They conclude that there is a need to "*continue pushing for closer co-ordination between regional and federal levels to increase policy and regulatory efficiency.*" [[Deloitte, 2015, p. 11](#)].

Deloitte Conseil further notes that the Belgian NEEAP lacks clear sectorial targets and an overall target for the mid and long term [[Deloitte, 2015, p. 14-15](#)].

1.3.2 The lack of monitoring and evaluation in Belgium

The almost non-existence of adequate monitoring and evaluation of energy efficiency and climate change policies in Belgium, with the exception of the federal climate action plan, makes it difficult if not impossible to say something meaningful about lessons that can be learned from “other projects”.

One of the staunchest critics of energy efficiency monitoring and evaluation practices in Belgium are Estache and Kaufman [2011]. The most up-to-date remarks concerning evaluation problems are those made by the Belgian climate experts [UNFCC, 2015]. Energy Efficiency Watch [2013] tried to assess the implementation of energy efficiency policies in Belgium. The regional NEEAPs are on the whole unreadable. The most useful information can be found in the annual National Reform Program reports [NRP, 2014; 2015]. In general, whenever researchers in Belgium ask the authorities for evaluation reports, they invariably get the same type of answer. The information is either not publicly available (confidentiality), or reference is made to the European and international reporting obligations. In practice, the only available information is the one provided in several EU reports.

1.3.2.1 Observations by Estache and Kaufman (2011)

Antonio Estache and Marc Kaufman in 2011 wrote an article on “Theory and evidence on the economics of energy efficiency. Lessons For the Belgian Building Sector”.

We have to concur with Estache and Kaufman (2011) that “... monitoring and evaluation of energy efficiency policies and of their effectiveness is particularly weak in Belgium” (p. 145).

As noted by Estache and Kaufman in 2011, there is no official full assessment of the energy efficiency performance in Belgium. “Although some of the data is available, there does not yet exist a clear set of data matching a clear methodology that could be used to track the efficiency performance in detail and objectively.” [Estache & Kaufman, 2011, p. 142]. Sadly, this is still the case at the time of writing (September 2015) (see also chapter 2).

The main conclusion and lesson learned from “other projects” about assessing the performance of the Belgian national package for energy efficiency is this:

“Evidence matters to sound policymaking. This evidence is lacking in terms of energy efficiency, and in particular in buildings, making a fair diagnostic of the efficiency challenges ahead difficult at this stage” [Estache & Kaufman, 2011, p. 146].

1.3.2.2 Observations by the Belgian climate experts

The federal thematic service Climate Change of the Federal Public service Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment is the most pertinent and up to date evaluation source. The fragmentation of authority in Belgium does not only make it difficult to evaluate the federal and regional NEEAPs, but also to assess the climate action plans in Belgium. In a compilation of questions to – and answers by – Belgium, in Session SB142 (2015) of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCC, 2015), the Belgian climate change experts point out a number of difficulties. We briefly discuss the most relevant of those remarks.

- In Belgium, it is very difficult, if not impossible, to completely avoid double counting when estimating the impacts of individual policies and measures. “For example, in the residential sector, financial support is being provided by the three regions for investments aimed at reducing households energy consumptions. In parallel, during several years, the Federal State offered a 40% income tax deduction for the same investments.” [UNFCC, 2015, p. 3];
- Another complication is that the timing of smaller or larger updates of original measures which remain continually in effect, differ between the competent entities (the Federal state

and the three Regions), while there is only one date reported for Belgium as a whole for the integrated measures and policies. [UNFCCC, 2015, p. 3];

- The division of competences makes evaluation and monitoring challenging. „*The implementation of climate change policies and measures, relating to transport, is based on plans drawn up respectively by the federal and regional governments, which set their own priorities and are free to determine their own goals within the scope of their competences.*“ [UNFCCC, 2015, p. 6];
- Also, the Regions cannot agree on targets. „*... as long as the burden sharing of the ESD target between the three regions and the federal state has not been concluded, no final conclusions can be drawn from a regional or national point of view.*“ [UNFCCC, 2015, p. 4].

VITO and ECONOTEC consultants in 2015 in a study commissioned by the Belgian Federal Public Service of Public Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment provide a thorough evaluation of the impact of policy instruments and measures implemented in the context of the Federal climate policy.

They state that In Belgium the impact of a given national policy and measure (can be the result of the sum of four different impacts (i.e. for each region and the Federal level). But *there is no information on how these impacts were assessed* by the different entities [VITO & ECONOTEC, 2015, p. 103]. Harmonisation of methodologies and assumptions could improve the quality of reporting (id, ibid, p. 103).

1.3.2.3 Observations by Energy Efficiency Watch (2013)

We do not wish to discuss the the country report for Belgium of Energy Efficiency Watch (2013) in much detail, for two reasons. Firstly, the report is already outdated, as it does not cover the most recent (2014) NEEAPS. Secondly, the quality of the assessment is fairly weak and does not seem to reflect the reality in Belgium, as described in the previous chapters of this report. This is more than likely related to the fact that only the Federal level provided an English version of its NEEAP. Even in 2015, the Brussels-Capital Region and the Walloon Region do not provide an English translation. This makes it difficult for non-French speakers to evaluate the NEEAPs in full. It is furthermore our experience that the regional NEEAPs of 2014 are for the most part incomprehensible, even for someone who understands Dutch and French.

We do quote a number of valuable results of the survey with national experts.

- The Energy-Efficiency-Watch survey conducted in 2011 and 2012 with national experts states that “ ... only around 30% of respondents that that the Belgian policy is ambitious or at least ambitious in a range of sectors.” [Energy Efficiency Watch, 2013, p. 6].
- According to the aforementioned survey of national experts on the implementation of energy efficiency policies in Belgium, “... 68% estimate that the ESD target will not be reached or, if reached, **will not lead to significant savings.**” [Energy Efficiency Watch, 2013, p. 6].

We do find it somewhat odd that Energy Efficiency Watch [2013] reports “*advanced monitoring, reporting and verification* in Flanders and Wallonia”. To date, the only serious *known* attempts at monitoring and reporting are done at the Federal level for evaluating the impact of their specific policy instruments and measures (PAMs) implemented in the context of the Federal climate policy [VITO & ECONOTEC, 2015]. Ironically, state reform after state reform the Federal level loses competences to the Regions, including those that are particularly relevant for energy and climate policies. The best quantitative and qualitative evaluation is thus currently only available for a steadily decreasing number of policy instruments.

1.3.2.4 Observations from several EU country reports

There are some doubts that Belgium will be able to reach its energy efficiency target.

Already in 2008, Schenk was led to “... the conclusion that energy efficiency is *“a second priority in energy policy”* in Belgium [Schenk, 2008, p. 103]. This evaluation is not contradicted by a study in 2014 of the Ecologic Institute and “eclareon”. In their country report for Belgium on the “Assessment of climate change policies in the European Semester” (ECOLOGIC, 2014) they state that per capita energy consumption and GHG emissions are high in Belgium when compared to other EU Member States [ECOLOGIC, 2014, p. 1]. This may lead to the conclusion that climate change *“does not seem to be among Belgium’s priorities at the moment”* [ECOLOGIC, 2014, p. 1]. This is confirmed by the aforementioned country report of Deloitte Conseil, who concede that Belgium’s energy efficiency has been improving in recent years, but its energy intensity remains higher than in its neighbouring countries [Deloitte, 2015, p. 14-15].

All EU Member States have committed to the Europe 2020 strategy. Each country has different economic circumstances and translates the overall EU objectives into national targets in its National Reform Programme. The National Reform Programme is a document which presents a country's policies and measures to sustain growth and jobs and to reach the Europe 2020 targets. The NRPs for Belgium do contain some relevant information. Another interesting source is the (as yet unofficial) “Energy Union” (European Commission) country report for Belgium.

Figure 5 Primary energy consumption and energy efficiency objective in Belgium.

Source: NRP, 2015, p. 29.

According to the National Reform Programme reports, In 2012, primary energy consumption in Belgium, the indicator selected to set the indicative energy efficiency target (42.7 Mtoe in 2020) remained some 9% below the projected level for 2020 (according to the PRIMES scenario, baseline 2007, of the European Commission), i.e. halfway towards the Belgian objective of 18% [NRP, 2014, p. 33]. In 2013, the primary energy consumption increased, after two consecutive decreases in 2011 and 2012. The primary energy consumption of 47.4 Mtoe in 2013 remained some 3.7 Mtoe above the Belgian EE objective of 42.7 Mtoe in 2020 [NRP, 2015, p. 29].

The relatively higher energy intensity can partly be explained by the particular structure of its economy and industry, which features a proportionally high share of energy-intensive activities (e.g. chemicals and metallurgy). A high energy intensity reduction is noted in the industrial sector, i.e. about 16,1% between 2005 and 2013. This is significantly more than the average energy intensity reduction in the EU28. However, this could be due to the restructuring of Belgium industrial activities in less energy intensive activities [Towards an Energy Union Belgium, 2015 p. 6]

“Final energy intensity in residential sector in Belgium (as reported at GDP constant prices Euro2010) decreased by more than 20% in Belgium between 2005 and 2013, but it is still above the EU average.” [Towards an Energy Union Belgium, 2015, p. 6].

The specific energy intensity of passenger cars remained stable. The specific energy intensity for freight transport increased consistently between 2000-2010 (by 34%), showing a deteriorating trend.” [Towards an Energy Union Belgium, 2015; p. 6]. Belgium is a transit and export-oriented economy, with a constantly growing transport sector (GHG emissions up by over 30% between 1990 and 2011) [Nachmany et al, 2015, p. 5].

The overall conclusion is that *“If the trend in primary energy consumption observed in the period 2005-2013 will continue up to 2020, Belgium would be at risk of not meeting its national target. Belgium has to increase its current efforts regarding energy efficiency to further decrease its current primary energy consumption (47.4 in 2013) to reach its ambitious 2020 target.”* [Towards an Energy Union Belgium, 2015, p. 6].

2. INTERACTION BETWEEN THE NATIONAL AND THE SUB-NATIONAL LEVELS

The interaction between the national (federal) and regional levels in Belgium has already been discussed at length.

Energy and climate policies need to be coordinated between the Federal and Regional levels, and across the regions. *“Belgium’s governmental structure requires the coordination of energy policy both between the federal and regional governments and across the regions.”* [Schenk, 2008, p. 101]. *“The degree of autonomy of the various government levels is such that coordination needs are extremely high.”* [Estache & Kaufman, 2011, p. 145].

The energy consultation group CONCERE/ENOVER (*“Concertation Etat-Régions pour l’Energie » / « Energieoverleg »*) is a formal forum for energy policy coordination. The body was created in 1991 by Belgium’s federal and regional governments, and became operational in 1992. It facilitates cooperation and information exchange among the federal and regional governments, as well as internationally. Its main tasks are:

- Collect information and promote information exchange between the Regions and the Federal government;
- Support all policy measures, including those involving both Federal and Regional authorities, in a spirit of internal cohesion and respect of the participants’ competences;
- Strive to harmonise certain provisions;
- Provide joint financing for some research projects;
- Agree on the reports to be submitted to international bodies and select representatives in Belgian regional delegations for international meetings.

ENOVER/CONCERE also reports (via the Belgian representation) to the European Commission on the transposition of energy directives and the execution of energy regulations.

CONCERE/ENOVER does not have the power to regulate. The group respects the autonomy of all parties. It gives advice and provides recommendations to Belgian regulatory bodies, but those are not binding. Plenary sessions are held monthly. Several working groups on thematic subjects have been created. The federal Energy Administration (Federal Public Service Economy, SMEs, Self-Employed and Energy - Directorate-General for Energy) provides assistance.

Although CONCERE/ENOVER is a good step in the direction of coordination, *“... it seems reasonable to expect that the implementation of this coordination is unlikely to meet the necessary levels.”* [Estache & Kaufman, 2011, p. 145]

Since 2007, there has been consulting and cooperation between the three Regions in Belgium to harmonize the transposition of the EU EPB directive into national legislation via CONCERE/ENOVER. The Regions decided to develop unique calculation methodologies to quantify the energy performance of new buildings and the performance of existing buildings for certification; and to that order develop a common software package (the so-called ALTRAN software, in use by the three Regions since 1 January 2014). Concerning energy savings, the harmonisation of the calculation methodologies is done with respect to the reporting of energy savings for NEEAP in the framework of the ESD Directive. The decision to develop the same approach in the three regions is *voluntarily*. The political decisions are made by the Regional governments.

The ESD directive compares the observed or the projected energy efficiency with that of a fixed baseline (the reference year). However, the impact assessments in the context of the Monitoring Mechanism Decision (MMD) compare the emissions in a scenario with the PAM and a business-as-usual

scenario. Additional assumptions concerning the business-as-usual scenario are needed, requiring additional harmonisation between the Regions [VITO & ECONOTEC, 2015, p. 103].

The methodologies to determine the energy savings from financial incentives to promote energy efficiency in residential buildings at the Federal level (tax deductions) and the Regional levels (subsidies or premiums) have been harmonised in CONCERE/ENOVER, but further harmonisation concerning emission factors might be necessary [VITO & ECONOTEC, 2015, p. 103].

The three Regions recently agreed to implement a unique Belgian environmental performance assessment referential for the certification of sustainable buildings called 'Ref-b'. Ref-b is based on Ba-tEx (see policy instruments of the Brussels-Capital Region), BREEAM (British certification system of sustainable buildings) and VALIDEO (a previous Belgian certification system for tertiary buildings created by the "Technical Control Bureau for Construction" (SECO) together with the Belgian Building Research Institute) [Monfils & Hauglustaine, 2014, p. 18].

For the harmonisation of climate policies in Belgium there are a number of bodies, a few of which we will mention briefly:

- The Inter-ministerial Conference for Environment;
- The Committee for Co-ordination of the International Environmental Policy;
- The National Climate Commission;
- The Interregional Environmental Agency (IRCEL/CELINE).

The Inter-ministerial Conference for Environment and the Committee for Co-ordination of the International Environmental Policy are in charge of coordination and preparation of climate change related matters within broader environmental policy and Belgian representation in relevant international institutions [Nachmany et al, 2015, p. 1-2].

The National Climate Commission was created in 2002 to coordinate the policies implemented at the regional levels. It has a permanent Secretariat and is composed of representatives of the Federal government and the three Regions. The Commission is responsible for preparing and implementing national climate change policy and reporting to the EU and international institutions, as well as approval of projects for the Kyoto Protocol Joint Implementation (JI) and Clean Development Mechanisms (CDM) [Nachmany et al, 2015, p. 1-2].

The National Climate Commission established Belgium's national climate plan for 2009–2012, which included an internal burden-sharing agreement. Due to a lack of consensus between the regions, an internal burden-sharing of non-ETS targets for 2013–2020 is not decided yet. Consequently, a follow-up national climate plan is still missing.

The Interregional Environmental Agency ("Intergewestelijke Cel voor het Leefmilieu" IRCEL / "Cellule Interrégionale de l'Environnement" CELINE) and other bodies are responsible, amongst others, for the preparation of regional and national GHG inventories. IRCEL/CELINE manages the national database concerning air pollution, which includes all the data acquired by the three regional monitoring networks in Belgium. IRCEL/CELINE transmits data concerning air quality to the European level and other international organisations.

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HERON (No: 649690): Deliverable D.1.1

LANDSCAPE OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICY PACKAGES IN A MULTI-LEVEL GOVERNMENT SYSTEM

**PART OF WORK PACKAGE 1: MAPPING OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICY
INSTRUMENTS AND AVAILABLE TECHNOLOGIES IN BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT**

NATIONAL REPORT FOR BULGARIA

JULY 2015

Partner: Black Sea Energy Research Centre

Institution: Black Sea Energy Research Centre

Steering Committee member (1): Lulin Radulov

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(1) The Steering Committee member has the responsibility for ensuring the quality of the report.

HERON: Forward – looking socio-economic research on Energy Efficiency in EU countries

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649690. The content of this document reflects only the authors' views and the EASME is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

CONTENTS

TABLE OF FIGURES	4
TABLE OF TABLES	5
ACRONYMS	6
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	7
THE ROLE OF GOVERNANCE AND ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICY PACKAGES ON THE NATIONAL LEVEL	8
1.1 Policy Packages and Policy Governance in Bulgaria	8
1.1.1 Buildings Sector	9
1.1.2 Transport Sector	11
1.2 National Programmes and Initiatives.....	12
1.2.1 Building sector.....	13
1.2.2 Transport sector	14
1.2.3 Energy Efficiency Obligation Scheme	17
1.3 Conclusions and Lessons Learned of other Projects about the Performance of the National Policy Packages for Energy Efficiency.....	18
1.3.1 Energy Efficiency Watch	18
1.3.2 ODYSSEE-MURE - Monitoring of Energy Efficiency in EU 27, Norway and Croatia ...	19
1.3.3 Refurbishment of the Public Building Stock Towards nZEB (RePublic_ZEB)	19
1.3.4 ENTRANZE – Policies to Enforce the Transition to Nearly Zero Energy buildings in the EU-27	20
1.3.5 Improving dwellings by enhancing actions on labeling for the EPBD (IDEAL-EPBD) ...	21
INTERACTION BETWEEN THE NATIONAL AND THE SUB-NATIONAL LEVELS	23
REFERENCES	24

TABLE OF FIGURES

Figure 1: Effective policy packages in energy efficiency policy **Fehler! Textmarke nicht definiert.**

Figure 2: A prototypical process for policy development in energy efficiency **Fehler! Textmarke nicht definiert.**

TABLE OF TABLES

Table 1: Summary of the effect of the measure implementation	17
Table 2: Average energy sales to final users in the period 2010-2012, ktoe.....	17
Table 3: Breakdown of the obligation scheme by year (2014-2020), ktoe	17

ACRONYMS

BDB	Bulgarian Development Bank
BGN	Bulgarian lev (national currency)
EE	Energy Efficiency
EEA	Energy Efficiency Act
EED	Energy Efficiency Directive
EEW	Energy Efficiency Watch
EPBD	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
ESCO	Energy Service Company
ESD	Energy Services Directive
EU	European Union
FEC	Final Energy Consumption
GHG	Green House Gases
ktoe	kiloton of oil equivalent
MTITC	Ministry of Transport, Information Technology and Communications
MRDPW	Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works
NEEEAP	National Energy Efficiency Action Plan
NAPPPEV	National Action Plan for the Promotion of the Production and Accelerated Penetration of Ecological Vehicles, including Electric Mobility
OP	Operational Programme
PEC	Primary Energy Consumption
R&D	Research and Development
SEDA	Sustainable Energy Development Agency

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The main official national documents describing policy packages for energy efficiency in Bulgaria, are the National Energy Efficiency Action Plans (NEEAPs).

The new NEEAP 2014 - 2020 (MEE 2014) was developed in accordance with the Energy Efficiency Directive (EED) and the recast of the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) requirements. In this plan Bulgaria sets the following indicative national energy saving targets for the period till 2020:

- Energy savings of 716 ktoe/y at Final Energy Consumption (FEC) level;
- Energy savings of 1590 ktoe/y at Primary Energy Consumption (PEC) level, including 169 ktoe/y in energy transformation, transmission and distribution processes;

The national indicative energy saving targets for all sectors are:

- In 2013, 6%/year of the average FEC value in scope of Energy Service Directive (ESD) for the period 2001 - 2005;
- In 2020, 7,9%/year of the average FEC value in the scope of EED for the period 2010-2012.

The overall regulatory framework is rather balanced, including the policy packages for public sector and industry. The bodies, responsible for the policy and measures implementation in line with NEEAP at national level are the Sustainable Energy Development Agency, Ministry of Energy, etc. and at regional level – the regional energy efficiency councils, Local Authorities, etc (MEE 2014). Central and local government authorities are obliged by the Energy Efficiency Act (EEA 2015) to prepare energy efficiency improvement plans as well as programmes for their implementation. In order to achieve the national savings target all obliged parties (industry, energy traders and owners of public buildings) have to contribute for the overall reduction with their share.

- The following policy packages are in force for supporting the achieving of the targets:
- Buildings sector: Minimum energy performances standards have been set for commissioning of new buildings and obligations are in force for energy audits of public sector buildings. Economic incentives and financing instruments have been developed with strong focus on multi-family residential buildings.
- Appliances: The policy package for appliances comprises the Ecodesign requirements, energy labelling and soft loans for the purchase of efficient appliances.
- Transport: The policy package for transport covers all types of transportation as road transport, rail transport, public transport, bicycling. Nevertheless, the programmes lack of important details and concrete measures. The sector is not well addressed in the NEEAPs. The majority of policy instruments have as principal objectives safety of travel, reduction of harmful emissions, use of biofuels etc. The energy saving effect is considered as an additional benefit.

THE ROLE OF GOVERNANCE AND ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICY PACKAGES ON THE NATIONAL LEVEL

1.1 POLICY PACKAGES AND POLICY GOVERNANCE IN BULGARIA

The main national documents that provide information about energy efficiency policy packages in all sectors in Bulgaria, including buildings and transport, are:

1. First National Energy Efficiency Action Plan 2008 – 2010, June 2007 (MEE 2007)

This Action Plan is the first of the three National Energy Efficiency Action Plans developed in accordance with the Directive 2006/32/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council on energy end-use efficiency and energy services, and sets an indicative energy savings target in 2016.

The plan introduces the measures needed to achieve the indicative target in all sectors.

The plan was prepared by the Ministry of Economy and Energy and the Sustainable Energy Development Agency.

2. Second National Energy Efficiency Action Plan 2011 – 2013, June 2011 (MEET 2011)

This is the second of the three National Energy Efficiency Action Plans developed in accordance with the Directive 2006/32/EC. The achieved savings are reported using the top-down method in order to determine the overall performance in attaining the national indicative target. This assessment includes only energy savings in FEC covered under the scope of the Directive. The plan contains a description of all energy efficiency measures – both the already implemented and the planned ones. The measures are divided by sectors and are presented in the form of a table with detailed description of each one of them.

3. National Energy Efficiency Action Plan 2014 – 2020, July 2014 (MEE 2014)

The National Energy Efficiency Action Plan (MEE 2014) is developed in accordance with the EED requirements and it follows a template including all obligations. The requirements of Directive 2010/31/EU on the energy performance of buildings are also taken into account. The plan sets an energy savings target for 2020 and lays down the policy measures for all sectors, needed for the implementation of EED.

In Bulgaria, the main official national documents describing policy packages for energy efficiency are the National Energy Efficiency Action Plans (NEEAPs).

In fulfilment of the requirements of the previous Energy Efficiency Act (EEA 2015) and in accordance with the provisions of Directive 2006/32/EC (ESD), Bulgaria has adopted an indicative energy saving target of 627 ktoe/y till 2016. Accordingly, Bulgaria developed and implemented a First and a Second three-year National Energy Efficiency Action Plans, containing concrete EE improvement measures at the level of final energy consumption.

The new National Energy Efficiency Action Plan 2014-2020 was developed in accordance with the EED and the recast of EPBD requirements. In this plan Bulgaria sets the following indicative national energy saving targets for the period till 2020:

- Energy savings of 716 ktoe/y at Final Energy Consumption (FEC) level;
- Energy savings of 1590 ktoe/y at Primary Energy Consumption (PEC) level, including 169 ktoe/y in energy transformation, transmission and distribution processes.

1.1.1 Buildings Sector

Objectives

The national indicative energy saving targets for all sectors in Bulgaria are the following:

- In 2013 - 6%/year of the average FEC value in scope of ESD for the period 2001-2005;
- In 2020 7,9%/year of the average FEC value in the scope of EED for the period 2010-2012.

No specific targets for the buildings sector are established in Bulgaria, but buildings are the main focus of energy efficiency policy and measures included in all NEEAPs.

The other objectives of NEEAP in the buildings sector are:

- Transposition of the EU directives – ESD, EED and EPBD recast;
- Improvement of the thermal comfort and/or reduction of the energy costs in residential and public buildings;
- Promotion of the local employment;
- Reduction of GHG and other dangerous emissions.

Synthesis of policy packages

The policy package in the buildings sector targets final consumers in residential and public buildings, and energy dealers on the supply side.

The first (SEDA 2007) and the second (SEDA 2011) NEEAPs which cover the period 2008 – 2013, and the new NEEAP 2014 – 2020 (MEE 2014) include the following energy efficiency measures on the demand side:

- Minimum energy performance standards for residential and public buildings;
- Minimum efficiency standards and labelling of electrical appliances;
- Financial support for energy efficiency in multi-family residential buildings;
- Individual billing and payment of heating energy in multi-family residential buildings;
- Mandatory energy efficiency control for water heating boilers and air-conditioning systems;
- Mandatory energy efficiency audits and certification for public buildings;
- Mandatory annual renovation of 5% of the total area of the central government buildings;
- Determination of the requirements for Nearly Zero Energy Buildings (NZEB) and Programme for NZEB public buildings;
- Individual targets for energy savings under Energy Efficiency Act (EEA 2015) for public buildings owners (only till 2016).
- Obligation scheme for energy dealers with more than 75 GWh annual sales of energy from 2008 to 2014, reduced to 20 GWh annual sales for the period 2014 – 2020. This measure is horizontal and concerns all sectors. No specific target for different sectors is available.

Target groups

Final energy consumers or end-use technologies in the different sectors

The NEEAP (MEE 2014) concerns final consumers in all sectors, but those in the building sector are the principal target group. The approach to residential and public buildings is different.

The existing residential buildings are addressed through financial and informative measures.

The subsidies are directed only towards multifamily residential buildings and individual billing in multifamily buildings connected to district heating and with vertical distribution system. All new residential and public buildings are covered by minimum energy performance standards and the research for national definition and requirements of NZEB.

The owners of the existing public buildings are subject to regulatory policy instruments - mandatory energy efficiency audits and certificates, mandatory annual renovation of 5% of the total area of the central government buildings, development of program for NZEB public buildings and individual obligations for energy savings under the Energy Efficiency Act (EEA 2015).

The principal target group of these regulatory measures includes the existing public buildings with more than 250 m² area. These buildings are concentrated in the urban areas and in the municipalities Sofia, Plovdiv, Varna, Ruse, Burgas etc.

Supply side actors

Energy dealers with more than 75 GWh annual amount of sold energy to the final consumers are already included in the obligation scheme with individual energy saving targets till 2016.

After 2014, with the enactment of the new Energy Efficiency Act (EEA 2015), this limit has been reduced to 20 GWh annual energy sales. The sales of fuels for motor vehicles are excluded from the new obligation scheme.

Governance framework

The “Energy Strategy of the Republic of Bulgaria up to 2020” (MEET 2011) gives highest priority to the energy efficiency policy.

Bulgaria has long experience in energy efficiency policies in the building sector. The first requirements for minimal values of the heat transition coefficient U, W/m²K of the walls, floors, ceilings and glass constructions and building elements were formulated in 1964.

The regulatory framework for the promotion of energy efficiency is described in the Energy Efficiency Act (EEA 2015):

- The Council of Ministers of the Republic of Bulgaria formulates the state policy for promotion of energy efficiency and provision of energy services and adopts National Energy Efficiency Action Plans. It adopts also decrees and decisions on specific subjects. On 02.02.2015, the Council of Ministers adopted with Decree № 18 a “National Programme for Energy Efficiency of Multifamily Residential Buildings” (MRDPW 2015). The programme is developed and proposed by MRDPW and aims at renovation of multifamily residential buildings through the implementation of energy efficiency measures;
- The Ministry of Energy implements the state policy to increase energy efficiency and the provision of energy services;
- The Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works implements the state policy on energy efficiency in buildings including the “National Programme for Energy Efficiency of Multifamily Residential Buildings” (MRDPW 2015b);
- The Sustainable Energy Development Agency (SEDA) implements the activities of the national policy for improving energy efficiency and provision of energy services. It plays an active role in the development of national energy efficiency action plans and elaborates annual reports on their implementation (SEDA, 2014);
- All other ministries and local authorities elaborate plans and programmes for implementation of energy efficiency measures in the building stock owned by them. They submit annual reports on the progress of the execution of these plans to the Executive Director of SEDA. The reports contain description of the activities and measures and indicate the amount of energy savings achieved. They have to be submitted not later than on the 31st day of March of the year following the year of implementation of the respective activities and measures. Information about the implementation of the plans is included in the annual reports prepared by SEDA (SEDA 2015a).

The non-governmental or sub-national actors active in the field of energy efficiency in buildings are:

- The owners of public services buildings with floor area of more than 250 m², and the owners of industrial systems consuming more than 3 000 MWh of energy per annum, have been obligated parties since 2010. Their individual targets until 2016 are not cancelled with the adoption of the new Energy Efficiency Act. The list of the 300 buildings with individual energy saving targets is published on the web-site of SEDA (SEDA 2010a);
- Energy traders with more than 75 GWh annual sales have mandatory individual energy saving targets from 2010 to 2016. According to the new Energy Efficiency Act (EEA 2015) they are obligated parties also in the new obligation scheme from 2014 to 2020. The threshold was reduced to 20 GWh annual sales but transport fuels are excluded. After 2016 the energy traders will remain the only obligated parties. The list of the 54 energy traders with individual energy saving targets is available on the web-site of SEDA (SEDA 2010b);
- Auditors performing energy efficiency audits and certification of buildings, registered in SEDA;
- Regional / local energy agencies;
- ESCOs;
- Energy efficiency funds and credit lines;
- EU funds through the Operational Programmes.

1.1.2 Transport Sector

Objectives

There are no specific targets set for the transport sector in Bulgaria.

NEEAPs do not pay sufficient attention to this sector. The majority of the policy instruments concerning transport have as principal objectives the safety of travel, reduction of harmful emissions, use of biofuels etc. The energy saving effect is considered an additional benefit.

The other objectives of the NEEAP (MEE 2014) related to the transport sector, are:

- Transposition of the EU directives;
- Improvement of the security of energy supply (oil is 100% imported in Bulgaria);
- Reduction of the GHG and other harmful emissions;
- Reduction of the transport congestions.

Synthesis of policy packages

The policy package in the transport sector targets primarily the final consumers.

The principal policy components are the following:

- Mandatory share of biofuels in the fuels for transport;
- Program for improvement of energy efficiency in the transport sector 2012-2020 (MTITC 2012);
- Mandatory technical inspections of vehicles;
- Training of the motor vehicles drivers in economical driving;
- Development of the railroad infrastructure and metro-transport extension;
- Municipal programmes for public transport optimization;
- Construction of bicycle lanes;
- Mandatory speed limits;
- National action plan to promote production and accelerated entry of environmental vehicles including electrical mobility in Bulgaria (Council of Ministers 2012).

Target groups

Final energy consumers or end-use technologies in the different sectors

The principal national target groups in the transport sector include:

- Automobile transport;
- Urban transport;
- Energy efficient modes of transport (rail etc).

Supply side actors

Transport fuel dealers – obligation to sell fuels with mandatory share of biofuels.

Regions and municipalities within the country

The principal target groups are concentrated in the urban areas and in the big urban municipalities.

Governance framework

The institutions responsible for the creation and the implementation of the national regulatory framework for promotion of energy efficiency in the transport sector and their respective obligations are described as follows:

- The Council of Ministers (<http://www.government.bg/>) bears the general responsibility for the sector's development and the energy efficiency in transport. It adopted the National Action Plan to Promote Production and Accelerated Entry of Efficient Vehicles including Electrical Mobility in Bulgaria (MTITC 2012b);
- The Ministry of Transport, Information Technology and Communications (MTITC) is in charge of the energy efficiency in transport. It cooperates with the Ministry of Energy for the development of the transport section of NEEAP (MEE 2014) and controls its implementation. Each year MTITC elaborates the transport part of the Annual Report for the implementation of NEEAP (MEE 2014).

Other responsibilities of this ministry include:

- mandatory technical inspections of vehicles ([MTITC 2014](#));
- training of the motor vehicles drivers in economical driving ([MTITC 2008](#));
- development of the transport infrastructure ([MTITC 2013](#));
- Local authorities are elaborating municipal programmes for public transport, construction of bicycle paths etc.

The plans and programs, developed by the obligated parties are submitted annually to the Executive Director of SEDA and included in the reports for the implementation of NEEAPs.

The non-governmental or sub-national actors active in the field of energy efficiency in transport are:

- Transport fuel traders with more than 75 GWh annual sales, who are obligated parties from 2010 to 2014 and are excluded from the new obligation scheme after 2014;
- Owners of transport companies consuming more than 3 000 MWh of energy per annum, who are obligated parties from 2010 with individual targets till 2016. The list of the transport companies with individual energy saving targets is available on the web-site of SEDA (SEDA 2010b).

1.2 NATIONAL PROGRAMMES AND INITIATIVES

1.2.1 Building sector

National energy efficiency program for multifamily residential buildings (MRDPW 2015b)

a) General information

On 02.02.2015, the Council of Ministers adopted with Decree №18 a “National Programme for Energy Efficiency of Residential Buildings”, the terms and conditions for granting financial assistance under the program, and determined the bodies responsible for its implementation” (MRDPW 2015). The program is aimed at renovation of multifamily residential buildings through implementation of energy efficiency measures. By 11.09.2015 the Associations of Owners had signed 265 contracts with the municipalities.

b) Type of policy instrument

The program is a financial policy instrument and provides 100% subsidy for the energy audit and the implementation of the energy efficiency measures. The total budget of the program is 1 billion BGN.

c) Objectives

The program is aimed at renovation of multifamily residential buildings, as it seeks through the implementation of energy efficiency measures to ensure better living conditions for their residents, thermal comfort and higher quality of living environment. The implementation of energy efficiency measures in multifamily buildings will contribute to:

- the achievement of higher level of energy efficiency and reduced energy costs;
- improved performance to extend the life cycle of buildings;
- ensuring conditions of living environment in accordance with sustainability criteria.

d) Target groups

The target group includes multifamily residential buildings with more than 32 dwellings on the whole territory of the country.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

The grants are received by owners’ associations and cover the full cost of renovation. Exemptions are the single family houses and buildings with less than 32 dwellings.

f) Implementation network

The owners in multifamily buildings register Associations of owners, which sign contracts with the Local Authority to represent them for the exercise of rights and fulfilment of their obligations under the Programme. The Local Authority receives financing from the Bulgarian Development Bank (BDB). After the completion of renovation the respective amounts of the grant are transferred to the BDB from the state budget (the budget of the MRDPW).

The MRDPW is the coordinator of the programme and it regulates the provision of grants, supports the municipalities in the implementation of the program and in the budgetary procedure for the year, and plans the funds to be provided in the national budget.

Mayors of municipalities are responsible for the overall technical and financial administration of the renovation of the buildings located on their territories and perform the following functions:

- negotiate all renovation activities;
- sign contracts for targeted funding with the BDB;
- conduct procedures for the award of the activities for renovation under the Public Procurement Act (PPA 2014) and the applicable regulations.

1.2.2 Transport sector

National Energy Efficiency Action Plan 2014 – 2020 (MEE 2014)

The energy efficiency action plan of transport sector is a part of the National Energy Efficiency Action Plan (MEE 2014).

a) General information

The implementation of the plan for improvement of energy efficiency in the transport sector is under the obligation of the MTITC according to the Energy Efficiency Act (EEA 2015).

b) Type of policy instrument

The plan is a financial policy instrument and supports with subsidies the implementation of energy efficiency measures.

c) Objectives

The energy efficiency projects included in the plan for the companies under the Ministry of Transport, Information Technology and Communications are:

- Repair and reconstruction of cable lines, etc. - estimated amount of electricity saved - 10 MWh/year;
- Installation of "Remote reporting control static electricity in State Company "National Railroad Structure" - expected amount of electricity saved - 10 MWh/year;
- Rehabilitation of the pylon and ramp lighting - the estimated amount of electricity saved - 25 MWh/year;
- Construction of new power supply of electrical railroad structure Danube Bridge - Ruse - expected electricity savings amount - 15 MWh/year;
- Reconstruction of key railway stations (replacement of windows, insulated walls, energy saving measures appliances for measuring, monitoring and control building systems and lighting) - expected energy savings - 145 MWh/year;
- Optimization of motion graphics and fast passenger trains on diesel fuel - expected energy savings - 1 174,43 MWh/year;
- Optimization of motion graphics and fast passenger trains (of electricity) - the estimated amount of electricity saved - 14,608 MWh/year;
- Improvement of efficiency of diesel locomotives by constant monitoring of their performance and regulation of fuel - expected energy savings - 348,84 MWh/yr.

d) Target groups;

The target group includes only rail transport and infrastructure companies under the Ministry of Transport, Information Technology and Communications.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms:

The projects in the plan are included in the Operational Program "Transport" (OPT 2013) financed by EU funds and comply with its rules.

f) Implementation network.

The authority, which is in charge of the implementation of this program, is the MTITC. Reports on its progress are submitted annually to the Executive Director of the SEDA and are included in the National Report for the implementation of the NEEAP.

Municipal programmes for public transport optimization

a) General information

The measure is aimed at the municipal administration of cities with population of more than 100 000 people and its purpose is to stimulate them to develop programmes which will include measures for increasing the effectiveness of the local public transport.

b) Type of policy instrument

The programmes are a financial policy instrument and support with subsidies the implementation of energy efficiency measures. The financing comes from the Operational Program “Regional Development”.

c) Objectives

The purpose is to stimulate the municipalities to develop programmes which will include measures for increasing the effectiveness of the public transport in the cities. They are: training of drivers in economical driving, provision of special roadway for the public transport cars, optimization of public traffic, installation of energy efficient traffic lights, systems for traffic control, etc.

d) Target groups

The target group is the urban transport in cities with population of more than 100 000 people.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms:

The programmes are included in municipal plans for energy efficiency and receive financing from the Operational Program “Regional Development” (OPRD 2013). The projects must comply with the rules of the Operational Program.

f) Implementation network

The information on the implementation of the municipal plans for energy efficiency is submitted annually to the Executive Director of SEDA and is included in the National report for the implementation of the NEEAP.

National action plan to promote production and accelerated entry of environmental vehicles including electrical mobility in Bulgaria 2012-2014 (Council on Ministers 2012)

a) General information

The National Action Plan was adopted by decision №862 of the Council of Ministers on 17.10.2012. Its purpose was to identify the key measures and activities to be implemented to stimulate production and purchase of environmentally friendly vehicles in the country.

b) Type of policy instrument

The Plan is a financial policy instrument, foreseeing:

- For electric vehicles - exemption from annual tax;
- For hybrid cars - exemption from annual tax (not less than 5 years);
- Introduction of preferential fees for initial registration of electric and hybrid cars;
- Release/relief of tolls for the use of road infrastructure;
- Providing a single grant / bonus for individuals and legal persons in the purchase of new green vehicles – 5000 BGN for new electric car and 2500 BGN for new hybrid car.

c) Objectives

The main objectives of the Plan are:

- To stimulate the production of electric and other green vehicles in Bulgaria, including auxiliary equipment and parts;
- To stimulate the research and development activities for the development of environmentally friendly vehicles and charging systems;
- To stimulate the demand for new ecological vehicles;

- Accelerated development of charging infrastructure for electrical vehicles;
- To raise the awareness and the capacity of stakeholders and the public about the nature, purpose and benefits from the sustainable mobility development;
- To promote the development of sustainable urban mobility.

d) Target groups

Target groups in the scope of the Plan are:

- electric vehicles - vehicles that use electric motor with full power and do not have an internal combustion engine;
- hybrid cars - vehicles that use two or more power systems of different types - an electric motor and an internal combustion engine (petrol or diesel);
- vehicles - passenger cars emitting CO₂ emissions to 120 g/km; vans - up to 175 g/km; buses - requirements EURO V.

Preferential treatment plan will be applied to vehicles used for the transport of people and goods and approved for use on the national and local road networks.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

Funding will be provided from the following sources:

- LIFE+ Program (LIFE 2015);
- STEER Program under IEE Framework Programme for Competitiveness and Innovation (CIP 2013);
- Operational Program "Transport" (OPT 2013);
- OP "Competitiveness of the Bulgarian Economy" (OPCBE 2013);
- OP "Regional Development" (OPRD 2013).

f) Implementation network

The implementation network includes – Ministry of Transport, Information Technology and Communications, Ministry of Energy, Ministry of Economy, Ministry of Environment and Waters, Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works, municipalities.

Individual energy saving targets

Article 10 of the Energy Efficiency Act, adopted by the Bulgarian National Assembly on 14.11.2008, determines three groups of obliged persons – energy dealers, public buildings owners and industrial systems owners (EEA 2015). The national indicative target, adopted in the National Energy Efficiency Action Plan (MEE 2014), is distributed among these three groups of obliged persons.

The obliged energy dealers include 52 companies. Their total energy savings target till 2016 is 4 644 GWh, which makes 64% of the national indicative target.

According to the EEA requirements, the energy dealers are obliged to submit to the Sustainable Energy Development Agency (SEDA) information about the activities and measures to reduce energy consumption every year until 31 March the next year (EEA 2015).

The methods for proving the achieved energy savings are energy audits or specialized methods adopted by the Council of Ministers. These methods could be applied only by companies authorized according to the requirements of the Energy Efficiency Act (EEA 2015).

SEDA is the institution which issues the certificates for achieved energy savings.

On the basis of the received in SEDA annual information from the obliged energy dealers, the achieved energy savings are shown in the table below.

Table 1: Summary of the effect of the measure implementation

	1st NEEAP 2008-2010	2nd NEEAP 2011-2013	NEEAP 2014	Total
Energy savings, GWh/year	809,0	934,4	173	1 916,4

1.2.3 Energy Efficiency Obligation Scheme

A “Methodology for the operation of the energy efficiency obligation schemes” (SEDA 2009) has been developed in accordance with the requirements of Article 7 of Directive 2012/27/EU on energy efficiency.

With the new Energy Efficiency Act (EEA 2015) the threshold for the obligated parties becomes:

- end suppliers, suppliers of last resort, traders selling electrical energy to final consumers more than 20 GWh per year;
- district heating companies and suppliers, which sell heat to final consumers more than 20 GWh per year;
- end suppliers and traders of natural gas selling to end users more than 1 million nm³ per year;
- liquid fuels traders selling to the end consumers more than 6,5 kt liquid fuels per year, with the exception of fuel for transport purposes;
- solid fuel traders who sell to end consumers more than 13 kt solid fuels per year.

In order to reach their individual targets, the obligated parties may implement energy saving measures in all final customer sectors — industry, transport, households, commerce, civil society organizations, agriculture, forestry and fishery, services, etc. The obligated parties may implement measures that achieve energy savings in the energy transformation, distribution and transmission sectors, including by means of efficient district heating and cooling systems infrastructure.

Table 2 shows the energy sales to final customers (equivalent to final energy consumption (FEC) in the three-year period from 2010 to 2012, based on the available data from the National Statistical Institute, and the average sales levels in the same period, excluding all sales to the transport sector.

Table 2: Average energy sales to final users in the period 2010-2012, ktoe

Indicator	2010	2011	2012	Average
FEC excl. transport	5 990	6 337	6 173	6 167

In the period 2014-2020, the minimum combined amount of energy savings achieved by all energy traders must include new energy savings equal to 1,5% of the annual amount of energy sold to all final customers. The obligations calculated for each year, both with and without full use of the 25% reduction permitted by Article 7(2), are given in Table 3.

Table 3: Breakdown of the obligation scheme by year (2014-2020), ktoe

Year	Obligations excl. transport	Obligations excl. transport and with full use of the 25% reduction permitted by Article 7(2)
2014	92,50	69,38
2015	185,00	138,75
2016	277,50	208,13
2017	370,00	277,50
2018	462,50	346,88
2019	555,00	416,25

2020	647,50	485,63
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In order to reach their targets, the obligated parties may implement horizontal measures aimed at increasing the energy efficiency of final customers, such as awareness and promotional campaigns. They may also pay contributions to the Energy Efficiency and Renewable Sources Fund or other specialised funds, programmes, measures, schemes and mechanisms used to finance measures to increase the energy efficiency of final customers, including agreements concluded with beneficiaries.

1.3 CONCLUSIONS AND LESSONS LEARNED OF OTHER PROJECTS ABOUT THE PERFORMANCE OF THE NATIONAL POLICY PACKAGES FOR ENERGY EFFICIENCY

1.3.1 Energy Efficiency Watch

The main objective of the Energy Efficiency Watch 3 project (EEW3) is to facilitate the implementation of the Energy Efficiency Directive (EED) across the EU and provide a constant feedback loop on the implementation of the European and national energy efficiency policies. To this end, EEW3 attempts to activate, consult and interface core networks (including parliamentarians, local and regional levels, business stakeholders and experts), do surveys, questionnaires and NEEAPs screening and analyse broad stakeholders input.

The project started on 19 August 2014 and will run until 18 August 2017.

The overall energy efficiency policy of Bulgaria is not overly ambitious. However, the policy packages designed for specific sectors (public sector, industry, governance) are promising. Further improvements could be recommended, i.e.:

- Introduction in the NEEAP of measures related to mobility management in public sector.
- Inclusion of particular information tools and education and training offers for retail staff and other actors of the supply chain in the policy package for appliances.
- With regard to the residential sector it is advisable to pay more attention to the provision of impartial advice and audits, the mandatory display of energy performance certificates in transactions (including advertisements) and the development of information tools for the buildings sector. It is furthermore recommended to clarify whether and when minimum energy performance standards are to be tightened (roadmap).
- Rising of excise duties on gas and electricity for business use as a means to strengthen incentives for the efficient use of energy.
- In the field of transport it is recommended to strengthen regulatory instruments, information and advice as well as R&D.

In 2011 and 2012, under Energy Efficiency Watch a quantitative and qualitative survey among the national experts on implementation of energy efficiency policies in the EU Member States was conducted (Egger 2012).

The overall ambition of the Bulgarian energy efficiency policy is rated medium-low. Only around 30% of the respondents (9 questionnaires were completed for Bulgaria) consider the Bulgarian policy as generally ambitious or at least ambitious in a range of sectors. Around 75% of the respondents think that progress over the last three years was rather low (no progress or only few additional policies). 60% of the respondents thus expect that the ESD target will not be reached or, if reached, will not lead to significant savings. The greatest gaps are reported for the transport and residential sectors. Financing is considered to be the greatest barrier to energy efficiency.

A general concern of respondents is that energy efficiency is not given sufficient political priority at national level.

With regard to buildings, respondents report a high need for building refurbishment and insufficient funding for this challenge. However, they also state that building legislation has a stronger focus on energy efficiency due to European Directives and that some funding programmes are available (partly from European structural funds). Experts are nonetheless concerned about the lack of an overall strategy for tackling energy efficiency in the residential sector. Respondents request a combination of legislation, funding programmes and information measures - all these instruments were considered to be currently insufficient.

According to the experts, the public sector lacks of resources, skills and partly also of interest regarding energy efficiency. It was positively noted that some municipalities had implemented energy efficiency projects.

Regarding transport sector, the need of improved public transport was mentioned as well as better mobility management.

In line with the result that financing is reported to be the greatest barrier to energy efficiency in Bulgaria, a great majority of 67% of the respondents considers energy efficiency funds as partly or very effective. However, energy audits are referred to by even more interviewees as an effective or at least partly effective instrument (78%) (Wuppertal, 2009), (EEW 2013).

1.3.2 ODYSSEE-MURE - Monitoring of Energy Efficiency in EU 27, Norway and Croatia

Financing instrument: Co-funded by the “Intelligent Energy - Europe” Programme of the European Union.

Partners: 33 partners from 28 EU countries, coordinated by ADEME (France).

Objectives: The main aim of the project is to provide easy accessed information on energy consumption and its trends and to evaluate the policy framework of the EU countries and Norway. The information gathered is stored in a web database, where the users have the option to evaluate and compare the energy efficiency progress, split by all sectors and energy end uses. This allows also the comparison with the observed trends in the energy consumption. The database contributes to the implementation evaluation of the National Energy Efficiency Action Plans (NEEAPs) through analysis of the national policies dynamics.

ODYSSEE is a database providing data on energy consumption, their drivers and energy efficiency indicators collected for all EU countries (and Norway) with datasets updated to 2012.

MURE is a database on energy efficiency policies and measures, which also includes recent proposed measures for the 3rd National Energy Efficiency Action Plans.

Scope: The Odyssee Mure database covers 28 countries and Norway. Mostly the consortium is consisted of national energy agencies or their representatives within the European network of energy efficiency agencies. It provides data for the energy end uses, the trends in the energy consumption and the policy framework implementation in each country. These tools support the energy efficiency experts, decision makers and all actors involved in the energy efficiency field.

Results: The project provides databases, analyses, and trends of the energy consumption per sector (households, services, industry, transport) that are basis for decisions of policy makers in the field of energy efficiency.

1.3.3 Refurbishment of the Public Building Stock Towards nZEB (RePublic_ZEB)

Financing instrument: Co-funded by the “Intelligent Energy – Europe” Programme of the European Union, <http://www.republiczeb.org/>.

Partners: 12 partners from 11 countries (Italy, Bulgaria, UK, Spain, Greece, Portugal, Romania, FYROM, Slovenia, Croatia, Hungary), coordinated by CTI (Italy).

Objectives: The main objectives of the project are to assess the state-of-the-art of the public buildings stock, based on energy consumption and CO₂ emissions, to develop a common framework and harmonised methodology for national definition of Near-zero energy buildings (nZEB), and to propose strategies and guidelines towards development of the nZEB market.

Scope: The RePublic_ZEB covers 10 target countries of the Mediterranean region and South-East Europe as they have identical climate conditions, energy needs for heating and cooling and RES potential.

The following working plan will support the targets achieving:

- analysis of the public building stock and definition of reference buildings;
- assessment of the status quo and analysis of opportunities for refurbishing public buildings towards nZEB;
- costs/benefits analysis of the "packages of measures" for the refurbishment towards nZEB;
- strategies and guidelines towards nZEBs;
- involvement of stakeholders and authorities;
- communication and dissemination.

Results: Bulgaria adopted a national definition of a nearly zero energy building in May 2015. It states that the nearly zero energy building is the one to have energy certificate Class A and 55 percent of its energy demand must be produced from RES on-site or nearby. After analysing the opportunities for building refurbishment towards nZEB, the partners developed “packages of measures” to facilitate the decision making process of all refurbishment actors. Several packages of measures are proposed taking into account the technologies that had been collected according to the different levels of refurbishment of the reference building categories in each target country. Among the proposed packages, typical combinations of energy efficiency measures exist, which represent the currently applied refurbishment local practice, as well as those combinations of innovative measures that represent a high level of energy efficiency. The quality of the packages will be analysed from an energy efficiency and economic perspective. It is planned to optimize the packages through building energy simulation. The Republic ZEB will offer also guidelines and solutions to promote successfully these technologies, which will be of substantial importance for the development of the local markets.

1.3.4 ENTRANZE – Policies to Enforce the Transition to Nearly Zero Energy buildings in the EU-27

Financing instrument: Co-funded by the “Intelligent Energy – Europe” Programme of the European Union.

Partners: 10 partners from 9 countries (Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Finland, France, Germany, Italy, Spain), coordinated by TU – Wien (Austria).

Objectives: The main objective of the project was to actively support policy making process by providing the required data, analysis of the energy consumption and CO₂ emissions and developing of guidelines to expand the nZEB and RES H/C penetration within the existing national building stocks. The project intended to establish a good network connection among building experts from European research and academia to national decision makers and key stakeholders and actors in order to set ambitious targets, but still representing the real conditions of buildings construction and renovation markets.

The core part of the project was the dialogue with policy makers and experts and focused on 9 countries, covering >60% of the EU-27 building stock. Data, scenarios and recommendations were also provided for EU-28 (+ Serbia).

Scope: The project targeted the policy and decision makers and all energy efficiency key actors to support them through:

- Acquiring new skills and knowledge for including nZEB technologies in the instruments for supporting building renovations;

- Having at their disposal a data instrument for taking proper decision;
- Exchanging know-how with advanced countries.

Results: The main conclusions and recommendations of the project are:

- Clear vision with clear targets until 2050 are needed for the energy performance of the building stock in order to develop target-oriented policy packages. Up to now only a few countries have adopted such targets.
- The technology-specific barriers and the heterogeneous target groups should be properly addressed through various policy and other packages of instruments.
- The huge lack of data regarding renovation activities and the energy performance of buildings leads to inappropriate planning. There is a need of building a data observatory, in particular for monitoring policy impacts.
- The EPBD (recast) is a first attempt to create a comparable framework for EU MS, nevertheless, further enhancement of the European and national legislations is necessary.
- In particular, an enhanced EPBD framework should set requirements for cost optimality to represent the absolute minimum requirements for existing regulations in the building codes. The nZEB energy performance levels should be cost-effective, but they still have to be more ambitious than cost-optimal energy performance levels. Thus, an enhanced EPBD has to be very precise in asking MS to present plans to close the gap between nZEB target levels in 2020 and the cost-optimal levels of current building codes.
- The EPBD should also gradually increase the binding character of nZEB requirements for existing buildings. Thus, a clear definition of nZEB or deep renovation is also required.
- Consistency in terminology and timing between Directives and CEN standardisation procedures should be further enhanced.

1.3.5 Improving dwellings by enhancing actions on labeling for the EPBD (IDEAL-EPBD)

Financing instrument: Co-funded by the “Intelligent Energy – Europe” Programme of the European Union.

Partners: 9 partners from The Netherlands, Denmark, Belgium, Finland, Germany, Bulgaria, Latvia, Czech Republic, coordinated by ECN (The Netherlands).

Objectives: The objective of the project is to contribute to increasing the effect of the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) for existing private dwellings, by defining and disseminating policy recommendations. Particular objectives:

- Monitoring the first results of labelling of existing, privately owned dwellings (<1000 m²) under the EPBD
- Provision of feedback on the implementation of the EPBD to policy makers, energy agencies and actors professionally involved in the energy efficiency improvement of dwellings, through organization of workshops for professionals and policy makers.
- Provision of recommendations for further improvement of EPBD.

Scope: The project studied the effectiveness of energy labels and energy audit reports. It also focused on drivers and barriers to energy efficiency renovations. The main research methods were in-depth interviews and electronic questionnaires among dwelling owners. Based on this research, policy recommendations have been developed to increase the effectiveness of energy labels for private dwellings and to support homeowner’s decision-making and implementation of energy efficiency measures. The results mainly target policymakers on national and regional/local level but also other stakeholders engaged and interested in energy efficiency in homes.

Results: The main recommendations for policy-makers in Bulgaria are as follows:

- Relatives, friends, and neighbours play a crucial role on the decision making related to home renovation. The good service and high quality works stimulate positive word-of-mouth, which

bad experiences have negative effect. This is one important reason for policy makers to make sure that advice, products and services are always of high quality and that knowledgeable professionals are involved.

- Associations of building owners in multifamily buildings need to be established to facilitate the decision making process concerning building renovation.
- The main stimuli to support building certification – the property tax exemption available for buildings with high energy performance - need to be revised.
- It is advisable to support the establishment of a competitive market for energy efficiency works in the smaller towns (e.g. publicly available list of companies carrying out renovation works in each locality)
- It is necessary to increase the awareness regarding energy saving, environmental protection, and their connection with the domestic energy consumption; particularly – to emphasize on the importance to consider the energy performance of a building at the time it is purchased or rented.

INTERACTION BETWEEN THE NATIONAL AND THE SUB-NATIONAL LEVELS

The energy efficiency policy in Bulgaria is implemented also by the local authorities. They are obliged to elaborate municipal energy efficiency plans and programmes for their implementation for a specified period. These plans are reported to SEDA and included in the report on the implementation of NEEAP (SEDA 2015).

The reports contain description of the activities and measures and indicate the amount of energy savings achieved. They shall be submitted to the Executive Director of SEDA not later than on the 31st day of March every year.

In the residential buildings sector, the local authorities are in charge of the overall technical and financial administration of the renovation of the buildings located on their territories, which receive funding through the “National energy efficiency program for multifamily residential buildings” (MRDPW 2015b). Their functions include:

- negotiation of all renovation activities;
- signing of contracts for targeted funding with BDB;
- conduction of procedures for the award of the activities for renovation under the Public Procurement Act and the applicable regulations.

The non-governmental or sub-national actors active in the field of energy efficiency in buildings and transport are:

- Energy traders with more than 75 GWh annual sales, owners of public services buildings with floor area of more than 250 m² and owners of industrial systems consuming more than 3 000 MWh of energy per annum, who are obligated parties with individual energy saving targets till 2016. In the new Energy Efficiency Act the energy traders are the only obligated parties after 2016 and the threshold was reduced to 20 GWh;
- Auditors registered in SEDA, who perform mandatory energy efficiency audits and certification of buildings at industrial systems with more than 3 000 MWh annual energy consumption. In the new Energy Efficiency Act all companies which are not Small and Medium Enterprises, perform mandatory energy efficiency audits (EEA 2015);
- Regional / local energy agencies are very active;
- ESCOs;
- Energy efficiency funds and Credit line;
- Transport fuel traders implement the requirement for mandatory share of biofuels in the fuels for transport.

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HERON project (No: 649690): Deliverable D.1.1

LANDSCAPE OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICY PACKAGES IN A MULTI-LEVEL GOVERNMENT SYSTEM

**PART OF WORK PACKAGE 1: MAPPING OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICY INSTRUMENTS AND
AVAILABLE TECHNOLOGIES IN BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT**

NATIONAL REPORT FOR ESTONIA

DATE: 11.AUGUST 2015

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HERON: Forward – looking socio-economic research on Energy Efficiency in EU countries

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649690. The content of this document reflects only the authors' views and the EASME is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

Contents

ACRONYMS	4
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	5
1. THE ROLE OF GOVERNANCE AND ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICY PACKAGES ON THE NATIONAL LEVEL	6
1.1 POLICY PACKAGES AND POLICY GOVERNANCE IN EUROPEAN MEMBER STATES.....	6
1.1.1 Buildings Sector	6
1.1.2 Transport Sector	10
1.2 National Programmes and Initiatives.....	15
1.2.1 Green Investment Scheme implementation in building sector	15
1.2.2 Green Investment Scheme in transport sector	17
1.2.3 ELMO – Estonian Electromobility Programme in transport sector	19
1.3 Conclusions and Lessons Learned of other Projects about the Performance of the National Policy Packages for Energy Efficiency	20
1.3.1 Buildings sector	20
1.3.2 Transport sector	22
2. INTERACTION BETWEEN THE NATIONAL AND THE SUB-NATIONAL LEVELS	24
REFERENCES.....	25

Table of Tables

Table 1 Transport sector’s energy consumption targets in Estonia	11
Table 2 Estonia’s Green Investment Scheme Transactions 2010-12.....	16
Table 3 GIS programs regarding transport and energy efficiency	18
Table 4 Summary of energy efficiency recommendations	21
Table 5 IEA energy efficiency recommendations for Estonia in transport sector.....	23

ACRONYMS

AAU	- Assigned Amount Units under UN FCCC
DH	- District heating
EIC	- Environmental Investment Centre
ELMO	- Estonian Electro-Mobility Programme
ENMAK	- Estonian National Energy Sector Development Plan
GIS	- Green Investment Scheme
EPBD	- Energy Performance of Buildings
EPC	- Energy Performance Certificates
EU ETS	- EU Emissions Trading Scheme
EV	- Electric Vehicle
JI	- Joint Implementation
KIK	- Estonian Environmental Investment Fund
KredEx	- Credit and Export Guarantee Fund
LEB	- Low-Energy Building
MEAC	- The Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communication
NEEAP	- National Energy Efficiency Action Plan
nZEB	- nearly Zero-Energy Buildings
ODEX	- Energy efficiency index of industry
RKAS	- State Real Estate Company Ltd (Riigi Kinnisvara AS)
SEAP	- Sustainable Energy Action Plan
UNFCCC	- United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The energy efficiency targets for the buildings sector are given in two major national programmes. Firstly, The National Reform Programme “Estonia 2020” describes the objectives established to improve competitiveness and activities needed to achieve these objectives. Final energy consumption is targeted to remain at the level of 2010 in 2020. This means that energy efficiency must be significantly raised in particular in the buildings sector. The Estonian government has made tangible progress in meeting the targets set so far. Starting from 2013 more stringent energy efficiency requirements established to new and reconstructed buildings by Ministry of Economy and Communication, having overall responsibility in energy efficiency. Implementation of the requirements of EPBD Directive is foreseen in the first order in public buildings to reach the maximum energy efficiency and to demonstrate the example. The reform programme includes the implementation of the investment package for energetic refurbishment of multiple apartment houses, also the fuel switch subsidies from oil to more efficient types of fuels in private houses.

Secondly, the Estonian National Development Plan of the Energy Sector until 2030 (ENMAK 2030+) with the vision till 2050 is one of the central strategic documents which fix the main pathways of development of many other programmes. ENMAK 2030+ draws the main concept lines of energy sector development up till 2030. The programme is the most updated document describing, in fact, the vision of possible development paths of all sectors including the buildings. Detailed description on existing stock of buildings is given based on what the further development paths for energy saving are formulated. Technical energy saving potential forms around 80% (9.3 TWh/y) of present energy consumption of buildings and it comprises roughly 1/3 of total final energy consumption (33-34 TWh/y) in Estonia

The energy efficiency target for the transport sector is set in the Estonian Transport Development Plan 2014–2020: to retain the transport sector’s energy consumption by the year 2020 on the level of the year 2012 and to create a basis for reducing energy consumption after the year 2020. The measures described in the strategy target both supply and demand-side management and cover all three efficiency dimensions: system efficiency, travel efficiency and vehicle efficiency. Green Investment Schemes have been an important national program in the transport sector enabling transport sector energy efficiency investment. The report presents transport schemes supported by GIS and the biggest national program related to transport energy efficiency – Estonian electro-mobility program ELMO that has supported the purchase of 1164 EV-s in Estonia, including 507 iMiEVs for social workers all over Estonia, providing a network of 165 quick chargers and ELMO rent system.

Most international transport energy efficiency related projects highlight the high potential of energy saving in transport sector. ODYSSEY-MURE project concluded that the energy efficiency index ODEX for transport in Estonia has increased by 17.3% (from 2000 to 2010) meaning that the energy intensity has increased. The difference of energy intensity of transport in Estonia and the EU is very essential: in Estonia 0.087 kg oe/EUR2000 and the EU average 0.032 kg oe/EUR2000 in 2010. IEA and OECD have recommended Estonian government to implement more policies related to transport energy efficiency including mandatory vehicle fuel efficiency standards, measures to improve vehicle fuel efficiency, improving operational efficiency through eco-driving and other measures.

1. THE ROLE OF GOVERNANCE AND ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICY PACKAGES ON THE NATIONAL LEVEL

1.1 POLICY PACKAGES AND POLICY GOVERNANCE IN EUROPEAN MEMBER STATES

1.1.1 Buildings Sector

Official documents, national programmes, strategies, action plans etc., give the targets for further improvement in energy saving and energy efficiency in buildings sector in a different way. Some of them give qualitative assessments or brief general descriptions only and suggest the overall improvement approaches. The others introduce the numerical data on the energy saving or efficiency targets up till 2020 or 2030. Energy efficiency has been referred as a priority or an objective in a number of national development plans, policy documents and reports to European Commission.

The Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communications is responsible for the elaboration and implementation of 12 different strategic documents for Estonia which are listed on MEAC website (MEAC, 2015). Seven of them are related to energy efficiency issues in buildings and/or transport sectors. The Ministry of the Environment quotes to energy efficiency in its two National Communications to UN FCCC as the prevailing share of greenhouse gas emissions is due to inefficient generation of energy based on local fossil fuel, oil shale. In the following these main national official documents are listed;

- National Real Estate Strategy, approved in 2007. The strategy is aimed to better usage of state-owned real estate and drafts the further development path, representing Estonia's strategy to achieve the "Europe 2020" objectives;
- Estonian National Housing Development Plan 2008 – 2013. Prepared by the MEAC, the Ministry of Justice and Kredex in 2007;
- Estonia's Fifth National Communication under the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change. Prepared by the Estonian Ministry of the Environment and the Estonian Environmental Research Centre in 2009.
- Estonian Renewable Energy Action Plan for 2020 (NREAP), 2010, in accordance with Directive 2009/28/EC on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources;
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- National Energy Efficiency Action Plan (NEEAP), 2014. Estonia's Communication to the European Commission under Article 24(2) of Directive 2012/27/EU;
- Estonian National Development Plan of the Energy Sector until 2030 (with the vision up to 2050). Prepared by the Estonian Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communication in 2014;
- Strategic Environmental Impact Assessment of the Estonian National Development Plan of the Energy Sector until 2030. 2015. Prepared by I. Möldre, Estonian Development Fund.
- "Estonia 2020", The National Reform Programme, finally approved in 2015. The programme (2050) to be submitted for approval to Estonian Government and Parliament in 2015.

The National Real Estate Strategy main targets are to improve the development of the real estate property which belongs to state from ecological, economic and spatial planning point of views. To ensure the maintenance of real estate in a best possible way considering economic efficiency and highest technical standards for maintenance including energy efficiency. The strategy foresees the implementation of energy saving technologies and construction materials to be used in newly built office buildings (Riigi ..., 2007). The strategy has been compiled by the Estonian Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communication in close cooperation with The Estonian Union of Co-operative Housing Associations (<http://www.ekyl.ee/?lang=en>).

The Estonian National Housing Development Plan for 2008-2013 constitutes a strategic basis for developing the housing sector. It has set out the directions and principles for resolving the individual issues specific to the housing sector. The principal aims in the field of housing are ensuring access to suitable and affordable housing for the population of Estonia, achieving high quality and sustainable housing stock and building diversified residential areas which are developing following the principles of sustainable development. The Plan was prepared in close cooperation with the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communications, the Ministry of Social Affairs, the Ministry of Internal Affairs, the Ministry of Justice and the Credit and Export Guarantee Fund KredEx. The objectives and measures of the Development Plan served as a basis for planning the state budget resources as well as for funding from the EU Structural Funds and the Cohesion Fund during the period of 2007-2013. The more important individual activities and courses of action have been identified for the near term. A detailed implementation plan has been developed on an annual basis in line with the state budget strategy (Estonian ..., 2008). See for more at Baltic Energy Efficiency Network for the building Stock (BEEN) project webpage at: <http://www.been-online.net/Mitglieder-des-Netzwerks.250.0.html?&L=1>.

Estonia's Fifth National Communication under the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change has been prepared by the Estonian Ministry of the Environment and the Estonian Environmental Research Centre in cooperation of universities and research institutions in 2009 (Estonian ..., 2009). The communication quotes on energy efficiency issues in relation with the environmental pollution spectrum and in particular the emissions due to energy generation based on main local energy carrier, oil shale.

The National Renewable Energy Action Plan until year 2020 is a comprehensive development plan summarizing the national renewable energy policies, forecasting final energy consumption and setting out renewable energy targets and forecast trajectories until 2020. It has been worked out by the Estonian Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communication (Eesti ..., 2010). The Action Plan is one of the fundamental documents for achieving the European Union Renewables Directive (2009/28/EC) targets and gives a comprehensive outlook of the development of the renewables sector. It has been worked out by the MEAC. The International Energy Agency web-page (National..., 2010) describes the Estonia's renewable energy 2020 targets as follows:

- Overall target: 25% of renewable energy in final consumption;
- Heating and Cooling: 18% of demand met by renewable energy sources;
- Electricity: 5% of electricity demand met by electricity generated from renewable energy sources;
- Transport: 3% of energy demand met by renewable energy sources.

Estonia has introduced a number of measures facilitating achievement of above enlisted targets, they could be listed as the following (National..., 2010):

- Feed-in tariff;
- Certificate of origin;
- Excise duty exemption for biofuels;
- Investment support for RES projects;
- National Energy Technology Programme – ETP;

As for the share of renewable energy in final consumption Estonia has reached the set target by today, also the present share of renewable energy sources based electricity generation is very close to 2020 target.

Estonia's sixth National Communication under the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change has been prepared by the Estonian Ministry of the Environment and Estonian Environmental Research Centre in 2013 (Estonian ..., 2013). Also the sixth communication quotes on energy efficiency issues in relation to the greenhouse gases emissions due to the energy generation based on main local energy carrier, oil shale (Estonian..., 2013).

Estonia's second National Energy Efficiency Action Plan (NEEAP) was prepared by Ministry of Economy and Communications as pursuant to Directive 2006/32/EC. NEEAP listed 99 energy efficiency measures in eight policy areas, including 34 measures in the buildings sector; seven in the public sector (except buildings); 12 in industry; 14 in the energy sector; 17 in transport; four in household appliances and the service sector; four in agriculture and seven in other areas. The largest reductions in energy use are expected to come from the following sectors (NEEAP, 2014):

- buildings: 3.5 PJ;
- transport: 2.5 PJ from changing motor fuels to biofuels.
- industry: 2.2 PJ; comprising 0.9 PJ ordinary fuels, 0.7 PJ electricity and 0.6 PJ heat;

Energy Efficiency Watch conducted a qualitative and quantitative survey with the help of national experts in the field of energy efficiency policies implementation in EU Member States. This comprehensive overview covered both the buildings and the transport sector. As a result 11 experts answered in the interviews on National Energy Efficiency Action Plan that Estonia has made very good progress in energy efficiency policies since the First NEEAP and is among the three best Member States. 55 % of the experts believe that the national energy savings target is likely to be achieved. Positive developments reported include the increased availability of funds (especially from emission trading), more businesses active in energy efficiency sector (especially building renovation and energy services) and more use of CHP. However, the critical issues include the lack of a coherent framework for energy efficiency, capacity in the public sectors, binding targets, financing and funding programmes (Egger C. et al., 2012).

"Estonia 2020", The National Reform Programme is a reform programme that describes the objectives established to improve competitiveness and activities needed to achieve these objectives. Final energy consumption is targeted to remain at the level of 2010 in 2020. For the buildings sector this means that energy efficiency must be significantly raised in particular in the buildings sector. The Estonian government has made tangible progress in meeting the targets set so far. Starting from 2013 more stringent energy efficiency requirements established to new and reconstructed buildings by MEAC. Implementation of the requirements of EPBD Directive is foreseen in the first order in public

buildings to reach the maximum energy efficiency and to demonstrate the example. The reform programme includes the implementation of the investment package for energetic refurbishment of apartment houses, also the fuel switch subsidies from oil to more efficient types of fuels in private houses and subsidy programme for energetic refurbishment of small private houses (Eesti 2020 ..., 2015).

The Estonian National Development Plan of the Energy Sector until 2030 (ENMAK 2030+) with the vision till 2050 is one of the central strategic documents which fix the main pathways of development of many other programmes. It has been approved by the Government already, and next it will be approved by the Parliament, most probably in the second half of 2015. ENMAK 2030+ draws the main concept lines of energy sector development up till 2030, but also the vision for development up till 2050. The programme is the most updated document describing, in fact, the vision of possible development paths of all sectors including the buildings. Detailed description on existing stock of buildings is given based on what the further development paths for energy saving are formulated. Technical energy saving potential forms around 80% (9.3 TWh/y) of present energy consumption of buildings and it comprises roughly 1/3 of total final energy consumption (33-34 TWh/y) in Estonia (Housing..., 2015). The development plan has been prepared by the MEAC within the close cooperation of other ministries, governmental institutions, universities and research institutes who took part in the preparatory seminars and brainstorming on voluntary basis. Also, the whole preparatory process was organised web-based to allow experts and wider public to participate in the specialised discussions and propose their comments and opinions on further development options of the energy sector (Energiatalgud..., 2015).

All national development plans have to pass the Environmental Impact Assessment. Thus is also valid for the abovementioned energy sector development plan.

Strategic Environmental Impact Assessment of the Estonian National Development Plan of the Energy Sector until 2030 was prepared by the Estonian Development Fund. The latter was also responsible to organize the practical work to prepare the material for the long term energy sector development plan. The impact assessment deals with the energy efficiency tasks related to electricity and heat generation and usage in various economic sectors. Among the major tasks under consideration, the heat generation efficiency for housing sector via continuing the sustainable maintenance of the district heating networks, also the options and long term perspectives to increase the renewable energy share in transport sector were analysed (Energiamaajanduse..., 2015).

Synthesis of policy packages

In buildings sector some examples could be brought. The National Housing development Plan is closely linked to the National Renewable Energy Action Plan and Estonia's Second National Energy Efficiency Action Plan. The governmental institutions closely cooperate in implementation of strategies and action plans which main lines coincide.

Target groups

The above listed programmes, action plans, strategies etc. do not specifically target on certain group at national, regional or local level. They tend to be rather general towards all levels. It is common that none of the official documents specify the target group, instead they include the general principles to be taken for the basis in regional or local level implementation practices. The 2020 targets in various sectors are handled as nationwide and are regulated with governmental and other legislative acts and local governments' decrees.

Governance framework

The governance framework in Estonia functions quite well. The ministries are cooperating in their common interest areas, they coordinate with each other when working out strategies, compiling development plans, action plans, they, also cooperate in the phase of practical implementation.

The Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communication (MEAC) holds the overall accountability for energy efficiency policy. There are two departments responsible for the most of tasks related to energy efficiency, district heating and renewable energy policies – the Energy Department, and the Building and Housing Department. The ministry works closely with two relevant executive agencies in the field of energy efficiency, Credit and Export Guarantee Fund KredEX and EIC (Environmental Investment Centre). The first working with targeted measures in residential housing sector and electromobility programme, and the another implements the measures targeting public infrastructure (heat and electricity generation), energy distribution systems and street lighting. Both agencies work with the issues linked to the promotion of energy efficiency (Energy..., 2013).

The Ministry of the Environment is increasingly involved in energy policy its' responsibility includes the development of green public procurement rules and guidelines for the purchase of energy-efficient goods. The two ministries keep close cooperation and coordination of energy and environment policy developments. The Energy and Water Regulatory Division of the Estonian Competition Authority carries out the promotion of energy efficiency through energy tariffs. The Estonian Development Fund has a unit working on long-term development in the energy sector (Energy ..., 2013).

The Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communication, the Ministry of the Environment and the Ministry of Finance together with state governed foundations Estonian Development Fund, Credit and Export Guarantee Fund KredEX and Enterprise Estonia work in close cooperation in the field of energy efficiency of buildings. The institutions support mutual activities in case their areas of interest coincide. An example could be brought about wider deployment of solar energy foreseen in National Development Plan of the Energy Sector until 2030 and also, this priority is fixed in the NREAP. The responsible ministries coordinate their action plans towards achieving the target.

There are two Energy agencies, one in Tallinn municipality – Tallinn Energy Agency, another in Tartu, Tartu Regional Energy Agency, both working with buildings' energy efficiency issues and proceed with training and wider scope information dissemination in improving energy efficiency at local level. However, for the successful work they still lack appropriate number of staff and relevant financing. The energetic refurbishment has gained high popularity in almost at all local governments. Estonia is lacking the national Energy Agency at present, still it was founded in 2009 under governance of MEAC and it functioned for two years only. The main task of the agency was to continue the energetic refurbishment work what Kredex housing department has started earlier.

1.1.2 Transport Sector

The main national official documents describing policy packages for energy efficiency in the transport sector are:

- National Development Plan for Energy Sector till 2030, with the vision till 2050 (to be submitted for approval to Estonian Government and Parliament) (ENMAK 2030+, 2015);
- Estonian Transport Development Plan 2014–2020, approved by the Estonian Parliament on 19 February 2014 (Transpordi... 2014);
- National Energy Efficiency Action Plan (NEEAP), 2014. Estonia's Communication to the European Commission under Article 24(2) of Directive 2012/27/EU. (NEEAP, 2014)

- The national reform programme “Estonia 2020”, approved in 2011. Estonia’s strategy for achieving the “Europe 2020” objectives. (National... 2015)

These documents are described below.

The National Energy Sector Development Plan; “ENMAK 2030+ Eesti energiamajanduse arengukava aastani 2030¹”. (ENMAK 2030+), compiled by Ministry of Economy and Communications is currently in the final draft version (13.02.2015) to be presented to the Parliament. It describes the vision for transport energy consumption in 2050 as follows:

The energy efficiency and environmental sustainability of transport has increased through the interaction between various measures, uptake of energy saving technologies, increased use of alternative fuels and partial modal shift of freight transport to rail.

The energy efficiency target for the transport sector is set in the Estonian **Transport Development Plan 2014–2020**; “Transpordi arengukava 2014-2020²”. (Compiled by Ministry of Economy and Communications and approved by the Parliament on 19.2.2014): to retain the transport sector’s energy consumption by the year 2020 on the level of the year 2012 and to create a basis for reducing energy consumption after the year 2020.

Table 1 Transport sector’s energy consumption targets in Estonia

Indicator / Year	Initial level 2012	Interim level 2017	Target level 2020
Transport sector’s energy consumption (million TJ)	33	33	33

Source: (Transpordi arengukava 2014-2020, 2014)

The measures target both supply and demand-side management and cover all three efficiency dimensions: system efficiency, travel efficiency and vehicle efficiency. The measures and activities for targeting demand and improving the transport **system efficiency** are:

- **replacing unnecessary travel** (measure 1.1):

1. Activities related to substituting obligatory commutes will be implemented within the framework of the Green Paper for Arranging Public Services and the Information Society Development Plan 2020 (e-Estonia).
2. Opportunities for teleworking will be developed.

- **reducing unnecessary travel** (measure 1.2):

1. Instructions, guidelines, best practices, etc. will be prepared for spatial planning and mobility arrangement, on the level of the state, local governments and the private sector.

¹ http://www.energiatalgud.ee/img_auth.php/5/5b/ENMAK_2030_Eeln%C3%B5u_13.02.2015.pdf

² <https://www.riigiteataja.ee/aktiisa/3210/2201/4001/arengukava.pdf>

2. New county plans will be established.

Measures and activities for targeting supply and improving the **travel efficiency** are:

- **giving preference to more sustainable means of transport** (measure 1.3):

1. Local governments will be supported from the EU structural aid in preparing and implementing sustainable urban mobility projects.
2. Third sector projects will be supported, oriented towards implementing the principles of mobility arrangement.

- **developing intelligent transport systems** (measure 1.4):

1. The transport system's real-time data collection infrastructure will be developed, incl. within the framework of other infrastructure investments (e.g. for sensor-based gathering and forwarding of road information).
2. Development projects or pilot projects for innovative solutions or solutions adapted to Estonia's needs will be initiated and implemented in co-operation with the private sector and researchers:
 - in the field of solutions for processing and analysis of the transport system's data (incl. real-time and preventive analysis), enabling to e.g. increase road safety and manage traffic loads;
 - in the field of solutions for sharing data in the transport system (incl. prototype services), and the relevant standards or interoperability rules (e.g. for data exchange between road users);
 - in the field of joint solutions for logistics planning and management.
3. Support will be provided for development of integrated travel planning between various transport modes and/or via additional services (e.g. ticket sales), and other transport information services, incl. especially for handheld devices.
4. Regulation facilitating the safe implementation of self-driving/autonomous vehicles, the relevant interoperability and safety standards, and the supervision principles will be developed.

- **developing nationwide public transport connections** (measure 5.1):

1. In order to increase the competitiveness of long-distance bus traffic, the reconstructing and constructing of bus stations and bus stops in functional area centres will continue, as will connecting them to the centres' important destinations.
2. In order to ensure the quality of railway traffic, investments into infrastructure modernisation will continue, so as to ensure the top speed of 120 km/h and, if not entailing disproportionately large costs, 140 km/h.
3. In order to ensure service quality, investments initiated in the period of 2006-2013 for ships and harbours necessary for retaining the connections will be completed. This includes reconstruction of the harbours necessary for the connection between Saaremaa and Hiiumaa, and acquisition of a new ship for operating the line.

- developing regional public transport connections (measure 5.2):

1. Line networks will be modernised.
2. Tendering documents will be adjusted for the purpose of fulfilling the requirements set with the service standard.
3. The arrangement of regional public transport will be taken from the county level to the level of larger regions including several counties.
4. In regions with low population density, flexible public transport solutions will be implemented, e.g. on-demand buses, social transport or social taxis.

- developing local public transport connections (measure 5.3):

1. Public transport projects in functional area centres will be supported from EU structural aid.
2. Acquisition of environment-friendly rolling stock in functional area centres will be supported in the extent that the environment-friendly rolling stock costs more than rolling stock with diesel engines.
3. Distribution of tasks between the state and local governments upon arranging public transport, and the related funding will be analysed and proposals for changes will be made if necessary.

- integrating and improving access to public transport (measure 5.4):

1. The ticket systems of public transport networks of larger cities and their surrounding regions (incl. railway traffic) will be integrated. Ticket sales systems will be integrated on a country-wide level.
2. A support measure will be established for local governments, to ensure that public transport stops that serve country-wide lines will be better connected to the local commuting and most important destinations.
3. Rolling stock will be consistently replaced with models suitable for serving people with movement disabilities.
4. Public transport's information availability will be improved, implementing information systems conforming to the needs of people with hearing and vision disabilities.

Measures and activities for improving the **vehicle efficiency** are:

- promoting the use of renewable fuel sources in road transport (measure 4.1);

The activities to implement with this measure are specified in the Estonian Energy Sector Development Plan until 2030:

1. Providing a motivating economic framework for entrepreneurs and investors in the production and consumption of biofuels and other alternative fuels.
2. Ensuring long-term investment security with the state tax policy
3. Analysing the use of alternative fuels in public sector and taking them into use on socio-economic grounds.
4. Research and development activities.

- **improving car fleet economy** (measure 4.2);

The activities to be implemented with the measure:

1. A system of energy labels for vehicles will be established and awareness-raising campaigns will be conducted.
2. Energy efficiency requirements will be prescribed for public procurement conditions upon acquisition of vehicles for the public sector's needs.

Estonia's second National Energy Efficiency Action Plan (NEEAP)³ was prepared by Ministry of Economy and Communications as pursuant to Directive 2006/32/EC. According to the **NEEAP (2014)**, the estimated final energy consumption in 2020 in transport sector is 38.4 PJ. The NEEAP excludes the final energy use in the transport sector from the calculation of overall energy savings (without further explanation). The overall amount of energy savings represents a total of 9468 GWh (34PJ) in Estonia during the period from 1 January 2014 to 31 December 2020. Gaps in 2020 forecasts and the fact that transport energy saving potential is excluded from the overall energy savings calculations shows that the latest NEEAP report is not in line with the Transport Development Plan.

The national reform programme "Estonia 2020"⁴, prepared by Estonian government describes the objectives for 2015 and 2020 established to improve competitiveness. The objective is set to retain the final energy consumption on the level of the year 2010 (approx. 2818 ktoe) i.e. reducing final consumption of energy by approx. 11% compared to the level forecast for 2020. Maintaining the level of final consumption at the level of 2010 means that energy saving must be increased in nearly all sectors, in particular in the household, industrial, transport and public sectors. Actions related to transport are in line with the Transport Development Plan described above.

Target groups

The Transport Development Plan 2014–2020 does not specify the target groups. Most of the measures are targeted to the national and regional level (as regional level in Estonia represents state on the county level), transport industry, transport users and local municipalities.

Governance framework

The Transport Development Plan describes the development plan's overall implementation, monitoring, cost and implementers, without specifically referring to energy efficiency. The main responsible bodies are the institutions (Road Administration)⁵ and state enterprises in the area of governance of the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communications⁶. Practically all other ministries, but primarily the Ministry of the Environment⁷ and the Ministry of Internal Affairs⁸ (responsible for planning and regional policy, Police and Border Guard Board) are involved in certain matters of implementing activities and applying support measures. In addition, state governed foundations like Estonian Devel-

³ https://ec.europa.eu/energy/sites/ener/files/documents/2014_neeap_en_estonia.pdf

⁴ https://riigikantselei.ee/sites/default/files/riigikantselei/strateegiaburoo/eesti2020/eesti2020_tegevuskava_14.05.2015.pdf

⁵ <http://www.mnt.ee>

⁶ <http://www.mkm.ee>

⁷ <http://www.envir.ee>

⁸ <http://www.siseministeerium.ee>

opment Fund⁹ (partly filling the tasks of national Climate and Energy Agency that existed 2009-2011), KredEX¹⁰ and Enterprise Estonia¹¹ have a role in promoting energy efficiency activities and supporting start-ups in Estonia, local governments, primarily larger cities, have an important role.

There are two local/regional level energy agencies in Estonia – Tallinn Energy Agency¹² and Tartu Region Energy Agency¹³. These agencies have an active role in capacity building, networking and dissemination activities.

Most of the energy efficiency measures and facilitating foundations/agencies are not covered with long-term finances and are highly dependent on EU funds, Green Investment Scheme negotiations and project-based funding in general.

1.2 National Programmes and Initiatives

1.2.1 Green Investment Scheme implementation in building sector

Estonia is using two flexible mechanisms of UN FCCC Kyoto Protocol: EU Emissions Trading Scheme (EU ETS) and Joint Implementation (JI). Estonia has the right to offer unused emission quota for sale internationally. Estonia has had significant volumes of excess Assigned Amount Units (AAU), which represent carbon credits to be sold. It gained the excess units thanks to the thorough rearrangement of the economy when modern technology and alternative ways of producing energy were introduced, more renewable energy sources were taken into use, and saving measures were introduced in energy production. This financing measure was added to Environmental Investment Centre's (EIC) portfolio and is titled the Green Investment Scheme (GIS) pursuant to which the revenue is directed to investments ensuring a decrease in CO₂ emissions as agreed with the buyer of the quota, for example ensuring the energy efficiency of public buildings or finance the electro-mobility programme in transport sector. This is, in fact the financing instrument giving excellent option for earmarked investments for energy efficiency and renewable energy wider deployment.

Estonia started selling AAUs in 2009, under the GIS and has earmarked the proceeds for projects that facilitate emissions reductions. Examples include CHP installations, improving DH networks, retrofitting boiler houses, improving energy efficiency in buildings and industry, wind farms and introducing more efficient buses and trams in city traffic, and electric vehicles. In the frame of the instrument the areas of financing will be decided by the buyers.

Type of policy instrument: Financial instrument as it provides financial support to district heating networks supplying both public and private sector with more efficiently and hence cheaper heat. It has gained high popularity and showed up very good result in decreased heat consumption. Instrument is also, efficiently used for energetic refurbishment projects in buildings sector.

The first grants channelled through EIC were for the renovation of the district heating networks, renovation of combined heat and power generation plants and more environmentally-sustainable boiler houses, see for more at: (<http://www.kik.ee/et/energeetika/hasti-tehtud>). Still, the most significant financing has been channelled to energetic refurbishment of public buildings, also electro-mobility programme. In 2010-2013 the Riigi Kinnisvara AS (RKAS) has elaborated to implementation the ener-

⁹ <http://www.arengufond.ee>

¹⁰ <http://www.kredex.ee>

¹¹ <http://www.eas.ee>

¹² <http://www.tallinn.ee/est/energiaagentuur>

¹³ <http://trea.ee>

getic refurbishment directed to increasing the energy efficiency of 543 public buildings based on the Assigned Amount Units trade in total volume of EUR 165,67 million (<http://www.rkas.ee/co2>).

Table 2 Estonia's Green Investment Scheme Transactions 2010-12

Programme	Objectives	Activities	Transaction time	Ministry in charge, Implementing body	Contract partner	Transaction amount
Establishment of renewable energy based combined heat and power plants, boiler house reconstruction, saving energy in district heating networks (41 projects)	Improve the process efficiency to generate in cogeneration the electricity to be sold to grid, and heat for supplying buildings. Decrease CO ₂ emissions from fuel burning.	Fuel switch from fossil to biomass excluding the CO ₂ emissions into air. Change of technology of fuel burning	2010	Ministry of the Environment, Environmental Investment Centre, EIC	Austria (2 contracts)	2.9 M AAUs
Establishment of energy efficient street lighting systems (7 cities), Saving energy in district heating networks and boiler house reconstruction (22 projects)	Energy saving in supplying heat to apartment houses		2012	Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communications, Ministry of Environment, Environmental Investment Centre, EIC	Austria	10,9 M AAUs

Source: EIC, http://www.kik.ee/sites/default/files/stories/RIS/aau_transactions_2010-12_eng_12.pdf (07.08.2015).

Objectives. In buildings sector the main idea of the policy instrument is to give subsidies to energy efficiency projects. This policy instrument concerns the whole buildings sector at national, regional and local levels including energy supply side (renewable energy based combined heat and power

plants, DH networks) and demand side (multiple apartment houses, office buildings). It is aimed to improve the energy efficiency in both, public and private sectors. At present the instrument is continuously used and new procurements, including also the energy efficiency of public buildings, are opened, see for more at RKAS homepage (Procurements, 2015).

Target groups. The policy instrument concerns the whole buildings sector, public and private, households and industrial buildings.

Rules and influencing mechanisms. The rules for the sale of AAU state that all the money from the trading must be channelled to environmentally friendly projects that lower the emission of CO₂ and other greenhouse gases. Which areas will be financed will be decided by the quota buyers. The Green Investment Scheme is regulated by the Ambient Air Protection Act (Välisõhu ..., 2004).

Implementation network. The Estonian government copied a successful German KfW scheme where finance from different funds was offered to private banks to make loans to home-owner associations. Essential elements were in place. For instance, energy audits were required as part of granting the loans. This started in 2009 but ended in summer 2012 when the scheme ran out of funds. Interest rates are fixed for ten years at less than commercial rates (4.4% maximum with loan average interest at 4%). Grants are 15% to 35% of the cost of the project, scaled to the effort, and 35% grant for comprehensive retrofits, including heat, ventilation and air-conditioning upgrades and triple glazing. (Energy ..., 2013).

1.2.2 Green Investment Scheme in transport sector

General information. The Green Investment Scheme (GIS) has been a financing mechanism for implementing projects aimed at improving energy efficiency. Under the GIS, revenues gained from the trading of Estonia's CO₂ quotas, as provided by Article 17 of the Kyoto Protocol, are channelled into environmentally sound projects and programmes that lower the emission of CO₂ and other greenhouse gases. The GIS is regulated by the Ambient Air Protection Act.

Estonia had excess emissions of about 91.5 million tonnes of CO₂ equivalent, or 18.3 million tonnes of CO₂ equivalent per year. 21 deals have been concluded 2010-2012 in order to sell 72.6 million AAUs (Assigned Amount Units, i.e. CO₂ emission units) for EUR 388 million. The deals have been concluded with the Republic of Austria, the Kingdom of Spain, the Grand Duchy of Luxembourg, and Japanese corporations. (EIC, www.kik.ee). GIS supports projects in the field of housing, wind energy, transport and street lightning.

Type of policy instrument: Economic policy instrument as it provides financial support to projects and programmes. Policy type: subsidy.

Objectives. Energy efficiency is among the objectives of three transport programmes under the GIS (Table 3).

Table 3 GIS programs regarding transport and energy efficiency

Programme	Objectives	Activities	Ministry in charge, Implementing body	Contract partner	Transaction amount
Development of public transport (2010)	To promote public transport and reduce transport CO ₂ emissions.	Buying 120 fuel-efficient buses for county lines (Ida-Viru county, Harju county, Tallinn)	Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communications, Road Administration	Spain	21 M EUR
ELMO – Electro-mobility Programme (2011-2014)	To promote emission-free personal transportation in order to achieve better city environment, energy efficiency and fuel independence.	1. Establishment of nation-wide quick charging network for electric cars 2. Provision of electric cars to social and other state workers; 3. Electric car purchase support scheme for private persons and organisations	Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communications, Foundation KredEx	Mitsubishi Corporation	10 M AAUs
Development of electric public transport in Tallinn		Procurement of energy efficient trams for Tallinn lines no. 3 and 4 (20 trams)	Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communications, Linna-transporti AS	Spain	53.4 MEUR

Source: EIC, http://www.kik.ee/sites/default/files/stories/RIS/aau_transactions_2010-12_eng_12.pdf (07.08.2015).

Target groups. Public transport operators, EV users

Rules and influencing mechanisms. The areas which will be financed, are negotiated and decided by the quota buyers. Products and services are bought via public procurements.

Implementation network. The Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communications co-ordinates the trade in permissible emission allowance. The Ministry of Environment is responsible for the coordination and implementation of CO₂ quota sales agreements. The Government determines an appropriate minister as the user of the revenues for the implementation of each GIS-scheme. The implementing agencies in transport energy efficiency projects are the Road Administration, Foundation KredEx, Tallinna Linnatranspordi AS (public transportation company owned by the Tallinn city).

1.2.3 ELMO – Estonian Electromobility Programme in transport sector

The biggest national level program that has been initiated with the GIS scheme is the national electromobility programme, ELMO.

General information. ELMO (www.elmo.ee) is mainly driven by innovation policy agenda. It is a Green Investment Scheme programme, which started in March 2011 when the Government of the Republic of Estonia concluded a contract with Mitsubishi Corporation, Japan, for the sale of CO₂ quotas in the amount of 10 million AAUs. The programme consists of three parts:

1. Infrastructure – a charging network of electric cars was created to cover the whole Estonia, being the first country in the world constructing it in 2012. The quick charging network with 165 chargers was constructed by ABB. The charging points are in all roads with dense traffic and in all settlements with over 5000 inhabitants, e.g. at petrol stations, cafes, shops, post offices, bank buildings, parking lots and also in ports. The distance between quick charging points is 40–60 km. The location and availability of quick charging points can be seen here: <http://elmo.ee/charging-network-2/>

2. Grant for electric cars – the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communications developed a support system for natural and legal persons for acquisition of electric cars, with a purpose to decrease the pollution load of transport and increase the use of renewable energy in transport through wider commissioning of electric cars.

The grant period was 2011–2014. According to the regulation and the procedure established by Foundation KredEx, the purchase of an electric car, including the down-payment of leasing and the purchase of one charger per one electric car, including the necessary installation work, was supported. Since November 2012, the purchase of plug-charged hybrid vehicles has also been supported.

In total, KredEx has supported 657 (339 for private persons and 318 for company's) car purchase and 350 home chargers. Most applicants (74%) came from Harju County (incl. Tallinn).

3. Demonstration and awareness raising activities:

- Estonian government purchased a fleet of 507 Mitsubishi iMiEVs **electric cars for the social workers** around Estonia for their public duties.

- **A demo centre** – an interactive exposition introducing the technology of electric cars was opened in June 2013 in Science Centre AHHA located in Tartu.

- **ELMO Rental** – a pilot car sharing program with 24 electric cars in Tallinn and Tartu, launched in July 2013.

In addition, KredEx is running promotional activities and campaigns for electric cars.

Type of policy instrument: Economic (mainly) and informative policy instrument. Policy types: subsidy and provision of information for sustainable transport. ELMO programme is fully financed using funds received from CO₂ emission trading scheme.

Objectives. The goal of the ELMO programme is to speed up the commissioning of electric cars in Estonia, and facilitate the achievement of the goal undertaken by the state to increase the use of re-

newable energy to 10% in transport sector by 2020. The programme promotes emission free personal transportation and electric cars in order to achieve better city environment, energy efficiency and fuel independence. Electric vehicles are considered as one option to bring renewable energy to transport sector.

Target groups. Private persons, companies, social workers, etc.

Rules and influencing mechanisms. The grant amount for the purchase of an electric car and down-payment of leasing is up to 50% of the purchase price of the electric car, but not more than EUR 18 000 for a person who is not a VAT payer. For VAT payers, the grant is 35% of eligible costs, but not more than EUR 18 000 per car. The owner of EV-s purchased with the grant have to cover their electricity consumption with green electricity certificates, the grant comes with a 5 MWh green certificate.

Implementation network.

Distribution of the purchase grant and the administration of the quick charging network is organised by Foundation KredEx.

1.3 Conclusions and Lessons Learned of other Projects about the Performance of the National Policy Packages for Energy Efficiency

1.3.1 Buildings sector

International Energy Agency made the Energy Policy Review on Estonia in 2013¹⁴ (Estonia, 2013). To summarize the detailed report, it is said that Estonia is recognised for its rapid reforms following its independence, with a clear preference for liberal economic policies well engaged with regional and international efforts to advance sustainable energy and efforts to address climate change challenges. Estonia clearly aspires to a more energy-efficient and sustainable economy. Estonia's policy challenges and opportunities extend beyond the 2020 horizon of EU obligations. The government of Estonia aims to use the EU directives as a step on the way to shaping longer-term objectives and has started working on Energy Strategy of Estonia to 2050.

The Energy Policy Report summarises the IEA 25 Energy Efficiency Policy Recommendations and plots Estonia's priorities against the 25 recommendations and should be regarded as a framework for a comprehensive portfolio of policies. To achieve savings in the buildings sector, the IEA recommends the following (Energy..., 2013):

¹⁴ Estonia joined the IEA in 2014. Following its accession to the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) in 2010, Estonia applied for International Energy Agency (IEA) membership in 2011. This review of Estonia's energy policies is part of the IEA accession process. It analyses the energy policy challenges and opportunities facing Estonia, and provides critiques and recommendations for future policy improvements. It is intended to guide the country towards a more secure and sustainable energy future.
<http://www.iea.org/publications/freepublications/publication/energy-policies-of-iea-countries---estonia-2013-review.html>.

Table 4 Summary of energy efficiency recommendations

Summary of energy efficiency recommendations	Priority	Notes
Mandatory building energy codes and minimum energy performance requirements.	Medium	Regular review, upgrade cycle and pilot activities are important.
Aiming for net zero-energy consumption buildings.	Medium	Promote zero/low-energy buildings
Improving energy efficiency of existing buildings.	High	Rationalise and extend existing schemes for this priority end-use, integrate with DH policies.
Buildings' energy labels and certificates.	Low	Work with EU labelling.
Energy performance of building components and systems.	Medium	Align local manufacturers with EU standards.

By present day we could evaluate that the majority of the points in those recommendations have already taken and they are in work. This means that Estonia has been successful in delivering the energy efficiency. However, Estonia can still more usefully structure and integrate the various functions delivering energy efficiency policies and programmes.

The implementation of government funding programmes for energy efficiency, climate change and DH support appears to be spread over different programmes that seem to be driven by funders' criteria and to overlap without consistent guiding principles. The relationship between the MEAC, and the Ministry of the Environment and operational programmes should be restructured to remove operational overlaps and improve consistency. Estonia should consider creating an energy efficiency unit, which would be able to commission, research, evaluate and implement energy efficiency priorities maximising delivery efficiency, reporting to the Energy Department in the MEAC. The latter should lead co-ordination of energy efficiency policies across government to merit required focus and operational clarity (Energy ..., 2013).

Finally the IEA Energy Policy Report on Estonia makes a number of recommendations in energy efficiency for buildings sector (Energy..., 2013):

- Focus on energy efficiency policies and programme activities that meet both Estonia's cost-effective priorities and the requirements of the EU directives.
- For new buildings, strengthen building codes with staged improvements in stringency and adopt a more ambitious pathway to zero- and low-energy buildings. Complement this with capacity-building measures.
- For the existing building stock, develop an integrated programme of fiscal and funding measures that enable priorities in the building stock to be improved over a defined time period. Increase the ratio of private-sector funding.
- Integrate building measures with policies on DH to ensure that end-use efficiency improvements in buildings are taken up and that consumers exposed to unsustainable DH systems have priority for insulation and high-efficiency local heating, such as a heat pump.

1.3.2 Transport sector

Energy Efficiency Watch (www.energy-efficiency-watch.org): 2013:

The Estonian NEEAP is very well elaborated and balanced. Estonia sees the buildings sector as priority for energy efficiency (EE) which is underlined by many good measures in that sector. In the transport sector, most measures are only planned. Currently, the activities mainly focus on improving the EE of vehicles by acquiring new public transportation rolling stock and by implementing an E-mobility programme. All types of measures have been addressed (planning instruments, regulatory instruments, economic incentives, information and advice, R&D) and different actors have been considered, but most measures are not implemented nor described in detail.

To further strengthen its framework in transport sector, Estonia should improve R&D support and there is a need to actually implement planned measures.

ODYSSEE – MURE 2010, Energy Efficiency Policies and Measures in Estonia in 2012:

The largest share of final energy is still consumed by households but the share has the downward trend. The second largest part of final consumption goes for transport and its share is growing.

In road transport, the consumption of diesel fuel has been increasing almost constantly, the trend towards increasing share of diesel fuel consumption is clearly pronounced since 1995.

There have been only slight changes in the structure of energy consumption by type of transport during 1995–2010: the shares of road transport and to some extent also of air transport have increased, the share of rail transport is declining. In road transport, consumption of both fuels – petrol and diesel – has been increasing. In Estonia, the proper analysis of energy efficiency in transport cannot be carried out as there is a lack of relevant reliable data. Based on general available data, it can be concluded that the energy efficiency index ODEX for transport in Estonia has increased by 17.3% (from 2000 to 2010) meaning that the energy intensity has increased. The difference of energy intensity of transport in Estonia and the EU is very essential: in Estonia 0.087 kg oe/EUR2000 and the EU average 0.032 kg oe/EUR2000 in 2010 (Energy..., 2012).

OECD/IEA, Energy Policies Beyond IEA Countries, 2013:

Estonia's National Energy Efficiency Action Plan (NEEAP) excludes energy used for transport from the country's final energy consumption.

Estonia has significant potential to reduce energy consumption in the buildings, district heating (DH) and transport sectors.

Transport fuels are imported from global markets and Estonia has effective storage and a number of sea- and land-based routes for supply.

Transport is the main source of CO₂ emissions in the non-ETS sector. Its emissions increased by 37% from 2000 to 2010, when they accounted for 12% of all energy-related CO₂ emissions in the country. Without ambitious measures, emissions are set to rise further, as the country grows wealthier. The private car ownership rate is one-fifth lower than in the wealthier EU15 countries (407 cars per 1 000 inhabitants in Estonia versus 503 in EU15 in 2009) and has plenty of room to expand. Freight transport, in turn, typically increases in tandem with gross domestic product (GDP). The 2010 National Renewable Energy Action Plan projects energy use in the sector to increase by 13% from the average of 2005-08 to 2020.

To achieve significant energy savings in the transport sector, the IEA recommends five key policy areas for Estonia (see **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.**5).

Table 5 IEA energy efficiency recommendations for Estonia in transport sector

Summary of energy efficiency recommendations	Priority	Notes
Mandatory vehicle fuel efficiency standards.	Low	Reasonable for a small technology-taking country to rely on EU processes.
Measures to improve vehicle fuel efficiency.	Low	
Fuel-efficient non-engine components.	Low	
Improving operational efficiency through eco-driving and other measures.	Med	Cost-effective energy and safety from eco-driving.
Improving transport system efficiency.	Med	Pursue transport energy efficiency plans.

The government of Estonia should:

- Review the proposed energy efficiency policy options in the transport sector and develop a strategy of prioritised measures to improve mobility in passenger and freight transport in order to minimise transport fuel demand.
- Apply EU policies to advance the efficiency of the vehicle fleet, meeting the unique mobility needs and characteristics of Estonia's vehicle fleet.
- Develop effective policies to improve mobility in cities and towns.
- Ensure that priorities are economic and that realistic funding is identified.
- Develop a strategy to ensure that freight transport effectively supports the economy and improves efficiency with efficient vehicles, modes and logistics management systems.

2. INTERACTION BETWEEN THE NATIONAL AND THE SUB-NATIONAL LEVELS

In terms of targeted strategies and actions, it is the state level that is most active in the field of energy efficiency. Besides ministerial institutions, also state governed foundations like Estonian Development Fund, KredEX and Enterprise Estonia have a role in promoting energy efficiency activities and supporting start-ups in Estonia. Estonian Development Fund (state governed foundation that partly took over the tasks of Estonian Climate Energy Agency 2009-2011) acted as a co-ordinator of the National Energy Development Plan 2030+ (ENMAK), which was an active participatory process, and involved teams of experts and background studies in the field of housing, transport, biofuels and electricity production and offered an interactive collaboration platform www.energiatalgud.ee.

Six Estonian municipalities have signed the Covenant of Mayors (Tallinn, Rakvere, Tartu, Jõgeva, Võru, Rõuge) with a total population of ca 550 000 inhabitants. Two cities have submitted Sustainable Energy Action Plans to the Covenant of Mayors: Rakvere and Tallinn (4.3% of Estonian cities and towns). The SEAP of Rakvere has been accepted by the Covenant of Mayors. SEAP of Tallinn is pending with clarifications requested, as of 24 July 2015. Also Tartu city, Jõgeva city and Võru city have published energy saving action plan (under IEE funded MESHARTILITY project).

There are two local/regional level Energy agencies, one in Tallinn municipality – Tallinn Energy Agency, another in Tartu, Tartu Regional Energy Agency, both working with buildings' energy efficiency issues and proceed with training and wider scope information dissemination in improving energy efficiency at local level. The energetic refurbishment has gained high popularity in almost at all local governments. These agencies have an active role in capacity building, networking and dissemination activities. Still, Estonia is lacking the national Energy Agency at present.

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HERON (No:649690): Deliverable D.1.1

**LANDSCAPE OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICY
PACKAGES IN A MULTI-LEVEL GOVERNMENT
SYSTEM
NATIONAL REPORT FOR GERMANY
2015-08-13**

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HERON: Forward – looking socio-economic research on Energy Efficiency in EU countries

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649690. The content of this document reflects only the authors' views and the EASME is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Contents

ACRONYMS	4
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	5
1. THE ROLE OF GOVERNANCE AND ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICY PACKAGES ON THE NATIONAL LEVEL.....	6
1.1 POLICY PACKAGES AND POLICY GOVERNANCE IN GERMANY	6
1.1.1 BUILDINGS SECTOR	8
1.1.2 TRANSPORT SECTOR.....	23
1.2 NATIONAL PROGRAMMES AND INITIATIVES	35
1.2.1 National Action Plan on Energy Efficiency (NAPE)	35
1.2.2 Climate Action Programme 2020.....	40
1.2.3 Horizontal measures.....	44
1.3 CONCLUSIONS AND LESSONS LEARNED OF OTHER PROJECTS ABOUT THE PERFORMANCE OF THE NATIONAL POLICY PACKAGES FOR ENERGY EFFICIENCY	46
1.3.1 Energy Efficiency Watch conclusions.....	46
1.3.2 ODYSSEE-MURE conclusions.....	46
1.3.3 Entranze conclusions	47
1.3.4 bigEE	48
1.3.5 IEA.....	48
1.3.6 ChangeBest – Promoting the Development of an Energy Efficiency Service (EES) Market.....	48
2. INTERACTION BETWEEN THE NATIONAL AND THE SUB-NATIONAL LEVELS	50
REFERENCES	52

Table of Figures

Figure 1: Effective policy packages in energy efficiency policy.....	Fehler! Textmarke nicht definiert.
Figure 2: A prototypical process for policy development in energy efficiency	Fehler! Textmarke nicht definiert.
Figure 3: Short-term measures and long-term work process of NAPE for the 18th legislative term	36

ACRONYMS

BAFA – Bundesamt für Wirtschaft und Ausfuhrkontrolle / Federal Office for Economic Affairs and Export Control

BImSchV – Bundesimmissionsschutzverordnung / Federal Immission Control Act

EEWärmeG – Erneuerbare Energien Wärme Gesetz / Renewable Energies Heat Act

EnEV – Energieinsparverordnung / Energy saving ordinance

EPC – Energy Performance Certificate

ESCO – Energy Service Company

HGV – Heavy Goods Vehicles

IEA – International Energy Agency

KfW – Kreditanstalt für Wiederaufbau / German promotional bank group

MAP – Marktanzreizprogramm / Market incentive programme

NAPE – National Action Plan on Energy Efficiency

NEEAP – National Energy Efficiency Action Plan

NTRI – National Top Runner Initiative

SME – Small and Medium-sized Enterprise

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Energy efficiency plays a major role in Germany. Together with renewable energies, energy efficiency is a central pillar of the energy transition (“Energiewende”). In the energy concept of 2010, concrete targets for energy efficiency have been set. In order to implement the energy transition and to fulfil the targets of the energy concept, the National Action Plan on Energy Efficiency (NAPE) was adopted. Together with the Climate Action Programme 2020, comprehensive policy packages have been introduced.

Germany has a long tradition of energy efficiency policy – the first thermal insulation ordinance (Wärmeschutzverordnung) was adopted in 1979. Especially regarding the buildings sector, comprehensive policy packages are already in place.

The federal government has implemented many regulations, initiatives and programmes. Besides national activities, the federal state and municipal level supports the uptake of energy efficiency. Federal states play an important role in implementing regulatory provision of the energy saving ordinance (EnEV) and the EU Ecodesign regulation, as they are responsible for supervising these. Many cities and municipalities committed themselves to significant emission reductions or joined frameworks of international city-alliances. Due to financial short passes, many municipalities use national or EU-funds to take energy efficiency action.

1. THE ROLE OF GOVERNANCE AND ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICY PACKAGES ON THE NATIONAL LEVEL

1.1 POLICY PACKAGES AND POLICY GOVERNANCE IN GERMANY

Below you will find a list of all main German official documents dealing with energy efficiency policy packages in the buildings in transport sector. Afterwards two recent plans / concepts are described in more detail: the third Energy Efficiency Action Plan as well as the German Energy Concept.

List of main national official documents dealing with energy efficiency policy packages:

1st National Energy Efficiency Action Plan: Edited by the Ministry for Economic Affairs and Technology in 2007. The 2007 NEEAP is based on the EU Directive 2006/32/EC. Its aim is to show national estimated energy consumptions, planned energy efficiency measures and the improvements of measures and policies.

<https://ec.europa.eu/energy/en/topics/energy-efficiency/energy-efficiency-directive/national-energy-efficiency-action-plans>

2nd National Energy Efficiency Action Plan: Edited by the Ministry for Economic Affairs and Technology in 2011. The NEEAP shows achievements of the national energy saving targets and provides overall information on the regulatory framework and the current status of energy efficiency policy. All in relation with the EU Directive 2006/32/EC.

<https://ec.europa.eu/energy/en/topics/energy-efficiency/energy-efficiency-directive/national-energy-efficiency-action-plans>

The Mobility and Fuels Strategy of the German Government (MFS) was published by the Federal Ministry of Transport, Building and Urban Development in June 2013. "The main focus is on a strategic understanding between government, industry and academia on the medium and long term prospects for fossil fuels and fuels based on renewable sources of energy and on promising drivetrain technologies and the supply infrastructures required for this."

http://www.bmvi.de/SharedDocs/EN/Anlagen/UI-MKS/mfs-strategy-final-en.pdf?__blob=publicationFile

3rd National Energy Efficiency Action Plan: Edited by the Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy in 2014. The NEEAP aims on showing national estimated energy consumptions, planned energy efficiency measures and the improvements on basis of the EU Directive 2006/32/EC. Main news of the third NEEAP are the 9% energy savings target until 2016, which is on a good track and a reduction of final energy consumption (220.7 in 2008 to 194.3 Mtoe in 2020).

<https://ec.europa.eu/energy/en/topics/energy-efficiency/energy-efficiency-directive/national-energy-efficiency-action-plans>

The Energy Concept: Approved by the German Federal Government in 2010. Is the roadmap of German energy policy and measures to increase the use of renewable energies, to expand the power grids, and to increase energy efficiency. Goal is a reduction of GHG of 80-95% by 2050 in relation to 1990 (Federal Ministry of Economic Affairs and Technology; Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation and Nuclear Safety 2010).

http://www.germany.info/contentblob/3043402/Daten/3903429/BMUBMWi_Energy_Concept_DD.pdf

Sixth National Communication under the UNFCCC: Edited in 2013 by the Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, Building and Nuclear Safety. It presents Germany's climate protection policies and actions in context of the background of legislative, political and socio-economic conditions based on data from 2009 to 2013. Additionally, measures and their projected effects are described. It also includes a report on financial support, technology transfer, and diverse activities like education and public awareness.

http://unfccc.int/national_reports/annex_i_natcom/submitted_natcom/items/7742.php

The energy transition: Edited by the Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy in 2015. It presents the overall energy transition strategy and its action areas. To accomplish the goals of the strategy, a roadmap with 10 points was established that set the agenda. In addition, the current status, challenges and accomplishments are shown in this document.

<http://www.bmwi.de/English/Redaktion/Pdf/making-a-success-of-the-energy-transition,property=pdf,bereich=bmwi2012,sprache=en,rwb=true.pdf>

National Action Plan on Energy Efficiency: Edited by Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy in 2014. It targets to support the national primary energy reduction target with measures that include information and advice, as well as the promotion of energy efficiency investments. The NAPE includes diverse instruments to approach and activate all relevant actors.

The 3rd National Energy Efficiency Action Plan (NEEAP) 2014 for the Federal Republic of Germany, pursuant to Directive 2012/27/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2012 on energy efficiency, was published in April 2014 (Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy 2014a).

https://ec.europa.eu/energy/sites/ener/files/documents/2014_neeap_en_germany.pdf

Climate Action Programme: Edited by Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, Building and Nuclear Safety in 2014. The programme sets out several measures to support the national CO₂ reduction target till 2020. It contains 9 components that address energy efficiency, housing, transportation, other emissions, emission trading, the energy sector, the state, R&D, and education.

http://www.bmub.bund.de/fileadmin/Daten_BMU/Pool/Broschueren/aktionsprogramm_klimaschutz_2020_broschuere_en_bf.pdf

General objectives / energy efficiency targets

The EU Energy End-use Efficiency and Energy Services Directive places a national indicative energy savings target of 9% of the average annual consumption of all energy users until 2016 compared to the average consumption of the period 2001 to 2005.

In the third German NEEAP it is stated, that a reduction in final energy consumption from 220.7 Mtoe in 2008 to 194.3 Mtoe in 2020 is expected.

The Energy Concept was approved by the German Federal Government in September 2010. It shows how the Government wants to continue / improve its energy policy up to 2050, especially regarding measures to increase the use of renewable energies, to expand the power grids, and to increase energy efficiency (Federal Ministry of Economics and Technology; Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation and Nuclear Safety 2010).

In the Energy Concept, the German Federal Government sets itself the target of reducing greenhouse gas emissions in Germany by

- 40% by 2020
- 55% by 2030
- 70% by 2040
- 80-95% by 2050

in relation to the base year of 1990.

Furthermore, the target for primary energy consumption in the Energy Concept is:

- 20% less energy consumption by 2020 than in 2008
- 50% less energy consumption by 2050 than in 2008

This means an annual average improvement in energy productivity of 2.1%, based on final energy consumption. Furthermore, compared to 2008, Germany seeks to cut electricity consumption by about 10% by 2020 and 25% by 2050.

One aim stated in the Energy Concept is: "Germany is to become one of the most energy-efficient and greenest economies in the world while enjoying competitive energy prices and a high level of prosperity." (Federal Ministry of Economics and Technology; Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation and Nuclear Safety 2010).

1.1.1 BUILDINGS SECTOR

Objectives

Building renovation is a central focus of the Energy Concept. One objective is to double the current rate of renovation, meaning to increase the current rate of less than 1% a year to 2% of the total building stock.

Another central objective is to reduce the heating requirement of the building stock over the long term. The target for 2050 is to have a building stock which is almost climate-neutral¹. Therefore, by 2020 the heating requirement should be reduced by 20% and by 2050 by 80%.

Other objectives in the buildings sector include that the additional investments will have a positive impact on growth and employment.

Synthesis of policy packages in the Buildings Sector

There are comprehensive policy packages targeting the buildings sector in place, especially regarding energy-related building renovations. There have been a lot of funding programmes on different levels in place for many years now. Additionally, according to the NEEAP “the International Energy Agency (IEA) still places Germany among the world leaders in energy efficiency in the construction sector”.

Policy components include:

- a market incentive programme to promote the use of renewable energies in the heating market
- Funding programmes of the ‚Kreditanstalt für Wiederaufbau‘ (KfW) for energy-efficiency building and renovation
- Energy audits
- Energy saving contracting
- Training for energy service providers
- Energy Savings Regulation (stock)
- Energy Savings Regulation (new build)
- Tax relief on energy renovations
- CO2 building renovation programme
- KfW municipal loans – energy-related building renovation
- Energy savings programme, government buildings (120-million prog.)
- Energy consultations at the premises of the consumer
- Caritas energy efficiency check
- Energy Efficiency Fund: Energy and electricity savings checks in private households

Though there are comprehensive policy packages in place, the existing instruments are not enough to meet the targets of the Energy Concept. Therefore, in the Energy Concept it is planned to update existing policies like the Energy Saving Ordinance (EnEV) and the Renewable Energies Heat Act (EEWärmeG) in order to meet the renovation targets.

Building renovation in Germany is not going to be targeted by compulsory regulation but by economic incentives.

Policy components of the Energy Concept that concern the buildings sector include:

- energy and electricity saving checks for private households

¹ Climate-neutral in this respect means that buildings have very low energy needs and that the remaining energy demand is covered primarily by renewable energy.

- informative energy performance certificates for buildings
- „Climate-neutral Building“ standard for all new buildings by 2020
- Renovation roadmap for existing buildings will start in 2020 focussing on the 80% reduction target by 2050.
- Moderate standards for 2020 for building renovations, only affecting buildings with the poorest standards
- State support for those home-owners that fulfil higher renovation standards or are ahead of meeting targets (CO2 Building Rehabilitation Programme, probably new tax incentives)
- Market incentive programme to promote the use of renewable energies in the heating market
- Grant programme for energy performance-enhancing urban rehabilitation
- Balanced revision of rent law
- Expansion of options for energy contracting
- Renewable Energies Heat Act (EE-WärmeG)
- Future inclusion of CO2 emissions into energy taxes in the heating market
- Industry should commit to improved and regular training programmes for the crafts sector
- German government as a good example for reducing energy consumption in its own buildings

Target groups in the Buildings Sector

In the NEEAP (as well as in the total German energy efficiency policy) the buildings sector plays a major role.

Measures of the NEEAP target especially

- National target groups
 - o Final energy consumers
 - o Supply side actors
 - o Public buildings of the Federal Government
- Local target groups
 - o Municipalities

The Energy Concept says: “Building renovation will be a central focus”.

The Energy Concepts targets, respectively wants to support the business sector in becoming more energy efficient in order to stay globally competitive.

Other target groups include

- Private households
- Public sector
- Industry
- Local authorities

Governance framework in the Buildings Sector

Energy efficiency plays a major role in Germany, and even before the EU Energy Efficiency Directive was adopted, Germany had a wide range of policy instruments for increasing energy efficiency. It is one of the few industrialised countries that have managed to decouple energy consumption and economic growth.

Following non-governmental or sub-national actors are mentioned in the NEEAP:

- Municipalities
- ESCOs
- Energy consultants
- Financial institutions (KfW)
- Others (Caritas as a welfare organisation)

Main actors that are generally involved in the implementation of energy efficiency policies in the buildings sector in Germany are²:

National governance level

Ministries:

The Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, Building and Nuclear Safety (BMUB) is responsible for policies that are reflected in its name. Main tasks are to prepare legislation for national and EU law, to fund R&D and support innovative technologies, to engage in national and international cooperation, and to communicate about relevant issues to push broad public participation and acceptance.

<http://www.bmub.bund.de/en/bmub/tasks-and-structure/>

<http://www.bmub.bund.de/en/>

The Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy (BMWi) is responsible for a stable social market economy, a social fabric and continuous innovation in Germany. Its policy-making therefore implies to foster a high level of competitiveness and employment for Germany. Main areas for action are investments, innovation, infrastructure, internationalisation, labour, and energy reforms.

<http://bmwi.de/EN/Ministry/tasks-and-structure.html>

<http://www.bmwi.de/EN/root.html>

The Federal Ministry for Education and Research (BMBF) is responsible for policies that are reflected in its name, even though education is part of the state (Länder) legislation. The target is to foster participation, prosperity, innovation, sustainability and health through education and specific funding. This also includes international cooperation in these areas.

<http://www.bmbf.de/en/index.php>

The Federal Ministry of Finance (BMF) is responsible for the federal budget, the national economic and fiscal policy strategy as well as for international finance issues. This includes areas like customs

² This is just a selection of the main actors. There are many more, especially when coming to very detailed technical issues or to the regional / municipal level.

and all means of taxes and taxation, legal matters, financial market policies, federal holdings and real estate, EU policy, and central administration and services.

<http://www.bundesfinanzministerium.de/Web/EN/Home/home.html>

The Federal Ministry of Justice and Consumer Protection (BMJV) is mainly responsible for legislation and advising the other Federal Ministries in the preparation of legislative proposals. Main competence areas are in the fields of civil law, commercial and economic law, criminal law, and procedural law as well as consumer policy that insures safety, transparency, comprehensibility and comparability of products and services.

http://www.bmjv.de/EN/Home/home_node.html

Other Actors:

Federal Offices:

Federal Offices in Germany are part of the national administration and are subordinated to ministries.

The Federal Office for Economic Affairs and Export Control (BAFA) is a superior federal authority subordinated to the BMWi. Its responsibilities are foreign trade, promotion of economic development, energy and administrative issues. For the energy sector, the BAFA implements measures to promote saving energy, renewables, and new efficient technologies.

<http://www.bafa.de/bafa/en/index.html>

The Federal Agency for Energy Efficiency (BfEE) is subordinated to the BAFA and therefore to the BMWi. It was established in 2009 based on the EU Directive 2006/32/EG on Energy Efficiency. Task of the BfEE is to implement measures of the EU energy efficiency policies.

<http://www.bfee-online.de/bfee/>

The Federal Office for Building and Regional Planning (BBR) is a superior federal authority subordinated to the BMUB. Tasks are to administrate Germany's building issues, cultural heritage, and real estate. Additional, the BBR is involved in research and advises the German government with respect to urban and regional development, building, real estate and housing.

http://www.bbr.bund.de/BBR/DE/Home/home_node.html

The Federal Institute for Research on Building, Urban Affairs and Spatial Development (BBSR) within the Federal office for Building and Regional Planning "is a departmental research institution under the portfolio of the Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, Building and Nuclear Safety (BMUB). It advises the Federal Government with sectoral specific scientific consultation in the political fields of spatial planning, urban development, housing and building".

http://www.bbsr.bund.de/BBSR/EN/Home/homepage_node.html;jsessionid=A8E0389F251D45423BE1A90D813698C4.live2053

The Federal Office for Environment (UBA) is a superior federal authority subordinated to the BMUB. It is responsible for environmental protection, which includes action areas like air, water and other environmental protection. It is active in climate protection, and avoidance of waste and pesticides. Additionally, the UBA is researching and collecting data, gives policy advice, provides information to citizens, and implements environmental laws.

<http://www.umweltbundesamt.de/en>

The Federal Statistical Office (DESTASTIS) is an independent agency that provides and disseminates statistical information that is objective, independent and of high quality. The federal statistics are available to everybody and free of charge. It is a basis for political decisions and strategic planning due to its reliable data.

<https://www.destatis.de/EN/Homepage.html>

National Energy Agency:

The German Energy Agency (dena) is a centre of expertise for energy efficiency, renewable energy sources and intelligent energy systems. Tasks are to support the implementation of the energy transition with advice and dissemination of information as well as funding of technologies and projects. It is also involved in Germany's promotion of climate protection technologies national and international wide.

<http://www.dena.de/en.html>

Non-Governmental Actors:

Associations

In Germany, about 15,000 associations exist. They represent their respective branches and their lobbying work also includes to make statements on draft laws. Such statements are usually available to the public and often can be downloaded on the respective websites. Associations' impact on national politics varies, some of them are quite influential.

The Association of Municipal Companies (VKU) advocates interests of the public supply and disposal service companies. The VKU is actively involving itself into national and EU policymaking. Its target is to support municipalities and public welfare. Therefore topics like energy efficiency and environmental protection are central for a sustainable development of municipalities.

<http://www.vku.de/startseite.html>

The Efficiency Network for Municipal Companies (ASEW) within the VKU offers a network to municipal companies. The network provides diverse eco-energy products and services. This includes advice, knowledge exchange, and information services free of charge for members, especially regarding energy efficiency.

<https://www.asew.de/de/Home/Startseite/Startseite.html>

The German Association of Energy and Water Industries (BDEW) represents local and municipal utilities up to regional and inter-regional suppliers. Main issues are natural gas, electricity, district heat as

well as water and wastewater. The focus lies on the development of concepts that comprise all energy sources. Sustainable energy and water as well as wastewater disposal is centre to BDEW efforts.

https://www.bdew.de/internet.nsf/id/EN_Home

The German Association for the Promotion of Energy Efficiency (BVFE e.V.) supports its members with information and advice with the goal to save energy and reduce costs to be more compatible on the market. With their strategy, BVFE follows two targets: climate protection and CO₂ emission reduction as well as reduction of costs for their members. Members compose of industry, craft, and social services of the private and public sector.

<http://www.bvfe-online.de/>

The German Industrial Energy Association (VIK e.V.) supports industrial and commercial energy customers. Central approach is to guarantee a competitive and secure energy supply in Germany. Therefore, VIC involves itself actively in lobbying for their members in Germany and the EU. Additionally, VIK sees its members not as problem of climate change but as the solution to it. VIC's idea is that members contribute with innovative products and efficient production to a sustainable production cycle.

<http://vik.de/home.html>

<http://www.die-energieeffizienten.de/home.html>

The Central Association of the Electrical Engineering and Electronics Industry (ZVEI) provides a forum for members in which regulations, standards and norms as well as enforcing instruments for Germany and Europe are discussed and agreed on. Additionally, ZVEI supports its members with technology and market-oriented services. ZVEI also actively involves itself in lobbying for their interest like standardisation in Germany and the EU.

<http://www.zvei.org/en/Pages/default.aspx>

The Association for Heat-Supply (VfW e.V.) has the target to disseminate energy contracting with heat, cold, compressed air, and electricity. Additional target is to make companies qualified energy contractors through compliance of professional standards as well as advice for good conceptual implementation. Professional advice is offered for members.

<http://www.energiecontracting.de/6-verband/wir-ueber-uns/aufgabe.php>

The German Association of Energy and Climate Protection Agencies (eaD) is a forum to exchange ideas and to lobby for members and their central positions. Additionally, the eaD targets on planning and realising plants, advices public and private enterprises, institutions and the public in respect to energy saving potentials as well as integrating renewable energy sources. Also position papers and special education programmes for professionals are offered.

<http://www.energieagenturen.de>

Association of Real Estate Owners (Haus & Grund) is a representative of house owners with about 900,000 members. The Association informs its members about all relevant issues like taxes, tenancy

laws, housing politics, and energy politics. The Association also provides various statements on national energy policies.

<http://www.hausundgrund.de>

German Confederation of Skilled Crafts (Zentralverband des deutschen Handwerks, ZDH) has the purpose to reach a consensus on all major issues in crafts policy. One topic the ZDH works on is the energy transition and its impacts on the German skilled crafts sector.

<http://www.zdh.de/english.html>

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<http://www.staedtetag.de/englisch/index.html>

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NABU's main objectives are the preservation of habitats and biodiversity, the promotion of sustainability in agriculture, forest management and water supply and distribution, as well as to enhance the significance of nature conservation in our society. Currently, transport (especially waterways) are high on the agenda, as NABU is part of the European project „Clean Air in ports“.

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Research Institutes

Research Institutes have an impact on German energy efficiency policy by providing specific consultancy services, by conducting projects that have been issued by ministries, by developing scenarios and by making statements on various topics.

Ecofys is a leading consultancy in renewable energy, energy & carbon efficiency, energy systems & markets and energy & climate policy. Ecofys has offices in the Netherlands, in Germany, the UK, the USA and Belgium.

<http://www.ecofys.com>

Fraunhofer Institute for Systems and Innovation Research (ISI) analyses the origins and impacts of innovations. The institute is organised in seven Competence Centers. Among these Centers is the Competence Center Energy Policy and Energy Markets, the Competence Center Energy Technology and Energy Systems, and the Competence Center Sustainability and Infrastructure Systems.

<http://www.isi.fraunhofer.de/isi-en/index.php>

Institute for Ecological Economy Research (IÖW) is a leading scientific institute in the field of practice-oriented sustainability research. Among their topics are “Environmental Policy & Governance”, as well as “Climate and Energy”.

<http://www.ioew.de/en/>

Institute for Energy and Environmental Research (IFEU) is a non-profit ecological research institute. Its foci lie on waste management, education, energy, industry & emissions, biomass & food, sustainability, life cycle assessment, risk assessment, EIA & SEA, and transport & environment.

<https://www.ifeu.de/english/index.php?seite=startseite>

Institute for Housing and the Environment (IWU) has three main fields of research: housing with a focus on housing supply, housing industry, city development and mobility research, energy with an emphasis on the efficient use of energy in buildings, and integrated sustainable development.

<http://www.iwu.de/1/home/>

Öko-Institut e.V., Institute for Applied Ecology is a leading European research and consultancy institute working for a sustainable future. Their main topics are Chemicals Management and Technology Assessment, Energy and Climate, Emission and Ambient Pollution Control, Radiation Protection, Agriculture and Biodiversity, Sustainability in Consumption, Mobility, Resource Management and Industry, Nuclear Engineering and Facility Safety as well as Law, Policy and Governance.

<http://www.oeko.de/en/>

Wuppertal Institute for Climate, Environment and Energy is taking an interdisciplinary approach and is working towards systems understanding. Designing transitions to a sustainable development is the Wuppertal Institute's stated mission. Transdisciplinary researchers are based in the research groups Future Energy and Mobility Structures; Energy, Transport and Climate Policy; Material Flows and Resource Management; and Sustainable Production and Consumption.

<http://wupperinst.org/en/home/>

Other national initiatives

The German Energy Efficiency Business Initiative (DENEFF) has the objective to accelerate the market development for energy efficiency products and services. Main action areas are to reach highest possible reductions of energy consumption through energy efficiency, to keep neutrality of technology-use in regulatory and funding policies, and to create regulatory frameworks that push energy efficiency services.

<http://www.deneff.org/>

http://www.deneff.org/fileadmin/downloads/DENEFF_english_summary.pdf

Society for Architecture and Environment (Bund Architektur und Umwelt e.V.) is one of the first organisations in Germany dealing with sustainable construction. The Society for Architecture and Environment sees itself as a platform for knowledge exchange and transfer.

<http://www.bau-architekten.de/index.php>

Local/Regional governance level:

Ministries of the Länder:

The Ministries of the Länder also have competencies in energy efficiency policy. E.g. quite a number of the Länder has developed its own energy and climate protection plan, energy concept, etc.

Baden-Württemberg:

The Ministry of the Environment, Climate Protection and the Energy Sector (UM) is responsible for the fields of energy transition, climate protection, the further development of renewable energies, maintaining the natural resources and resource efficiency, as well as environmental technology and international cooperation.

<http://um.baden-wuerttemberg.de/en/home/>

Bavaria:

The Bavarian Ministry of the Interior, for Building and Transport is responsible for a wide range of issues. These are for instance public administration, municipal affairs, public building and works, housing policy and private building, urban renewal and development, mobility and transport, as well as highways, roads and bridges.

<http://www.innenministerium.bayern.de/hil/english/index.php>

The Bavarian Ministry of Economic Affairs and Media, Energy and Technology is responsible for the respective areas in its name. Concerning energy issues the goal is to ensure access to reliable, competitive and affordable energy. Renewable energies are part of the strategic policy development of Bavaria to build-up a reliable and sustainable energy supply.

<http://www.stmwi.bayern.de/en/>

The Bavarian State Ministry of the Environment and Consumer Protection is responsible for diverse topics. These are for instance nature conservation and landscape management, water and flood management, environmental and climate protection, recycling and waste management, nuclear energy and decommissioning, food safety and animal health, sustainable development, as well as consumer protection and international cooperation.

<http://www.stmuv.bayern.de/english/index.htm>

Brandenburg:

The Ministry of Rural Development, Environment and Agriculture of the Federal State of Brandenburg is responsible for the respective areas in its name. This includes resorts like waste management, soil, emission and climate protection, rural development, agriculture and fishery, nature and water conservation.

<http://www.mlul.brandenburg.de/sixcms/detail.php/bb1.c.279082.de>

The Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy of the Federal State of Brandenburg shapes the economic and energy policy, which are seen as closely related. The focus of the ministry lies on the systemic integration of renewables and the development of storage technologies. Currently, the ministry sees conventional energies as indispensable until other energy sources are broadly available.

<http://www.mwe.brandenburg.de/sixcms/detail.php/bb1.c.214029.de>

Hesse:

The Hessian Ministry of the Environment, Climate Protection, Agriculture and Consumer Protection is responsible for the protection of nature and the environment, of soil, water, air and climate. It also monitors food safety and is in charge of consumer protection, animal welfare and radiation protection as well as nuclear safety. The aim is a sustainable regional and urban development.

<https://english.hessen.de/>

The Ministry of Economics, Energy, Transport and Regional Development is aiming on a well-balanced ecological approach. It promotes and develops renewable energies and targets on the improvement of energy efficiency to build reliable, affordable, future-oriented energy supply. Additionally, the mobility and transportation sector is central for the ministry and the development of the region.

<https://english.hessen.de/>

Mecklenburg-Vorpommern:

The Ministry for Economic Affairs, Construction and Tourism sets frameworks with the target of a sustainable economic development and an increase of the employment rate. Apart of that the ministry is in charge of all related issues of the respective areas, also concerning energy efficient construction and sustainable tourism development.

http://www.regierung-mv.de/cms2/Regierungsportal_prod/Regierungsportal/de/wm/index.jsp

The Ministry for Energy, Infrastructure and State Development is responsible for maintenance and construction of the infrastructure, the transport and mobility sector, the energy sector and the urban and regional development.

http://www.regierung-mv.de/cms2/Regierungsportal_prod/Regierungsportal/de/vm/index.jsp

Lower Saxony:

The Ministry for Environment, Energy and Climate Protection is responsible for environmental, emissions, soil and water protection, as well as for water and waste management and the nuclear sector. Additionally, it is active in the fields of climate protection and energy policy. Especially energy efficiency and a sustainable use of resources and land are targets in respect to challenges of climate change.

<http://www.umwelt.niedersachsen.de/startseite/>

North Rhine-Westphalia:

The Ministry for Climate Protection, Environment, Agriculture, Conservation and Consumer Protection has a broad area of responsibility. Generally, it is responsible for policymaking, implementation and monitoring for the state. Topic areas like eco-efficiency, sustainability and innovative energy supply (renewables and efficiency is also topic of the Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy) are in the focus of the ministry. The protection of natural resources is seen as key challenge of the future and is therefore supported by all sub-sector policies and measures.

<https://www.umwelt.nrw.de/english/>

The Ministry for Economic Affairs, Energy, Industry, Mid-Sized Sector and Craft is strongly involved in Germany's energy transition. It focuses on the development and implementation of renewables and a compatible transition of energy sources. A masterplan for the development of the sector and the transition is under discussion.

<http://www.mweimh.nrw.de>

The Ministry of Construction, Housing, Urban Development and Transport is focused on an environmental sustainable development. This includes for instance energy efficiency measures. For the urban development, the focus is on a social, economic and ecologic balance.

<http://www.mbwsv.nrw.de>

Rhineland-Palatinate:

The Ministry for Economic Affairs, Climate, Energy and Regional Planning lies a focus on climate protection through the State Directive for the Promotion of Climate Protection. With that Directive, climate protection, mitigation and adaptation measures are legal obligations in the state. The energy transition is also a main area of action. Here, energy efficiency and the expansion of renewable energy sources are superior targets.

<http://www.mwkel.rlp.de/Startseite/>

Saarland

The Ministry for Economic Affairs, Employment, Energy and Transport has a broad perspective. For the energy and transport sectors, topics like renewable energy sources, energy advice and climate protection, as well as the promotion for public transportation and cycle mobility improvements are of main interest.

http://www.saarland.de/ministerium_wirtschaft_arbeit_energie_verkehr.htm

Saxony

The State Ministry of Economic Affairs, Labour and Transport is responsible e.g. for Saxony's energy policy and for its transport infrastructure.

<http://www.smwa.sachsen.de/index.html>

<http://www.sachsen.de/en/1185.htm>

Saxony-Anhalt:

The Ministry of Science and Economic Affairs is organised in four units: 1) economic order, administration and legislation, 2) research, innovation and Europe, 3) Business promotion, energy and mining, 4) Universities and science. In 2014 an Energy Concept 2030 was developed.

<http://www.mw.sachsen-anhalt.de/ministerium/>

<http://www.sachsen-anhalt.de/lang/english/the-federal-state/the-ministries-and-ministers/ministry-of-sciences-and-economic-affairs/>

The Ministry of Agriculture and the Environment is among others responsible for climate protection and energy.

<http://www.sachsen-anhalt.de/lang/english/the-federal-state/the-ministries-and-ministers/ministry-of-agriculture-and-the-environment/>

Schleswig-Holstein:

The Ministry of Energy, Agriculture, the Environment and Rural Areas is responsible e.g. for renewable energies.

http://www.schleswig-holstein.de/EN/StateGovernment/V/v_node.html

The Ministry of Economic Affairs, Employment, Transport and Technology is responsible e.g. for transport policy, as well as for renewable energies.

http://www.schleswig-holstein.de/EN/StateGovernment/VII/vii_node.html

Thüringia:

The Ministry of the Environment, Energy and Nature Conservancy is responsible e.g. for renewable energies, energy efficiency, energy in buildings, and sustainable mobility.

<http://www.thueringen.de/th8/tmuen/index.aspx>

Non-Governmental Actors:

Energy Agencies (just a short selection, as in each of the 16 Länder one agency is implemented and various cities also have their own climate protection / energy agency):

Berlin Energy Agency (Berliner Energieagentur) “is a modern energy service company located in Berlin. As part of the three business divisions Consulting, Contracting and International Know-how Transfer they develop and realize innovative projects that reduce high energy costs as well as CO2 emissions.”

<http://www.berliner-e-agentur.de/en/partner-innovation>

EnergyAgency.NRW is a “service provider to the state of North Rhine-Westphalia to all matters relating to energy. The EnergyAgency.NRW manages the energy industry cluster ‘EnergyRegion.NRW’ and the cluster EnergyResearch.NRW ‘CEF.NRW’. Furthermore, the EnergyAgency.NRW offers energy consulting services in the form of initial and contracting consultancy for companies and administrative bodies, as well as information and continuous training facilities for specialists and individuals. The portfolio also includes courses in user behavior, mediation services and state-wide campaigns as well as joint actions.”

<http://www.energieagentur.nrw.de/english/energyagencynrw-more-information-25393.asp>

Climate protection and Energy Agency Baden-Württemberg (Klimaschutz- und Energieagentur Baden-Württemberg, KEA) is an independent service provider and thought leading on the topics energy saving and renewable energies - from the Land for the Land. KEA's broad expert knowledge is offered to the Ministries, local governments, companies and citizens of Baden-Württemberg.

<http://www.kea-bw.de/home/>

Energy Agency of the State of Rhineland-Palatine supports local authorities and public organisations, companies and citizens in implementing activities of the energy transition in Rhineland-Palatine. The Energy Agency informs and implements own projects on renewable energy, energy efficiency and energy saving.

<http://www.energieagentur.rlp.de>

1.1.2 TRANSPORT SECTOR

Objectives

According to the Energy Concept the target for the transport sector is that final energy consumption should be reduced by about 10% by 2020 and by about 40% by 2050, compared with the base year of 2005.

Another objective is to have a million electric vehicles on the roads by 2020 and six million by 2030.

Other objectives of establishing policy packages in the transport sector include

- reduction of oil dependence
- helping to balance energy supply and demand (with electric vehicles storing electricity)

Synthesis of policy packages in the Transport Sector

There are a number of policy packages targeting the transport sector in place, however, not as comprehensive as in the buildings sector. The Energy Concept focuses mostly on electric mobility.

Policy components of the Energy Concept include:

- Push for the expansion of electric mobility (part of the National Development Plan for Electric Mobility)
- Labelling regulation for electric vehicles (40th Ordinance on the Implementation of the Federal Immission Control Act, BImSchV)
- Zero-emission vehicles, meaning the coupling of electric mobility with renewable energies
- Push of technological innovations in order to make electric vehicles electricity storages.
- National Hydrogen and Fuel Cell Technology Innovation Programme
- Promotion of promising development and demonstration projects of technologies for producing second-generation biofuels.
- Increasing the proportion of bio-components in fuels and establishing appropriate conditions for this

Target groups in the Transport Sector

The Transport sector does not play a major role in the NEEAP. Measures of the NEEAP are imposed on

- Final energy consumers (HGV toll, air traffic tax)

The Energy Concepts targets, respectively wants to support the business sector in becoming more energy efficient in order to stay globally competitive. Additionally it targets / supports the R&D sector in order to come up with innovative energy efficient technology.

The transport sector policy packages of the Energy Concept mainly target national target groups like

- Final energy consumers or end-use technologies (vehicles running with gas, diesel)
- Supply side actors / industry
- Research and Development

Governance framework in the Transport Sector

Energy efficiency plays a major role in Germany, and even before the EU Energy Efficiency Directive was adopted, Germany had a wide range of policy instruments for increasing energy efficiency. It is one of the few industrialised countries that have managed to decouple energy consumption and economic growth.

Main actors that are generally involved in the implementation of energy efficiency policies in the transport sector in Germany are³:

National governance level

Ministries:

The Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, Building and Nuclear Safety (BMUB) is responsible for policies that are reflected in its name. Main tasks are to prepare legislation for national and EU law, to fund R&D and support innovative technologies, to engage in national and international cooperation, and to communicate about relevant issues to push broad public participation and acceptance.

<http://www.bmub.bund.de/en/bmub/tasks-and-structure/>

<http://www.bmub.bund.de/en/>

The Federal Ministry of Transport and Digital Infrastructure (BMVI) is responsible for the digitalisation, and all means of transportation infrastructure. It supports policy making in those areas, supervises the transport sector, supports R&D and cooperates in that means with the EU and other countries. This includes internet and communication issues, aviation and air navigation, maritime issues and shipping, railway, land transportation, hydrology, and the construction of transport infrastructure.

http://www.bmvi.de/EN/Home/home_node.html

The Federal Ministry for Education and Research (BMBF) is responsible for policies that are reflected in its name, even though education is part of the state (Länder) legislation. The target is to foster participation, prosperity, innovation, sustainability and health through education and specific funding. This also includes international cooperation in these areas.

<http://www.bmbf.de/en/index.php>

The Federal Ministry of Finance (BMF) is responsible for the federal budget, the national economic and fiscal policy strategy as well as for international finance issues. This includes areas like customs and all means of taxes and taxation, legal matters, financial market policies, federal holdings and real estate, EU policy, and central administration and services.

<http://www.bundesfinanzministerium.de/Web/EN/Home/home.html>

³ This is just a selection of the main actors. There are many more, especially when coming to very detailed technical issues or to the regional / municipal level.

The Federal Ministry of Justice and Consumer Protection (BMJV) is mainly responsible for legislation and advising the other Federal Ministries in the preparation of legislative proposals. Main competence areas are in the fields of civil law, commercial and economic law, criminal law, and procedural law as well as consumer policy that insures safety, transparency, comprehensibility and comparability of products and services.

http://www.bmju.de/EN/Home/home_node.html

Other Actors:

Federal Offices:

Federal Offices in Germany are part of the national administration and are subordinated to ministries.

The Federal Office for Economic Affairs and Export Control (BAFA) is a superior federal authority subordinated to the BMWi. Its responsibilities are foreign trade, promotion of economic development, energy and administrative issues. For the energy sector, the BAFA implements measures to promote saving energy, renewables, and new efficient technologies.

<http://www.bafa.de/bafa/en/index.html>

The Federal Agency for Energy Efficiency (BfEE) is subordinated to the BAFA and therefore to the BMWi. It was established in 2009 based on the EU Directive 2006/32/EG on Energy Efficiency. Task of the BfEE is to implement measures of the EU energy efficiency policies.

<http://www.bfee-online.de/bfee/>

The Federal Office for Building and Regional Planning (BBR) is a superior federal authority subordinated to the BMUB. Tasks are to administrate Germany's building issues, cultural heritage, and real estate. Additionally, the BBR is involved in research and advises the German government with respect to urban and regional development, building, real estate and housing.

http://www.bbr.bund.de/BBR/DE/Home/home_node.html

The Federal Institute for Research on Building, Urban Affairs and Spatial Development (BBSR) within the Federal office for Building and Regional Planning "is a departmental research institution under the portfolio of the Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, Building and Nuclear Safety (BMUB). It advises the Federal Government with sectoral specific scientific consultation in the political fields of spatial planning, urban development, housing and building".

http://www.bbsr.bund.de/BBSR/EN/Home/homepage_node.html;jsessionid=A8E0389F251D45423BE1A90D813698C4.live2053

The Federal Office for Environment (UBA) is a superior federal authority subordinated to the BMUB. It is responsible for environmental protection, which includes action areas like air, water and other environmental protection. It is active in climate protection, and avoidance of waste and pesticides. Additionally, the UBA is researching and collecting data, gives policy advice, provides information to citizens, and implements environmental laws.

<http://www.umweltbundesamt.de/en>

The Federal Statistical Office (DESTASTIS) is an independent agency that provides and disseminates statistical information that is objective, independent and of high quality. The federal statistics are available to everybody and free of charge. It is a basis for political decisions and strategic planning due to its reliable data.

<https://www.destatis.de/EN/Homepage.html>

National Energy Agency:

The German Energy Agency (dena) is a centre of expertise for energy efficiency, renewable energy sources and intelligent energy systems. Tasks are to support the implementation of the energy transition with advice and dissemination of information as well as funding of technologies and projects. It is also involved in Germany's promotion of climate protection technologies national and international wide.

<http://www.dena.de/en.html>

Deutsche Bahn AG "was founded in 1994. Today it is one of the world's leading passenger and logistics companies and operates in 130 countries."

<http://www.deutschebahn.com/en/start-en.html>

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Ecofys is a leading consultancy in renewable energy, energy & carbon efficiency, energy systems & markets and energy & climate policy. Ecofys has offices in the Netherlands, in Germany, the UK, the USA and Belgium.

<http://www.ecofys.com>

Fraunhofer Institute for Systems and Innovation Research (ISI) analyses the origins and impacts of innovations. The institute is organised in seven Competence Centers. Among these Centers is the Competence Center Energy Policy and Energy Markets, the Competence Center Energy Technology and Energy Systems, and the Competence Center Sustainability and Infrastructure Systems.

<http://www.isi.fraunhofer.de/isi-en/index.php>

Institute for Ecological Economy Research (IÖW) is a leading scientific institute in the field of practice-oriented sustainability research. Among their topics are “Environmental Policy & Governance”, as well as “Climate and Energy”.

<http://www.ioew.de/en/>

Institute for Energy and Environmental Research (IFEU) is a non-profit ecological research institute. Its foci lie on waste management, education, energy, industry & emissions, biomass & food, sustainability, life cycle assessment, risk assessment, EIA & SEA, and transport & environment.

<https://www.ifeu.de/english/index.php?seite=startseite>

Institute for Housing and the Environment (IWU) has three main fields of research: housing with a focus on housing supply, housing industry, city development and mobility research, energy with an emphasis on the efficient use of energy in buildings, and integrated sustainable development.

<http://www.iwu.de/1/home/>

Öko-Institut e.V., Institute for Applied Ecology is a leading European research and consultancy institute working for a sustainable future. Their main topics are Chemicals Management and Technology Assessment, Energy and Climate, Emission and Ambient Pollution Control, Radiation Protection, Agriculture and Biodiversity, Sustainability in Consumption, Mobility, Resource Management and Industry, Nuclear Engineering and Facility Safety as well as Law, Policy and Governance.

<http://www.oeko.de/en/>

Wuppertal Institute for Climate, Environment and Energy is taking an interdisciplinary approach and is working towards systems understanding. Designing transitions to a sustainable development is the Wuppertal Institute's stated mission. Transdisciplinary researchers are based in the research groups Future Energy and Mobility Structures; Energy, Transport and Climate Policy; Material Flows and Resource Management; and Sustainable Production and Consumption.

<http://wupperinst.org/en/home/>

Other national initiatives

The German Energy Efficiency Business Initiative (DENEFF) has the objective to accelerate the market development for energy efficiency products and services. Main action areas are to reach highest possible reductions of energy consumption through energy efficiency, to keep neutrality of technology-use in regulatory and funding policies, and to create regulatory frameworks that push energy efficiency services.

<http://www.deneff.org/>

http://www.deneff.org/fileadmin/downloads/DENEFF_english_summary.pdf

Society for Architecture and Environment (Bund Architektur und Umwelt e.V.) is one of the first organisations in Germany dealing with sustainable construction. The Society for Architecture and Environment sees itself as a platform for knowledge exchange and transfer.

<http://www.bau-architekten.de/index.php>

Association of German Transport Companies (Verband Deutscher Verkehrsunternehmen e.V., VDV) has about 600 members that are “companies performing public passenger transport and rail freight

transport in Germany. The VDV advises and supports its member companies and politicians, supports the exchange of experience and know-how between the members and prepares technical, operational, legal and economic principles.”

<https://www.vdv.de/english.aspx>

German Association for Transport (Verkehrsclub Deutschland, VCD) is a non-profit organisation heading for an environmentally compatible and socially acceptable, safe and healthy mobility. As an environmentally oriented transport association, VCD does not concentrate on a fluent road traffic alone, but supports a sensible coexistence of all transport modes.

<https://www.vcd.org/startseite/>

German Association of the Automotive Industry (Verband der deutschen Automobilindustrie, VDA) “consists of more than 620 companies involved in production for the automotive industry in the Federal Republic of Germany. The members are divided into three manufacturer groups automobile manufacturers, automotive suppliers, and trailers, special bodies, buses. These three manufacturer groups find their representation in three divisions each assigned a managing director. More than 70 employees in 20 departments actively pursue the interests of the German automotive industry.”

<https://www.vda.de/en>

German Cyclist’s Association (Allgemeiner Deutscher Fahrrad-Club, ADFC) “is the advocate for cycling in Germany. The ADFC works with cities, state and federal governments to improve the conditions for everyday cycling as well as cycling for tourists”.

<http://www.adfc.de/about-us/about-us>

German Automobile Association (Allgemeiner Deutscher Automobil-Club e.V., ADAC) is with currently more than 19 million members the biggest automobile association in Europe and second worldwide. It is a lobbyist of drivers for all topics of mobility. The association is involved especially in road traffic, consumer protection, road safety and road safety education.

<https://www.adac.de>

Local/Regional governance level:

Ministries of the Länder:

The Ministries of the Länder also have competencies in energy efficiency policy. E.g. quite a number of the Länder has developed its own energy and climate protection plan, energy concept, etc.

Baden-Württemberg:

The Ministry of the Environment, Climate Protection and the Energy Sector (UM) is responsible for the fields of energy transition, climate protection, the further development of renewable energies, maintaining the natural resources and resource efficiency, as well as environmental technology and international cooperation.

<http://um.baden-wuerttemberg.de/en/home/>

Bavaria:

The Bavarian Ministry of the Interior, for Building and Transport is responsible for a wide range of issues. These are for instance public administration, municipal affairs, public building and works, housing policy and private building, urban renewal and development, mobility and transport, as well as highways, roads and bridges.

<http://www.innenministerium.bayern.de/hil/english/index.php>

The Bavarian State Ministry of the Environment and Consumer Protection is responsible for diverse topics. These are for instance nature conservation and landscape management, water and flood management, environmental and climate protection, recycling and waste management, nuclear energy and decommissioning, food safety and animal health, sustainable development, as well as consumer protection and international cooperation.

<http://www.stmuv.bayern.de/english/index.htm>

Brandenburg:

The Ministry of Rural Development, Environment and Agriculture of the Federal State of Brandenburg is responsible for the respective areas in its name. This includes resorts like waste management, soil, emission and climate protection, rural development, agriculture and fishery, nature and water conservation.

<http://www.mlul.brandenburg.de/sixcms/detail.php/bb1.c.279082.de>

Hesse:

The Hessian Ministry of the Environment, Climate Protection, Agriculture and Consumer Protection is responsible for the protection of nature and the environment, of soil, water, air and climate. It also monitors food safety and is in charge of consumer protection, animal welfare and radiation protection as well as nuclear safety. The aim is a sustainable regional and urban development.

<https://english.hessen.de/>

The Ministry of Economics, Energy, Transport and Regional Development is aiming on a well-balanced ecological approach. It promotes and develops renewable energies and targets on the improvement of energy efficiency to build reliable, affordable, future-oriented energy supply. Additionally, the mobility and transportation sector is central for the ministry and the development of the region.

<https://english.hessen.de/>

Mecklenburg-Vorpommern:

The Ministry for Economic Affairs, Construction and Tourism sets frameworks with the target of a sustainable economic development and an increase of the employment rate. Apart of that the ministry is in charge of all related issues of the respective areas, also concerning energy efficient construction and sustainable tourism development.

http://www.regierung-mv.de/cms2/Regierungsportal_prod/Regierungsportal/de/wm/index.jsp

The Ministry for Energy, Infrastructure and State Development is responsible for maintenance and construction of the infrastructure, the transport and mobility sector, the energy sector and the urban and regional development.

http://www.regierung-mv.de/cms2/Regierungsportal_prod/Regierungsportal/de/vm/index.jsp

Lower Saxony:

The Ministry for Environment, Energy and Climate Protection is responsible for environmental, emissions, soil and water protection, as well as for water and waste management and the nuclear sector. Additionally, it is active in the fields of climate protection and energy policy. Especially energy efficiency and a sustainable use of resources and land are targets in respect to challenges of climate change.

<http://www.umwelt.niedersachsen.de/startseite/>

North Rhine-Westphalia:

The Ministry for Climate Protection, Environment, Agriculture, Conservation and Consumer Protection has a broad area of responsibility. Generally, it is responsible for policymaking, implementation and monitoring for the state. Topic areas like eco-efficiency, sustainability and innovative energy supply (renewables and efficiency is also topic of the Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy) are in the focus of the ministry. The protection of natural resources is seen as key challenge of the future and is therefore supported by all sub-sector policies and measures.

<https://www.umwelt.nrw.de/english/>

The Ministry for Economic Affairs, Energy, Industry, Mid-Sized Sector and Craft is strongly involved in Germany's energy transition. It focuses on the development and implementation of renewables and a compatible transition of energy sources. A masterplan for the development of the sector and the transition is under discussion.

<http://www.mweimh.nrw.de>

The Ministry Construction, Housing, Urban Development and Transport is focused on an environmental sustainable development. This includes for instance energy efficiency measures. For the urban development, the focus is on a social, economic and ecologic balance.

<http://www.mbwsv.nrw.de>

Rhineland-Palatinate:

The Ministry for Economic Affairs, Climate, Energy and Regional Planning lies a focus on climate protection through the State Directive for the Promotion of Climate Protection. With that Directive, climate protection, mitigation and adaptation measures are legal obligations in the state. The energy transition is also a main area of action. Here, energy efficiency and the expansion of renewable energy sources are superior targets.

<http://www.mwkel.rlp.de/Startseite/>

Saarland

The Ministry for Economic Affairs, Employment, Energy and Transport has a broad perspective. For the energy and transport sectors, topics like renewable energy sources, energy advice and climate protection, as well as the promotion for public transportation and cycle mobility improvements are of main interest.

http://www.saarland.de/ministerium_wirtschaft_arbeit_energie_verkehr.htm

Saxony

The State Ministry of Economic Affairs, Labour and Transport is responsible e.g. for Saxony's energy policy and for its transport infrastructure.

<http://www.smwa.sachsen.de/index.html>

<http://www.sachsen.de/en/1185.htm>

Saxony-Anhalt:

The Ministry of Science and Economic Affairs is organised in four units: 1) economic order, administration and legislation, 2) research, innovation and Europe, 3) Business promotion, energy and mining, 4) Universities and science. In 2014 an Energy Concept 2030 was developed.

<http://www.mw.sachsen-anhalt.de/ministerium/>

<http://www.sachsen-anhalt.de/lang/english/the-federal-state/the-ministries-and-ministers/ministry-of-sciences-and-economic-affairs/>

The Ministry of Agriculture and the Environment is among others responsible for climate protection and energy.

<http://www.sachsen-anhalt.de/lang/english/the-federal-state/the-ministries-and-ministers/ministry-of-agriculture-and-the-environment/>

Schleswig-Holstein:

The Ministry of Economic Affairs, Employment, Transport and Technology is responsible e.g. for transport policy, as well as for renewable energies.

http://www.schleswig-holstein.de/EN/StateGovernment/VII/vii_node.html

Thüringia:

The Ministry of the Environment, Energy and Nature Conservancy is responsible e.g. for renewable energies, energy efficiency, energy in buildings, and sustainable mobility.

<http://www.thueringen.de/th8/tmuen/index.aspx>

Non-Governmental Actors:

Energy Agencies (just a short selection, as in each of the 16 Länder one agency is implemented and various cities also have their own climate protection / energy agency):

Berlin Energy Agency (Berliner Energieagentur) “is a modern energy service company located in Berlin. As part of the three business divisions Consulting, Contracting and International Know-how Transfer they develop and realize innovative projects that reduce high energy costs as well as CO2 emissions.”

<http://www.berliner-e-agentur.de/en/partner-innovation>

EnergyAgency.NRW is a “service provider to the state of North Rhine-Westphalia to all matters relating to energy. The EnergyAgency.NRW manages the energy industry cluster ‘EnergyRegion.NRW’ and the cluster EnergyResearch.NRW ‘CEF.NRW’. Furthermore, the EnergyAgency.NRW offers energy consulting services in the form of initial and contracting consultancy for companies and administrative bodies, as well as information and continuous training facilities for specialists and individuals. The portfolio also includes courses in user behavior, mediation services and state-wide campaigns as well as joint actions.”

<http://www.energieagentur.nrw.de/english/energyagency nrw-more-information-25393.asp>

Climate protection and Energy Agency Baden-Württemberg (Klimaschutz- und Energieagentur Baden-Württemberg, KEA) is an independent service provider and thought leading on the topics energy saving and renewable energies - from the Land for the Land. KEA’s broad expert knowledge is offered to the Ministries, local governments, companies and citizens of Baden-Württemberg.

<http://www.kea-bw.de/home/>

Energy Agency of the State of Rhineland-Palatine supports local authorities and public organisations, companies and citizens in implementing activities of the energy transition in Rhineland-Palatine. The Energy Agency informs and implements own projects on renewable energy, energy efficiency and energy saving.

<http://www.energieagentur.rlp.de>

Other actors:

Association for Transport and Logistics in North Rhine-Westphalia (Verband Verkehrswirtschaft und Logistik Nordrhein-Westfalen e.V., VVWL) is the leading entrepreneur and employers association for transport, logistics, forwarding industry, companies of movers, and disposal companies in North Rhine-Westphalia.

<http://www.vvwl.de>

1.2 NATIONAL PROGRAMMES AND INITIATIVES

In this chapter the National Action Plan on Energy Efficiency (NAPE) and the Climate Action Programme 2020 are described. Both plans / programmes seek to reach the targets outlined in the Energy Concept. The NAPE focuses on the buildings sector, whereas the Climate Action Programme also has a focus on the transport sector.

1.2.1 National Action Plan on Energy Efficiency (NAPE)

General information

Germany's energy efficiency target is to reduce primary energy consumption by 20% by 2020 compared with 2008 and by 50% by 2050. In order to reach this target, the German Federal Government launched a comprehensive strategy on 3rd December 2014 – the National Action Plan on Energy Efficiency (NAPE). The priorities of the NAPE include information and advice, and promotion of energy efficiency investments. It describes three cornerstones (Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy 2014):

1. Stepping up energy efficiency in the building sector
2. Establishing energy efficiency as an investment and business model
3. Increasing individual responsibility for energy efficiency

The NAPE aims to convince all stakeholders that it is necessary to raise energy efficiency and wants to involve all stakeholders in the according efforts. The NAPE tries to show the scope and opportunities and also provides evidence confirming the benefits of a commitment to energy efficiency (Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy 2014). The NAPE includes a set of instruments in order to motivate companies and consumers (consulting, communication and information about efficiency measures, funding facilities and standards for new installations). In the NAPE short-term measures as well as longer-term work processes that will form the core of the Energy Efficiency Strategy for the 18th legislative term, are described.

Figure 1: Short-term measures and long-term work process of NAPE for the 18th legislative term

Source: Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy

Source: Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy 2014

The central short-term measures of the NAPE are:

Regulatory policy instruments

- a) Energy audit obligation for non-SMEs (implementation of Article 8 of the EU Energy Efficiency Directive 2012/27/EU)

The **objective** is the obligation to large-scale enterprises (non-SMEs) to carry out regular energy audits complying with DIN EN 16247-1, the first of them by 5 December 2015 and then every four years.

Target groups are large-scale enterprises (non-SMEs).

Rules and influencing mechanisms: companies that operate an energy management system certified to DIN EN ISO 50001 or an EMAS environmental management system will be exempted from the obligation to conduct energy audits.

Implementation network: By cabinet decision of 5 November 2014, the Federal Government adopted a draft bill to amend the Energy Services Act (EDL-G) to implement Article 8 (4-7) of the Energy Efficiency Directive.

Dissemination and awareness instruments/Informative policy instruments

a) National energy efficiency label for old heating installations

b) Top Runner Strategy – at national and EU level

The **objective** of the National Top Runner Initiative (NTRI) is to increase the motivation for electrical and product-specific energy efficiency and the rational use of power and extend it along the value chain in product lines and across sectors.

The **target groups** of the initiative include equipment manufacturers, dealers and consumers. It is planned to develop an external moderated dialogue with these target groups.

Rules and influencing mechanisms: The voluntary label for the most energy-efficient equipment – the EU Energy Star – will be integrated into the National Top Runner Initiative (NTRI).

Implementation network: With its National Top Runner Initiative (NTRI), the Federal Government will bundle measures for speeding up the market penetration of high-quality services and products (top runners) that contribute to reducing energy consumption. The start of the initiative is planned for 2015 and the earmarked funding is six million euros per year.

Economic policy instruments

a) Granting tax incentives for energy efficiency renovations

The **objective** is to offer an additional assistance option next to the CO2 Building Renovation Programme.

Target groups are owner / occupiers.

Regarding **rules and influencing mechanisms:** eligible for assistance are measures for raising energy efficiency and installing renewable heating in residential buildings.

Implementation network: Introduction as of 2015 over a period of five years. The Federal Government will hold talks on implementation with the federal states to take a final decision (was planned for February 2015).

b) Upgrading, continuation and increase of the CO2 Building Renovation Programme until 2018 (KfW programmes for energy-efficient construction and rehabilitation)

The **objective** is to upgrade programmes in residential buildings and also to include funding for energy efficiency in non-residential buildings.

Upgrade in residential buildings:

- Introduction of the subsidy assessment standard, Efficiency House Plus, for residential buildings, including consulting
- Greater mobilisation of condominium owners' associations
- Allocation of 300 million euros for grant funding with reciprocal cover arrangement for interest subsidies and grant funding.

Funding in non-residential buildings:

- Commercial buildings (including buildings for processing agricultural produce)
- Municipal and social service buildings
- Introduction of the subsidy assessment standard, KfW Efficiency House Plus, for the non-residential sector, including consulting

Target groups are owners and tenants of residential and non-residential buildings.

Rules and influencing mechanisms: Continuation of the successfully tested KfW funding programmes for residential buildings under the CO2 Building Renovation Programme and introduction of a KfW programme for promoting energy-efficient non-residential buildings in line with the current KfW programmes of the CO2 Building Renovation Programme.

Implementation network: The programmes are closely linked to other instruments (including energy consulting, tenancy law, MAP) and will contribute to the achievement of the objectives in tandem with these.

c) Funding for energy performance contracting (including default guarantees)

This measure has the **objective** to lessen default risks for banks and thus enable SMEs to offer energy performance contracting. By expanding the present guarantees, typical risks of energy performance contracting (long term contracts, investment risks of the contractor, etc.) should be reduced.

Target groups include guarantor banks, as well as municipalities and SMEs that will receive assistance in making use of energy performance contracting.

No information is available on **rules and influencing mechanisms** and on the **implementation network**.

d) Upgrading KfW energy efficiency programmes

The **objective** of the upgrading is to introduce a new basic standard (10 percent savings) and a new premium standard (30 percent savings), with the aim of simple, transparent and uniform certification of energy savings.

Target groups of KfW energy efficiency programmes are mostly building owners.

No information is available on **rules and influencing mechanisms**.

Regarding the **implementation network**, KfW will start the implementation in 2015. The cooperation with the federal states' development agencies will be stepped up and the measure will be publicised.

e) Introduction of a competitive tendering scheme

The **objective** is to let the market search for the most cost-efficient, feasible savings potential and compare the measures of various actors in different sectors.

Target groups are energy service providers, municipal utilities, energy cooperatives, manufacturers and other actors.

Regarding **rules and influencing mechanisms** there will be open and closed tenders. The contracts will be awarded to bids for measures with the most economic cost-benefit ratio (euro per saved kWh).

Regarding the **implementation network**, the national government plans the competitive tendering. In 2015 the pilot phase of the electrical energy efficiency project “STEP up!” should start. The planned funding in 2015 is 15 million euros, in 2016 50 million euros, in 2017 100 million euros and in 2018 150 million euros.

Capacity building and networking

a) Quality assurance and optimising existing energy consulting

The **objective** is to upgrade existing energy advisory programmes (including consumer protection organisations and on-site consulting from BAFA⁴), in order to meet specific needs like the linking and improving of the consistency and transparency of advisory services and the reduction of competition between energy consulting programmes.

Direct Target groups are consumer protection organisations and , as their energy advisory services are to be upgraded. Indirect target groups are building owners and particularly condominium owners’ associations and others, as on-site consulting services for them are to be upgraded.

No information is available on **rules and influencing mechanisms** and on the **implementation network**.

b) Energy Efficiency Networks Initiative

The **objective** is to set up and implement nationwide energy efficiency networks on a voluntary basis, where companies can define and implement energy efficiency targets for their network in a direct exchange of experience supervised and moderated by energy consultants. One aim of the network approach is to strengthen corporate responsibility.

Target groups are companies.

Rules and influencing mechanisms: The setting up of Networks is voluntary.

Implementation network: the Federal Government has started an initiative with major private-sector associations and organisations to establish about 500 networks with uniform minimum requirements by 2020.

⁴ BAFA = Federal Office for Economic Affairs and Export Control

1.2.2 Climate Action Programme 2020

General information

The German Cabinet adopted the Climate Action Programme 2020 on 3rd December 2014. The programme includes measures that should be implemented by 2020 in order to fulfil Germany's climate objectives (reducing GHG emissions by 40% compared to the base year 1990).

The Climate Action Programme contains 9 components (Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, Building and Nuclear Safety 2014b):

- 1) National Energy Efficiency Action Plan (NAPE)
- 2) Strategy on climate-friendly building and housing
- 3) Climate action measures in the transport sector
- 4) Reducing non-energy-related emissions in industry, commerce, trade, services, waste management and agriculture
- 5) Reforming emissions trading
- 6) Energy sector
- 7) The model function of the state
- 8) Research and development
- 9) Consultation, awareness raising and initiatives at all levels

For each component the expected contribution in order to close the mitigation gap is listed, and where possible, also quantified. In total, the Climate Action Programme should lead to a reduction of 62 to 78 million tonnes CO₂ equivalent in 2020 compared to the current projection for 2020. Additionally, 3 to 4 million tonnes CO₂ equivalent can be reduced by implementing soft, cross-sectoral measures. Therefore, a total reduction of 82 million tonnes CO₂ equivalent due to this programme can be expected.

Relevant here is especially component No. 2 – the strategy on climate-friendly building and housing. This component has a major contribution in meeting the 2020 targets, as it should lead to a reduction of 5.7 to 10 million tonnes of CO₂ equivalent (taking overlaps into account). 1.5 to 4.7 million tonnes of CO₂ equivalent are over and above the reductions in the buildings sector already included in the NAPE (Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, Building and Nuclear Safety 2014a).

Also component No. 3 – Climate action measures in the transport sector – is relevant here. The measures in the transport sector described in the Climate Action Plan should lead to a reduction of 7 – 10 millions of CO₂ equivalent until 2020 (taking overlaps into account) (Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, Building and Nuclear Safety 2014a).

Instruments of the Climate Action Programme 2020 in the **Buildings Sector** include those of the NAPE. Additionally, the Climate Action Programme 2020 lists the following instruments:

Regulatory policy instruments

- a) Climate-friendly housing for low-income households

The **objective** of this instrument is to support low-income households in renting refurbished homes. Currently, the regulation of income support benefits takes into account only the rent, not the heating

costs. Therefore, low-income households often rent non-refurbished homes and have to pay high heating costs.

Target groups are low-income households.

Rules and influencing mechanisms: If becoming a regulatory policy instruments, it would be mandatory with respective sanctions.

Implementation network: The German government is conducting an open-ended review procedure to add a climate component to the housing benefit.

b) Rents maps

The **objective** of this instrument is to review the regulations on local reference rents in order to take greater into account the energy performance of buildings.

Target groups are local municipalities that are setting up the local rents maps.

Rules and influencing mechanisms: If becoming a regulatory policy instruments, it would be mandatory with respective sanctions.

Implementation network: Local municipalities that are setting up the local rents maps would have to take the new regulation into account.

c) Climate-friendly heat generation

The **objective** of this instrument is to drive forward climate-friendly heat generation. Another important objective is to ensure that housing companies do not lose tax reliefs if they operate photovoltaic systems or combined heat and power plants (as it is the case up to now).

Target groups are housing companies.

Rules and influencing mechanisms: There is no information available.

Implementation network: The German government will amend the guidelines on micro-CHP units. Local authorities, like tax offices, have to deal with the tax reliefs.

Dissemination and awareness instruments/Informative policy instruments

a) Competition for ideas: making climate-friendly building an attractive option

The **objective** of this instrument is to make energy-efficient refurbishment a “lifestyle product”. In order to support this, a competition for innovative ideas will be held.

Target groups are advertising, psychology, construction, etc.

Rules and influencing mechanisms: There is no information available.

Implementation network: There is no information available.

Economic policy instruments

d) Energy efficiency measures and climate action in local authorities

The **objective** of this instrument is to broaden the energy basis in the buildings sector through neighbourhood-based approaches in order to include more renewables and in small-scale approaches to improve the energy-efficient refurbishment of the building stock.

Target groups include local authorities like municipalities.

Rules and influencing mechanisms: The German government will increase funding for the KfW energy efficient urban rehabilitation programme, improve its terms and conditions and the way it is linked to and coordinated with other grant programmes and create better options for accessing funding from more than one scheme.

Implementation network: The KfW energy efficient urban rehabilitation programme, as well as local authority climate action projects under the National Climate Initiative (NKI) is funded by the German government.

Capacity building and networking

a) Training initiative in building efficiency

The **objective** of this training initiative is to train designers and tradespeople on all aspects of energy-efficient building and refurbishment.

Target groups are designers, tradespeople, people working in the construction industry, as well as trainees and trainers.

Rules and influencing mechanisms: There is no information available.

Implementation network: One project of this initiative is “BUILD UP Skills – QUALITRAIN” financed by EU funds. Another project by the BMUB is part of the European Social Fund.

The central instruments of the Climate Action Programme 2020 for the **Transport Sector** are:

Planning instruments

a) Upgrading rail infrastructure

The **objective** of this instrument is to strengthen rail freight transport.

Target groups are logistic companies.

Rules and influencing mechanisms: No information available.

Implementation network: Such a prioritisation strategy has been set out in the 2015 Federal Transport Infrastructure Plan.

b) Strengthening inland waterway transport

The **objective** of this instrument is to create incentives to shift freight transport to inland waterways.

Target groups are logistic companies.

Rules and influencing mechanisms: No information available.

Implementation network: The Federal Government will take care of the specific actions to be made.

c) Cycle and pedestrian transport

The **objective** is to strengthen cycle and pedestrian transport through various measures like developments in electric bikes and pedelecs, upgrading towpaths, grant programmes for cycle and pedestrian transport, allocation of federal funds to build cycle paths, development of new financing instruments.

Target groups are passengers, local authorities.

Rules and influencing mechanisms: No information available.

Implementation network: No information available.

- d) Promotion of the establishment of an appropriate number of charging stations

The **objective** is to meet the efforts to advance the federal government's mobility and fuel strategy and to implement the Clean Power for Transport Directive.

Target groups are drivers of electric vehicles.

Rules and influencing mechanisms: No information available.

Implementation network: No information available.

Regulatory policy instruments

- a) Promotion of car sharing

The **objective** is to introduce legislation to promote car sharing in towns and cities.

Target groups are passengers.

Rules and influencing mechanisms: If becoming a regulatory policy instruments, it would be mandatory with respective sanctions.

Implementation network: Federal Government is responsible.

Financial policy instruments

- a) HGV toll

The **objective** of the HGV toll in road freight transport is to create an incentive to shift freight onto the railways, to make sure that vehicles are used to their full capacity and, by incorporating emission classes and in future also external costs, to encourage the use of HGVs with lower specific emissions of air pollutants.

Target groups of the extended HGV toll are all vehicles with a maximum laden weight of 7.5 tonnes or more, to an additional 1,100 kilometres of trunk road and from 2018 to all trunk roads. A separate toll category will be created for Euro VI vehicles.

Rules and influencing mechanisms: No information available.

Implementation network: No information available.

- b) Funds for long-distance public transport

The **objective** is to increase long-distance public transport.

Target groups are logistic companies and passengers.

Rules and influencing mechanisms: No information available.

Implementation network: The Federal Government will take care of the specific actions to be made.

- c) Depreciation allowance for commercial electric vehicles

The **objective** is to increase the use of electric drives in vehicles

Target groups include the commercial sector.

Rules and influencing mechanisms: No information available.

Implementation network: This instrument would be jointly financed by the federal government and the Länder.

Dissemination and awareness instruments

- a) Promotion of corporate mobility management

The **objective** is to achieve greater use of local public transport and to increase occupancy rates of cars in commuter traffic.

Target groups are commuters.

Rules and influencing mechanisms: No information available.

Implementation network: No information available.

- b) Fuel-saving training courses

The **objective** is to encourage fuel-saving driving techniques.

Target groups are people that are purchasing a new car. Vouchers for fuel-saving training courses should be issued to them.

Rules and influencing mechanisms: No information available.

Implementation network: No information available.

1.2.3 Horizontal measures

1.2.3.1 The German Ecotax

In 1999, Germany introduced an ecotax, based on the “Act on the Introduction of the Ecological Tax Reform” (Bundesgesetzblatt 1999). Its objective is to increase the price of energy and in turn reduce the burden on labour costs. The higher taxes on energy consumption should lead to a reduction in energy use and also to a more efficient use, and in consequence leading to innovative new technologies. The revenue of the taxes are returned to the tax payers in the way of lower pension contributions. This leads to a reduction of non-wage labour costs and to a reduction of the factor ‘labour’ as a whole. Thus, existing jobs can be saved and new jobs created.

Taxes on motor fuel, light heating oil, natural gas, non-low sulphur fuels have been increased and a tax on electricity has been introduced. Target groups are all tax payers with some exemptions, particularly for industry in order to prevent competitive disadvantages. Most import exemptions are the following (www.foes.de):

- Manufacturing sector, forestry and agriculture: they pay a reduced rate of 60%, if the base amount of 511 EUR per energy source (based on electricity and heating fuels) is exceeded
- Manufacturing sector: They enjoy a tax cap if the burden of the eco tax rate is 1.2 times higher than the tax relief from the reduction in pension contributions. Such companies receive a refund of 95% of the difference.
- Public transport has to pay only 50% of the tax rate.
- Combined heat and power plants (CHP): If they have a utilisation rate of at least 70%, they are fully exempt from the mineral oil tax.

- Highly efficient gas-steam power plants: If they fulfil certain conditions, they are fully exempt from the mineral oil tax.
- Electricity from renewable resources: If this electricity is intended for the producer's own use, it is exempt from the electricity tax.

1.3 CONCLUSIONS AND LESSONS LEARNED OF OTHER PROJECTS ABOUT THE PERFORMANCE OF THE NATIONAL POLICY PACKAGES FOR ENERGY EFFICIENCY

1.3.1 Energy Efficiency Watch conclusions

What Energy Efficiency Watch says about Germany:

The Energy Efficiency Watch project analyses all the adopted National Energy Efficiency Action Plans (NEEAPs). The conclusion regarding the German NEEAP is, that it can be “considered to be of a rather high quality” (Energy Efficiency Watch 2013). Comprehensive policy packages addressing investment decisions of consumers and multipliers are implemented. Also, an overarching energy efficiency governance framework is in place. Long-term targets for 2020 and 2050 are described in the NEEAP. Additional positive aspects are a high number of energy agencies at different governance levels and the implemented monitoring, reporting and verification scheme. Next to the analyses of the NEEAPS, interviews with experts have been carried out in the Energy Efficiency Watch project. The interviews with German experts show the same picture of the German energy efficiency policy. The interviews also show that the **transport sector** can be considered as the sector with the weakest link to the German energy efficiency policy and interviewees also see little political will to change that.

Regarding the **residential buildings** sector, a high number of activities to improve energy efficiency are in place. Such activities include e.g. the definition of minimum energy performance standards, the introduction of economic incentives for retrofitting and newly building buildings, and the granting of subsidies for energy audits (Energy Efficiency Watch 2013). One remark is, that EPC standards could be strengthened.

The **general conclusion regarding the building sector** is, that education and training should be improved to ensure that the energy performance standards are attained. Additionally, the regulation of the energy performance certificates should be amended with an obligation for standards in building advertisement plus the setting-up of a national registry.

Regarding the **transport sector**, the German energy efficiency policy is described as having strengths and weaknesses. Main emphasis lies on economic incentives, information, advice and education. Other instruments like regulatory ones, are not used that often. Accordingly, the **conclusion** regarding the German energy efficiency policy for the transport sector is, that improvements could be made, e.g. through adding regulatory instruments like speed limits and driving restrictions.

1.3.2 ODYSSEE-MURE conclusions

What ODYSSEE-MURE says about Germany:

In its Energy Efficiency Profile for Germany ODYSSEE-MURE (2012) shows **trends in energy efficiency** in total and for the industry, household and transport sector by using the energy efficiency index for the whole economy (ODEX). Taking a look on energy efficiency improvements from 1991 to 2010, an increase of 1.2%/year on average efficiency gains can be observed. In detail, until 2009 there was a steady improvement of energy efficiency all sectors. After 2009 energy efficiency decreased slightly.

Concerning **energy efficiency policy measures** especially the new Energy Concept in 2010 and the Energiewende in 2011 (energy turnaround) are seen as main steps towards energy efficiency. The target of the Energiewende concept was to develop a strategy to reduce primary energy consumption by 20% in 2020 and by 50% in 2050. Key issue of this idea is to significantly increase energy efficiency and meeting the energy demand by renewables. An impact evaluation of ODYSSEE-MURE shows that especially policies in the buildings sector (non-residential and residential) have a huge efficiency potential while the industry and transport sectors contribute only (comparatively) small efficiency gains.

- Energy efficiency trends for the **household sector** show that this sector benefited between 1991 and 2010 from more efficient appliances and space heating, which caused an energy efficiency gain of 1.3%/year. Since 2009, energy efficiency stagnates in this sector.
- For the **transport sector** energy efficiency trends show steady improvements for the period between 1991 and 2010. Still, modal shift had a comparatively small impact on transport energy consumption.
- For the **transport sector** ODYSSEE-MURE lists the national strategy to push electric vehicles and the German approach to advocate ambitious CO₂ limits for all vehicles. Also the emission-based vehicle tax is mentioned within several others.
- The **buildings sector** (both non-residential and residential) plays a crucial role to cut down CO₂ emissions in Germany and energy efficiency is a key instrument to reach this target. ODYSSEE-MURE lists diverse measures of the German government that are planned: implementing the climate neutral building standard for new buildings by 2020, measures within the Energy Saving Ordinance of 2012, market incentive programmes for renewable power and heat generation as well as the KfW Bank programme “Energy-efficient rebuilding”. As mentioned above this sector’s impact on energy efficiency is estimated very high.

1.3.3 Entranze conclusions

What Entranze says about Germany:

The Entranze project is about the fast and effective penetration of nearly Zero-Energy Buildings (nZEB) and renewable heating and cooling (RES-H/C) within the existing national building stocks.

Entranze finds that national programmes and strategies in Germany are adequate and regularly revisited. Good research is awarded and KfW Bank funding programmes are comprehensively reviewed. Despite well-established policies and measures for the refurbishment of buildings, the Entranze project calculates, that existing instruments will not be sufficient for reaching the targets. Therefore, a number of policy recommendations have been developed (Entranze project 2014):

- “Develop a long-term transfer strategy with long-term and intermediate targets and a sufficient monitoring
- the creation of suitable and cost efficient enforcement instruments for the EnEV
- improvement and extension of information tools
- implementation of a use obligation of RES-H in case of boiler replacement in existing buildings
- changes in the financial support scheme
- improve the role of public buildings as best practices”

1.3.4 bigEE

What bigEE says about Germany:

The web-based knowledge platform bigee.net deals with energy efficiency in buildings, building-related technologies and appliances in the world's main climatic zones. Regarding the German energy efficiency policy for buildings, bigEE argues that "Germany's energy efficiency efforts have been well orchestrated" (www.bigee.net). Energy performance certificates as well as other certifications schemes are available. Additionally, the government offers financial incentives for all building sectors via KfW. Consumer information centres and specially trained energy advisors offer information on funding possibilities and opportunities to save energy. So, the general conclusion is, that "Germany has established a comprehensive package in order to increase the energy efficiency of its building stock" (www.bigee.net).

1.3.5 IEA

What IEA says about Germany:

According to IEA's 2013 review for Germany, "Germany is among the world leaders in terms of energy-efficient buildings" (IEA 2013). The review says, that Germany has stricter requirements in building codes (the EnEV) compared to other countries. Additionally, a number of policies targeting the refurbishment of buildings are in place, together with a high target of 2% increase in the annual refurbishment rate. However, as the IEA review notes, refurbishment of existing buildings is not mandatory.

Regarding transport, the IEA review points out, that the German automobile industry plays a leading role in the development of fuel-efficient technologies, and that German energy efficiency policy in the transport sector focuses on improving the technical efficiency of light and heavy-duty road vehicles, whereas the switching to more fuel-efficient modes of transport do not play a major role.

1.3.6 ChangeBest – Promoting the Development of an Energy Efficiency Service (EES) Market

www.changebest.eu

ChangeBest was a project within the Intelligent Energy Europe Programme and ran from 2009 to 2012. It aimed at promoting the development of an energy efficiency service market in Europe. Co-ordinated by the Wuppertal Institute and Prof. Dr. Wolfgang Irrek, Hochschule Ruhr West / University of Applied Sciences, 20 project partners, a few subcontractors and further experts as well as at least 38 partners from practice (energy companies and ESCOs) co-operated in this project within the framework of the "Intelligent Energy Europe Programme" of the European Commission.

In total 48 new EES have been developed and field tested during the 3 year project lifetime. Project tasks included developing and introducing energy efficiency services for private households and business clients, based on analyses, experience exchange, general strategy concepts and bilateral dialogues with individual companies on their business plans and product developments.

ChangeBest provides a detailed assessment of the EES markets with conclusions and recommendations for the policy strategy to support EES development at the level of the European Union (EU) and the 17 project countries.

Main conclusions regarding the EES market in Germany were that the „German EES market is one of the most established in Europe. Several national framework conditions supported and support the development of the EES market. Currently, policies and measures within the German National Energy Efficiency Action Plan as well as of the German Integrated Energy and Climate Plan stimulate activities to increase energy efficiency. The EU Directive on energy end- use efficiency and energy services has not been fully implemented in Germany yet and has therefore no impact so far. The policy mix certainly has a substantial influence on the current and future development of the EES market in Germany. However, there are currently no direct measures to stimulate a broad introduction of EES in the different market segments.”

2. INTERACTION BETWEEN THE NATIONAL AND THE SUB-NATIONAL LEVELS

Being a federal state, policy making in Germany takes place in a multi-level system: The federal republic (Bund), the 16 federal states (Länder) and the districts (consisting of several municipalities) or district-free cities, respectively, all have specific competencies and functions. While the federal republic and the states have their own legislative power granted by the Basic Law, the competencies of the districts and district-free cities are legally fixed by the state legislatures.

With respect to energy (efficiency) policy, the Bund is the major actor. According to the German Basic Law, the federal parliament (Bundestag) has the power to adopt laws on matters of energy and climate protection, though these have to be approved by the upper house, the Bundesrat, which represents the federal states. Consequently, the German government sets the guidelines of energy and climate policy and is the crucial actor pushing the “Energiewende” forward and implementing the National Action Plan for Energy Efficiency. Not least to their role in the Bundesrat, the Länder also play an important part in German energy (efficiency) policy.

Looking at the importance of the local and regional level for German energy (efficiency) policy, one finds an intricate picture. First one has to keep in mind that there are tasks and services municipalities are legally obliged to fulfil and offer. Some of these have relevance for the implementation of the German energy efficiency policy. For instance, municipalities are responsible for monitoring the compliance of building codes including minimum energy performance standards. Yet, how municipalities have to monitor the compliance is regulated by the states. Another important field, in which municipal administrations may (or may not) support national energy efficiency policy is urban planning. One example is zoning regulation, which can include regulation on permissible heating systems and/or make the use of district heating obligatory. If the land where new residential or commercial buildings are to be built is sold by the municipality, it can even demand higher minimum energy performance standards than federal law prescribes. Nevertheless, not least due to the currently low number of newly built buildings, the regulatory power of municipalities with respect to the energy efficiency of (new) buildings is limited. Urban planning also has relevance for the energy efficiency of the transport sector. Planning a city in a way to encourage walking and bike use, to facilitate the use of public transportation and to increase the cost of car use, is possible (though not easy). Additionally, urban and land-use planning is of importance for the development of renewable energies since the land-use plan has to e.g. allow the installation of wind farms on specific sites.

Principally, municipalities have the option to devise and implement their own incentives and measures supporting their citizens and the local economy to invest in energy efficiency. Yet in many cases this competence cannot be used due to budgetary limits. The predominant share of municipalities in Germany run deficits even without implementing expensive additional energy efficiency policies. The unfavourable financial situation of many municipalities is one of the reasons why the federal government helps to fund local energy and climate protection measures through various channels. For instance, it funds the development of Climate Action Plans, an opportunity more than 1400 municipalities have used in recent years. The federal governments also supports specific measures, like the retrofitting of street lighting. Since the beginning of the current decade, the Bund sponsors the development and implementation of action plans aiming at retrofitting whole neighbourhoods, including an improvement of energy efficiency.

Few cities and districts may also use their public enterprises to further energy efficiency. Those municipalities which still (or again) own utilities can use their managerial power for investments in ener-

gy efficiency and renewable energies. Many municipalities also hold shares in housing companies and thereby are able to encourage the (energy efficiency) refurbishment of their dwelling stocks.

Many cities and municipalities committed themselves to significant emission reduction targets or joined (inter)national networks of cities wanting to contribute one's share to climate protection. For instance, in July 2015 57 German cities are member of the Covenant of Mayors (CoM), of which all have already submitted a Sustainable Energy Action Plan. More than 450 municipalities in Germany belong to the Climate Alliance and have thereby pledged to reduce their greenhouse gas emissions by 10 % every 5 years. National initiatives and networks are important as well. More than 140 cities and regions are part of the initiative 100%-Renewable with the aim of completely switching their energy supply to renewable energies.

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HERON (No: 649690): Deliverable D1.1

LANDSCAPE OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICY PACKAGES IN A MULTI-LEVEL GOVERNMENT SYSTEM

**PART OF WORK PACKAGE 1: MAPPING OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICY INSTRUMENTS AND
AVAILABLE TECHNOLOGIES IN BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT**

Partner: *Energy Policy & Development Centre – National & Kapodistrian University of Athens*

NATIONAL REPORT

HELLAS, AUGUST 2015

Università Commerciale
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OXFORD
BROOKES
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HERON: Forward – looking socio-economic research on Energy Efficiency in EU countries

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649690. The content of this document reflects only the authors’ views and the EASME is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Contents

GLOSSARY	FEHLER! TEXTMARKE NICHT DEFINIERT.
ACRONYMS	4
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	6
1. THE ROLE OF GOVERNANCE AND ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICY PACKAGES ON THE NATIONAL LEVEL	7
1.1 POLICY PACKAGES AND POLICY GOVERNANCE IN EUROPEAN MEMBER STATES.....	11
1.2 NATIONAL PROGRAMMES AND INITIATIVES.....	31
1.3 CONCLUSIONS AND LESSONS LEARNED OF OTHER PROJECTS ABOUT THE PERFORMANCE OF THE NATIONAL POLICY PACKAGES FOR ENERGY EFFICIENCY.....	45
2. INTERACTION BETWEEN THE NATIONAL AND THE SUB-NATIONAL LEVELS	48
REFERENCES.....	50

Table of Figures

Figure 1: Effective policy packages in energy efficiency policy.....	8
Figure 2: A prototypical process for policy development in energy efficiency	9

Table of Tables

Table 1: Savings per sector.	13
Table 2: Development of energy figures for 2007, 2009 and 2011, and the national indicative target.	14
Table 3: List of policy instruments for the energy efficiency in the building sector.	15
Table 4: List of policy instruments for the energy efficiency in the transport sector.	26

ACRONYMS

AMVIR	Association of Motor Vehicles Importers Representatives
BAT	Best Available Technologies
BI	Buildings' Infrastructures SA
CAA	Civil Aviation Authority
CEB	Council of Europe Development
CERTH	Centre for Research and Technology Hellas
CHP	Combined Heat and Power
CNG	Compressed Natural Gas
CoR	Committee of the Regions
CRES	Center for Renewable Energy Sources and Saving
CSF	Community Support Framework
EC	European Commission
EE	Energy Efficiency
EES	Energy Efficiency Service
EEW	Energy Efficiency Watch
EIB	European Investment Bank
EIPAK	(Greek interpretation) Greek Institute of PAssive Building
EPC	Energy Performance Certificate
EPBD	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
ESCO	Energy Services COmpany
EU	European Union
GG	Government Gazette
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GSRT	General Secretariat for Research and Technology
HBA	Hellenic Bank Association
HF	Holding Fund
HIT	Hellenic Institute of Transport
HRADF	Hellenic Republic Asset Development Fund
HSA	Hellenic Statistical Authority
JESSICA	Joint European Support for Sustainable Investment in City Areas
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
IEA	International Energy Agency
IEE	Intelligent Energy Europe
KENAK	Greek Regulation for the Energy Efficiency of Buildings
LA	Local Authorities
LED	Light-Emitting Diode
LPG	Liquefied Petroleum Gas
MA	Managing Authority

MD	Managing Director
MEECC	Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change
MEIST	Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism
MLG	Multi-Level Governance
NBG	National Bank of Greece
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
NEEAP	National Energy Efficiency Action Plan
NKUA	National and Kapodistrian University of Athens
NZEB	Nearly Zero Energy Building
NTUA	National Technical University of Athens
OASA	Athens Urban Transport Organisation
OASTH	Organization of Urban Transportation of Thessaloniki
OECD	Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development
OP	Operational Programme
OPC	Operational Programme for Competitiveness
OPE	Operational Programme for Energy
OPESD	Operational Programme for Environment and Sustainable Development
OSE SA	National Railway Infrastructure administrator
OTA	(Greek interpretation) Local Authorities
PI	Policy Instrument
PPCs	Public Passenger Cars
PPP	Public – Private – Partnership
R&D	Research and Development
RAE	Regulatory Energy Authority
REACM	Regional Energy Agency of Central Makedonia
RED	Renewable Energy Directive
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
RUE	Rational Use of Energy
SG	Secretary General
SEAP	Sustainable Energy Action Plan
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
SUMPs	Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans
TCG	Technical Chamber of Greece
UDF	Urban Development Fund
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
YPEKA	(Greek interpretation) Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change
WP	Work Package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report aims to present the overview of Hellenic energy efficiency policy packages for the building (residential and tertiary) and the transport sectors supported by a multi-level governance framework.

The Hellenic energy efficiency policy packages for these sectors include a variety of policy instruments (regulatory, financial, dissemination, awareness and capacity building), Action Plans, Programmes and Initiatives and are addressing both final energy consumers and the “supply side” (such as ESCOs, energy inspectors, professionals). The Programmes and Initiatives concern mainly the building sector, with emphasis to the public sector.

Particularly, concerning the buildings sector, the majority of the policy instruments and programmes are targeting to the final energy consumers. The policy instruments for the final energy consumers include:

- financial mechanisms such as the Green Fund and subsidies for renovation,
- regulatory standards such as energy labelling, energy audits and green public procurements,
- voluntary approaches such as eco-design requirements for appliances,
- dissemination, awareness and capacity building through information campaigns for certain programmes such as “Energy Efficiency at Household buildings” and European Initiatives (BUILD UP).

Concerning the transport sector, the policy package has the following policy components according to the Avoid-Shift-Improve (ASI) approach:

- System efficiency: new transport infrastructure;
- Travel efficiency: Reshaping of the public transport system, eco-driving, promotion of cycling, consumer information on fuel economy of new passenger cars;
- Vehicle efficiency: incentives for the replacement of old technology cars, tax exemptions for electric and hybrid vehicles;

Furthermore, a synopsis of project results on the performance of the Hellenic national energy efficiency policy packages is presented.

The supportive multi-level governance framework (MLG) has three levels (European, national and local/regional) each of which has a considerable horizontal structure, particularly the national one that includes all relevant Ministries, the Technical Chamber, the Hellenic Statistical Authority, as well as other governmental and non governmental entities. The MLG of the building sector is more extended and active vertically and horizontally compared to that of the transport sector.

The interaction/cooperation (in terms of correlations and outcomes) among the three levels (European, national and local/regional) in the two selected sectors is described considering the two dimensions (horizontal and vertical) of the MLG and as a total. The European and the national policy levels are considered to be the most active ones, while the local/regional policy level interacts with the aforementioned levels mainly through programmes and initiatives.

1. THE ROLE OF GOVERNANCE AND ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICY PACKAGES ON THE NATIONAL LEVEL

Conceptual Reference Points for Analysing Energy Efficiency Policies in European Member States: Policy Packages and Policy Governance

Evaluations and assessments of national and local energy efficiency policies have shown that a comprehensive mix of policies is likely to be most effective to reduce energy consumption (Thomas et al, 2013, Höfele et al. 2012, www.bigee.net). Well-designed **packages of policies and measures** need to assist various actors in overcoming their specific barriers and strengthening their incentives.

Particularly in the buildings and transport sector, several policy instruments will need to interact and reinforce each other, leading to a comprehensive policy package. Ideally, every policy or measure has its own function within the package, its advantages, its specific target groups or objects and specific operational mechanisms¹ (for more information see Policy Guide on www.bigee.net).

For the buildings sector, for example, two types (and foci) of integrated policy packages can be distinguished in principle:

(1) Packages directly addressing final energy consumers or end-use technologies in the different sectors and

2) packages complementarily focussing the “supply side” of measures and services, such as energy companies, energy service companies (ESCOs), architects, installation contractors, manufacturers etc.

In this respect, it is worth noting that innovation policies constitute an important pillar of public regulation, as they allow manufacturers to produce new more efficient products to be employed in the consumer market (on the other hand, process innovation measures can be seen as another case in which the policy does not target energy efficiency by design but it directly contributes to reduce the final energy consumption, see D.1.3). Such supports are economically justified by the market failures that the innovation process generates (e.g., uncertainty and knowledge spillovers). Thus, technology development, technology diffusion and market demand have to go in parallel in order to obtain physical efficiency gains without loss of economic efficiency in government spending.

The analyses of the first round of National Energy Efficiency Action Plans show, that all Member States have displayed policies and instruments belonging to the first type while the second was rather underrepresented and developed only in a few European member states (Wuppertal Institute and Ecofys 2009, see also: Thomas et al. 2013).

¹ described as rules-influencing mechanisms and implementation network in the evaluation method AMS

Figure 1: Effective policy packages in energy efficiency policy

Source: Wuppertal Institute and Ecofys (2009)

The above mentioned components of comprehensive policy packages also include a third type of measures and activities: governance frameworks. The International Energy Agency (IEA, 2010), for example, puts special attention to these frameworks by distinguishing between enabling frameworks, institutional arrangements and co-ordination mechanisms. Such overarching frames provide stable conditions for related investments or services. For this reason, integrated policy packages should be complemented by consolidating efforts at Member State level targeting at

- institutional framework conditions for energy efficiency policy (e.g. energy agencies, also at regional or local level),
- institutional and organisational framework conditions for energy efficiency programmes (energy efficiency mechanisms)
- a legal framework (e.g. for energy services) and
- a participatory process involving stakeholders in national energy efficiency policy.

A few EU Member States already have substantial experience in setting up such comprehensive supportive frameworks. For energy efficiency mechanisms, two approaches are usually distinguished: On the one hand, the government can establish the requisite framework either via an energy efficiency obligation or mandatory savings target (with or without certificate trading). On the other hand, such a framework can be set up by an energy saving trust or fund (including, if appropriate, an obligation for the energy industry to provide funding). In such systems (especially the obligation-based solutions), energy companies play a far greater role in supporting energy efficiency improvement compared to 'conventional' policy instruments. Moreover, many Member States have enhanced market-based improvement of energy efficiency with the help of energy efficiency service (EES).

The setting up of coherent policy packages requires also an understanding of the **governance process**, in which policies are getting both developed and implemented. The prototypical process described in the figure below provides a procedural frame for Member States on how to align the pro-

cess of national target setting with the development, implementation and evaluation of policy programmes. Starting with the assessment of the energy savings potential in each sector, a strategic plan (roadmap) has to be developed before supportive framework conditions and sectoral policy packages can be designed to tap the potentials. Ex ante evaluations of potential costs and effects allow to assess the total anticipated effects of savings compared to the national ESD target.

Figure 2: A prototypical process for policy development in energy efficiency

Source: Wuppertal Institute (2012)

To achieve the full potential of energy efficiency policies and measures in the **transport sector**, it is important to appreciate its complexity. As in the building sector, for example, single, uncoordinated measures can have only limited success. Thus, **policy packages** which consist of harmonised policies and measures and which address all three dimensions of energy efficiency in the transport sector can be expected to be most effective. Ideally, positive incentives („pull“-measures) need to be supported by disincentives („push“-measures). For instance, a well developed and convenient public transport infrastructure can have a „pull-effect“. In combination with restrictions to car use, for example by parking restrictions or pricing measures („push-effect“), the shift to more energy efficient modes can

be even more rapid. This example shows that a well-coordinated combination of push- and pull-measures can contribute to higher energy efficiency in the transport sector².

Energy-efficient transportation needs to be encouraged on three different levels. There is potential to achieve greater energy efficiency for individual vehicles (vehicle efficiency) and trips (travel efficiency), as well as the whole transport system (system efficiency).

Corresponding to these three levels of energy efficiency in transport, three basic strategies exist to improve energy efficiency:

- Avoid travel or reduce the need to travel, in order to increase system efficiency
- Shift to more efficient modes of transport, in order to increase travel efficiency.
- Improve the energy efficiency of different modes of transport and vehicle technology, in order to improve the vehicle efficiency.

The mixture of appropriate (push- and pull-) measures depends on the circumstances in each individual country or city.

² Regulatory-push and demand-pull measures have to be intended also in economic sense. While demand-pull actions tend to alter the market (e.g. fuel taxes), supply actions operate mostly on R&D incentives for manufactures. Further distinction can be done by separating prescriptive instruments from voluntary approaches. All these categories have to be taken into account as they dynamically interact. For recent evidence in OECD countries see Costantini, Crespi and Palma (2015). Characterizing the policy mix and its impact on eco-innovation in energy-efficient technologies. SEEDS WP 11/2015.

1.1 POLICY PACKAGES AND POLICY GOVERNANCE IN EUROPEAN MEMBER STATES

Energy Efficiency (EE) has been quoted as an objective, target or priority in a set of national official documents. Most of them contain brief descriptions or detailed presentations of policy packages (programmes, measures, initiatives, policy instruments) that need to be implemented and their respective policy governance so as to promote the respective EE technologies and practices in the main national sectors (buildings (residential-tertiary), transportation, industry).

These documents – for the two sectors (buildings-transportation) that the HERON project examines - are (in chronological order):

1. *“Development Plan for Transportation for the period 2007-2013 and for twenty years”*: It was prepared by the Ministry of Transportation and Communications in 2006. The document aimed to explore and imprint the basic national options and priorities of the transport sector for a long-term planning (Ministry of Transportation and Communications, 2006).
2. *“First Hellenic National Energy Efficiency Action Plan - Pursuant to Directive 2006/32/EC”*. It was prepared by the Ministry of Development and the Centre for Renewable Energy Sources (CRES) in 2008 for fulfilling the requirements of Directive 2006/32/EC (First Hellenic National Energy Efficiency Action Plan, 2008).
3. *“5th National Communication of Greece to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC)”*. It was prepared and submitted to the UNFCCC by the Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change in year 2010 (Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, 2010).
4. *“2nd National Energy Efficiency Action Plan 2008-2016, Pursuant to Directive 2006/32/EC”*. It was prepared by CRES and issued as part of the implementation of Directive 2006/32/EC on energy end-use efficiency and Law 3855/2010 on “Measures to improve energy end-use efficiency, energy services and other provisions” (Government Gazette 95 A, 23.6.2010) (Second Hellenic National Energy Efficiency Action Plan 2008-2016, 2011).
5. *“National Energy Plan – Roadmap to 2050”*. The Committee of National Energy Planning prepared and submitted this report to the Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change (MEECC) in 2012. The aim was to present data and assumptions for defining the national development strategy for the energy system (Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, 2012).
6. *“National Annual Report under Article 24(1) of Directive 2012/27/EU”*. This national report concerned the progress towards meeting the national 2020 targets for improving energy efficiency and was drawn up in accordance with Annex XIV to the relevant Directive (Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, Secretariat General for Energy and Climate Change, 2013).
7. *“6th National Communication and 1st Biennial Report under the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change”*. It was prepared and submitted to the UNFCCC by the Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change (MEECC) in year 2014 (Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, 2014).
8. *“Report of long-term strategy for motivating investments for renovations of the national building stock consisted of households, commercial buildings, public and private (Article 4, Directive 27/2012/EC)”*. It was prepared by the MEECC in 2014 and is the first version of the long-term strategy for motivating investments for building renovations according to article 4 of Directive 27/2012/EC (Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, 2014).

9. *“Exploring an integrated urban intervention for the city of Athens”*. It was prepared in April 2014 by the Municipality of Athens and the Organization of Regulatory Plan of the city of Athens³ for providing a proposal about the integrated urban planning of the Hellenic capital (Municipality of Athens, 2014).
10. *“Third Hellenic National Energy Efficiency Action Plan, 2014 – Pursuant to Article 24(2) of Directive 2012/27/EU”*. It concerned the implementation of national energy efficiency improvement objectives for year 2020 and was based on Annex XIV of Directive 2012/27/EU. It was prepared by the Centre for Renewable Energy Sources in December 2014 (Third Hellenic National Energy Efficiency Action Plan, 2014).

Objectives

Current objectives

The current national target is 9% reduction of final energy savings for year 2016⁴ (corresponding to energy savings of 16,46 TWh) compared to the average annual final energy consumption of the reporting period (2001-2005) (industries participating in the Emission Trading Scheme are excluded)(6th National Communication of Greece to UNFCCC, 2014; Third Hellenic National Energy Efficiency Action Plan, 2014; Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, Secretariat General for Energy and Climate Change, 2013; Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, 2010).

This objective was set initially under the provisions of Directive 2006/32/EC, but still remains in place and progress towards it is being monitored through the National Energy Efficiency Action Plans (NEEAPs) (Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, Secretariat General for Energy and Climate Change, 2013). It is also characterized as a “stepping stone” towards measures for improving the national EE efforts (Third Hellenic NEEAP, 2014).

There is an additional objective for the buildings sector that was set in accordance with the requirements of Directive 2012/27/EC⁵. The objective concerns renovations of up to an annual share of 3% of the total floor area of buildings that are owned and occupied by the central public administration with a total useful floor area more than 500 m² (Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, 2014). The MEECC has prepared an initial list of 82 such buildings, with total floor area of 310.000 m² so as to launch planned renovations of 3% of their total floor area (approximately 10.000 m² annually) (Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, 2014).

The EE target set for year 2020 is to achieve final energy consumption levels of 18,4 Mtoe (Third Hellenic NEEAP, 2014).

Sectoral objectives

Sectoral EE targets were set in the **First NEEAP** for the year 2016. These sectoral targets are also included in the *“Report of long-term strategy for motivating investments for renovations of the national building stock consisted of households, commercial buildings, public and private”* (Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, 2014).

The methodology used in the first NEEAP for the calculation of the national indicative EE target was specified in Article 4 of Directive 2006/32/EC. The national energy savings target expressed in TWh resulted from the multiplication of the overall average of final inland consumption in the five years (2001-2005) with the percentage 9% (First Hellenic NEEAP, 2008). So, the national indicative annual energy savings target for 2016 was set at 16,46 TWh and the national intermediate indicative annual

³ <http://www.organismosathinas.gr/>

⁴ The 5th National Communication of Greece to UNFCCC refers to 9% reductions for the time period 2008-2016.

⁵ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32012L0027&from=EN>

energy savings target for 2010 at 5,10 TWh (First Hellenic NEEAP, 2008). The following table presents a summary of the optimum distribution of the savings target towards the sectors, according to the First NEEAP.

Table 1: Savings per sector.

	Savings for target achievement (in GWh)	
	2010	2016
Residential sector	1679	5533
Tertiary sector	1529	5715
Industry (outside the ETS)	127	680
Transport	1787	6731
Total Savings	5122	18659

(Source: First Hellenic National Energy Efficiency Action Plan, 2008)

The **Second NEEAP** was prepared as pursuant to Directive 2006/32/EC and Law 3855/2010 (Government Gazette 95 A, 23.6.2010) and included (Second Hellenic NEEAP 2008-2016, 2011):

- Description and evaluation of all measures that had been, were being or were planned to be implemented to end-use sectors (launched from 2007 onwards);
- Extensive description of the energy savings achieved through EE measures with direct reference to the First NEEAP;
- Presentation of the progress towards the interim energy savings target in 2010 based on data and estimates, with a forecast on energy savings for 2016;
- Description of the national strategies (forecasts and targets) for primary energy savings.

The interim final energy savings target for year 2010 (5,1 TWh) was exceeded (indicative amount 9,24 TWh, having excluded the effect of economic recession) (Second Hellenic NEEAP 2008-2016, 2011). However, the achievement of the interim target could not be largely attributed to EE measures but to economic recession.

According to Article 3 of Directive 2012/27/EU, all EU Member States have to set an indicative national EE target for 2020, based on either primary or final energy consumption, primary or final energy savings, or energy intensity (Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, Secretariat General for Energy and Climate Change, 2013). In the most recent national official documents (3rd NEEAP, National Energy Plan – Roadmap to 2050), only quantified EE targets in ktoe/TWh are defined for 2020. There are not sectoral EE targets for year 2020.

More specifically, **in the Third NEEAP of Hellas**, ODEX indicators were used for the assessment of the energy savings due to technological interventions excluding simultaneously the influence of externalities⁶. For setting the Greek national EE target for 2020, the following were considered (Third Hellenic National Energy Efficiency Action Plan, 2014):

- energy consumption in the 28 EU Member States in 2020 should not exceed 1,483 Mtoe of primary energy or 1,086 Mtoe of final energy,
- the measures: i) in Directive 2012/27/EU, ii) which have been adopted and are still being adopted to meet the national energy saving targets described in Law 3855/2010 “*Measures to improve energy efficiency in end use, energy services and other provisions*” (Government Gazette 95 A, 23.06.2010), as part of implementing Directive 2006/32/EC.

⁶ such as economic recession, weather conditions etc

The EE target set for 2020 is to achieve final energy consumption levels of 18,4 Mtoe. This level was decided by taking into account estimates regarding the development of the Hellenic economy, the implementation of policy instruments and programmes for EE, RES and the achievement of energy savings in final energy consumption and primary energy production. Energy savings target for the period 2014-2020⁷ is 3.332,7 ktoe (38,8 TWh), out of which the total for all new annual savings is 902,1 ktoe (10,5 TWh). The intermediate periods for checking the progress towards the total EE target and the new expected savings, are the following (Third Hellenic NEEAP, 2014; Ministry of Finance, 2015):

1. 2014-2015, concerning which the intermediate target will be 300,7 ktoe (3,5 TWh), and
2. 2016-2018, concerning which the intermediate target will be 1.678,9 ktoe (19,5 TWh).

Table 2: Development of energy figures for 2007, 2009 and 2011, and the national indicative target.

	2007	2009	2011	2020 (Target under Directive 2012/27/EU)
Gross inland energy consumption (Mtoe)	31,5	30,5	27,8	25,4
Primary energy consumption (Mtoe)	30,7	29,6	26,9	24,7
Total final energy consumption (Mtoe)	22,1	20,5	18,9	18,4
Energy intensity of primary energy consumption (ktoe/€)	0,137	0,128	0,129	0,109
Energy intensity of final energy consumption (ktoe/€)	0,099	0,089	0,091	0,081

(Source: Third Hellenic National Energy Efficiency Action Plan, 2014)

The “National Energy Plan – Roadmap to 2050” refers mainly to the national targets for RES penetration in the energy demand and supply sectors. The policy instruments - included in the National Energy Plan and addressing the final energy consumption - were about continuation and progress of policy instruments presented and quantified in the 1st and 2nd NEEAPs for achieving the 9% target in 2016 compared to the reference period (Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, 2012).

Other objectives

Other objectives for the establishment of EE policy packages concern: i) Compliance with national/European/international legal provisions; ii) Economic development; iii) Multiple benefits.

1) Buildings Sector

Synthesis of policy packages

The policy package for the EE in this sector covers both “supply side” and “demand side”, but not equally. The majority of the policy instruments and programmes are targeting to the final energy consumers (demand side). The policy instruments that target to the supply side actors, are mainly for energy service companies through Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs).

The policy instruments for the final energy consumers include: financial mechanisms such as the Green Fund and subsidies for renovation, regulatory standards such as energy labelling, energy audits and green public procurements, voluntary approaches such as eco-design requirements for appliances, information campaigns for certain programmes.

Table 3 includes the list of policy instruments for the building sector.

⁷ calculated under Article 7 of the Directive concerning the adoption of EE obligation schemes,

Table 3: List of policy instruments for the energy efficiency in the building sector.

National policy	Policy instrument (type)	Directives/Regulations	National Laws/Ministerial Decisions
Buildings sector			
Promotion of energy efficient appliances and energy equipment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Energy labelling of household lamps and dish-washers, air-conditioners, electric ovens, electric refrigerators, freezers and their combinations (Regulatory standards) · labelling and standard product information of the consumption of energy and other resources by energy-related products (Voluntary approaches) 	1998/11/EC, 1999/9/EC, 2002/31/EC, 2002/40/EC, 2003/66/EC, 2010/30/EC – Commission Regulation No. 626/2011 (supplementing Directive)	Ministerial Decision 12400/1108/29 (Government Gazette (GG) 2301 B, 14.10.2011)
	<p>Ecodesign requirements for household washers, refrigerating appliances, televisions, washing machines; glandless circulators (standalone and integrated in products; electric motors; no-load condition power consumption and average active efficiency of external supplies, non-directional household lamps, fluorescent lamps without integrated ballast, high intensity discharge lamps, ballasts and luminaires able to operate such lamps; simple set-top boxes, standby and off mode electric power consumption of household and office equipment; energy efficiency requirements for ballasts for fluorescent lighting (Voluntary approaches)</p>	Directive 2000/55/EC Directive 2005/32/EC (implemented through Regulations No 641/2009, 640/2009, 642/2009, 643/2009, 278/2009, 244/2009-amended by 859/2009, 245/2009-amended by 347/2010, 107/2009, 1275/2008) Directive 2009/125/EC (implemented through Regulations No 1016/2010, 1015/2010)	Presidential Decree 7/2011 (GG 14 A/11.2.2011) Presidential Decree 32/2010 (GG 70 A, 14.05.2010) Ministerial Decision Δ6/B/14826/2008 (GG 1122 B, 17.6.2008)
	<p>Energy labelling (Voluntary approaches)</p>	Regulation No. 2422/2001 – Program Energy Star (Voluntary participation), Regulation No. 106/2008	Ministerial Decision Δ6/B/14826/2008 – GG 1122/B/17.6.2008)
Promotion of EE	Efficiency of hot water boilers (Regulatory standards)	92/42/EC	
	<p>Energy inspectors for energy performance of buildings (Regulatory policy instruments)</p>	2010/31/EC ⁸ 2002/91/EC	Act of legislation (GG A 237, 5.12.2012), Presidential Decree 100/2010 (GG 177 A, 6.10.2010 for energy in-

⁸ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2010:153:0013:0035:EL:PDF>

	Energy audits (Regulatory Policy Instruments (PI))		spectors), Presidential Degree 72/2010 (GG 132 A, 05.08.2010), Law 3885/2010 (Government Gazette 95 A, 23.6.2010), Regulation for EE of buildings (Δ6/B/5825-30.3.2010, GG 407 B, 9.4.2010), Law 3661/2008 (GG 89 A, 19.5.2008)
	End-use efficiency and energy services (ESCOs) (Other policy instruments), Green Public Procurements (Voluntary approaches), Metering (Regulatory PI), Voluntary agreements (Voluntary approaches)	2006/32/EC 2009/33/EC ⁹	Ministerial Decision Δ5-ΗΛ/Β/ Φ1.20/ οικ.6262/20.03.2013 (GG 832 B, 9.04.2013), Law 3855/2010 (GG 95 A, 23.6.2010), Ministerial Decision Δ6/B/14826/2008 – GG 1122 B, 17.6.2008), Law 3661/2008 (GG 89 A, 19.5.2008)
	Energy Performance of Buildings (references to building code, minimum requirements, interventions, green roofs, renovations etc) (Regulatory, financial and informative policy instruments)	2010/31/EC	Law 4122/2013 (GG 42 A, 19.02.2013 - NZEB), Law 4067/2012 (GG 79A, 2012), Law 3855/2010 (GG 95 A, 23.6.2010), Law 3842/2010 (GG 58 A, 23.04.2010), Law 3661/2008 (GG 89 A, 19.5.2008) Decision 3046/304/89 (GG 59Δ - Building code), Law 1577/1985 (GG 210 A, 18.12.1985)
	Financial incentives , EE requirements (Economic PI)	Directive 2010/31/EU	Law 3851/2010 (GG 85 A, 4.6.2010)
	Taxation of energy products and electricity (applies for gas oil (diesel) for heating and other use, biodiesel and kerosene for heating and other use) (Economic policy instrument)	Directive 2010/31/EU, 2004/74/EC, 2004/75/EC, 2003/17/EC, 2003/96/EC,	Law 4092/2012 (GG 220 A, 8.11.2012), Law 3845/2010 (GG 65 A, 6.05.2010), Law 3833/2010 (GG 40 A, 15.03.2010), Law 3828/2010 (GG 31 A, 25.02.2010), Law 3336/2005 (GG 96 A, 20.04.2005)
	Green Fund (Regulatory - financial PI)		Law 3889/2010 (GG 182 A, 14.10.2010)
	Financial incentives (subsidy) (replacement of oil with natural gas heating systems) (financial PI)		Ministerial Decision Φ.14/02/19398/2927 (GG B 3071/14.11.2014 ¹⁰)
	EE (energy audits, energy management system, metering, procurements by Public Bodies, ESCOs) (Regulatory policy instrument)	2012/27/EU	The draft law was -for 2nd time- under public consultation until 1 st of July 2015 ¹¹ and results are not announced yet (YPEKA, 2015; 2014 ¹²).

Source: MEIST, 2015; MEECC, 2015; MEECC, 2013; Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, 2014; DG Clima, DG Energy

⁹ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2009:120:0005:0012:EL:PDF>

¹⁰ https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B7Jb_n_W6q6bR1INNE92THd3c1E/view?usp=sharing&pli=1

¹¹ <http://www.opengov.gr/minenv/?p=6692>

¹² <http://www.opengov.gr/minenv/?p=6288>

Target groups

National level

According to the national official documents, the EE policies and measures target the following sectors (Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, 2012; Third Hellenic National Energy Efficiency Action Plan, 2014; Hellenic Republic, MEECC, 2014):

- Buildings (residential and tertiary sub-sectors);
- Industry;
- Transport;
- Energy supply: transformation, transmission and distribution.

The EE policies and measures are designed to take into account the potential of all final energy consumption sectors in energy saving and EE. The main sectors of energy consumption are considered to be the residential sector, industry and transport (Third Hellenic NEEAP, 2014). The sectors with the greatest potential are buildings, transport and industry (MEECC, 2012; Third Hellenic NEEAP, 2014).

According to the Third Hellenic NEEAP, the public sector should be the leader for implementing EE interventions in public buildings, since they have very high potential for energy saving.

The target groups are (Third Hellenic NEEAP, 2014; Hellenic Republic, MEECC, 2014):

Types of Buildings

- New and existing residential buildings;
- Tertiary sector buildings
 - Public: schools, museums, hospitals, ministerial departments, legal entities, new and existing central and general government buildings, facilities such as sports centers, etc;
 - Private: existing & new SMEs;
 - Social housing buildings.

End-use technologies

- Building design and envelope: thermal insulation, shading systems, green roofs, energy management systems and Building Energy Management Systems (BEMS), cool materials on roofs and facades, bioclimatic interventions such as passive solar systems.
- Heating-Cooling and Hot Water systems: solar thermal systems, RES, heat pumps, highly efficient boilers, high-efficiency CHP.
- Lighting: lighting control systems with motion sensors, LEDs, light bulbs of maximum energy efficiency (A, A+, A++).
- Appliances: high efficient devices (such as high energy class and inverter-type air-conditions).

Actors: Final energy consumers, natural and legal persons, supply side actors such as ESCOs, businesses and professionals working in the field of energy savings, energy inspectors, etc.

Regional/Local level

The target groups are: 1st grade local authorities¹³ (municipalities) and capitals of prefectures.

¹³ Mentioned also as First level of local authorities

Apart from those aforementioned in the national level, end-uses such as municipal lighting, public open areas of urban environment, open sports grounds, sewage treatment plants, pumping stations, etc. are also included.

Governance framework¹⁴ for the Hellenic building sector

None of the recent official documents about the Hellenic EE policy describe clearly and in detail the multi-level governance framework. From the available information and taking into account Annex I of this report, the Hellenic case presents a loose MLG framework. There are three main governance levels: Supranational/EU level; National/Hellenic and Regional-Local level. More analytically:

Supranational governance level

For most countries inter-governmental agencies and international organisations are involved in the EE policy process¹⁵ (IEA, 2009). This is not happening for the Hellenic EE policy, which is designed by the national pertinent authorities and adjusted depending on the commitments undertaken by the country in international or European Union level.

The only governmental level that can be considered as first in this vertical dimension of the Hellenic MGL framework is the European Union (EU) level. This is justified as follows. For all Member States, including Greece as well, the EU has a broad view of EE policy and initiates programmes across countries and regions, such as the JESSICA, the Covenant of Mayors, Horizon 2020 etc (see respective session in this report). This first governmental level is interacting with the second one, the Hellenic governmental level, through the European Union law¹⁶ which is divided into: i) Primary law which refers in particular to the Treaties that are the basis for all EU action; ii) Secondary law which is derived from the principles and objectives set out in the Treaties and includes regulations, directives¹⁷ and decisions.

As an EU Member State, Greece, has the primary responsibility for the correct and timely application of EU Treaties and legislation by its pertinent authorities, while the European Commission monitors the application of Union law.

National governance level

The central role in developing EE policies is undertaken by the Hellenic government (as a total) since it is the pertinent authority that: i) sets priorities; ii) develops and coordinates strategies within national borders; iii) enters into agreements outside of the national borders (IEA, 2009). iv) has the ability to leverage significant resources through the taxation process (IEA, 2009). The Hellenic government may also decide to withdraw from an intention or position so as to avoid direct interactions with communities (IEA, 2009). That justifies the fact that national governments often delegate certain aspects of EE policy development and implementation to lower levels of government with direct connections to communities (IEA, 2009).

The description of the pertinent national governmental authorities for national EE policy that concerns buildings follows (MEECC, 2014; 6th National Communication of Greece to UNFCCC, 2014; 5th National Communication to UNFCCC, 2010). Emphasis is given on quoting information about the responsibilities and the contribution that each authority has in relation with the EE policy for buildings.

¹⁴ = Implementation network in the AMS method

¹⁵ Such as World Bank, Global Environment Facility, European Bank for Reconstruction and Development etc.

¹⁶ http://ec.europa.eu/atwork/applying-eu-law/index_en.htm

¹⁷ EU Member States must achieve the results that EU directives set out. Their national authorities will select the form and method to meet the expected results. Different national laws are brought into line with each other due to the use of EU Directives, and become common in matters that affect the operation of the single market (e.g. product safety standards).

1. Ministry of Reconstruction of Production, Environment and Energy (former Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change (MEECC))

General information: MEECC¹⁸ is the responsible national authority for Energy and Climate Change Policy. MEECC has developed a strategic plan with 4 pillars¹⁹, which are:

Pillar 1: Moving towards a competitive economy of low carbon consumption. The strategic objectives for this pillar are: i) **Improve energy efficiency**; ii) Increase the share of the country's energy use from renewable sources and natural gas, whilst ensuring the reliability of energy supplies; iii) Secure consumers the provision of reliable energy products and services; iv) Promote green products, sustainable production and consumption patterns.

Pillar 2: Natural resource protection and environmental enhancement. The respective strategic objectives are: i) Protection and promotion of biodiversity and natural landscape; ii) Ensuring the effective management and protection of water resources; iii) Effective management and protection of forests; iv) Environmental Crises prevention and effective risk management.

Pillar 3: Improve quality of life with respect to the environment. The strategic objectives include: i) Urban Regeneration; ii) Improvement of air quality and soundscape; iii) Enhancement of accessibility and sustainable mobility for all; iv) Efficient waste management and promotion of recycling.

Pillar 4: Enhancement of environmental governance mechanisms and processes. Its strategic objectives are: i) Strengthening the planning system in order to ensure policy cohesion; ii) Simplification and coding of environmental legislation whilst strengthening its enforcement mechanisms; iii) Promotion of environmental research, innovative technologies and accessibility to environmental information; iv) Enabling environmental accountability and volunteerism.

Role for the national EE policy: MEECC coordinates the major dissemination programs and campaigns referring to the development and penetration of policy instruments, technologies and practices for EE. MEECC monitors and supervises the implementation of measures for achieving the national indicative energy savings target through the provision of energy services and other measures to improve EE, and prepares a report on their results (2nd NEEAP, 2010; 3rd NEEAP, 2014). It has also the administrative, managing and executive responsibility of implementing the EE requirements of the "Energy Efficiency Action Plans", relevant incentives and other measures to improve EE and those relating to the public sector. MEECC has under the Hellenic version of its website a session about EE²⁰ providing information for 3 national sectors: buildings, transportation and industry. Information is about recent legislation and reports for the building sector.

2. Ministry of Finance

Role for the national EE policy: The Ministry of Finance²¹ is responsible for supporting environmental investments (including RES and EE) - Energy and Environmental taxation (5th National Communication of Greece to UNFCCC, 2010).

3. Ministry of Interior and Administrative Reconstruction

Role for the national EE policy: This Ministry²² is responsible for natural and technological disasters (climate change ones included) (5th National Communication of Greece to UNFCCC, 2010). A share of the public buildings is under the responsibility of this Ministry. In 2007 the number of public buildings

¹⁸ <http://www.ypeka.gr>

¹⁹ <http://www.ypeka.gr/Default.aspx?tabid=230&locale=en-US&language=el-GR>

²⁰ <http://www.ypeka.gr/Default.aspx?tabid=281&locale=el-GR&language=en-US>

²¹ <http://www.mnec.gr/?q=el>

²² http://www.ydmed.gov.gr/?page_id=42

was estimated at approximately 200.000, representing a share of 5% of the tertiary sector (Greenpeace, 2007).

4. Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Marine and Tourism

Role for the national EE policy: The Ministry²³ is assigned – as part of the implementation network of the Hellenic Climate Change Policy - with the responsibilities of Industrial development- Environmental management and sustainable development of the Aegean islands – Protection of marine environment (5th National Communication of Greece to UNFCCC, 2010). The sectors of Infrastructure and Shipping are mostly related with energy and environmental issues. More detailed information is quoted in the respective Session of this report about Transport.

5. Ministry of Culture, Education and Religious Affairs

Role for the national EE policy: Two sectors are linked with EE, the Education and the Research-Innovation ones. The Ministry is assigned - as part of the implementation network of the Hellenic Climate Change Policy - with the responsibilities of the conservation of historical and cultural monuments and environment (5th National Communication of Greece to UNFCCC, 2010). Furthermore, Environmental Education is part of the programs of schools of Primary and Secondary Education according to Law 1892 /1990 and the relevant circulars. This type of education is relatively a new attempt to make pupils aware of the relationship between humans, natural and social environment, to raise their awareness about the relevant associated problems.

6. Ministry of Health and Social Insurance

Role for the national EE policy: The Ministry is assigned - as part of the implementation network of the Hellenic Climate Change Policy - with the responsibilities of managing environmental risk and hygiene. Furthermore, a number of public buildings (hospitals, administrative services) are under its authority (5th National Communication of Greece to UNFCCC, 2010).

Local/Regional governance level

Local and regional authorities have significant powers in key sectors (ie education, environment, economic development, town and country planning, transport, public services and social policies) (European Union, Committee of the Regions, 2009). Particularly for climate policy, due to their: i) closer proximity to citizens; ii) greater flexibility than national governments and iii) practical involvement in many issues related to climate policies (energy, transport, industry, housing, environment, etc.) (Galarraga I., 2011). Local and regional authorities hold an even more critical role in implementing EE policies, since apart from being the implementation agents for national EE policies, they also frequently (IEA, 2009): a) Demonstrate leadership by: i) managing their own substantial capital work programmes, property management, community services and daily operations; ii) pursuing EE procurement practices. B) Encourage their communities to engage in EE activities.

Due to their respective competences and administrative set-up, they often contribute in setting regulations and providing incentives for EE improvements (EC, 2013). Particularly, for housing interventions which are - in principle - implemented at the local level, local authorities and citizens' organisations ensure strong partnerships, efficient monitoring and audit mechanisms (EC, 2013).

On the other hand, local and regional authorities/governments cannot promote EE just by themselves, but depend on national governments for instance regarding policy direction, legal frameworks and funding (IEA, 2009). Their actions will be effective, if they are fully integrated and coordinated within the EU and national frameworks (EC, 2013). However, it must also be acknowledged that sev-

²³ <http://www.mindev.gov.gr/el/index.php>

eral problems might arise from the coexistence of state and regional efforts, depending on the nature of the policy overlap (Galarraga I., 2011).

General information for Hellenic municipalities and prefectures: The current administrative division of Greece was formed on the basis of the Kallikratis²⁴ plan and is in force since 1st January 2011 (Ministry of Interior, 2012). The final structure of this new administrative division includes (from top to bottom): i) Decentralized Administration Authorities; ii) Regions; iii) Regional Units; and iv) Municipalities (Municipality Units; Local communities). Finally, through the regrouping of the first and second level local authorities into larger geographical units along with mergers of municipalities, communities and prefectural administrations respectively, the division of the country has: seven (7) Decentralised Administration Authorities, thirteen (13) Regions (these form the second level of Local Authorities) and 325 municipalities (first level of Local Authorities) (Ministry of Interior, 2012).

Role in national EE policy: The Local Authorities (LA) are the target groups in a series of programmes, initiatives and policy instruments (Covenant of Mayors, Pact of islands, EXOIKONOMO, Green Roofs etc – see next session 1.2). Municipal responsibilities include (8) eight specific areas mainly comprising the fields of: Development; Environment; Quality of Life and proper functioning of cities and settlements; Employment; Social Protection and Solidarity; Education, Culture and Sports; Civil Protection; Rural development- Livestock – Fisheries. EE is not clearly stated as one of them, but is indirectly included in: i) Environment, ii) Quality of Life and proper functioning of cities and settlements, iii) Education.

Regions design, plan and implement regional policies within the context of their competencies, according to the principles of transparency, effectiveness and efficiency. They exercise their competences within the framework of the relevant laws and administrative regulations, in the fields of: A. Planning, Development; B. Agriculture, Livestock, Fishery; C. Natural Resources, Energy-Industry (water management, mineral wealth, energy, industry and manufacturing); D. Employment, Trade, Tourism; E. Transports, Communications; F. Works, Spatial planning, Environment; G. Health; H. Education, Culture, Sports; I. Civil protection, Logistics. For Regions, EE has a more visible role compared to that in the case of municipalities.

Other actors within the national governance level

The following entities are mentioned as part of the implementation network (YPEKA, 2014; 6th National Communication of Greece to UNFCCC, 2014; 5th National Communication of Greece to UNFCCC, 2010). Emphasis is given again in quoting information about the responsibilities and the contribution that each entity has in relation with the EE policy for buildings.

Center for Renewable Energy Sources and Saving

Role in national EE policy: The support provided by CRES, particularly through studies, action plans and national reports, involves the fulfilment of national obligations under the NEEAP and generally, under national and European legislation, relating to the EE of buildings, energy saving, RES and co-generation issues. CRES participates also in research programmes (FP7, Intelligent Energy Europe, Horizon 2020). CRES has a session on its web-site²⁵ providing information about a spectrum of issues related to EE (Buildings, transport, metering, GHG emissions, energy inspections/audits, certifications of materials and systems).

CRES has developed and completed a catalogue with institutes that are activated in RES and EE services and products. The purpose of this effort was to support the Hellenic market and to inform con-

²⁴ <http://www.kallikratis.eu/>

²⁵ <http://www.cres.gr/services/istos.chtm?prnbr=24762&locale=el>

sumers and investors about these types of market activities. The “Catalogue of Hellenic Energy Professionals” includes information about the type of activity of the involved companies and professionals, the category of RES, the relevant technology that is in use and contact data. However, there is no indication if this catalogue is updated (the date on the site is year 2007).

Hellenic Statistical Authority

Role in national EE policy: Provides data needed for the national EE policy (population, energy consumption, types of buildings, vehicles etc).

Technical Chamber of Greece

Role in national EE policy: The TCG is active in EE issues. It has an updated web-site²⁶ about EE issues concerning buildings, which contains relevant Laws, regulations and decisions; information about energy inspectors, the building code (KENAK), guidelines about energy reviews. The user will find also software for the calculation of the Energy Performance of Buildings (EPB) and an example of a study about EPB. TCG organizes seminars and workshops for its members about KENAK. TCG also organizes the exams²⁷ for providing the certificates for the qualified energy inspectors in buildings.

Public Properties Company

Role in national EE policy: Among the objectives for the Programming Period 2014-2020²⁸ the Public Properties Company will pursue to: i) promote sustainable development by protecting and promoting natural environment, improving energy efficiency of the installation and promoting moderate forms of exploitation; ii) support the transfer to a low carbon economy and iii) to adapt to climate change.

Buildings' Infrastructures S.A.

Role in national EE policy: BI provides the whole construction of public buildings (production chain, from land acquisition, licensing and design, to public procurement, project supervision and equipment). Construction is done either directly by BI, or through Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs) managed by BI, or even by bilateral contracts with local authorities. BI needs to implement the requirements of the relevant legislation for the energy performance of Buildings. BI can also participate at the JESSICA initiative (see relevant session for programmes and initiatives).

Academic Institutions and Research Institutes

There are research teams in academic Institutions (national technical and non-technical universities etc.) and research institutes (e.g. National Observatory of Athens etc.) that work on EE issues (technologies, practices and policy) (5th National Communication of Greece to UNFCCC, 2010). Some indicative ones are the following:

National and Kapodistrian University of Athens: 1. Department of Physics, Research Team of the Built Environment²⁹; 2. Energy Policy and Development Centre³⁰.

National Technical University of Athens – School of Architecture³¹: Installations and Architectural Environment Lab (translation from Greek: Energy-Bioclimatic Design and Architectural Environment).

²⁶ http://portal.tee.gr/portal/page/portal/SCIENTIFIC_WORK/GR_ENERGEIAS/kenak

²⁷ http://portal.tee.gr/portal/page/portal/mhtrwo/mitrwo/kenak_exams

²⁸ <http://www.etasa.gr/page.aspx?itemID=SPG326>

²⁹ <http://env.phys.uoa.gr/ereyna/ereynhtikes-omades.html>

³⁰ <http://www.kepa.uoa.gr>

³¹ <http://www.arch.ntua.gr/unit/868>

Technical University of Crete – School of Environmental Engineering³²: Energy efficiency in the built environment; Green buildings. Zero carbon emission buildings.

Contribution to the national governance level by non-Governmental entities

Greek Institute of Passive Building - EIPAK

Role in national EE policy: The Greek Institute of PAssive Building aims to support the involved professionals in the building construction sector (architectures, engineers, civil engineers, mechanical engineers, constructors, companies of construction and trading of passive systems) and the wider public by informing them with seminars, workshops, public discussions about how to design and implement passive buildings.

Banks Association

Role in national EE policy: Four national banks participated in the EXOIKONOMO/"Saving Energy at Home" programmes programmes ie Alpha Bank S.A., National Bank of Greece S.A., Piraeus Bank S.A. and E.F.G. Bank Eurobank – Ergasias S.A. (3rd NEEAP, 2014). In the JESSICA initiative five banks participated (National Bank of Greece, Investment Bank of Greece, Eurobank, Piraeus Bank, Pancretan Co-operative Bank) (see subsequent session about Programmes and Initiatives). Hellenic Banks offer services to their customers for "green investments". More specifically, the following are indicative:

*Piraeus Bank*³³: The Piraeus Bank Group offers to its customers green services for investments in all green business sectors including RES and energy saving. Procedures and preconditions are discussed between the Green experts of the Bank and the interested customers³⁴.

*E.F.G. Bank Eurobank – Ergasias S.A.*³⁵: It provides a range of banking products, designed to protect the environment and to support green businesses. Among them is the "Green Home Loan" that concerns Greek households with a range of innovative products.

*National Bank of Greece*³⁶: Its green banking products include: i) the ESTIA GREEN which is a pioneering housing loan, with solutions for the purchase or construction of an environment friendly, energy efficient home, and for energy improvements at home; ii) the "NBG Green Loan" which is designed to provide to the customer the necessary amount of money for energy improvements at home or for purchasing a new hybrid-technology car; iii) the "Energy Efficiency at Household Buildings" Program³⁷ for upgrading the energy performance of the customer's home with: 100% subsidy of the interest rate; a grant for up to 70% of the total budget; compensation of the cost of the energy inspections; compensation of the project consultant's fee.

Alpha Bank: The green banking products include: The new "Energy Saving Home" housing loan³⁸ from Alpha Green Solutions was created for improving the energy consumption of the customer's residence, while enjoying preferential granting terms. Another banking programme concerns the transport sector and is described in the relevant session.

³²http://www.enveng.tuc.gr/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=285&Itemid=704&lang=en

³³<http://www.piraeusbank.gr/el/epiheiriseis-epaggelmaties/ypiresies-epixeiriseon/exeidikeumenes-ypiresies/prasines-ypiresies-epixeiriseon> and <http://www.piraeusbank.gr/en/epiheiriseis-epaggelmaties/ypiresies-epixeiriseon/exeidikeumenes-ypiresies/prasines-ypiresies-epixeiriseon>

³⁴Same with footnote 53

³⁵<http://www.eurobank.gr/online/home/genericnew.aspx?code=EKEFrontidaGiaToPeribalonPrasina&mid=858&lang=en>

³⁶<https://www.nbg.gr/en/retail/eco-banking-solutions/products-services/estia-green>

³⁷<https://www.nbg.gr/en/retail/eco-banking-solutions/products-services/energy-efficiency-at-household-buildings>

³⁸<http://www.alpha.gr/page/default.asp?id=7823&la=2>

Other entities

Other entities that are involved, but with no available information about their activities and particularly related to the national EE policy are: Association of Building Manufacturers³⁹, Associations of property owners (e.g. Hellenic Property Federation⁴⁰); Manufacturers Associations (Federation of Manufacturers and Construction Industry Greece - OMKOOE); Environmental NGOs and Institutes (eg Greenpeace, WWF, INZEB, etc.). The Ministry has a registry of ESCOs⁴¹ (Ministerial Decision Δ6/B/13280/07.06.2011 (Government gazette 1228 B). The uploaded catalogue of the registered ESCOs includes 30 such companies in the country.

Other actors within the local/regional governance level

Regional energy agencies

Anatoliki S.A. – Development Agency of Eastern Thessaloniki's Local Authorities – Center for the Development of Human Resources and the support of Local economy⁴²

Role in national EE policy: The Agency has contributed in: i) promoting recycling in the Municipalities of Eastern Thessaloniki and the Municipality of Thessaloniki; ii) addressing employment issues; iii) promoting RES and EE; iv) management of mobility and water resources; v) functionality of social structures; vi) operational planning of LAs and vii) supporting the operation of the European Network of Elected Greeks in Local Authorities Abroad. (The web-site of the agency seems updated).

Regional Energy Agency of Central Macedonia (REACM)⁴³

Role in national EE policy: REACM has implemented a large number of projects regarding energy production and energy saving (assessment and promotion of best practices; planning and implementation).

Ios-Aegean Energy Agency

Role in national EE policy: The Ios Aegean Energy Agency⁴⁴, in cooperation with the Regulatory Energy Authority (RAE), the CRES, the former Ministry of Development (now MEECC) and other national and/or local institutions, undertook in 2008 the initiative to elaborate a consistent strategy for the development of RES and energy savings in Aegean islands. This initiative coincided with the publication of the Common Ministerial Degree for the land planning for RES in the Greek territory (2464/3.12.2008). The executive summary report was uploaded at the web-site in year 2009.

Regional Energy Agency of Crete

Role in national EE policy: The Regional Energy Agency of Crete⁴⁵ has been involved in environment-energy educational projects in schools since 1997. The results of the above initiatives have been very successful and have been widely disseminated not only to the rest of the schools in the island of Crete but also to many other schools in Greece (Zografakis N. et al., 2008).

³⁹ <http://www.ekat.gr/> (only Greek version)

⁴⁰ <http://www.pomida.gr/>

⁴¹ <http://www.escoregistry.gr/>

⁴² according to article 274 paragraph 1b of the presidential decree 323/89

⁴³ <http://www.anatoliki.gr/en/regional-energy-agency-of-central-macedonia>

⁴⁴ <http://www.aegean-energy.gr/en/strategy.htm>

⁴⁵ <http://www.apdkritis.gov.gr/el/services/tabid/161/Default.aspx> -

http://www.crete.gov.gr/index.php?option=com_content&view=category&id=334&Itemid=517&lang=el

Role of EE policy in Greece through the governance framework for buildings

The EE policy of Greece is considered as a component of its Climate Change Policy. It was one of the main directions that the government followed along with the exploitation of RES and the penetration of natural gas after the ratification of the Kyoto Protocol by Greece in 2002. These directions were presented in the 2nd National Climate Change Programme, that was elaborated and adopted in 2002 (approved by Act of the Ministerial Council 5/27.02.2003, Government Gazette 58 A/05.03.2003). The main actions, foreseen for EE, included: i) Promotion of energy saving measures in industry and in the residential – tertiary sectors; and ii) Promotion of energy efficient appliances and energy equipment in the residential – tertiary sectors.

By the year 2002, when Greece officially included EE in its climate change policy mixture, other EU Member States had already gained experience with EE policies. The following cases are indicatively: a) the United Kingdom with the “Energy Efficiency Standards of Performance” that were introduced in 1994 and were followed by the “Energy Efficiency Agreements in 2004; b) the Netherlands with the First Long Term Agreements in 1992, the Benchmarking Covenant in 1999 and the Long Term Agreements in 2003; c) Finland with voluntary agreements for EE in 1992. Additionally, Greece did not implement the same type of policy instruments. The majority of the implemented policy instruments is regulatory, financial or belongs to the dissemination-awareness type. For the time period from 2003 up to date, EE policy has gained attention and is promoted annually even more, but yet efforts need to intensify. It is indicative that it is only one of the four strategic objectives of Pillar 1 of the MEECC as aforementioned, while for the Ministry of Infrastructure, Transport it is still not part of its mission.

There is no other national legislation and regulation apart from those that are based on EU-requirements (see tables of this report and session 1.2). The country started more intensive efforts for energy efficiency activities after the transposition of Directive 2006/32/EC. The Energy Efficiency National Action Plan was a requirement and it constituted a valuable supporting policy and tool for the limiting the total amount of GHG emissions (5th National Communication of Greece to UNFCCC, 2010). It describes the needed policies and measures for achieving the targets set by the directive, namely reduction of 9% of end-use energy consumption for the time period 2008-2016 compared to the average of the time period 2001-2005 (5th National Communication of Greece to UNFCCC, 2010). Horizontal, intersectoral and measures focusing to the residential, tertiary (public and private), non-ETS industry and transport sector are included (5th National Communication of Greece to UNFCCC, 2010). These policies and measures continued with the next two National Energy Efficiency Action Plans (2nd NEEAP, 2010, 3rd NEEAP, 2014).

There is no dedicated Committee or body for EE issues with the assignment of coordinating efforts for promoting EE policies, technologies and practices. There is a diversity of involved entities with most important ones for the building sector the MEECC and CRES (see previous sessions). The MLG includes almost all involved stakeholders, but there absence of end-users (household associations, hotel or school managers etc).

2) Transport Sector

Synthesis of policy packages

The policy package for EE in the transport sector covers both “supply side” and “demand side”.

The policy package has the following policy components: System efficiency: new transport infrastructure; Travel efficiency: Reshaping of the public transport system, eco-driving, cycling, consumer information on fuel economy of new passenger cars; Vehicle efficiency: incentives for the replacement of old technology cars, tax exemptions for electric and hybrid vehicles;

Table 4 includes the policy instruments for the energy efficiency in the transport sector.

Table 4: List of policy instruments for the energy efficiency in the transport sector.

Transport sector			
Emission reduction actions in transport	Emission standards (Euro 5 and Euro 6) (Regulatory policy instrument)	EU Regulation No. 715/2007	Draft Law for Directive 2012/27/EC
	Establishment of Permanent Committee on Green Transportation (Regulatory policy instrument)		Law 3710/2008 (Government Gazette (GG) 216 A, 23.10.2008)
	Energy labeling for tyres in transport (Regulatory – informative policy instrument)	EC Regulation 1235/2011 EC Regulation No. 1222/2009	
	Consumer information on fuel economy and CO ₂ emissions of new passenger cars (Dissemination and awareness policy instrument)	1999/94/EC, 2003/73 (Regulations 1882/2003, 1137/2008)	Ministerial Decision 11762/2006 (GG 327 B, 17.3.2006)
Reduction of GHG emissions, promotion of RES, EE	Taxation of energy products and electricity (applies for gas oil (diesel), biodiesel and kerosene for transport for transport (Economic instrument)	2003/96/EC, 2004/74/EC, 2004/75/EC, 2003/17/EC	Law 4092/2012 (GG 220 A, 8.11.2012), Law 3986/2011 (GG 152 A, 1.07.2011), Law 3845/2010 (GG 65 A, 6.05.2010), Law 3833/2010 (GG 40 A, 15.3.2010), Law 3828/2010 (GG 31 A, 25.02.2010), Law 3336/2005 (GG 96 A, 20.04.2005)
	Registration tax rates (Euro 5) (Hybrid and electric cars are exempted) (Economic instrument)	EC Regulations 566/2011, 692/2008 (Euro 5 and Euro 4), 715/2007 Directive 1998/69/EC, Directive 94/12/EC	Law 3156/2003 (GG 157 A, 25.06.2003)
	Circulation fee (road tax) (Economic instrument)	EC Regulations 715/2007 (Euro 5 and Euro 6), Directive 1999/96/EC (Euro 3 and Euro 4), Directive 91/542/EC (Euro 2 and Euro 1)	Law 4093/2012 (GG 222 A, 12.11.2012), Law 3986/2011 (GG 152 A, 1.07.2011)

GHG reduction actions in transport and promotion of energy efficiency	Incentives to replace old technology cars (Economic policy instrument)		Law 4316/2014 (GG 270 A, 24.12.2014), Law 4223/2013 (GG 287 A, 31.12.2013), Law 4110/2013 (GG 17 A, 23.01.2013), Law 3943/2011 (GG 66 A 31.03.2011), Decision No. 5006718EΞ2001 (GG 246 B, 11.02.2011), Law 3899/2010 (GG 212/A 17.12.2010 and 246/B 11.02.2011), Law 3333/2005 (GG 91 A, 12.4.2005) Law 3245/2004 (GG A 110, 16.6.2004), Law 3109/2003 (GG 38 A, 19.02.2003)
	Green Public Procurements for transport (Voluntary approaches)	Directive 2009/33/EC	Law 3982/2011 (GG 143 A, 17.06.2011), Law 3855/2010 (GG 95 A, 23.06.2010)
	Cycling and pedestrianism in the city (Planning and dissemination-awareness policy instrument)		Expected legislation for the city of Athens within year 2015 ⁴⁶ (MEECC, 2014), Ministerial Decision 33523/7564/10-6-200247
	Improvement of infrastructure for electric vehicles (Planning policy instrument)		Joint Ministerial Decision 71287/6443 (GG 50 B, 15.01.2015), Law 4233/2014 (GG 22 A, 29.01.2014), Law 4070/2012 (GG 82 A, 10.04.2012)
Promotion of energy efficiency	Eco-driving (Dissemination – Awareness – educational policy instrument)		Ministerial Decision No. 76568/1197 (GG B 81, 19.01.2015 ⁴⁷ , amending the previous one), Ministerial Decision A3/50984/7947 (GG B 3056/2/11/2013, Ministerial Decision 552/88 (GG B4/7-1-2013), Law 3855/2010 (GG 95 A, 23.6.2010)

Source: MEIST, 2015; MEECC, 2015; MEECC, 2013; Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, 2014; DG Clima, DG Energy.

⁴⁶ <http://www.ypeka.gr/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=cwreF0yvYc%3D&tabid=37&language=el-GR>

⁴⁷ <http://www.hellenicparliament.gr/Praktika/Synedriaseis-Olomeleias?sessionRecord=e7696f4c-a10c-4222-a036-aa69e43b97ff>

⁴⁸ <http://www.odigostoupoliti.eu/adia-odigisis-ekpedefsi-ke-exetasi-ipopsifion-odigon-motopodilaton-motosikleton-ke-aftokiniton/>

Target groups

National level

The target groups are (Third Hellenic NEEAP, 2014; Hellenic Republic, MEECC, 2014):

Transport (road, rail)

- Passenger
- Freight

End-use technologies

- Cars (private and public): vehicles meeting EURO 5 standards, CNG and LPG-powered private passenger vehicles, electric vehicles (including motorcycles, bicycles, heavy vehicles), LPG vehicles and bi-fuel natural gas vehicles (municipal fleet).
- Buses: natural gas public transport buses.
- Light trucks (private and public): vehicles meeting EURO 5 standards.
- Infrastructure: vehicle recharging points (RES-powered and/or conventional).

Actors: Private vehicle drivers, professional drivers (taxi and truck drivers), vehicle fleet operators, vehicle sellers, car dealers, public services and organizations (fleet), driving instructors, specialized experts in transport issues, central administration, local government, transport project management bodies, financial leasing services, owners of car parks.

Regional/Local level

The target groups are local governments, the large municipalities of Athens and Thessaloniki, other urban centers and Hellenic municipalities.

The end-use technologies concern the urban mobility (private vehicles and municipal fleet).

Governance framework⁴⁹ for the Hellenic transport sector

Based on the available information from the official national documents and taking into account the previous two sessions, the Hellenic case presents an even looser MGL framework for the transport sector compared to that of the buildings sector. There are three main governance levels: Supranational/EU level; National/Hellenic and Regional-Local level. More analytically:

Supranational governance level

Same as in the case of the building sector, no difference.

National governance level

Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Marine⁵⁰ and Tourism (Former Ministry of Infrastructure, Transport and Networks)

General information: The Ministry of Infrastructure, Transport and Networks⁵¹ aims to: i) plan and implement the respective Hellenic policy (for the areas under its responsibility) and create the appropriate institutional framework at European and international level for the development of top

⁴⁹ = Implementation network in the AMS method

⁵⁰ Quoted as Shipping also

⁵¹The web-site of the Ministry quotes the former title also

<http://www.yme.gr/index.php?getwhat=1&oid=531&id=&tid=531>

quality transport, mass-transit, telecom and postal services under conditions of healthy competition; ii) ensure the safety of transport, mass-transit and telecommunications; iii) promote the Information Society; iv) contribute to the economic development of the country and to the improvement of its citizens's quality of life in the aforementioned areas.

The Ministry has dedicated to road passenger transport issues the Passenger Transport Directorate⁵² which includes the:

1. *Urban Transportation Department.* It is responsible for: a) all issues relating to urban transportation in the Greater Athens region (buses, trolleys, tramway, urban train, metro) and Thessaloniki; b) urban transportation in other parts of Greece by buses (run by KTEL S.A. or KTEL, RODA in Rhodes and DEAS in Kos, under law 2963/2001 (A'268)); c) all issues relating to Public Passenger Cars (PPCs) (taxis, booked vehicles) which operate in conformity with law 3109/2003, private buses, private cars and iv) the issuing of vehicle licenses, plates, etc.
2. *Intercity Transportation Department.* It is responsible for: a) Issues related to the access to the profession of road passenger carrier (national or international transport), according to Presidential Decree 346/2001 which transposed directives 96/26 and 98/76 into the national legislation; b) Issues concerning the operation of regular intercity transportation services within the country by Public Buses (PBs) run by KTEL S.A., KTEL or individual operators (in isolated islands where KTEL is not present), according to law 2963/2001; c) International road passenger transport (regular – occasional) by means of tourist buses.

Role in national EE policy: The Ministry is part of the implementation network for the Climate Change policy of the country, but also of its Energy Policy as well. It provides information and data for the vehicle fleet and its technical characteristics (5th National Communication of Greece to UNFCCC, 2010). As aforementioned, two sectors (Infrastructure and Shipping) are mostly related with energy and environmental issues.

Local/Regional governance level

Same as in the case of the building sector.

Other actors within the national governance level

Athens Urban Transport Organisation (OASA)

Role in national EE policy: For improving the polluted atmosphere of the greater's Athens area, OASA⁵³ replaced buses and trolley buses with new technology vehicles. ETHEL S.A. (the company responsible for thermal buses) and ILPAP S.A. (the company responsible for trolley buses) currently possess the younger fleet of vehicles at European level. ILPAP has 360⁵⁴ trolley buses of antipollution (clean) technology and ETHEL has 2153 buses according to Euro 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 technologies (OASA, 2012). Simultaneously, OASA and the other transport companies participate actively in European technological development research programs for the use of biodiesel in buses.

STASY S.A. or Urban Rail Transport S.A.

Role in national EE policy: The company aims to deliver a safe, reliable, environment friendly and comfortable means of transport. STASY S.A.⁵⁵ promotes recycling and energy saving practices. The company employs contemporary practices to maximize energy savings while exploring the possibility of RES usage. All depots use natural gas rather than petrol in order to meet their heating needs.

⁵² <http://www.yme.gr/index.php?tid=544>

⁵³ <http://www.oasa.gr/content.php?id=peribpol>

⁵⁴ <http://www.oasa.gr/content.php?id=peribpol>

⁵⁵ <http://www.stasy.gr/index.php?id=460&L=1>

Organization of Urban Transportation of Thessaloniki (OASTH)⁵⁶

Role in national EE policy: OASTH has established a telematic system to: i) locate buses and coordinate their routing; ii) to provide visual and audio announcements of stops within the buses and at 200⁵⁷ telematic "smart stops" (expected time of arrival is announced).

Hellenic Civil Aviation Authority⁵⁸

Role in national EE policy: It provides information on Landing and Take-off cycles for both domestic and international aviation (5th National Communication of Greece to UNFCCC, 2010).

Hellenic Institute of Transport⁵⁹

Role in national EE policy: The Department C: Transport Economics - Environment - Non-land Transport of HIT focuses on the economic, energy and environmental issues of the transport sector as well as the planning, study, management and operation of the non land transport system. Indicative EE research areas of Department C are: energy issues (energy consumption, clean energy for transport, operational issues and utilization of energy sources especially the environmentally sustainable ones); Analysis and evaluation of transport economics; General issues of transport policy. HIT has developed a database for the Hellenic transport sector (information at: <http://www.hitportal.gr/> - <http://www.certh.gr/DF57175C.el.aspx>)

Contribution to the national governance level by non-Governmental entities

Association of Motor Vehicles Importers Representatives (AMVIR)⁶⁰

Role in national EE policy: Data from the AMVIR are supplementary to the official data and are only used in cases where official data are temporarily not available. These data are used by NTUA experts for the preparation of GHG emissions (5th National Communication of Greece to UNFCCC, 2010).

Banks

(see also the respective session for the building sector)

Alpha Bank: The Green transport⁶¹ is a "green" consumer loan, from Alpha Green Solutions – Green Transport, for purchasing a new environment-friendly (hybrid technology) car . The loan is offered without any pledge or withholding of the ownership of the car and the customer's purchase is financed up to 100% of the value for the vehicle. Amount of loan: From 1.500 Euro to 40.000 Euro. Interest rate: Fluctuating interest rate, today 8,75% (plus the contribution of Law 128/75, 0,60%). Duration: From 6 to 84 months. Application fees: 120 Euro.

Other actors within the local/regional governance level

e- Trikala

Role in national EE policy: During the last years, e-Trikala⁶² is cooperating as a consulting company with the Central Union of Greek Municipalities.

⁵⁶ <http://oasth.gr/#en/general-characteristics/>

⁵⁷ <http://oasth.gr/#en/general-characteristics/>

⁵⁸ <http://www.ypa.gr/en/profile/mission/>

⁵⁹ <http://www.imet.gr/Default.aspx?tabid=41&language=en-US#&slider1=9>

⁶⁰ <http://www.seaa.gr/en/content/52>

⁶¹ <http://www.alpha.gr/page/default.asp?la=2&id=8006>

⁶² <http://www.e-trikalas.gr/en/aboutus>

Other entities

No relevant information for EE issues is available for ATTIKO METRO S.A., National Federation Motorists of Long-distance Communications – POYAS), KTEL, Public Transport Services to Athens Airport, Olympic Airways.

Role of EE policy in Greece through the governance framework for transport

Compared to the multi-level governance framework of the building sector the transport sector has a limited one, with less involvement of municipalities and regions. There are less energy agencies or research institutes that work on such issues.

1.2 NATIONAL PROGRAMMES AND INITIATIVES

Basic terms

Programs or strategies and Action Plans set the framework under which certain actions will be implemented focusing in the achievement of targets that are either general or specified. A strategy refers to a broad plan of actions that is implemented through policies and measures (IPCC, 2007). An action plan is similar to the strategy, with the addition of explicit (who, what, when) prioritized actions or targets (specific, measurable, realistic, time-bound) (Hills D., Bennett A., 2010). Programs or strategies, Action Plans can include a set of policy instruments oriented towards a certain component of the national climate change policy.

National programmes for energy efficiency

Third Hellenic National Energy Efficiency Action Plan (NEEAP)

General information: The Third Hellenic NEEAP for the implementation of national EE improvement objectives for 2020 was released in December 2014, following the 1st and 2nd NEEAP submitted in 2008 and 2011 respectively. The third NEEAP was developed by: i) the Directorate for Energy Policy and Energy Efficiency, ii) the Secretariat-General for Energy and Mineral Raw Materials, iii) the Ministry of the Environment, Energy and Climate Change (mentioned also as YPEKA) and iv) the Directorate for Energy Policy and Planning of the Centre for Renewable Energy Sources and Saving (CRES).

The target for 2020 is to achieve final energy consumption levels of 18,4 Mtoe and primary energy consumption of 24,7 Mtoe. This target resulted from the estimated development of the Greek economy, the implementation of EE measures and programmes, the RES penetration and the achieved energy savings in final consumption and primary energy production.

The 3rd NEEAP takes into consideration also projects under the Third Community Support Framework 2000-2006⁶³. Through this Framework infrastructure projects were completed and delivered, contributing to the intermediate energy savings target for 2010. These included (NEEAP, 2014): Extension of the Athens Metro & the suburban railway in the wider Athens region; New national and regional trunk routes; Creation of low traffic circulation streets, pavements and cycling paths; Street lighting using RES.

By 2016, the following actions are expected to be completed (NEEAP, 2014): i) Creation of new infrastructure (road improvements, new bus lanes, installation of smart traffic lights for public transport, modernization and extension of the rail network, etc.); ii) Installation of RES in urban and municipal transport remote service points (stops, ticket vendors, stationmasters etc.) for EE purposes.

⁶³ http://www.hellaskps.gr/Index2_en.htm

The policy instruments and programmes of the 3rd NEEAP regarding the building sector are focused on: i) building renovation (ie EPCs, “Energy Efficiency at Household Buildings”, installation of solar thermal systems in households and tertiary sector buildings, etc.); ii) energy labeling of appliances; iii) energy upgrade of public buildings (“SAVE” programme, EE interventions such as green roofs, high efficient lighting, etc.)

The policy instruments and programmes for the transport sector include: i) New transport infrastructure, urban mobility plans, reshaping of the public transport system; ii) Eco-driving, cycling, consumer information on fuel economy of new passenger cars, eco-labelling; iii) Incentives for the replacement of old technology cars, tax exemptions for electric and hybrid vehicles, etc.

SAVE I Program (“Exoikonomo”)

General information: The “SAVE I” program started on 2009. Its continuation program “SAVE II” (ΕΞΟΙΚΟΝΟΜΩ II) was published in March 2012. The total budget for the “SAVE I” program reached 100 million EUR and was covered by the National Strategic Reference Framework (NSRF) 2007-2013 and the Operational Program “Competitiveness and Entrepreneurship”⁶⁴. The maximum budget for each local authority was determined by the population of each municipality.

Expected results: 104 municipalities have joined the “SAVE I” program for the period 2014-2020 with expected primary energy savings of 5,96 ktoe (2,35 ktoe from improvements in existing municipal buildings, 2,56 ktoe in public lighting and 1,05 ktoe in other technical municipal infrastructure) (Hellenic Republic, MEECC, Secretariat General for Energy and Climate Change, 2013).

Type of policy instrument: financial/ Actions for developing and promoting RES and EE installations.

Objectives: “SAVE I” (Exoikonomo I) or “ENERGY EFFICIENCY I” Program aimed to implement actions and best practices⁶⁵ for reductions in energy consumption of the urban environment⁶⁶.

Target groups: Municipalities with a population of over 10.000 residents⁶⁷ and capitals of prefectures (without certain criteria).

Rules and influencing mechanisms: No available information since the programme was completed.

Implementation network: *Supervisory authority:* MEECC. The organization responsible for receiving Municipalities’ proposals was CRES. The ministry proceeded to the establishment of an external evaluators’ registry. Candidate evaluators for the registry should justify related experience to each intervention axis of the initiative and experience related to NSRF and CSFs. Additionally, the set of criteria used were mostly related to the completeness of the application, necessity and eligibility of interventions and the energy savings to be achieved (in ktoe and KWh terms) (Remaco SA, 2010).

SAVE II Program⁶⁸ (“Exoikonomo II”)

General information: The “SAVE II” (ΕΞΟΙΚΟΝΟΜΩ II) or “ENERGY EFFICIENCY II” Program⁶⁹ was the continuation of “SAVE I” program. Its application period was 1.4.2012-30.6.2012, but was completed on 31.7.2013⁷⁰. It provided funding to projects undertaken by municipalities which were not subsidi-

⁶⁴ <https://setis.ec.europa.eu/energy-research/country/greece>

⁶⁵ such as technical interventions, awareness raising actions for citizens, local authorities, businesses and other actors (NEEAP, 2014)

⁶⁶ especially for the municipal building stock of local authorities, the renovation of public areas, in the municipal and private transport sector and the energy intensive municipal facilities

⁶⁷ based on the census of the National Statistical Service of Greece as of 2001

⁶⁸ <http://exoikonomisi.ypeka.gr/Default.aspx?tabid=652&language=el-GR>

⁶⁹ <http://www.ypeka.gr/Default.aspx?tabid=842&language=el-GR>

⁷⁰ <http://www.ypeka.gr/Default.aspx?tabid=842&language=el-GR>

dized by the “SAVE I” Program. It included simplified evaluation procedures so as to stimulate increased participation of municipalities in the Program. Eligible activities concerned:

1. Buildings and infrastructure, such as energy upgrade of the building envelope, electro-mechanical facilities, lighting system, BEMS installation, and;
2. Support and other activities, such as technical & energy performance studies, energy audits and awareness-raising actions.

The overall budget for “SAVE II” program was 75 million EUR and was covered by the NSRF, 2007-2013 and the Operational Program “Environment and Sustainable Development” (EPPERAA)⁷¹. The maximum budget for each local authority was determined by the population of each municipality.

Expected results: The implementation is 2011-2015; the number of municipalities that were expected to join the Program was 139 and the expected energy savings for 2014-2020 were 8,3 ktoe (Hellenic Republic, MEECC, Secretariat General for Energy and Climate Change, 2013).

Type of policy instrument: Financial policy instrument (subsidy)/policy instrument for Dissemination and awareness, capacity building for the technical staff of the municipalities due to actions for developing and promoting RES and EE installations.

Objectives: It aims to implement actions and best practices for the energy consumption reduction in the urban environment.

Target groups: Local/regional/national authorities and facilitators, building professionals, building occupants (BUILD UP, 2015).

Rules and influencing mechanisms: Successful proposals will be financed by 70% from the programme and the rest 30% from the municipalities themselves. The open call⁷² for the programmes has all the information about requirements of participation, eligible costs, types of projects, deadlines etc. There are also rules in case that the project does not deliver the expected energy savings.

Implementation network: Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, Special managing Authority of the Operational Programme (OP) “Environment and Sustainable Development”⁷³.

“Energy Efficiency at Household Buildings”⁷⁴ (EXOIKONOMO KAT’ OIKON)

General information: The Joint Ministerial Decision on the “Energy Efficiency at Household Buildings” Program (Government Gazette B 54 / 26.01.2011)⁷⁵ enacted this Program. Its implementation is under the Buildings’ Energy Efficiency Regulation (KENAK, Δ6/B/5825/30.03.2010, Government Gazette B 407) and Presidential Decree 100/30.09.2010 (GG 177 A) concerning energy inspectors/auditors. The Program is applied through a Holding Fund called “EE at Household Buildings Fund” (Decision no. 31654/20.07.2010, GG B 1262). The budget is 396 million EUR (NEEAP, 2014). In the framework of this program, a public information campaign was organized about the benefits of the involvement in the program and for facilitating those who decided to be benefited from it.

The banks which participate in the “Energy Efficiency at Household Buildings” Program, finance also (green loans) EE improvements of their residential and commercial customers. Relevant large-scale awareness-raising and campaigns are organized by the banks as well for this purpose (NEEAP, 2014).

Expected results: The overall objective of the Program is to help save energy up to 1 billion kWh annually. The implementation period is 2011-2015 and expected energy savings for 2014-2020 will be

⁷¹ Site: <http://www.epper.gr/el/Pages/Default.aspx>

⁷² Open call for SAVE II - <http://www.ypeka.gr/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=csANTJr%2fWjY%3d&tabid=842&language=el-GR>

⁷³ Open call for SAVE II - <http://www.ypeka.gr/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=csANTJr%2fWjY%3d&tabid=842&language=el-GR>

⁷⁴ <http://exoikonomisi.ypeka.gr/Default.aspx?tabid=629&locale=en-US&language=el-GR>

⁷⁵ Government Gazette 1/E2.1/12300/667

82,4 ktoe (MEECC, 2014; Hellenic Republic, MEECC, Secretariat General for Energy and Climate Change, 2013).

Type of policy instrument: It is of voluntary approach. Under its framework there are: financial policy instrument (subsidy); policy instrument for Dissemination and awareness, capacity building for the technical staff of companies due to actions for developing and promoting RES and EE installations.

Objectives: It aims at providing financial incentives for EE interventions in household sector.

Target groups: It concerns households (hot-water, heating-cooling) in the whole Greek territory. Owners, who have certain income restrictions, of buildings (detached house, block of flats, individual apartment) which: are legal/legalized; are located in areas with an average zone price lower than or equal to 2100 €/m²; are used as residence; are classified as low EE buildings (with EPC in class D or below) and are not scheduled to be demolished (NEEAP, 2014).

Rules and influencing mechanisms: All applications should cover a requirement so as to achieve the minimum energy target of the Program: the package of interventions should result in the upgrade by at least one energy class or, alternatively, provide annual primary energy savings greater than 30% of the consumption of the reference building (kWh/m²) (MEECC, 2014; Hellenic Republic, MEECC, Secretariat General for Energy and Climate Change, 2013). The eligible EE improvements concern replacement of windows, installation of shading systems, thermal insulation and advancement of heating/cooling and hot-water system. Any house, block of flats or apartment is considered as eligible residence for this program, if is meeting the following criteria: i) Used as a primary or secondary residence; ii) Located in areas with lower than / or equal price band to 2.100 € / m².; iii) Has building permit, issued by 31.12.1989; iv) is classified under the Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) in category lower or equal to the D; iv) It is not judged as demolished.

Implementation network: The supervisory party is the Ministry of Reconstruction of Production, Environment and Energy (mentioned in short also as YPEKA). The parties involved in management and implementation are: The Management Authority of the OP “Competitiveness and Entrepreneurship”; Department for planning and coordination of NSRF with co-financed actions in the fields of Energy, Natural Resources and Climate Change (EYSED EN/KA) under YPEKA; E.T.E.AN. A.E., the Hellenic Fund for Entrepreneurship and Development , prior (TEMPME S.A.) – “Energy Efficiency at Household Buildings” Holding Fund; The Hellenic Energy Inspectorate of YPEKA ; Energy Inspectors enrolled in the Registry of Energy Inspectors of YPEKA; Financial Institutions / Banks (NEEAP, 2014).

“Allazo KLIMAtistiko”⁷⁶ (Replace Airconditioning)

General information: The initiative started in early June 2009. Although it was scheduled to be completed in December 2009, due to excess demand, it was completed on 22nd of August 2009 (Remaco SA, 2010).

The total budget of the initiative, in public expenditure terms, was 15 million EUR and the grant quote was 35% with a maximum grant limit of 500 EUR per household. Grant was computed on retail price of air-conditioners. The initiative was financed by the OP Competitiveness and the Regional Operational Programs (Remaco SA, 2010). Public expenditure is expected – after its completion - to reach 40 million EUR (Remaco SA, 2010). According to discussions with the Intermediate Management Body of the Energy, Natural Resources & Manufacturing of the Ministry of Development⁷⁷, there is no intention to have a second round of financing for this kind of initiative (Remaco SA, 2010).

Type of policy instrument: economic/ subsidy.

⁷⁶ <http://www.allazoklima.gr>

⁷⁷ Responsible authority

Objectives: It provides for replacing old air conditioning equipment by brand-new equipment in households (Remaco SA, 2010). Its results are⁷⁸: i) Expected annual energy savings of 41,6 GWh, while the initial objective was for 16,96 GWh; ii) Expected annual reduction of CO₂ emissions of 36,6 kt while the initial objective was for 14,9 kt; iii) Until the end of July 2009, 110.402 air-conditioners were replaced and recycled while the initial objective was for 45.000 (Remaco SA, 2010).

Target groups: All citizens that possess obsolete air-conditioning equipment with high energy consumption and wish to replace them can participate.

Rules and influencing mechanisms: It funds the replacement of air conditions. All types of air conditions are included. Each citizen can withdraw up to two (2) air conditioning devices and through this action, to replace them by purchasing up to two (2) others of inverter technology and with high rate of energy classes, from any shop that is participating at the action (Remaco SA, 2010).

Implementation network: The responsible authority was the Intermediate Management Body for Energy, Natural Resources & Manufacturing (Remaco SA, 2010). The initiative operated through electric appliances retailers who were responsible to collect the appropriate documentation, collect obsolete equipment and transfer it to recycling centers. Citizens were paying their share (65% of retail price) for the equipment purchased and retailers were receiving the remaining amount based to the sales performed (provided that they submitted the appropriate documentation) (Remaco SA, 2010).

Green Enterprise

General information: It was launched in year 2010 and aimed to: reduce the energy and environmental impacts of manufacturing companies; develop and promote “green” products and services; improve environmental and social profile of businesses and; adopt international environmental standards (Ministry of Finance, 2015). It was funded by NSRF with a budget of 30.000.000EUR and provided support to projects with an investment cost from 30.000 EUR to 200.000 EUR (NEEAP, 2014). Initially, 54 projects were approved with total budget 7,5 million EUR (public funding 3,3 million EUR) (MEECC, NREAP, 2012; Ministry of Finance, 2013). The difficult access to finance and the great delays at getting environmental permits and other licenses of activity constituted the main problems for eligible enterprises (Ministry of Finance, 2013).

Type of policy instrument: Financial policy instrument.

Objectives: To create the conditions for including the environmental dimension into the processes of enterprises, in order to intervene with the procedure of production chain. Eligible for financing were micro- and small-sized enterprises of the manufacturing sector⁷⁹.

Target groups: All sectors could participate and it concerned investors, public administration, end-users, SMEs, companies, engineers (MEECC, NREAP, 2012).

Rules and influencing mechanisms: Eligible for funding were energy and water saving recovery interventions or bioclimatic and RES interventions (3rd NEEAP, 2014).

Implementation network: Enterprise and Business Park Licensing Directorate of the Ministry of Development and Competitiveness, Intermediate Body of the OP “Competitiveness and Entrepreneurship” (OPCE), Ministry of Development and Competitiveness (supervisory body).

Green Fund⁸⁰

General information: The establishment of Green Fund (“*Prasino Tameio*”) was enacted with Law 3889/2010⁸¹. The Ministerial Decision No. 4503/2012 (Government Gazette B 3184, 30.11.2012),

⁷⁸ source: former Ministry of Development

⁷⁹ http://www.un.org/esa/dsd/dsd_aofw_ni/ni_pdfs/NationalReports/greece/Greece_CSD18-19-Chapter_V-10YFP-SCP.pdf

⁸⁰ <http://www.prasinotameio.gr/index.php/en/>

⁸¹ Article 3, Law 3889/2010. (http://www.prasinotameio.gr/images/documents/n3889_10%20prasino%20tameio.pdf)

pursuant to Article 3 of Law 3889/2010, distributed the resources addressed to climate change mitigation/adaptation and EE actions (3rd NEEAP, 2014). This Fund⁸² has undertaken the responsibility for funding EE projects, among others. It finances programs established by the Ministry of Reconstruction of Production, Environment and Energy or other Ministries, agencies related to them, local authorities and legal entities of the broader public sector. Those programs may concern sustainable development and energy actions or business plans for such actions. Actors related to EE such as ESCOs, energy auditors, end-users, etc. can be also beneficiaries.

Type of policy instrument: The establishment of the “Green Fund” is a regulatory/institutional policy instrument. Its activities will support the implementation of financial policy instruments (subsidies, soft loans, tax exemptions etc) along with awareness policy instruments.

Objectives: 1) Assist managerially, technically and financially programs, measures and actions aiming at restoration and improvement of environment, 2) Support of national environmental policy, and 3) Serve societal needs through the governance, management and exploitation of “green resources”⁸³.

Target groups: MEECC or other ministries and subordinated agencies, devolved administrations in general, local authorities, legal entities of the broader public sector⁸⁴, unions or other associations of legal and natural persons. Final consumers, natural and legal persons, all end-use sectors may be also beneficiaries.

Rules and influencing mechanisms: The recipients of financing are specified in the open call of the financing program, which specifies the budget and its distribution. The evaluation and selection criteria for operations and actions are also specified. The criteria must include eligibility, maturity, completeness, appropriateness and consistency of the program with the relevant national and EU policies and legislation, and the managing capacity of the implementing body.

Every financing program for a budgeted expenditure - excluding VAT - greater than or equal to 50.000.00 EUR must receive approval by the Minister of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, on the recommendation of its Board of Directors. For amounts less than 50.000.00 EUR, it must receive approval by decision of the Board of Directors of the Fund. These decisions are setting the amount and method of payment of the grants or loans and the procedures and conditions for payment and any other issue relating to the implementation of the programs. A summary of the program and its individual data (ie categories of actions, timeframe, financial planning, categories of beneficiaries), and any other relevant details shall be posted on the Green Fund’s website, before approving any program and anyone can submit comments on the program proposed.

Implementation network: Ministry of Reconstruction of Production, Environment and Energy.

Standard demonstration projects on the use of Renewable Energy Sources (RES) and/or Energy Saving (ES) in public buildings

General information: The programme was funded by the OP “Environment and Sustainable Development”⁸⁵ with total financing of 40 million EUR (NEEAP, 2014). Its application period was from 20 July 2010 to 15 April 2011. It aimed at achieving energy savings in the central and the general government, encouraging and increasing the use of RES through standard demonstration projects, reducing air pollution and reducing emissions of gases that cause climate change. The actions for funding included heat insulation, installing natural lighting and ventilation systems, energy monitoring systems, replacement of old air conditioning systems, etc. (NEEAP, 2014). A total of 13 buildings have joined the programme with a total budget of 30,5 million EUR (NEEAP, 2014).

⁸² <http://www.prasinotameio.gr/index.php/el/programmata-kai-dikaiouxi>

⁸³ “Green resources” are revenue and resources from: Blue Fund, Special Fund of Regulatory and Urban Scheme Implementation, Special Agency of Forests and Fund of Environmental Balance (Law 3889/2010).

⁸⁴ defined by Article 1 of Law 1256/1982

⁸⁵ http://www.eperaa.gr/el/Pages/ProclamationsEYDFS.aspx?item=2125&leftmenu_id=ProclamationsEYD.aspx

Type of policy instrument: Economic policy instrument (subsidy); policy instrument promotion for Research and Development (R&D) and Best Available Technologies (BAT) (funding for research/development/ demonstration projects).

Objectives: To reduce energy requirements for heating, cooling, lighting and domestic hot water (NEEAP, 2014).

Target groups: Public buildings housing ministerial departments, public legal entities (except LAs) and companies supervised by Ministries and a state share of 100% (all located in the whole country).

Rules and influencing mechanisms: The open call had information about the procedures, the eligible costs, the types of actions etc.

Implementation network: Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change (supervisory authority), all ministries, public entities (except Local Authorities).

“Bioclimatic Demonstration Schools”

General information: This programme started on 2011 and promoted bioclimatic design interventions in new or under construction primary and secondary education schools aimed at achieving energy savings. The actions funded include (NEEAP, 2014):

- construction of school buildings with bioclimatic design,
- supply and installation of passive and active solar systems, hybrid & RES systems, natural lighting and ventilation systems, solar chimneys, solar protection and shading systems and green roofs, support systems (data metering, recording and monitoring systems for the energy systems of buildings), and control systems for electromechanical installations,
- studies and other actions.

The total budget was 25 million EUR and was funded by the OP “Environment and Sustainable Development” (3rd NEEAP, 2014). By March 2014, 5 schools joined the programme with a total eligible budget of 17 million EUR (3rd NEEAP, 2014).

Type of policy instrument: Economic policy instrument (subsidy) and, dissemination - awareness policy instrument (pupils are in an EE environment, change of behaviour), policy instrument for R&D and BAT promotion (funding for research/development/ demonstration projects).

Objectives: To reduce energy requirements for heating, cooling, lighting and domestic hot water (3rd NEEAP, 2014).

Target groups: Public school buildings.

Rules and influencing mechanisms: No available information.

Implementation network: Local Authorities, Ministry of Education and Religious Affairs, Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, Buildings’ Infrastructure S.A.

‘Standard demonstration projects on the use of RES and/or ES measures in existing public primary and secondary education school buildings’

General information: This programme started in 2011⁸⁶ and included the implementation of projects in existing primary and secondary education school buildings to achieve energy savings in heating, cooling, lighting and hot water and to increase RES generation for heating and/or cooling.

Type of policy instrument: Economic policy instrument (subsidy) and, dissemination - awareness policy instrument (pupils are in an EE environment, change of behaviour), policy instrument for R&D and BAT promotion (funding for research/development/ demonstration projects).

⁸⁶ <http://www.ypeka.gr/Default.aspx?tabid=389&snid=5b524%5d=1330&language=el-GR>

Objectives: Achieve energy savings in heating, cooling, lighting and hot water and to increase RES generation for heating and/or cooling.

Target groups: New or under construction public school buildings. 73 schools have joined this programme, with a total eligible budget of 46 million EUR (3rd NEEAP, 2014).

Rules and influencing mechanisms: An essential condition of the programme is that the building should be upgraded by at least one energy class (3rd NEEAP, 2014).

Implementation network: Local Authorities, Ministry of Education and Religious Affairs, Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, Buildings' Infrastructure S.A.

"Green roofs on public buildings"

General information: The programme is now closed. Its application period was from 5.12.2011 up to 21.5.2012⁸⁷. It concerned the implementation of pilot techniques about green roofs in public buildings (Ministries, Local Governments, Regions of the country, legal public and private entities of non-profit organizations). This programme aimed to the familiarization of citizens and users with the building practices of Green Development. It included actions to distribute information and raise awareness. The total financing was 20 million EUR (NEEAP, 2014). Eighty-seven recommendations were positively assessed for participation with a total budget of 15 million EUR (BUILD SEE, 2014).

Type of policy instrument: It was a voluntary economic policy instrument (subsidy), but also a dissemination and awareness policy instrument since it: i) promoted information on EE issues (technologies and practices linked with green roofs); raised awareness on EE issues and the existence of relevant companies (ie ESCOs). It supported R&D on EE and BAT (funding for research/development/demonstration projects).

Objectives: To reduce the annual energy consumption for heating and cooling the floor beneath the green roof by at least 5% compared to the annual energy consumption before the implementation of green roofs (BUILD SEE, 2014).

Target groups: Public buildings (Ministries, First and second level of LAs, public entities etc).

Rules and influencing mechanisms: The programme lays down the requirements (eligible costs, percentage of subsidy in relation with the type of the proposed project⁸⁸) from the target groups so as to proceed with pilot applications for green roofs and the methodology to be used to select the public sector buildings where the pilot projects will be implemented⁸⁹.

Implementation network: Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change and CRES.

"Building the Future" project⁹⁰

General information: It is an EE program co-funded by EU that expects over 3 million energy saving interventions in Greek residential and commercial buildings by year 2020. It works in the framework of voluntary agreements with industrial and commercial sectors and provides citizens, who wish to renovate their buildings, with certified, high-standard products at better prices than the current market prices. The Program was launched on April 9, 2012, and is planned to be completed in year 2020. It is conducted by a partnership among citizens, the public and the private sector. It is developed in three levels: Level 1-Large scale interventions; Level 2- Demonstration actions (including NZEBs); Level 3-Research and Innovation (applied research for development of innovative high EE products).

⁸⁷ <http://www.espa.gr/el/Pages/Proclamationsfs.aspx?item=1905>

⁸⁸ <http://www.anaptyxis.eu/environmental/nea/34-green-roofs.html>

⁸⁹ http://www.espa.gr/Lists/Proclamations/Attachments/1905/periv_111201_Prosklisi_Pras_Domata.pdf

⁹⁰ Site: http://www.ktizontastomellon.gr/index.php/pws-symmetexw/syhnes_erotiseis/

Type of policy instrument: voluntary approach, economic/ subsidy.

Objectives: Aims to: i) greatly reduce the energy consumption of Greek households and service buildings; ii) reduce their energy costs; iii) improve the life quality and reduce the life costs of society; iv) increase the economic activity of the manufacturing sector; v) improve the competitiveness of the manufacturing industry, and vi) create large number of new jobs.

Target groups: Building professionals (manufacturers, suppliers and installers) - Building occupants.

Rules and influencing mechanisms: Any citizen, interested to participate, should follow a 3 steps procedure: First: accesses the project website, to find the lists with the approved products/ category, relevant information about these products and their installation, details and tips for the best solution of each case. Second: addresses to the store with the logo "Building the future", to receive information about available appliances with the price reduction and proceed to purchase them. Finally, when all installations are finished, a technician from CRES should be asked to visit the house, measure EE, check that the installed appliances are the approved ones and installed in an efficient way.

Implementation network: Ministry of Reconstruction of Production, Environment and Energy, CRES.

Supporting and monitoring of the pilot implementation of energy efficiency improvement projects in public buildings by Energy Service Companies (ESCOs)

General information: The project⁹¹ started in 2012 and will end in 2015. It is funded by the OP "Environment and Sustainable Development" 2007-2013 and aims to (3rd NEEAP, 2014): i) assist the MEECC in developing the ESCO market and identifying technical, procedural and regulatory parameters for implementing this type of contracts and projects, through pilot applications, ii) ensure that ESCOs have access to EE programs for public sector buildings and make use of the Third Party Financing mechanism for achieving the national targets in public buildings, using the expertise and funds of the private sector, iii) disseminate the project results as a guide, and iv) determine the implementation framework for the ESCO market and implement energy projects in the public sector buildings.

The budget of the project is 589.713 EUR and the estimated budget, provided by ESCOs, for interventions in the relevant buildings is 3,4 million EUR (NEEAP, 2014).

Expected results: Based on the case studies of 6 buildings, the expected outcomes are (3rd NEEAP, 2014): 5,184 MWh of annual energy savings; 23% of total saving; 38 man-years of jobs; 3,4 million EUR of overall investment costs; 674.000 EUR of total annual economic profit for public bodies.

Type of policy instrument: Dissemination-Awareness policy instrument (due to actions for promoting energy services/ ESCOs) and regulatory policy instrument (due to actions for determining the ESCO implementation network).

Objectives: To remove regulatory and non-regulatory barriers that prevents the conclusion of Energy Performance Contracts in the public sector.

Target groups: public sector buildings.

Rules and influencing mechanisms: No available information.

Implementation network: CRES, ESCOs.

Energy upgrading of social housing buildings "Green Pilot Urban Neighborhood"⁹²

General information: The program's duration is from 2012 to 2015. It is regional (Attica) and will present the pilot and innovative implementation of techniques, energy saving systems and integration technologies for Renewable Energy Sources (RES), which would cover most of the energy needs

⁹¹ <http://www.ktizontastomellon.gr/index.php/parallhles-driseis/Escos/>

⁹² : http://www.ktizontastomellon.gr/index.php/parallhles-driseis/Prasini_geitonia1/

for heating -cooling, hot water and electricity of urban housing units, which are occupied by low-income citizens, and are part of an optimized urban environment. As part of this action, four energy (4) buildings in the municipality of Agia Barbara in Attica will be upgraded (BUILD SEE, 2014). These buildings are inhabited by citizens of low interest and demonstrate considerable potential of energy saving. This program is based on voluntary agreements with the participation of Greek industries and commercial companies and co-financed by the OP 'Environment and Sustainable Development' (OPESD). The budget of the program amounts to 7 million EUR (3rd NEEAP, 2014).

Type of policy instrument: Under this programme there are voluntary approaches and financial policy instruments (subsidy).

Objectives: To create an urban residential unit "of almost zero energy balance" (BUILD SEE, 2014).

Target groups: social housing buildings.

Rules and influencing mechanisms: No available information.

Implementation network: CRES.

Strengthening SMEs active in manufacturing, tourism and trade – services

General information: The programme was initially implemented in 2013. Its application submission period was 25/2/2013-16/5/2013⁹³. Now, there is a new announcement from the Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism (Decision No. 3426/827/A2/8.6.2015)⁹⁴. Its primary objectives concern the support of SMEs, but supports also EE actions (secondary objectives) (see below objectives).

The Action is financed by the European Regional Fund through the Regional Operational Programs of Macedonia - Thrace, Western Greece Peloponnese - Ionian Islands, Crete and the Aegean Islands, Thessaly - Mainland Greece - Epirus, Attica. For the first announcement, financing was granted to projects with a maximum eligible budget of 30.000 - 300.000 EUR in the area of Manufacturing, of 20.000 - 300.000 EUR in Tourism and of 20.000 - 100.000 EUR in Trade –Services (3rd NEEAP, 2014). The percentage of public funding depends on the area where the investment was made, and on the size of the enterprise (medium and small and micro-enterprises) (NEEAP, 2014).

Type of policy instrument: This programme covers a range of policy instruments (taking into consideration both announcements) (Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism, 2015). It was a voluntary approach since it was not mandatory for the target groups. It was an economic policy instrument since it provided financial support through an approved amount of subsidy to the target groups. It was also informative since it was promoting ESCOs if the investment plan concerned EE⁹⁵.

Objectives: To provide support to small and medium-sized enterprises, whether they are existing, new or in the process of being established, and are making investments for innovations, environment and ICT (3rd NEEAP, 2014).

Target groups: existing and new enterprises, active in manufacturing, tourism and trade-services.

Rules and influencing mechanisms: There were rules about: i) the SMEs that could participate (type, activities); ii) the total amount of the investment plans; iii) the percentages of the provided public subsidies per region; iv) the types of eligible costs; v) the duration of the investment plans; vi) the procedures of the applying, verifying and receiving the subsidy. Eligible actions included in both announcements investment plans related to EE: building works, electromechanical installations, pro-

⁹³ <http://p-energy.gr/news/readmore/?id=34>

⁹⁴ <http://www.taxheaven.gr/laws/circular/view/id/21036>

⁹⁵ the interested target groups had to hire and consult companies that would prepare and conduct the investment plan

duction, storage, distribution and administration areas of undertakings, purchase - transport - installation of environmental protection equipment and systems.

Implementation network: For the first announcement: i) Ministry of Development and Competitiveness (supervisory authority); ii) Special Managing Service of the OP 'Competitiveness and Entrepreneurship', Intermediate Body of the OP 'Competitiveness and Entrepreneurship' (EFEPAE) and Regions (3rd NEEAP, 2014).

“Standard demonstration projects on the use of Renewable Energy Sources and Energy Saving Actions in new, under construction or existing buildings, gyms and swimming pools owned by local authorities and municipal enterprises of local authorities”

General information: The Programme provides funds to demonstration projects on RES and EE actions in new, under construction or existing buildings, gyms and swimming pools owned by local authorities and municipal enterprises of local authorities. The total budget for the programme is approximately 25 million EUR and covered 100% by the NSRF 2007-2013 (3rd NEEAP, 2014).

Type of policy instrument: Economic policy instrument (subsidy) and, policy instrument for R&D and BAT promotion (funding for research/development/ demonstration projects).

Objectives: The implementation of actions and proven best practices for reducing energy consumption in the urban environment, with emphasis on the building sector (municipal buildings of 1st grade LA) and the upgrade of public spaces, as well as, in the area of municipal and private transport and energy intensive municipal facilities. Also, the implementation of technical interventions and actions will raise awareness and mobilise citizens, the local government, businesses and bodies.

Expected results: average energy saving of 47,6%; 50,4% average percentage of GHG emissions reduction; total GHG reduction of 0,5 kt CO₂eq; creation of 115 man-years of employment (3rd NEEAP, 2014).

Target groups: Local authorities and municipal enterprises of local authorities.

Rules and influencing mechanisms: Funding may be received by demonstration projects using RES and Energy Saving Actions in new, under construction or existing buildings, gyms and swimming pools, owned by local authorities and municipal enterprises of local authorities.

Implementation network: Municipalities.

Intelligent Nearly Zero Energy Theme Museums

General information: The programme aims to promote energy savings in the public sector, encouraging and increasing the use of RES through standard demonstration projects, reducing air pollution and GHG emissions (NEEAP, 2014). The following actions can be funded by the programme: i) Energy upgrade and saving interventions and RES actions, ii) Information and awareness-raising campaigns for museum visitors about EE and RES issues. Iii) energy inspections and issue of Energy Performance Certificates for buildings that join the programme, including the installation of systems for measuring, monitoring, recording, processing and viewing - on site and online - the operating data and results of Building Energy Management Systems (BEMS), control and operational management systems for electromechanical installations (NEEAP, 2014). The total budget is 10 million EUR. Five (5) actions were accepted for funding with a total budget of 2.115.679,49 EUR (3rd NEEAP, 2014).

Type of policy instrument: Economic policy instrument (subsidy) and, policy instrument for R&D and BAT promotion (funding for research/development/ demonstration projects).

Objectives: Its primary objective is to convert the buildings ideally to Buildings of Almost Zero Energy Consumption after the proposed interventions with maximum primary energy consumption of up to 60 kWh/m² per year (ERDF PP8 REGION OF WESTERN GREECE, 2014).

Target groups: Museums whose legal status is either non-profit private legal entity for a public benefit purpose or non-profit civil partnership.

Rules and influencing mechanisms: The program funds energy upgrade and saving actions with interventions in the building envelope⁹⁶, RES actions⁹⁷ and publicity, information and awareness-raising actions for visitors on Energy Saving (ES) and RES issues.

Implementation network: Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change and CRES.

Joint European Support for Sustainable Investment in City Areas (JESSICA) initiative

General information: It is a policy initiative of the European Commission (EC - DG REGIO), launched in 2006 together with the European Investment Bank (EIB) and the Council of Europe Development Bank (CEB)⁹⁸, aiming to establish a common approach for financing urban development and strengthening the urban dimension in cohesion policy through repayable assistance (Kovacheva S., 2013; EIB, 2012).

For its implementation in Greece, actions such as calls of interest, preliminary studies, assessments etc were launched in 2011. More specifically, the EIB, acting as the JESSICA Holding Fund Greece⁹⁹ (at the Hellenic Managing Authorities' request), launched a call for expression of interest (for the period: 18 March 2011 - 30 May 2011) (EIB, 2010). The call concerned the selection of Urban Development Funds that received financing of approximately EUR 258 million from the JESSICA Holding Fund Greece to use up to 31 December 2015¹⁰⁰. This amount was to facilitate the disbursement of EU Structural Funds¹⁰¹ in the form of repayable investments in public-private partnerships or other urban projects included in Hellenic integrated plans for sustainable urban development. JESSICA for Greece was financed partly from EU structural funds and partly from national public funding. Five funds (see at the Implementation network more details), selected in an open and transparent procedure, provided loans and equity at sub-commercial terms to urban development projects (EIB, 2012).

Requests for Expression of Interest were issued in May 2012 (Tsipouri L. and Athanassopoulou S., 2012). During December 2012, the European Commission approved, under EU State aid rules, the Greek (along with a similar Bulgarian) scheme aimed at supporting urban regeneration projects through the JESSICA initiative¹⁰². The Commission found the scheme to be in line with EU state aid rules, more specifically, Article 107(3)(c) of the Treaty on the functioning of the EU (TFEU). The scheme allows supporting the development of certain economic areas, provided that it does not adversely affect trade between Member States and in particular it addresses market failures affecting urban regeneration projects without unduly distorting competition in the EU Single Market.

Today the web-site for the implementation of the JESSICA initiative in Greece is not fully functional¹⁰³ so as to get updated information about this fund. The latest actions appear to have occurred in March 2015. Due to the financial crisis in Greece¹⁰⁴ and the resulting lack of liquidity in the Greek

⁹⁶ installing thermal insulation on the building envelope, installing external shading or other sun protection systems, planting roofs, using cool or other specialised materials on roofs and/or exterior walls, replacing window frames and glass panes with new certified, energy-efficient ones, and other EE improvement measures, passive solar systems installation: passive solar heating systems, day lighting systems, natural and/or hybrid ventilation and cooling systems and techniques, and other passive systems, bioclimatic interventions in the surrounding area to improve microclimatic conditions and ensure environmental comfort and energy saving conditions, interventions for upgrading and modifying existing facilities: central heating and/or cooling, hot water, artificial lighting, ventilation

⁹⁷ photovoltaic installations, shallow geothermal energy, biomass combustion installations, solar thermal systems, small wind turbines, other RES exploitation systems, heating or cooling systems and heat pumps, interventions to convert the existing E/M installations to improve their functional features and performance

⁹⁸ A Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) between the EC, the EIB and the CEB was signed in May 2006, providing the framework for a coordinated approach by these 3 partner institutions for financing urban renewal and development during the programming period 2007-2013 of the Community Structural Funds (EIB, 2007).

⁹⁹ <http://www.eib.org/products/blending/jessica/eoi/vp959.htm>

¹⁰⁰ http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release_IP-12-1413_en.htm

¹⁰¹ Structural Funds: the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) and the European Social Fund (ESF), referred to under Regulations (EC) No. 1083/2006, 1080/2006 and 1081/2006.

¹⁰² http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release_IP-12-1413_en.htm

¹⁰³ <http://www.jessicafund.gr/?lang=en>

¹⁰⁴ <http://stateaidhub.eu/blogs/stateaiduncovered/post/16>

banking system, the implementation of JESSICA is encountering difficulties. In one project case, the JESSICA funding was postponed in 2013 as it was characterized as State Aid because of the framework created by the aforementioned conditions (EC, 2013).

Type of policy instrument: JESSICA is characterized as a financial instrument¹⁰⁵ set up by the EC, but actually it is a range of sophisticated financial engineering instruments¹⁰⁶ including equity investments, loans and guarantees that offer new opportunities for the use of EU Structural Funds¹⁰⁷. It is implemented through Public-Private Partnership (voluntary approach).

Objectives¹⁰⁸: i) To increase Structural Funds' efficiency and productivity by using "non-grant" financial instruments, thus creating stronger incentives for successful project implementation; ii) To increase leverage with additional financial resources for public-private partnerships for urban development projects focusing on sustainability/ recyclability; iii) To exploit new partnerships and synergies (Kovacheva S., 2013); iv) To use financial and managerial expertise from international financial institutions such as the EIB.

Target groups: MAs in the Member States (MS) of the European Union (EU) can participate in the initiative (EIB, 2010; EIB, 2007). JESSICA concerns their investments/projects in sustainable urban transformation (brownfields/city regeneration, renewable energy, energy efficiency, clusters' development, transport, tourism/public service infrastructure) (Kovacheva S., 2013). Mainly, JESSICA targets those projects that would not attract sufficient finance through normal market mechanisms such as Energy Efficiency (EE) and Renewable Energy projects with medium to high risk and likely have long payback periods (EIB, 2012). More specifically, possible types of JESSICA energy projects with added value are (Kovacheva S., 2013): Energy Efficiency, Co-generation and Energy Management: (i) Renovation or extension of existing district heating or cooling networks; high-efficiency combined heat and power; ii) Energy savings/energy efficiency in buildings.

Rules and influencing mechanisms: There are two steps before using the initiative. Member States are able to use JESSICA, if they have included an urban agenda in their "OP¹⁰⁹" and, ideally, if they have also included a statement on the potential use of JESSICA in delivering this agenda. As a second step, Member States will need to decide what proportion of their Structural Funds they would like to channel using JESSICA (EIB, 2012).

There are rules about: the Managing Authority, the Holding Fund, the Urban Development Fund, the Fund manager of the Urban Development Project and for the Public-Private-Partnerships, the Contracts, and the Operational Rules.

For JESSICA in Greece, projects are selected based on: i) their viability in a 20-year time span; ii) their legal-technical environmental maturity and iii) the experience and credit worthiness of the beneficiaries (Tsipouri L. and Athanassopoulou S., 2012). All funds provided by EIB were deposited to the

¹⁰⁵ http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release_IP-12-1413_en.htm

¹⁰⁶ FEIs are instruments with a revolving character, which means that FEIs invest on a repayable basis, on the contrary to Grants which are non-repayable investments. Their concept is to use mathematical techniques to solve financial problems. Frequently, financial engineering is referred to as quantitative analysis and is used by regular commercial banks, investment banks, insurance agencies and hedge funds (<http://www.investopedia.com/terms/f/financialengineering.asp#ixzz3fP6GIT9U>). FEIs invest in Final Recipients, typically enterprises, Public Private Partnerships (PPPs) or Urban Projects through the provision of Loans, Guarantees or Equity in line with an agreed investment strategy (EIB, 2013). FEIs are referred also as financial engineering operations (EC, Directorate – General Regional Policy, 2013). FEIs are used for sharing risk between investors and the enterprises in which they invest. Although such financial instruments are complex, they are gaining prominence in public policy towards enterprises, particularly small and medium-sized enterprises [SMEs] (Nicolaidis P., 2013).

¹⁰⁷ <http://www.eib.org/products/blending/jessica/index.htm>

¹⁰⁸ <http://www.eib.org/products/blending/jessica/index.htm>

¹⁰⁹ OP are documents presenting the national development strategies. They are submitted by the Member States and are adopted by the European Commission, covering the use of EU Structural Funds and National co-financing contributions during the programming period 2007-2013 in the context of the NSRF (EIB, 2012).

Central Bank of Greece (Tsipouri L. and Athanassopoulou S., 2012). Based on the financing needs of the UDFs, funds were released to them (Tsipouri L. and Athanassopoulou S., 2012). UDFs were obliged to invest the designated funds in projects by June 2015 (50% by the end of 2013, 80% by the end of 2014), otherwise penalties will be imposed in their management fees (Tsipouri L. and Athanassopoulou S., 2012). Banks receive a management fee of 2%-3%, which was also a criterion for awarding UDFs (Tsipouri L. and Athanassopoulou S., 2012).

The initiative foresees independent experts. The deadline of the respective Contract Notice for the selection of independent experts¹¹⁰ for proposals under the JESSICA initiative for Greece was released on December 14th, 2012 (Mantzoufas N., 2012).

Implementation network: Five national banks were selected as Urban Development Funds to implement JESSICA in Greece: the National Bank of Greece, Pireaus Bank, the Investment Bank of Greece, EFG Eurobank and the Pancretan Cooperative Bank. Participating banks must provide financing for up to 30% of the eligible investment cost.

European initiatives

These are initiatives, not funded or organized by Hellenic entities, but national entities can participate and benefit from their activities. These are Covenant of Mayors¹¹¹, Build up – The European Portal for energy efficiency in buildings¹¹².

National Initiatives

THE PACT OF ISLANDS

General information: The Pact of Islands¹¹³ started as an initiative comprised by 16 Greek islands and 2 regional authorities from the Aegean area. Now, it is an European islands' scheme for cooperation in sustainable energy planning and a political commitment of European islands to: i) developing Sustainable Energy Action Plans and ii) identifying bankable energy projects so as to contribute to the EU sustainability targets for the year 2020.

Type of policy instrument: Voluntary approach (1st and 2nd level LAs are not obliged to participate).

Target groups: Up to April 2011, 48 European politicians from islands municipalities and regions all over Europe signed the Pact of Islands making the political commitment to achieve the 20-20-20 objectives of the European Union for 2020. The Greek signatories are: i) the Municipalities of Aegina, Andros, Ios, Kythnos, Lesvos, Limnos, Lipsi, Milos, Mykonos, Naxos and Small Cyclades, Samothraki, Santorini, Sifnos, Skyros and Syros-Ermoupolis; ii) the Regions of North and South Aegean. More island Municipalities of the Aegean have already expressed their intention to join this initiative.

Rules and influencing mechanisms: There is no available information.

Implementation network: DAFNI, the Network of Sustainable Greek Islands and the Aegean Energy Agency (see previous session in the MLG framework) are the Supporting Structures for the Aegean authorities, assisting them to fulfill their commitments.

Horizontal measures (addressed to a number of sectors including building and transport)

The following policy measures address all final energy consumption sectors including residential, tertiary, transport sectors, and industries (that fall under Directive 2003/87/EC establishing a GHG emis-

¹¹⁰http://www.sesma.gr/uploads/media/Independent_experts_in_the_context_of_the_Jessica_initiative_in_Greece.pdf

¹¹¹<http://www.covenantofmayors.eu/>

¹¹²<http://www.buildup.eu>

¹¹³<http://www.dafni.net.gr/en/collaborations/pact-of-islands.htm>

sion allowance trading scheme within the Community and amending Council Directive 1996/61/EC (3rd NEEAP, 2014). These are (3rd NEEAP, 2014):

1. **Energy audits and energy management systems**
2. **Metering and billing**
3. **Consumer information and training programmes**
4. **Qualification, accreditation and certification schemes**
5. **Energy Services**
6. There are also **other horizontal measures**, which include actions not closely linked to a specific sector, but are considered to be **important for the application and monitoring of all actions in all sectors** and focus on the collection and evaluation of relevant information and the securing of financial support through the operational programmes (3rd NEEAP, 2014).
7. **Energy Efficiency National Fund, financing and technical support:** Although there is not an established EE national fund yet, its duties can be exercised by the Green Fund. This Fund provides directly subsidies or ensures financing for business plans for investments and programmes for the sustainable use of energy and sustainable development (3rd NEEAP, 2014). More information in the previous part which includes national programmes and initiatives.

1.3 CONCLUSIONS AND LESSONS LEARNED OF OTHER PROJECTS ABOUT THE PERFORMANCE OF THE NATIONAL POLICY PACKAGES FOR ENERGY EFFICIENCY

Most of the entities that are part of the Hellenic MLG framework have participated in funded projects (from FP7, Intelligent Energy Europe, Horizon 2020, Interreg¹¹⁴) about EE issues (the performance of policy instruments for the promotion of energy efficiency objectives, the support and adoption of technologies and practices). These collaborations provided valuable lessons and experience for the Hellenic researchers and stakeholders so as to be able to design more effective policy instruments and overcome barriers that were identified. The following projects are presented in chronological order according to the year they were launched.

ENTRANZE – Policies to Enforce the Transition to Nearly Zero Energy buildings in the EU-27

General information: ENTRANZE was an IEE funded project that started in April 2012 and ended in September 2014. **Site:** <http://www.entranze.eu/>

Objectives: ENTRANZE project aimed to: i) actively support policy making by providing the required data, analysis and guidelines to achieve a fast and strong penetration of nZEB and RES-H/C within the existing national building stocks; ii) connect building experts coming from European research and academia with national decision makers and key stakeholders so as to build ambitious, but reality proof, policies and roadmaps. The latter (dialogue with policy makers and experts) was the core part of the project and focused on nine countries, covering >60% of the EU-27 building stock. Data, scenarios and recommendations were also provided for EU-27 (+ Croatia and Serbia).

Outcomes for Greece: ENTRANZE report provided a brief overview of buildings policy frameworks in the EU-27 Member States, along with: i) synthesis of existing energy requirements in the EU countries' building codes, ii) policy status-quo in moving towards nearly zero-energy buildings and iii) existing economic instruments for improvements of the energy performance of existing and new buildings. Since the project concentrated only on the nine countries, there are no specific outcomes for other EU countries, such as Greece. However, general guidelines - for policy instruments that might

¹¹⁴ <http://www.interreg.gr/en/>

increase the number of NZEBs - applicable to EU Member States are provided in some of the delivered reports. These guidelines were: i) National policy makers should create an effective target-oriented policy environment with clear focus and ii) an effective set-up, implementation and monitoring of policy packages should be done. This need occurred by the fact –presented on the deliverables- that the policy packages implemented so far have not resulted with the desired outcomes on the performance of national policy packages for energy efficiency. No specific outcomes for buildings and/or transport sector are presented.

RePublic_ZEB – Zeroing in on energy

General information: RePublic_ZEB is an IEE funded project with partners from the South-Eastern European countries for developing and promoting Near Zero Energy Building (nZEB) tools. Its started on 01/03/2014 and will end on 31/08/2016. **Site:** <http://www.republiczeb.org/>

Objectives: Its core objective *“is to define cost-benefit optimised “packages of measures” based on efficient and quality-guaranteed technologies for the refurbishment of the public building stock towards nZEB that are standardised and adopted by builders and building owners”*. Its core objective is supported by: i) State-of-the-art assessment of the public building stock through a country-specific evaluation of the energy consumption and CO₂ emissions; ii) Definition of reference buildings; and iii) Development of a common framework and a harmonised methodology for the definition of a nZEB concept for public buildings.

Outcomes for Greece: It is an on-going project. Each partner of the target countries describes the national regulatory framework of the nZEB legislation (information about national nZEB definition, its application in practice, the numerical requirements of nZEBs, requirements at cost optimal level, relevant content of national plans (National Energy Efficiency Action Plan, National Plan for increasing the number of nZEBs, Renewable Energy Action Plan), characteristics of the target country (climatic conditions, energy prices, etc)) (RePublic_ZEB, 2015). According to the project’s outcomes (so far), EE in Greece is not as been promoted as desired due to institutional, financial and legislative barriers. The nZEB definition has been introduced to the national legislation but only in general terms. Detailed requirements and application in practice are not yet specified (RePublic_ZEB, 2015). In addition, it is suggested to ensure the continued adoption and implementation of measures related to informing and educating consumers so that they choose highly energy-efficient buildings / products and changes their behaviour regarding energy use and consumption (RePublic_ZEB, 2015).

ODYSSEE-MURE - Monitoring of Energy Efficiency in EU 27, Norway and Croatia

General information: The ODYSSEE-MURE project is supported by the IEE programme and is part of the activity of the EnR Club. Its implementation period is 01/04/2013 - 30/09/2015 (Ongoing). **Site:** <http://www.odyssee-mure.eu/>

Objectives: The general objective of the project is to provide a comprehensive monitoring of energy consumption and efficiency trends, and an evaluation of EE policy measures by sector for EU countries and Norway. More specifically: i) Evaluate and compare EE progress by sector, and relate this progress to the observed trends in energy consumption; ii) Contribute to the evaluation of national EE policy measures and analyze the dynamics of implementation over the NEAAPs.

The project will develop specific data facilities so as to provide results in an interactive and attractive way to decision makers and actors involved in energy efficiency. Its originality is to: i) cover all sectors and end-uses with a homogeneous and harmonized approach and to: ii) provide an overall picture of the trends and measures by sector.

Outcomes for Greece: A report was prepared by CRES for the case study of Greece for this project (CRES, 2012). It included: i) analysis of EE trends in Greece during the period 1990 – 2010; ii) overview of EE trends on the basis of indicators extracted from the ODYSSEE database; iii) Overview of EE policies and measures based on MURE database. One of the key messages is that the economic recession has a visible impact to a greater or lesser extent, in all sectors of final energy consumption in

Greece, especially from 2008 onwards (CRES, 2012). Lessons from quantitative EE measure evaluations are (CRES, 2012): i) emphasis was given - during the last years - in measures for the buildings and transportation because of their increase in final energy consumption and the respectively high potential for energy savings. However, priority has been given in the implementation of measures for the transport sector; ii) Emphasis was placed for developing the needed structures, for the implementation of the developed regulatory framework for EE and certification of buildings, the measurement of the achieved savings, the public consultation with market players.

Energy Efficiency Watch

General information: It is an initiative that was created among Parliamentarians and was based on Parliamentary Call. There have been two projects EEW1 and EEW2 accomplished under the Intelligent Energy Europe program of the European Commission. The last one, the Energy-Efficiency-Watch 3 project (**EEW3**)¹¹⁵ started on the 19th of August 2014 and will be running for 3 years. **Site:** <http://www.energy-efficiency-watch.org/index.php?id=5>

Objectives: To: i) facilitate the implementation of the Energy Efficiency Directive; ii) support market transition by collecting information on the implementation of energy efficiency policies and providing this information to a variety of stakeholders such as European Parliament, European Commission, national, regional, local policy makers and experts. The core objective of EEW3 is to establish a constant feedback loop on the implementation of European and national energy efficiency policies and thus enable mutual learning on effective policy making across the EU. EEW3 screens progress of national policies, looks into legislative documents, seeks experts' knowledge via an EU-wide survey and creates new consultation platforms with a wide spectrum of stakeholders (parliamentarians, regions, cities, business and expert stakeholders) (Energy Efficiency Watch (1), 2013).

Target groups: Members of European Parliament; Members of national parliaments in the EU; Civil servants in public administrations in all EU Member States who deal with energy efficiency and especially with the NEEAPs and the transformation/ implementation of the Energy Services Directive on the national level; energy efficiency related regional and local networks, industry associations, consultants and experts; energy efficiency related civil society (Energy Efficiency Watch (2), 2013).

Outcomes for Greece: The conclusions of the assessment of the EE Action Plan and Policies for the Hellenic case were the following (Energy Efficiency Watch, 2013):

- The ambition of the Hellenic policy framework is medium, while large potentials remain untapped.
- The most important gap in EE policies was identified at the public sector since there is not an overall strategy of this sector and there are no targets for energy consumption of its buildings.
- The promotion of EE in the industrial sector will be reinforced if there are obligations/commitments to energy management and energy audits and if economic incentives and energy saving targets are set.
- The improved connecting of measures in the transport sector will occur if these measures; i) address more the residential sector as the potential user of public transport, ii) bikes and pedestrian paths are promoted by means of campaigns and financial incentives and iii). In vehicle users are pushed to use other modes of transport by a stronger regulation.
- The aspects of the policy package for appliances will be strengthened by economic incentives and education, and training for retail staff.

¹¹⁵ Energy Efficiency Watch, 2013

2. INTERACTION BETWEEN THE NATIONAL AND THE SUB-NATIONAL LEVELS

For this deliverable the term “Interaction” is used so as to describe the cooperation (in types of relationships and outcomes) within the multi-level governance structure as this is described in the previous sessions for the two sectors – buildings and transport – regarding the Hellenic case. The relationships of cooperation among the involved entities will be described for the two dimensions (horizontal and vertical) of the MLG and as a total (see previous session) and how these were reflected through the programmes, initiatives and policy instruments (described in previous sessions).

Interactions in the vertical dimension of the MLG

European – National level: The European level is the most active one due to a large number of relevant EU Directives, programs and initiatives. The Hellenic level follows by incorporating the EU Directives into national legislation (see Tables 3 and 4). There are cases (Directive 2012/27/EU) in which there was delay to incorporate the necessary EU Directive, Regulation or Decisions, which can be attributed to the need of organizing public discussions and quoting the possible problems that will raise. Additionally, due to the fact that the country does not have the same long term experience as other EU Member States the careful consideration or the gradual incorporation of the respective EU legislation was necessary. Most of the described programmes are financed by the EU Structural Funds provoking the national level to act accordingly. The national level will need to intensify its efforts and examine its horizontal structure so as to be more effective.

National – local/regional level: Between the two of them, the most active one is the national one, while the local/regional is activated each time according to the programmes-initiatives or policy instruments that are addressed to it as well. The 3rd NEEAP has foreseen a set of measures that require its involvement for reaching out the end-users. The role of the local/regional level in implementing EE policy instruments, promoting EE technologies and practices has not been strong. The cooperation among the two levels in a more organized manner and aiming to reach the end-users will be a key parameter, particularly for the penetration of EE technologies and practices.

European – local/regional level: The two levels interact directly through the Covenant of Mayors, the Intelligent Energy Europe and the Interreg. The number of Hellenic municipalities that are signatories to the agreement are 104¹¹⁶, but there are only 77¹¹⁷ SEAPs (regardless their status (accepted, submitted or requested clarifications). The percentage is rather low compared to that of other countries. The initiative of “Pact of Islands” is an encouraging effort for reinforcing and coordinating the activities of the local/regional level in Greece.

Interaction in the horizontal dimension of the MLG

The level that has more interactions under this dimension is the national one, due to the larger number of entities (governmental, non-governmental, private ones) that are involved through programmes-initiatives and policy instruments. The SAVE I, SAVE II, EXOIKONOMO KAT’ OIKON, JESSICA and the “Strengthening SMEs active in manufacturing, tourism and trade –services” appear to have activated more than other programmes the majority of the entities that are part of the horizontal dimension of this level.

¹¹⁶http://www.covenantofmayors.eu/about/signatories_en.html?q=Search+for+a+Signatory...&country_search=gr&population=&date_of_adhesion=&status=

¹¹⁷http://www.covenantofmayors.eu/actions/sustainable-energy-action-plans_en.html?city=Search+for+a+Sustainable+Energy+Action+Plan...&country_seap=gr&co2=&date_of_approval=&accepted=

Interactions in MLG as a total

For some of the EU financed programmes the whole MLG was activated step by step. European, national and local/regional level had to cooperate and set the framework (conditions, rules, institutes, monitoring and evaluation mechanisms) so as to reach the end-users (such were the cases of EXOIKONOMO I and II, JESSICA). In the case of JESSICA, both dimensions were activated simultaneously, but the outcome was not the expected one.

Reinforcing MLG

The concept of MLG has not been fully operational in the Hellenic case. The MLG for the buildings sector is more extended and active compared to the one for the transport sector. Non-governmental or market actors were not actually involved in the designing of national energy efficiency policies/strategies/targets. Up to now, they are activated by expressing their opinion in public consultations.

For implementing Multi-level governance, the country will need new forms of organisation, procedures and skills, in other words new institutional capacity (EC, 2013).

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HERON (No: 649690): Deliverable D.1.1

LANDSCAPE OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICY PACKAGES IN A MULTI-LEVEL GOVERNMENT SYSTEM

D.1.1

**PART OF WORK PACKAGE 1: MAPPING OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICY INSTRUMENTS AND
AVAILABLE TECHNOLOGIES IN BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT**

NATIONAL REPORT FOR ITALY

DATE

Partner: “*Università Commerciale Luigi Bocconi*”

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HERON: Forward – looking socio-economic research on Energy Efficiency in EU countries

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649690. The content of this document reflects only the authors' views and the EASME is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Contents

ACRONYMS	4
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	6
1. THE ROLE OF GOVERNANCE AND ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICY PACKAGES ON THE NATIONAL LEVEL	8
1.1 POLICY PACKAGES AND POLICY GOVERNANCE IN ITALY	8
1.2 NATIONAL PROGRAMMES AND INITIATIVES.....	25
1.3 CONCLUSIONS AND LESSONS LEARNED OF OTHER PROJECTS ABOUT THE PERFORMANCE OF THE NATIONAL POLICY PACKAGES FOR ENERGY EFFICIENCY.....	32
2. INTERACTION BETWEEN THE NATIONAL AND THE SUB-NATIONAL LEVELS	38
REFERENCES.....	40

Table of Tables

Table 1 Policy instruments for energy efficiency in the building sector in Italy	25
Table 2 Policy instruments for energy efficiency in the transport sector in Italy.....	28

Table of Figures

Fig. 1 Energy-efficiency instruments available in the different sectors of intervention.....	11
Fig. 2 Total energy savings expected by the energy efficiency improvements of existing public buildings by 2020.....	12
Fig. 3 Scheme summarizing the general functioning of the “National Energy Efficiency Control Room” (Cabina di Regia per l’efficienza energetica).....	17
Fig. 4 ACEEE 2014 International Energy Efficiency Scorecard.....	33
Fig. 5 White Certificates score for each criterion. Radar graph	34
Fig. 6 Evaluation by EEW for the building sector.	35
Fig. 7 Evaluation by EEW for the transport sector.	36

ACRONYMS

ABI: Associazione Bancaria Italiana (National Banks Association).

ACEEE: American Council for an Energy Efficient Economy.

AEEG: Italian Regulatory Authority for Electricity Gas and Water.

CIPE: Comitato Interministeriale per la Programmazione Economica (Committee for the Economic Planning)

CNR: Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (National Research Council).

D.I.: Decreto Interministeriale (Inter-ministerial Decree).

D.L.: Decreto Legge (Law Decree).

Dlgs: Decreto Legislativo (Legislative Decree).

D.M.: Decreto Ministeriale (Ministerial Decree).

D.P.R.: Decreto del Presidente della Repubblica (Decree of the President of the Republic).

EE: Energy Efficiency.

ENEA: Agenzia nazionale per le nuove tecnologie, l'energia e lo sviluppo economico sostenibile (Italian National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development)

EPBD: Energy Performance of Buildings Directive.

ESCO: Energy Service Company.

EU: European Union.

GME: Gestore dei Mercati Energetici (Energy Market operator).

GSE: Gestore dei Servizi Energetici (Energy Service Operator).

L.: National Law.

MATTM: Italian Ministry for the Environment and the Protection of Land and Sea.

MISE: Italian Ministry of Economic Development.

MIT: Italian Ministry of Infrastructures and Transport.

NAP: National Allocation Plan

NEEAP: National Energy Efficiency Action Plan.

NLP: National Logistic Plan

PNIRE: Piano Nazionale Infrastrutturale per la ricarica dei veicoli alimentati ad energia elettrica (National infrastructural plan to set up electric vehicle charging points).

RAEE: Rapporto Annuale sull'Efficienza Energetica (Annual Report on Energy Efficiency).

RENAEL: Rete Nazionale delle Agenzie Energetiche Locali (Italian Network of Local Energy Agency).

SEN: Strategia Energetica Nazionale (National Energy Strategy).

Please note that throughout the report, "SEN, 2013" is used to refer to the following reference: Ministry of Economic Development. (2013). National Energy Strategy 2013. Available at:

http://www.encharter.org/fileadmin/user_upload/Energy_policies_and_legislation/Italy_2013_National_Energy_Strategy_ENG.pdf

Please note that throughout the report, “NEEAP, 2014” is used to refer to the following reference: Ministry of Economic Development. (2014a). Italian Energy Efficiency Action Plan 2014. Available at:

https://ec.europa.eu/energy/sites/ener/files/documents/2014_neeap_en_italy.pdf

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Italy has defined challenging energy efficiency objectives to 2020 both in the buildings and transport sectors. Many important energy efficiency targets are already reached. As evidenced in the ACEEE 2014 International Energy Efficiency Scorecard, Italy ranked second at World level in terms of national efforts to improve its energy efficiency levels.

These Italian challenging energy efficiency targets are supported by a wide and comprehensive set of policy packages. These policies, both in the buildings and transport sectors, are subject to a complex governance scheme. In fact Italian energy issues are governed under a system of “concurrent legislative powers”. This means that the Regions have legislative powers over energy matters, except for the fundamental principles, which are determined by the central Government. The application of this constitutional provision has caused considerable difficulty in terms of harmonizing energy efficiency legislation.

Also the local level is very important for energy efficiency promotion both in the buildings and transport sectors. Municipal authorities in particular are responsible of important urban planning instruments deeply affecting the energy efficiency choices:

- Municipal buildings regulations (Regolamenti Edilizi). These planning instruments define compulsory energy efficiency rules for new and existing buildings;
- Traffic Plans and regulation of urban traffic (prohibition to access city centre for the most polluting vehicles, etc.).

However, in the last years there were fruitful legislative interventions aimed at improving the Italian energy efficiency governance. One of the most interesting experiences in energy efficiency governance improvements is related to the creation, among the Ministry of Economic Development, of the National Energy Efficiency Control Room (Cabina di Regia per l’Efficienza Energetica). Established in January 2015, it aims to coordinate all the different stakeholders (both in the public and private sectors) and administration levels (national and regional levels) operating in the Italian energy efficiency market.

At national level, in relation to the buildings sector, the main energy efficiency policy packages could be grouped into 4 main families:

- Minimum energy performance standards for buildings (Regulatory Standards);
- Energy efficiency market instruments (energy savings tradable certificates);
- Tax deductions for improving energy efficiency in buildings;
- Economic incentives for the promotion of energy efficiency technology in private and public buildings.

In relation to the buildings sector, Italy has two international excellences:

- White Certificates. Italy, in 2005, was the first country in the World to adopt such an energy efficiency support scheme. To date, this tool is replicated also in other countries and the White Certificate Italian experience remains a landmark;
- Smart Meters. With more than 90% of total national population with a Smart Meter in their houses, Italy is one of the countries with the widest smart grid in the World.

Also in the transport sector comprehensive and wide policy packages are in place at national level. However, these transport energy efficiency policy packages are less homogeneous compared to buildings policies, and they are strictly related to the adoption in Italy of EU Directives.

1. THE ROLE OF GOVERNANCE AND ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICY PACKAGES ON THE NATIONAL LEVEL

1.1 POLICY PACKAGES AND POLICY GOVERNANCE IN ITALY

The Italian Energy Efficiency overall strategy is defined in two main national official documents:

- **Italian Energy Efficiency Action Plan (NEEAP)**, first published in 2007 and reviewed in 2011 and 2014;
- **National Energy Strategy (Strategia Energetica Nazionale - SEN)**, launched in 2013 by the Italian Ministry of Economic Development.

The two documents are quite different one from another. In fact, while in the NEEAP the reduction target has been set on the basis of a minimum percentage of savings compared with the reference consumption value, in the SEN the target is calculated as the difference between two possible evolution scenarios of the national energy system:

- The first, known as “No-measure scenario”, maps the evolution of the system in the event that all the energy efficiency support measures are suspended (this evolution includes none of the savings expected under the NEEAP after 2011);
- The second or “SEN Scenario”, instead, charts the system’s evolution under a package of energy efficiency measures (part of which are already included in the NEEAP) (NEEAP, 2014).

The NEEAP, whose first version dates back to 2007 and reviewed in 2011 and 2014, was elaborated by the “Italian National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development” (ENEA) and includes a series of energy efficiency targets (those related to the 20-20-20 strategy) and policy instruments aimed at achieving such targets¹. Particular attention is dedicated to the new policy measures introduced with the legislative decree 102/2014 (Dlgs. 4 July 2014, n. 102)², which acknowledges the EU Directive 2012/27. In the last NEEAP (2014 version), two main energy efficiency targets are identified (NEEAP, 2014):

- A medium-term target (2020);
- A long-term target up (2050).

The Italian NEEAP is developed in accordance with the guidelines defined in the EU Energy Efficiency Directive and in the “Guidance for National Energy Efficiency Action Plans” (European Commission, 2013). The Italian NEEAP has specific focuses both on buildings and transports, even if these objectives are not defined as compulsory.

The SEN³ instead, launched in 2013 by the Italian Ministry of Economic Development, is a voluntary document aimed to define a common strategy for the future of the Italian energy sector (both tradi-

¹ Available on line at: <http://www.ufficienzaenergetica.enea.it/doc/paee/PAEE-2014-definitivo.pdf>

² <http://www.normattiva.it/do/atto/vediPermalink?atto.dataPubblicazioneGazzetta=2014-07-18&atto.codiceRedazionale=14G00113>

³ Available on line at: http://www.sviluppoeconomico.gov.it/images/stories/normativa/20130314_Strategia_Energetica_Nazionale.pdf

tional and renewable energy sources). Energy efficiency is one of the seven SEN energy priorities (SEN, 2013).

In relation to the medium-term target, Italy aims to reduce **20 Mtoe** of primary energy by 2020 and **15 Mtoe** of final energy by 2020 under the EU Directive 2012/27/EU. The long-term target instead is not defined in the Italian NEEAP. However, an energy efficiency 2050 target is defined in the Italian SEN. Italy's National Energy Strategy (SEN) declares "primary consumption will have to fall in the range of **17-26%** by 2050 compared to 2010, by decoupling economic growth from energy consumption. In particular, efforts in building and transport will be critical" (SEN, 2013).

At national level, a further important document is constituted by the Italian National Logistics Plan (Piano Nazionale della Logistica – NLP) for the period 2011/2020, elaborated in 2010 within the Ministry of Infrastructures and Transportation⁴. This plan represents a synthesis of the policy interventions, which are defined by 10 strategic guidelines and 51 actions articulated in norms and regulations, to be implemented across all the different transport and logistic sectors. The document also includes the evaluation for each intervention considered by the plan (NLP, 2010).

In addition, the 6th National Communication of Italy (6NC)⁵ submitted to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) by the Italian Ministry of the Environment, Land and Sea⁶ (MATTM) and reporting the status of Convention on Climate Change, also reports energy efficiency targets and strategies at national level both in the transport and building sector.

It is also worth mentioning the national Annual Report (Notification of methodology) under Article 7 of Directive 2012/27/EU on energy efficiency obligation schemes. This national report⁷ concerned the progress towards meeting the national 2020 targets for improving energy efficiency. Last version of this report was elaborated in June 2014 by Italian Ministry of Economic Development, Directorate-General for electricity, market, renewable energy, energy efficiency and nuclear energy.

Finally, the document 17/2013 of the Italian Inter-ministerial Committee for the Economic Planning (CIPE, 2013), updates the national GHG reduction plan for the period 2003-2010 elaborated by the MATTM in collaboration with the Ministry of Economics and Finance (CIPE, 2002), which constitutes the guidelines of the Italian strategy for the Kyoto protocol.

1) Building Sector

Objectives

The Italian NEEAP, since its first edition in 2007, identifies the residential sector as the key contributor to the national energy efficiency targets. In the 2007 and 2011 NEEAPs in fact, two-thirds of the total Italian energy savings were entrusted to the residential and services sectors (De Paoli, 2013).

In the 2014 NEEAP, residential and services sectors are still key contributors to the national energy efficiency target, even if transport and industrial sectors are more deeply committed compared to the 2007 and 2011 NEEAP editions. Based on the expected energy savings defined in the 2014 NEEAP, two main targets are defined for the Italian residential sector for 2020 (NEEAP, 2014):

⁴ <http://www.mit.gov.it/mit/site.php>

⁵ http://unfccc.int/files/national_reports/annex_i_natcom/submitted_natcom/application/pdf/ita_nc6_resubmission.pdf

⁶ <http://www.minambiente.it/>

⁷ Available on line at: https://ec.europa.eu/energy/sites/ener/files/documents/article7_en_italy.pdf

- Residential **final energy consumption** target to 2020: **3,67 Mtoe/year** expected saving;
- Residential **primary energy consumption** target to 2020: **5,14 Mtoe/year** expected saving.

With reference to the primary energy savings target of the residential sector, the 2014 NEEAP highlights as “for the residential, services and industry sectors, the overall savings were estimated to be electricity for more than one fifth, and heat for the rest (assumption supported by the monitoring performed on the incentive instruments)”(NEEAP, 2014).

The same energy efficiency targets for the residential sector were defined in the National Energy Strategy (SEN). The SEN defines energy efficiency targets only in terms of final energy consumption. For the residential sector, the SEN defines a final energy consumption target to 2020 of **3-4 Mtoe/year** expected savings.

The Italian NEEAPs underline the key role of energy efficiency measures in the residential sector as a contributor for a better and stronger Italian economic development. As highlighted in the 2014 NEEAP document, “in these years of crisis, the building sector has managed to remain afloat thanks to the positive contribution of building maintenance (ordinary and, especially, extraordinary), which has partly offset the sector’s steep drop which started in 2008. Nowadays, two thirds of investments in the building sector relate to renovations of existing buildings, showing a by now well-settled trend towards the recovery of the building stock”. As the building sector is one of the most important Italian economic sectors (ANCE, 2012), the energy efficiency policy packages contribute to strengthen general national economic growth.

In its introduction, the 2014 NEEAP highlights also that “Italy’s energy prices are on an average higher than those of its European competitors”. By underlining this aspect in a national energy efficiency plan, it is possible to see the national legislator’s purpose to reduce energy consumption in the building sector not only as an energy efficiency measure, but also as a measure to reduce families’ energy bills and national energy poverty. This is particularly important for Italy, as between 5 and 20 per cent of households was in Energy Poverty in 2012 (Banca d’Italia, 2014).

Also the Italian National Energy Strategy (SEN) underlines the strong link existing between energy efficiency policies in the residential sector and more general objectives. In particular, the SEN underlines the important role of energy efficiency policies in:

- Reducing energy costs;
- Reducing emissions;
- Reducing environmental impact;
- Improving the safety and independence of energy supply;
- Supporting economic growth.

Synthesis of policy packages

In Italy, comprehensive policy packages targeting the buildings sector are in place. Italian energy efficiency policies focus more on the energy supply side than the demand side. This “supply side focus” is strictly related to political reasons. National authorities have often preferred supply side energy efficiency policies, as their results are generally more evident and faster to be obtained compared with energy demand side policies (De Paoli, 2014).

However, the main national energy efficiency policy packages have also tackled the energy demand side. One of the sectors in which energy demand is most targeted is the buildings sector. In fact several policies and instruments were adopted in Italy over the past three years to encourage final customers to change their habits in energy use. These policies are: incentives, grants or subsidies, the

provision of information, flagship/exemplary projects, workplace activities and education on energy saving.

Moreover, Italy is the leading country in the World for energy demand-side management in the building sector (NEEAP, 2014). In fact “Italy is the world’s leading country in the spread of smart-metering systems which are an essential component for the management/reduction of energy demand (demand-side management)” (NEEAP, 2014). Smart metering is a remote metering system based on a network of sensors for real-time monitoring of electricity, gas and water consumption. More than 90% of Italian families have a smart meter in their houses (NEEAP, 2014).

The Italian NEEAPs set out a number of measures and incentive schemes designed to achieve energy savings in all energy-using sectors. Energy efficiency measures concerning the building sector, in accordance with the 2014 NEEAP classification, can be grouped in four main policy components:

- **Minimum energy performance standards for buildings** (Regulatory Standards);
- **The energy efficiency certificates scheme** (White Certificates);
- **Tax deductions** for improving energy efficiency in buildings;
- **Economic incentives** for the promotion of energy efficiency technologies in private and public buildings (Thermal Account and National Energy Efficiency Fund for the public authorities).

As evidenced in the SEN energy efficiency policies summary (Fig.1), the buildings sector (both residential and services) is targeted by all the four main Italian energy efficiency instrument categories (SEN, 2013).

Fig. 1 Energy-efficiency instruments available in the different sectors of intervention.

Sector	Main instruments				Relevance
	Normative/ Standards	White Certificates (TEE)	Incentives (Heating Account)	Tax relief	
Residential	New [†]	✓	✓	✓	✓
Services	New [†]	✓	✓	✓	✓
Public Sector	New [†]	✓	✓	-	✓
Industry	-	✓	-	-	-
Transport	✓	✓	-	-	-

Source: SEN 2013

Target groups

According to the Italian main buildings national energy efficiency policies, the main target groups are:

- Residential buildings (new and existing);
- Public buildings (new and existing);
- Services buildings (new and existing);
- Industrial buildings (new and existing).

The energy efficiency policies and measures are designed to take into account the potential of all final energy consumption sectors in energy saving and energy efficiency. In particular, increasing ener-

gy efficiency in the buildings sector is one the main target of both the NEEAP and the SEN. In fact, as highlighted in the 2014 NEEAP, the buildings sector (residential and service) is expected to achieve a final energy saving of about **4,9 Mtoe/year** by 2020 (5,10 Mtoe/year for the industry sector and 5,50 Mtoe/year for the transport sector). This is a very relevant energy efficiency contribution required from the building sector at national level.

The Regional and local levels are not directly targeted by energy efficiency specific targets. In fact a compulsory **regional burden sharing system** was foreseen only for renewable energies targets (Energy Strategy Group, 2014).

Moreover, the Italian 2014 NEEAP emphasizes the importance of the promotion of energy efficiency in public buildings of national, regional and local authorities. In fact, as evidenced in the NEEAP energy efficiency forecast to 2020, the energy upgrading of public buildings at all levels will contribute to an energy saving of **458 GWh/year** from 2014 to 2020.

Fig. 2 Total energy savings expected by the energy efficiency improvements of existing public buildings by 2020.

Year	Floor area subject to the obligation to improve energy efficiency (m ²)	Total Consumption (GWh/y)	Savings (GWh/y)							Total savings by 2020 (GWh/y)
			2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	
2014	412,919	62.8	17.0	17.0	17.0	17.0	17.0	17.0	17.0	119.1
2015	407,090	61.9		16.8	16.8	16.8	16.8	16.8	16.8	100.7
2016	401,633	61.1			16.6	16.6	16.6	16.6	16.6	82.8
2017	389,977	59.3				16.1	16.1	16.1	16.1	64.3
2018	378,671	57.6					15.6	15.6	15.6	46.8
2019	367,705	55.9						15.2	15.2	30.3
2020	357,067	54.3							14.7	14.7
Total	2,715,061	413.0	17.0	33.8	50.4	66.4	82.0	97.2	111.9	458.7

Source: ENEA using data from the Public Domain Agency

In relation to end-users, the Italian NEEAP 2014 foresees a series of information and training campaigns directed to public sector employees (in particular in schools), banks and financial institutes, SMEs and the general public.

Governance framework

The general role of energy efficiency policies in Italy is related to the achievement of the European "20-20-20 targets" by 2020.

Italy has a long-standing experience with energy efficiency policies. In the first Italian "National Energy Programme" (Programma Energetico Nazionale) dated 1975, although the main focus was on the energy-supply side and nuclear power promotion, there was an attachment dedicated to energy savings, with a specific focus on buildings sector. This document constituted the base for the first Italian

law on energy efficiency in buildings dated 1976⁸. The importance of energy efficiency was strengthened in the following National Energy Programmes, in particular in the third edition (1981) with a specific law on energy savings and in the 1988 edition where energy saving was identified as one of the first Italian energy objectives. Thus Italy, since the first '80s, has shown a relevant policy activity aimed at promoting energy efficiency for the buildings sector.

Italy's first-moving on energy efficiency policies allowed to define some successful measures and policies earlier than the European legislation framework was established. It is the case of the White Certificates mechanism, adopted in Italy during 2004-2005, first country in the World to adopt such a scheme (NEEAP, 2007). Today, the Italian energy efficiency regulations are totally compliant with European legislation, despite some difficulties in the adoption of some Directives into the national legislative context (ENEA, 2015).

The Italian energy efficiency governance model in the buildings sector is very complex (De Paoli, 2013), as several national and regional actors are involved both in defining general strategies and setting technical and regulatory schemes. In fact, national laws entrust the management of different energy efficiency sectorial aspects to different political bodies at different scales, on the basis of the European subsidiarity principle.

In Italy, the energy efficiency policy in the building sector involves 4 of the 16 Italian ministries:

- **Ministry of the Environment and Protection of Land and Sea (MATTM)**. MATTM⁹ (Ministero dell'Ambiente e della Tutela del Territorio e del Mare) is responsible for sustainable development, protection of territory, pollution and industrial risks, international protection of the environment, appraisal of environmental impact, nature conservation, waste and cleanup, and protection of seas and inland waters. Its main roles in the buildings sector are related to the definition of the overall national buildings energy efficiency strategies/objectives and to the setting of the general buildings energy efficiency legislative frameworks. Moreover MATTM has an important role in defining and promoting national energy efficiency in buildings awareness campaigns;
- **Ministry of Economy and Finance (MEF)**. MEF¹⁰ (Ministero dell'Economia e delle Finanze) is responsible "for national economic, financial and budget policy, planning of public investment, coordinating public expenditure and verifying its trends, revenue policies and tax system. It operates the State's public land and heritage, land register and customs; it plans, coordinates and verifies operations to foster economic, local and sectoral development, and is responsible for setting out cohesion policies. The Ministry performs a supervisory role over entities and activities as well as performing such functions as concern its relations with supervisory and regulatory authorities"¹¹. Its main role in building sector is to define, develop and manage economic and financial supporting schemes aimed to promote and strengthen energy efficiency measures in the buildings sector. Moreover it collaborates with others Ministries to the definition of the overall national building energy efficiency strategies and objectives;

⁸ L. 30 April 1976, n. 373

⁹ <http://www.minambiente.it/>

¹⁰ <http://www.tesoro.it/english-corner/index.html>

¹¹ <http://www.tesoro.it/english-corner/index.html>

- **Ministry of Economic Development (MISE).** MISE¹² (Ministero dello Sviluppo Economico) is responsible for a wide range of policies, including economic development and cohesion, energy and mineral resources, telecommunications, internationalization, tourism and business incentives. Its main roles in the building sector are related to the definition of buildings energy efficiency technical regulation schemes and to monitoring the performances of implemented policies. Moreover it collaborates with other Ministries to the definition of the overall national buildings energy efficiency strategies and objectives;
- **Ministry for regional affairs** (ministry without a dedicated budget)¹³. This Ministry (Ministro per gli affari regionali) is under the direct control of the National Government. Its main role in the building sector is related to the coordination of the energy efficiency policies across the national and regional levels.

Italian Ministries, in their activities related to the promotion of energy efficiency in the building sector, are supported by two national technical authorities:

- **Energy Service Operator (GSE)¹⁴.** GSE (Gestore Servizi Energetici) is the state-owned company which promotes and supports the diffusion of renewable energy sources in Italy. In particular, GSE fosters sustainable development by providing support for renewable electricity generation and by taking actions to build awareness of environmentally-efficient energy uses. GSE plays a crucial role in Italian building energy efficiency promotion, since it represents the managing authority of two of the most important financial supporting schemes: White Certificates¹⁵ and Thermal Account¹⁶;
- **Italian Regulatory Authority for Electricity Gas and Water (AEEG)¹⁷.** AEEG (Autorità per l'energia elettrica, il gas e il sistema idrico) is "an independent body established under Law 481 of 14 November 1995 to regulate and control the electricity and gas sectors"¹⁸. Its regulatory powers include the setting of tariffs, as well as the definition the standard of service quality and the technical and economic conditions governing access and interconnections to the networks for those services where technical, legal or other constraints would interfere with normal competitive market conditions. It also controls the ability of the market for protecting the interests of users and consumers.

Beside the national level, Regional and municipal authorities also play a central role in defining and implementing Italian buildings energy efficiency policies. The main local actors in buildings energy efficiency policies definition and management are:

¹² <http://www.sviluppoeconomico.gov.it/index.php/en/>

¹³ <http://www.affariregionali.it/>

¹⁴ <http://www.gse.it/en/company/Pages/default.aspx>

¹⁵ The Decree of 28 Dec. 2012 provides that the activities of management, evaluation and certification of the savings associated with energy efficiency projects under the white certificates schemes shall be transferred from AEEG to GSE as of 3 Feb. 2013. See: <http://www.gse.it/en/White%20Certificates/Pages/default.aspx>

¹⁶ http://www.gse.it/en/Heating_Cooling/Pages/default.aspx

¹⁷ <http://www.autorita.energia.it/it/inglese/about/presentazione.htm>

¹⁸ <http://www.autorita.energia.it/it/inglese/about/presentazione.htm>

- **Regional authorities**¹⁹. Italy has 20 different regional authorities²⁰. Regional authorities play a crucial role on the implementation of Italian building energy efficiency policies. In fact, Regions have specific competencies on building energy efficiency planning and technical regulation. In particular each Region has its own “Regional Energy Plan” with a specific section dedicated to energy efficiency in the building sector. Moreover Regional authorities have specific competencies in defining and controlling the building energy certifications. In particular, the main competencies of regional authorities are related to technical definition and monitoring of regional energy efficiency certification schemes, training and accreditation of operators realizing energy efficiency certifications, monitoring and control (through inspections) of buildings energy efficiency certifications and qualified energy efficiency operators and collection of policy implementation data;
- **Provincial authorities/Metropolitan cities**. Italy had more than 100 provincial authorities but they were abolished in 2014²¹ and replaced by 10 “Metropolitan cities” authorities. These provincial/metropolitan authorities do not assume a specific role in defining energy efficiency policy in buildings. Some provincial authorities have adopted provincial energy efficiency plans with a specific focus on buildings. Other provincial authorities, like in the Milan Provincial case study analyzed in HERON report 1.2, played a crucial role in defining innovative energy efficiency financial mechanisms;
- **Municipal authorities**. The role of Italian municipalities in implementing buildings energy efficiency policies and measures is also important. Municipal authorities are responsible of the definition of the buildings regulation in more than 8.000 Italian municipalities. Moreover, Italian municipalities are the most active at European level in the Covenant of Mayors. According to the data provided by the Covenant of Mayors at 30 July 2015, 2.598 Italian municipalities result with an approved Sustainable Energy Action Plan (SEAP).

Italian Regions can define their buildings energy efficiency regulation mechanisms and schemes, therefore each of them has its energy efficiency laws in the buildings sector. As this proliferation of buildings regulatory schemes represented an important barrier to energy efficiency in the sector (Energy Strategy Group, 2013), in June 2015 the Italian Parliament approved 3 norms to create a common national buildings regulatory framework²².

In order to create a strong and clear dialogue among the different levels of responsibilities, several coordination mechanisms within, between and across different levels of government were defined. These coordination mechanisms can be grouped in the following 4 categories:

¹⁹ <http://www.fficienzaenergetica.enea.it/l-fficienza-energetica-nelle-regioni/>

²⁰ Among these regions, there are five autonomous regions with special statute (namely Sardinia, Sicily, Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol, Aosta Valley and Friuli-Venezia Giulia) with specific legislative competencies also in the buildings energy efficiency regulation.

²¹ On April, 3rd 2014 the Italian Chamber of Deputies approved Law n.56/2014, which transformed Italian provinces into institutional bodies of second level with no dedicated budgets and specific roles.

²² <http://www.regionieambiente.it/energia/fficienza/2121-pubblicati-i-decreti-di-completamento-del-quadro-normativo-sullefficienza-energetica-degli-edifici.html>

- Horizontal coordination mechanisms at national level among different ministries and among political and technical offices (“National Energy Efficiency Control Room” “Cabina di Regia per l’efficienza energetica”);
- Vertical coordination mechanisms among national and regional levels (“Unified State-Regions Conference” “Conferenza Stato Regioni”);
- Vertical coordination among regional and local levels (for example in the consultation processes set by Regional authorities during the preparation of their Regional Energy and Environmental Plans);
- Coordination among public authorities and private sector (Thematic tables at all levels).

Two main energy efficiency coordination mechanisms have been defined at national level:

- **National Energy Efficiency Control Room** (Cabina di Regia per l’efficienza energetica);
- **Unified State-Regions Conference** (Conferenza Unificata Stato Regioni).

Launched in January 2015 by the Ministry of Economic Development (D.I. 9 January 2015), the “National Energy Efficiency Control Room” aims to coordinate all the different stakeholders operating on energy efficiency in Italy. The most innovative aspect of this new national coordination office is the involvement of all the national ministries with competencies on energy efficiency, the national energy efficiency technical offices, the representatives of the Regions and representatives of the private sector as banks, energy efficiency operators and other interested subjects with competences on energy efficiency themes. Two of the main missions of the “National Energy Efficiency Control Room” are to manage the National Energy Efficiency Fund and to define a general plan for an energy efficiency renewal of public buildings at national and regional levels.

Fig. 3 Scheme summarizing the general functioning of the “National Energy Efficiency Control Room” (Cabina di Regia per l’efficienza energetica).

Source: IEFE-Bocconi University elaboration.

The Unified State-Regions Conference (Conferenza Unificata Stato-Regioni) instead is a permanent institution set in 1997²³ in order to improve the dialogue among national, regional and local levels. This institutional body is not dedicated to energy efficiency, as it has competences on several normative aspects. However, since Regions have several exclusive competences on energy efficiency, the Unified State-Regions Conference has often been used to define and set energy efficiency policies and measures.

At national level, there are two main technical organizations with a key role in the definition of Italian buildings energy efficiency policies and measures. These key national technical organizations are:

- **Organization for New Technologies, Energy and the Environment (ENEA).** ENEA²⁴ (Agenzia Nazionale per le Nuove Tecnologie, l’Energia e lo Sviluppo Economico Sostenibile) is the national energy agency. ENEA performs research activities and provides agency services in support to public administrations, public and private enterprises, and citizens. Specifically, ENEA is concerned with energy efficiency, renewable energy sources and nuclear energy;
- **National Research Council (CNR).** CNR²⁵ (Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche) is the largest public research institution in Italy, the only one under the Research Ministry which performs

²³ http://www.statoregioni.it/home_UNI.asp?CONF=UNI

²⁴ <http://www.enea.it/en>

²⁵ http://www.cnr.it/sitocnr/Englishversion/brochureCNR_ENG.pdf

multidisciplinary activities. Its role is to promote innovation and competitiveness of the national industrial system, to promote the internationalization of the national research system as well as to provide technologies and solutions to emerging public and private needs.

These two technical organizations are steadily consulted by national public authorities in order to define energy efficiency policies and measures. At regional and local level, this technical support to public authorities is provided by several regional and/or provincial/local energy agencies. Regional, provincial and local energy agencies are grouped into the national RENAEL association²⁶ (Italian network of Local Energy Agencies). Based on ManagEnergy²⁷ project data, in Italy there are several regional, provincial and local Energy Agencies.

There are also non-governmental and market actors with relevant roles in promoting energy efficiency in the building sector. Main non-governmental and market actors are:

- ESCOs. Italy already has a number of certification schemes for operators and services in the field of energy efficiency and one specifically for ESCOs. As highlighted in the 2014 NEEAP, “the ESCO sector in Italy is somewhat diverse, with 1.900 units registered by the Italian Regulatory Authority for Electricity Gas and Water (AEEG) in 2011. In actual fact, the companies operating routinely in the sector (in particular within the White Certificates scheme) are just 15% of the total (about 390 operators)”(NEEAP, 2014);
- Financial institutions. Italian financial institutions are also involved in the energy efficiency governance framework. Financial institutions, through their national association ABI (Associazione Bancaria Italiana)²⁸, have a supporting and consulting role in the “National Energy Efficiency Control Room”;
- Expert/industrial associations. Italian energy consultants are involved in energy efficiency national governance models. In particular national energy managers, through FIRE association²⁹, the federation which looks after and represents the professional interests of Italian Energy Managers, play an relevant role in encouraging the rational use of energy in Italy;
- Consumer and environmental associations. Environmental associations (Legambiente³⁰, etc.) and some consumers associations conduct over years several public awareness campaigns aimed at promoting energy efficiency among final energy consumers. Specific campaigns³¹ were dedicated to energy efficiency in the building sector.
- National electricity and gas distributors. Several national electricity and gas distributors (ENEL, ENI and several Multi-utilities) have launched several awareness campaigns aimed at promoting energy efficiency in the building sector.

²⁶ <http://www.renael.net/ITA/chisiamo.aspx>

²⁷ http://www.managenergy.net/countries/26#name_regional

²⁸ <https://www.abi.it/Pagine/default.aspx>

²⁹ <http://www.fire-italia.org/fire-in-english/>

³⁰ <http://www.legambiente.it/>

³¹ See for example the campaign “Tutti in Classe A”. More information available on: <http://www.legambiente.it/contenuti/dossier/tutti-classe-A>

These non-governmental and market actors, as well as sub-national authorities, were largely involved in the designing and setting of the Italian Energy Efficiency Action Plan and National Energy Strategy. The National Energy Strategy, for instance, was the outcome of “an extensive public consultation, through a wide involvement of all the stakeholders. During the two months of public consultation, meetings have been organized at the Ministry of Economic Development with more than 100 stakeholders among institutions, industry associations, social partners and trade unions, research and study centers” (SEN, 2013).

2) Transport Sector

Objectives

Since the first NEEAP in 2007, the energy efficiency effort required from the transport sector has steadily grown. This growing effort is deeply related to the high level of energy inefficiency of the Italian transport sector (NEEAP, 2014). Based on the 2014 NEEAP energy efficiency expected savings to 2020, the biggest national effort in terms of national final energy savings has been requested to the transport sector. Also in terms of primary energy savings the contribution required from the transport sector is high.

The 2014 NEEAP national long-term energy efficiency targets for the transport sector are:

- Transport final energy consumption target to 2020: **5.50 Mtoe/year** expected saving;
- Transport primary energy consumption target to 2020: **6.05 Mtoe/year** expecting saving.

Another long-term general target regarding energy efficiency in the transport sector is defined in the 2013 National Energy Strategy (SEN). The SEN sets that “primary energy consumption will have to fall in the range of **17-26%** by **2050** compared to 2010, by decoupling economic growth from energy consumption. In particular, efforts in building and transport will be critical”.

It is important to mention, as highlighted in the 2014 NEEAP, that “in the transport sector, the entire savings were assumed to have been made in the form of oil products”.

Many transport sectorial objectives have been launched in Italy in order to be compliant with European legal provisions on the theme (ENEA, 2015). For example, all the Italian legislation related to CO₂ cars’ emissions is compliant with the European Regulation 333/2014.

There are several other transport energy efficiency objectives defined in some sectorial national planning instruments:

- **Electrification of the transport sector (2050 target).** The “National infrastructures plan to set up electric vehicle charging points”³² (PNIRE) defines some medium and long-term objectives. The PNIRE foresees “a substantial increase in the degree of electrification, which will almost double by 2050, reaching at least **38%**, particularly in electricity and transport”. This will contribute achieving the decarbonisation goals in the Italian transport sector;
- **Renewable energy targets in the transport sector (2020 target).** The Italian legislative decree 28/2011 (Dlgs. 3 March 2011, n.28) on renewable energy promotion defines that “the share of energy from renewable sources in all forms of transport has to be in 2020 at least **10%** of final energy consumption of the transport sector in the same year”;
- **More efficient logistic sector.** Italy’s National Plan for Logistics 2011-2020 defines several qualitative 2020 targets for the national logistic sector. In particular, it defines sectorial and specific targets regarding the strengthening of national transport infrastructures, the reduction of travels with empty lorries, etc.;
- **Economic development.** As the people and freights transport sector represents a significant quota of Italian GDP³³, the relaunch of the transport sector through a more efficient organization of the infrastructures and institutional frameworks is seen at national level as a fun-

³² http://www.mit.gov.it/mit/mop_all.php?p_id=14588

³³ http://www.mit.gov.it/mit/mop_all.php?p_id=23271

damental way to improve Italian economic development. See for example the 2015 National Strategic Plan for ports and logistics and the strong focus on economic development of the country (Ministry of Transport, 2015).

Synthesis of policy packages

In Italy there are comprehensive policy packages targeting supply as well as demand in the transport sector. Transport supply targets are often set in terms of improvements of transport infrastructures (Energy Efficiency Watch, 2013) and/or in terms of local transport services activated.

Transport demand targets instead are often defined in terms of reduction of private travels and freights transferred in a defined time period (ENEA, 2011). The reduction of person and freights demand is perceived as a priority in the Italian legislative framework but at the moment no specific targets are in place.

The components of Italian policies concerning the three main transport dimensions are:

- **Vehicle efficiency dimension.** This dimension is fully considered by the Italian policy framework. In Italy, CO₂ vehicles' emissions standards are in place (compliant with European prescriptions), municipalities have set several limits to polluting vehicles acceding to city centers (Euromobility, 2014) and there are strategic plans (at national and regional levels) and funds aimed to renew public transport fleets;
- **Travel efficiency dimension.** This dimension is often analyzed in the Italian transport policy framework. The increase of efficiency of travels in the logistic sector for example, is perceived as one of the first objectives in the National Logistic Strategic Plan, as several lorries travel with no or few freights. Also in local public transport services the improvement of the quality and efficiency of single travels is seen as a priority in order to attract more people on public transport services and to improve the economics of services (ISFORT, 2014);
- **System efficiency dimension.** Despite the significant national transport infrastructures delays compared to other European countries (Ministry of Transport, 2013), Italy has set several thematic Plans and funds to improve the transport infrastructures and the general system efficiency dimension.

Target groups

Italian transport policies have two main target groups:

- Passengers (both private and public transports);
- Freight transport (at different scale, from urban to national dimension).

In particular the main target groups of Italian energy efficiency policies in the transport sector are the owners of most pollutant vehicles, the public transport services with low rate of efficiency, managing authorities of main Italian transport infrastructures and public authorities.

In relation to end-users, the Italian NEEAP 2014 foresees a series of information and training campaigns directed to public sector employees (in particular in schools), banks and financial institutes, SMEs and the general public.

Moreover, as highlighted in the 2013 publication "Energy Efficiency in Europe, Assessment of Energy Efficiency Action Plans and Policies in EU Member States" (Energy Efficiency Watch, 2013), the

transport sector has a marginal role in the Italian Energy Efficiency Action Plan (NEEAP), as very few measures concerning this sector are described in the NEEAP.

Governance framework

The Italian transport governance is extremely complicated as the competencies are fragmented among national, regional, provincial and local levels. Several relevant actors are involved in the formulation/delivery/evaluation of the transport energy efficiency policy instruments. A central role in transport national regulations is played by the Ministry of Transport and by the National Transport Authority settled in 2013. At sub-national level, the regional authorities have specific competencies on public transport services management. At local level municipalities have specific competencies on implementing solutions for more efficient people and freights transport (through their mobility and traffic plans).

At national level, three ministries are involved in promotion of energy efficiency policies and measures in the transport sector:

- **Ministry of Infrastructure and Transport (MIT).** MIT³⁴ (*Ministero delle Infrastrutture e dei Trasporti*) is responsible for the planning and management of all Italian transport infrastructures (motorways, roads, ports, airports, railways). The main role of MIT in the transport sector is related to the definition of overall public transport and logistics national strategies and planning instruments, especially for urban transport schemes. In particular MIT main duties in the transport sector are:
 - Planning the infrastructural networks and the works for the modal integration between different transportation systems;
 - Navigation and maritime transport, supervision on ports, maritime government property, safety navigation and inland water transport;
 - Land transport, traffic and land transports safety;
 - Air transport, discipline and rules, address, supervision of the sector institutions.
- **Ministry of Economic Development (MISE).** MISE³⁵ (*Ministero dello Sviluppo Economico*) is responsible for a wide range of policies, including economic development and cohesion, energy and natural resources, telecommunications, internationalization, tourism and business incentives. Its main role in the transport sector is in defining economic and financial supporting schemes aimed at promoting energy efficiency in people and freights transport solutions. Moreover, it collaborates with other ministries in defining overall national transport strategies and plans.
- **Ministry of the Environment and Protection of Land and Sea (MATTM).** MATTM³⁶ (*Ministero dell'Ambiente e della Tutela del Territorio e del Mare*) is responsible for sustainable development, protection of territory, pollution and industrial risks, international protection of the environment, appraisal of environmental impact, nature conservation, waste and clean-

³⁴ <http://www.mit.gov.it/mit/site.php>

³⁵ <http://www.sviluppoeconomico.gov.it/index.php/en/>

³⁶ <http://www.minambiente.it/>

up, and protection of seas and inland waters. In the transport sector, MATTM collaborates with other in-charge ministries in defining and preparing overall transport national energy efficiency strategies and measures.

At present, no coordination mechanisms purposely regarding the transport sector are in place. The Italian Ministry of Transport, in the 2015 “Strategic plan for the development of ports and logistics”³⁷, expresses the need to simplify the national transport governance model (Ministry of Transport, 2015) and to define new and more efficient coordination mechanisms among the different bodies with specific competences on transports.

At national level, there are other relevant actors with important legislative and advisory roles. The main actors participating to the national transport governance system are:

- **National Transport Authority.** The main role of the National Transport Authority³⁸ (Autorità di regolazione dei trasporti) is to promote and protect high competition levels in the following sectors: Railways, ports, airports, toll motorways, passenger and freights transport. Even though the National Transport Authority does not have specific competencies for improving the energy efficiency of Italian transport, its measures could indirectly contribute to increase the efficiency level of people and freights transport services;
 - **Port Authorities.** Italy has 23 Port Authorities, controlled by the Port Authorities General Command under the competence of the Ministry of Transport. They are fully responsible of the management activities of the port. Even though Port Authorities do not have specific competencies on improving the energy efficiency of Italian ship transport, their measures could indirectly contribute to the improvement of the efficiency levels of ships transport services;
 - **Airport managing authorities.** Italian airports are public properties whose management is given in concession to private operators. Many of these private dealers of Italian airports adopt energy efficiency measures in their structures;
 - **Organization for New Technologies, Energy and the Environment (ENEA).** ENEA performs research activities and provides agency services in support to public administrations, public and private enterprises, and citizens. Specifically, ENEA is concerned with energy efficiency, renewable energy sources, nuclear energy.
- National Research Council (CNR).** CNR³⁹ is the largest public research institution in Italy, the only one under the Research Ministry performing multidisciplinary activities . Its role is to promote innovation and competitiveness of the national industrial system, to promote the internationalization of the national research system, to provide technologies and solutions to emerging public and private needs.

In Italy regional and local authorities play a crucial role in promoting more sustainable and energy efficient transport. In particular:

³⁷ <http://www.mit.gov.it/mit/site.php?p=cm&o=vd&id=4027>

³⁸ <http://www.autorita-trasporti.it/>

³⁹ <http://www.cnr.it/sitocnr/Englishversion/Englishversion.html>

- **Regional authorities.** Italian Regions have exclusive competencies on local public transports. Funds for local public transport services are established at national level. These national funds are used for the functioning of the local transport services which in Italy are commonly managed through concessions mechanisms;
- **Provincial/Metropolitan City authorities.** Provincial authorities have specific competencies on planning and management of extra-urban transport services. These activities include also the management of public tenders for the entrustment of these services to private operators. Moreover some provincial authorities have a Provincial transport plan aimed to improve the provision of public transport services at provincial level;
- **Municipal authorities.** In Italy municipalities play a crucial role in promoting energy efficiency in people and freights transport sector. In particular municipal authorities could act on improving the energy efficiency of transport through:
 - **Urban Traffic Plan (PUT).** The PUT is a mandatory plan for any municipality with more than 30.000 inhabitants. These plans set several measures for energy efficiency gains of public and freights transports. Moreover, as evidenced in OECD report⁴⁰, “most local Italian administrators have not addressed the problem of urban goods transport. The current Guidelines for Urban Traffic Plans, the planning instrument for urban transport in Italy which was introduced in 1986, does not propose strategies for urban goods transport, although the relevance of freight transport is recognized”;
 - **Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans (SUMPS).** Many Italian municipalities have adopted a Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan;
 - **Urban traffic regulation measures.** Municipal authorities have the power to introduce congestion charge (as for example in Milan), introduce restricted access areas to the city center, fix vehicle’s pollutant emissions limits, etc.

⁴⁰ OECD (2003), Delivering the Goods. 21st Century Challenges to Urban Goods Transport. <http://www.internationaltransportforum.org/pub/pdf/03DeliveringGoods.pdf>

1.2 NATIONAL PROGRAMMES AND INITIATIVES

The main national programmes and initiatives targeting energy efficiency in the buildings sector are summarized in the following table.

Table 1 Policy instruments for energy efficiency in the building sector in Italy

Policy instruments for energy efficiency in the building sector in Italy	
Regulatory policy instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Energy performance in buildings. Transposition of EPBD and EPBD recast EU directives (Dlgs. 19 August 2005, n. 192⁴¹, modified with Dlgs. 30 May 2008, n. 115⁴²; L. 3 August 2013, n. 90)⁴³; · Transposition of the Energy Efficiency Directive 2012/27/EU (Dlgs. 4 July 2014, n. 102)⁴⁴; · Rules for implementing the national energy plan in the field of rational use of energy, energy saving and development of renewable energy sources (L. 9 January 1991, n. 10)⁴⁵; · Regulation on Accreditation of Italian Energy Certifiers (D.P.R. 16 April 2013, n. 75)⁴⁶; · Green Public Procurement. Minimum Environmental Criteria for several appliances related to buildings, in particular public lighting and energy services for buildings (D.M.10 April 2013, n. 102)⁴⁷; · Energy labeling of households appliances (Dlgs. 28 June 2012, n. 104)⁴⁸; · Simplification/exemption of authorization procedures for some energy efficiency measures (municipal level);

⁴¹ www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto.legislativo:2005-08-19;192!vig=

⁴² www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto.legislativo:2008-05-30;115!vig=

⁴³ www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:legge:2013-08-03;90!vig=

⁴⁴ www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto.legislativo:2014-07-04;102!vig=

⁴⁵ www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:legge:1991-01-09;10!vig=

⁴⁶ www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto.del.presidente.della.repubblica:2013-04-16;75!vig=

⁴⁷ www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto.legge:2013-08-31;102!vig=

⁴⁸ www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto.legislativo:2012-06-28;104!vig=

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Regional Regulatory Schemes on energy efficiency in buildings (regional level); · Municipal buildings regulations (municipal level).
Dissemination and awareness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Pilot Projects on multi service smart metering (Deliberation 19 September 2013, 393/2013/R/gas of the AEEG)⁴⁹; · Transparent billing methods (Deliberation 18 November 2008 – ARG/com 164/08 of the AEEG)⁵⁰; · National Green Procurement Plan (“Piano d’Azione Nazionale per il GPP”) (D.M.10 April 2013, n. 102)⁵¹; · ENEA website “Obiettivo efficienza energetica” (Target: energy efficiency)⁵²; · Several dissemination/awareness campaigns on specific energy efficiency themes (all experiences are mapped in the NEEAP – National Energy Efficiency Action Plan 2014)⁵³; · Buildings energy efficiency voluntary certification schemes and environmental voluntary certification schemes (Casa Clima⁵⁴, Protocollo Itaca⁵⁵, LEED⁵⁶, etc.); · Sustainable Energy Action Plans (SEAPs) (municipal level).

⁴⁹ <http://www.autorita.energia.it/allegati/docs/13/393-13.pdf>

⁵⁰ <http://www.autorita.energia.it/allegati/docs/08/164-08arg.pdf>

⁵¹ www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto.legge:2013-08-31;102!vig=

⁵² <http://www.energiaenergetica.enea.it/>

⁵³ <http://www.energiaenergetica.enea.it/politiche-e-strategie-1/politiche-e-strategie-in-italia/paee/paee-2014.aspx>

⁵⁴ <http://www.klimahaus.it/en/climatehouse/1-0.html>

⁵⁵ <http://www.itaca.org/index.asp>

⁵⁶ <http://www.gbcitalia.org/page/show/sistemi-di-verifica-nuova-pagina>

Economic policy instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Thermal Account⁵⁷ (D.M. 28 December 2012)⁵⁸; · Tax deductions (introduced with L. 27 December 2006, n. 296⁵⁹, namely the Budget Law 2007 – “Legge finanziaria 2007”, and renewed several times with modifications); · White Certificates (or Energy Efficiency Certificates) scheme and Obligation for national energy distributors (D.M. 20 July 2004)⁶⁰; · Kyoto Fund (introduced with L. 27 December 2006, n. 296⁶¹, namely the Budget Law 2007 – “Legge finanziaria 2007”, and implemented through following acts); · National Fund for Energy Efficiency (“Fondo Nazionale per l’Efficienza Energetica”) (Dlgs. 4 July 2014, n. 102)⁶²; · Measures for the energy efficiency in schools (“Misure per l’efficientamento energetico degli edifici scolastici”) (D.I. 14 April 2015, n. 66)⁶³; · Fund for home purchase and/or renovation (“Plafond Casa”) (Cassa Depositi e Prestiti) (D.L. 31 August 2013, n. 102⁶⁴, converted into L. 28 October 2013, n. 124⁶⁵).
Capacity building	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Integrated plan for the uptake of energy efficiency (“Piano integrato di diffusione dell’efficienza energetica”, PIDEE) (Dlgs. 4 July 2014, n. 102)⁶⁶; · General conference on Energy Efficiency (“Stati Generali Efficienza Energetica”⁶⁷ (ENEA);

⁵⁷ Incentive mechanism for small projects designed to increase energy efficiency and generate thermal energy from renewable sources.

⁵⁸ http://www.gse.it/it/Conto%20Termico/GSE_Documenti/DM_28_DICEMBRE_2012_CONTO_TERMICO.PDF

⁵⁹ www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:legge:2006-12-27;296!vig=

⁶⁰ http://www.sviluppoeconomico.gov.it/images/stories/normativa/DM_Certificati_bianchi_28_dicembre_2012.pdf

⁶¹ www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:legge:2006-12-27;296!vig=

⁶² www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto.legislativo:2014-07-04;102!vig=

⁶³ www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto.legislativo:2015-05-07;66!vig=

⁶⁴ www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto.legge:2013-08-31;102!vig=

⁶⁵ www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:legge:2013-10-28;124!vig=

⁶⁶ www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto.legislativo:2014-07-04;102!vig=

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · ENEA training platform and e-learning courses for experts on energy efficiency in buildings⁶⁸.
Policy instruments for the promotion of energy services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Definition of ESCOs and set-up of a voluntary national certification scheme for certified ESCOs (Dlgs. 30 May 2008, n. 115)⁶⁹.
Research and Development and BAT promotion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · National Electric System Research (ENEA, CNR and RSE carry out R&D activities on urgent and strategic issues which have results for the benefit of the national electric system users as a whole); · National “Smart Cities and Communities and Social Innovation” funds (2012 and 2013) (Director Decree 5 July 2012, N.391/Ric)⁷⁰; · National prize for energy efficiency measures (GSE’s “Premio Efficienza Energetica”)⁷¹; · ENEA reports on energy efficiency best available technologies⁷².

The main national programmes and initiatives targeting energy efficiency in the transport sector are summarized in the following table.

Table 2 Policy instruments for energy efficiency in the transport sector in Italy

Policy instruments for energy efficiency in the transport sector in Italy	
Planning Instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Italy's National Plan for Logistics 2011/2020 (Piano Nazionale della Logistica 2011-2020) (Ministry of Transport note prot. 567/CGA 30 may 2012)⁷³; · National Strategic Plan for Ports and Logistic (Piano

⁶⁷ <http://www.statigeneralefficienzaenergetica.it/>

⁶⁸ <http://www.formazione.enea.it/>

⁶⁹ www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto.legislativo:2008-05-30;115!vig=

⁷⁰ <http://attiministeriali.miur.it/anno-2012/luglio/dd-05072012.aspx>

⁷¹ <http://www.gse.it/it/Conto%20Energia/Fotovoltaico/Premio%20efficienza%20energetica/Pages/default.aspx>

⁷² <http://www.enea.it/en>

⁷³ http://www.mit.gov.it/mit/mop_all.php?p_id=12956

	<p>Strategico Nazionale della Portualità e della Logistica) (Ministry of Transport 2015)⁷⁴;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · National infrastructure plan to set up electric vehicle charging points (Piano Nazionale Infrastrutturale per la ricarica dei veicoli alimentati ad energia elettrica, PNIRE) (L. 7 August 2012, n.134)⁷⁵; · National Action Plan for Intelligent Transport System (Piano di Azione Nazionale sui Sistemi Intelligenti di Trasporto) (DL 12 February 2014, n.44)⁷⁶; · Promotion of use of biomethane in transports. (Dlgs. 3 March 2011, N.28, Article 8)⁷⁷; · Five years bus fleet renewal plan (Piano quinquennale per il rinnovo del parco mezzi del trasporto passeggeri su gomma) (L 27 December 2014, N.147)⁷⁸; · Contract for the development of the national rail infrastructures (Contratto di Programma 2012-2016. Parte Investimenti) (Report to Italian Senate 3 February 2015 n.21)⁷⁹; · Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans, SUMP (Piani Urbani per la Mobilità Sostenibile); · National Green Procurement Plan (Piano d’Azione Nazionale per il GPP) (D.M. 11 April 2008, updated with D.M. 10 April 2013)⁸⁰; · Sustainable Energy Action Plan, SEAPs (Piani d’Azione per l’Energia Sostenibile).
Regulatory instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Vehicle Certification. Vehicle CO₂ emissions standards (several national laws compliant with European policies on theme); · Renewable energy in transport sector. (Dlgs. 3 March 2011, N.28)⁸¹;

⁷⁴ http://www.mit.gov.it/mit/mop_all.php?p_id=23923

⁷⁵ www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:legge:2012-08-07;134!vig=

⁷⁶ www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto.legislativo:2014-03-04;44!vig=

⁷⁷ www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto.legislativo:2011-03-03;28!vig=

⁷⁸ www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:legge:2014-10-10;147!vig=

⁷⁹ <http://documenti.camera.it/leg17/dossier/Pdf/TR0255.pdf>

⁸⁰ http://www.minambiente.it/sites/default/files/archivio/allegati/GPP/PAN_GPP.pdf

⁸¹ www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto.legislativo:2011-03-03;28!vig=

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Urban Traffic Plans (Piano Urbano del Traffico) (Dlgs. 30 April 1992, N.285)⁸²; · Obligation for national fuel producers to input into consumption 1% of biofuels of total traditional fuel. (L.11 March 2006, n. 81)⁸³; · National quality standards for biofuels (AEEG Resolution 160/2012/R/GAS)⁸⁴; · Minimum Environmental Criteria for the acquisition of vehicles for road transport (Criteri Minimi Ambientali per l'acquisizione dei veicoli adibiti al trasporto su strada) (D.M 8 May 2012)⁸⁵; · Limits to polluting vehicles (Regional legislations).
Economic instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Government subsidies for the purchase of low-emission vehicles (D.L. 10 February 2009, n. 5, converted into law by L. 9 April 2009, n.33⁸⁶; L. 7 August 2012, n.134⁸⁷); · Incentives for the promotion of biofuels in transport sector (Dlgs. 3 March 2011, N.28)⁸⁸; · Ad-hoc fund of Ministry of Infrastructure and Transport on PNIRE implementation 2013-2015 (L. 7 August 2012, n.134)⁸⁹; · Ministry call in favour of the Regions to fund a network of electric vehicle charging points (L. 7 August 2012, n.134)⁹⁰; · National electric car sharing project in cities (co-financed by the Ministry of Environment)⁹¹; · National funds for the development of underground

⁸² www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto.legislativo:1992-04-30;285!vig=

⁸³ www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:legge:2006-03-11;81!vig=

⁸⁴ <http://www.autorita.energia.it/allegati/docs/12/160-12.pdf>

⁸⁵ <http://www.minambiente.it/pagina/il-piano-dazione-nazionale-il-gpp-pan-gpp>

⁸⁶ www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto.legge:2009-02-10;5!vig=

⁸⁷ www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:legge:2012-08-07;134!vig=

⁸⁸ www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto.legislativo:2011-03-03;28!vig=

⁸⁹ www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:legge:2012-08-07;134!vig=

⁹⁰ www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:legge:2012-08-07;134!vig=

⁹¹ <http://www.icscarsharing.it/main/>

	<p>railways (Defined in annual Italian Budget Laws);</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Funds related to the “Five years bus fleet renewal plan” (L. 27 December 2013, N.147⁹²); · Structural fund on thematic area “sustainable movement of people and goods” (EU 2014-2020 Structural Funds); · Road tax (tax exemption for electric vehicles and discount on car assurance) and regional schemes for tax exemption for GPL and methane vehicles. (Regional legislations); · National funds for local public transports (indirect effects for example in fleets renewal, etc.). (Defined in annual Italian Budget Laws); · Funding for energy efficiency, renewable energy and bike-sharing (L. 24 December 2007, N.244)⁹³.
Information and awareness instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Guide to fuel saving and decreasing CO₂ emission by cars (Guida sul risparmio di carburanti e sulle emissioni di anidride carbonica delle autovetture)⁹⁴ (Published by MATTM, MIT and MISE); · National Logistics Platform UIRNET⁹⁵ (Sistema Nazionale della Logistica Integrata e Intermodalità) (D.M 20 June 2005, N.18T⁹⁶); · Events and initiatives within the European Sustainable Mobility Week; · National observatory on local public transports policies Osservatorio nazionale sulle politiche per il trasporto pubblico locale (L. 24 December 2007, N.244)⁹⁷.
Policy instruments for Research and	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Design and implementation of a Green Wheel bicycle

⁹² www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:legge:2013-12-27;147!vig=

⁹³ www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:legge:2007-12-24;244!vig=

⁹⁴ http://www.sviluppoeconomico.gov.it/images/stories/documenti/Guida_auto_2014.pdf

⁹⁵ <https://www.uirnet.it/uirnet/>

⁹⁶ https://www.uirnet.it/uirnet/resources/cms/documents/Decreto_Ministeriale_18T_del_20.06.2005.pdf

⁹⁷ www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:legge:2007-12-24;244!vig=

Development	(Initiative of Ministry of Environment); <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · National “Smart Cities and Communities and Social Innovation” funds 2012 and 2013 (Director Decree 5 July 2012, N.391/Ric)⁹⁸; · National technological maritime platform (Piattaforma Tecnologica Nazionale Marittima) (Dlgs. 21 November 2005, N.284)⁹⁹.
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Horizontal measures

There are several horizontal measures affecting both the buildings and transport sectors. Horizontal measures indirectly affecting the improvement of energy efficiency in the building sector are:

- Green Public Procurement;
- Improvement of national, regional and local public authorities budgets and/or reduction of their functioning costs (Spending Review);
- Promotion of renewable energies in new and existing buildings;
- Urban planning instruments, in particular in Italy municipal buildings regulations (Regolamenti Edilizi) often identify specific energy efficiency rules for new and existing buildings.

Horizontal measures indirectly affecting the improvement of energy efficiency in the transport sector are:

- Spending review conducted by central authorities and regarding regional and local public authorities managing public transport services;
- Promotion of renewable energies in all the sectors included in the promotion of transport sustainable fuels.

1.3 CONCLUSIONS AND LESSONS LEARNED OF OTHER PROJECTS ABOUT THE PERFORMANCE OF THE NATIONAL POLICY PACKAGES FOR ENERGY EFFICIENCY

International Energy Efficiency Scorecard

In 2011, the “American Council for an Energy-Efficient Economy” (ACEEE) ranked Italy third at World level, after the United Kingdom and Germany, in terms of national effort to improve energy efficiency levels (NEEAP, 2014). In 2014 Italy improved its ranking position in the ACEEE International Energy Efficiency Scorecard. In fact Italy ranked second among the most advanced world economies. The ranking, that involves 16 economies representing together 80% of world gross domestic product and

⁹⁸ <http://hubmiur.pubblica.istruzione.it/web/ricerca/smart-cities-and-communities-and-social-innovation>

⁹⁹ www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto.legislativo:2005-11-21;284!vig=

accounting for 71% of global energy consumption, is led by Germany, whereas Italy holds the record of energy efficiency in the transportation area.

Fig. 4 ACEEE 2014 International Energy Efficiency Scorecard.

2014 International Energy Efficiency Scorecard

Source: ACEEE 2014

Germany has the highest overall score, with 65 out of 100 possible points. The top-scoring countries in each category are: China in buildings, Germany in industry, Italy in transportation, and a three-way tie between France, Italy, and the European Union in national efforts (ACEEE, 2014).

ODYSSEE-MURE

Based on the ODYSSEE-MURE high impact/high number of applicants criteria¹⁰⁰, these are the 5 most effective Italian energy efficiency policies:

- White Certificates: market based instruments promoting energy efficiency (ODYSSEE-MURE scoring: 5)
- Energy Performance of buildings: design norms for building shell and thermal equipments (ODYSSEE-MURE scoring: 4)
- EU-related: Energy Performance of Buildings (Directive 2002/91/EC) - Energy Performance of Buildings (ODYSSEE-MURE scoring: 3)
- Financial package for old vehicles scrapping (ODYSSEE-MURE scoring: 3)

¹⁰⁰ <http://www.measures-odyssee-mure.eu/successful-detail-measures.asp>

- Fiscal incentives for energy savings in the household sector: Ecobonus 2014 and tax deduction for renovations and appliances (ODYSEE-MURE scoring: 2)

Based on the ODYSSEE-MURE overall energy efficiency evaluation, White Certificates are the most Italian successful energy efficiency policy.

Fig. 5 White Certificates score for each criterion. Radar graph

Source: ODYSSEE-MURE.

As evidenced in the ODYSSEE-MURE analysis of White Certificates, the policy performed very well both in terms of high impacts at national level and in terms of cost efficiency of the measure. Also in all the other criteria White Certificates perform very well.

Energy Efficiency Watch

According to the Italy's Report elaborated by the Energy Efficiency Watch¹⁰¹ (EEW), "some parts of the Italian NEEAP remain unsatisfactory, which has also been recognised by the assessment of interviewed domestic experts. The NEEAP assessment shows that Italian energy efficiency can be considered extensive, although the lack of a long-term target is noticeable. The involvement of non-governmental and market actors, the existence of both a national and regional energy agency and the white certificate scheme are identified as positive elements. The interviewed experts, on the contrary, are far more critical regarding the progress of Italian policy. More than 80 per cent of the interviewees see no or little progress in the last three years. Almost 90 per cent of the interviewees con-

¹⁰¹ The Energy-Efficiency-Watch project aims to portray the progress made in the implementation of energy efficiency policies across the European Union. Under the framework of this project, an expert survey on the implementation of energy efficiency policies in all 27 Member States was conducted. The project also screens the National Energy Efficiency Action Plans in order to highlight strengths and weaknesses of national energy efficiency policy packages. The Energy-Efficiency-Watch project is coordinated by EUFORES. The project partners are eceee, Energy Cities, FEDARENE, Upper Austrian Energy Agency, Wuppertal Institute and Ecofys. For further details, see: <http://www.energy-efficiency-watch.org/index.php?id=5>

sider Italian energy-efficiency to be of low ambition or only ambitious in few sectors. More than 70 per cent of the survey participants believe that Italy will fail to or barely meet its target” (EEW, 2013). Sectoral evaluation shows that policies in the building sector performed much better than those targeting the transport sector, this latter showing a poor and unbalanced mix of policy instruments (Fig. 6 and Fig. 7).

Fig. 6 Evaluation by EEW for the building sector.

Fig. 7 Evaluation by EEW for the transport sector.

OECD. Environmental Performance Review. Country report. Italy 2013. Assessment and Recommendations¹⁰²

OECD, in its Italian country report 2013, highlights the relevant results reached by the Italian energy efficiency policy, mainly in the building sector. OECD shows a mature energy efficiency policy framework, important energy savings results reached and the cost-effectiveness.

“Italy has introduced a number of regulatory measures and economic instruments to promote energy efficiency, including tax incentives and a trading mechanism. These measures have contributed to energy savings above the intermediate target set by the national Energy Efficiency Action Plan, mainly in regard to electricity used by the residential sector. Progress in the service and transport sectors has been more modest and below expectations, underlining the need for additional efforts. Analysis suggests that energy efficiency measures have been cost-effective, with benefits (in terms of avoided energy costs) well above the costs borne by energy users and tax payers. The market for energy efficiency certificates (white certificates, or WCs) has been the most cost-effective measure. It could be further expanded and reinforced. The effectiveness of the current incentive mechanisms would also benefit from more complete and consistent implementation of the certification of building energy performance, which is currently uneven across regions”.

The main Italian energy efficiency problem is related to the governance model. This is too complex and instable and it will require significant adjustments.

¹⁰² <http://www.oecd.org/env/country-reviews/EPR%20Assessment%20and%20recs%20ITALY%202013.pdf>

“Despite progress, Italy’s renewables and energy efficiency policies have lacked a general long-term vision. Management of the incentive systems for energy efficiency and renewables involves a number of different agencies and institutions, which results in co-ordination difficulties and increasing transaction costs. There has been a multitude of overlapping measures, which have also changed several times within a few years. This has created unnecessary complexity and regulatory uncertainty, although recent measures have addressed some of these problems”.

2. INTERACTION BETWEEN THE NATIONAL AND THE SUB-NATIONAL LEVELS

In Italy, energy issues are governed under a system of “concurrent legislative powers”, as defined in the Constitution - Title V. This means that the Regions have legislative powers over energy matters, except for the fundamental principles, which are determined by the central Government. The application of this constitutional provision causes a considerable difficulty in terms of harmonizing legislation (SEN, 2013), with growing numbers of disputes being heard by the Constitutional Court (SEN, 2013). Moreover, a corollary of this law is the more extensive role entrusted to the Regions in administrative matters. As a result, the authorization for any given energy project requires the agreement of the Region concerned, even for works of national interest and not just for those of regional and local interest (SEN, 2013).

For all these reasons, as highlighted in the SEN, “the achievement of the energy efficiency targets - as well as for renewable energy – needs, as a prerequisite, the organic collaboration and coordinated action between the State and the local governments, as for the widespread nature of interventions as for the allocation of functions”. In fact, “potential savings are very broad and only a careful action of local government can give rise to them, such as in the fields of local transport and mobility, public lighting, buildings, district heating”.

The main functions of the national level in the definition of buildings and transport energy efficiency policies and measures are:

- Defining the overall energy efficiency objectives and strategies;
- Defining energy efficiency technical regulation;
- Monitoring the results of policies and measures;
- Implementing national dissemination campaigns;
- Defining economic and supporting schemes to promote and strengthen energy efficiency (only Ministry of Economy and Finance).

In Italy, also the regional level has a central role in energy efficiency policies in the buildings and transport sector. The main roles of Italian Regions in the buildings energy efficiency legislative framework are:

- Technical definition and monitoring of regional energy efficiency certification schemes;
- Training and accreditation of operators realizing energy efficiency certifications;
- Monitoring and control (through inspections) of buildings energy efficiency certifications and qualified energy efficiency operators;
- Cadastre of heating plants;
- Collection of data.

Regarding the buildings sectors, Italian Regions can define their buildings energy efficiency regulation mechanisms and schemes, therefore each of them has its energy efficiency laws in the buildings sector. As this proliferation of buildings regulatory schemes could constitute an important barrier to

achieve energy efficiency in the sector, in June 2015 the Italian Parliament approved some norms to create a common national framework¹⁰³.

Also the local level is particularly active and important in the definition and implementation of energy efficiency policies. First of all, municipal authorities are responsible for the definition of the buildings regulation, one of the most important tools for the improvement of energy efficiency in the buildings sector. Moreover Italian municipalities are the most active at European level in the Covenant of Mayors. In fact, based on Covenant of Mayors data on 30 July 2015, there are 2.598 Italian municipalities with an approved Sustainable Energy Action Plan (SEAP).

In conclusion it is possible to affirm that in Italy all the policy levels are deeply involved and particularly active in energy efficiency. All the policy levels are important in the definition and implementation of energy efficiency policies and measures. Regions in particular, as evidenced in the previous analysis, are strongly supporting the national level in the definition of energy efficiency policies and measures through the Unified State-Region conference and the National Energy Efficiency Control Room.

Also non-governmental and market actors, as well as sub-national authorities, were largely involved in the designing and setting of the Italian Energy Efficiency Action Plan (NEEAP) and the National Energy Strategy (SEN). In fact, these documents were the outcome of “an extensive public consultation, through a wide involvement of all the stakeholders. During the two months of public consultation, meetings have been organized at the Ministry of Economic Development with more than 100 stakeholders among Institutions, industry associations, social partners and trade unions, research and study centers”. In this case the involvement of non-governmental and market actors occurred through specific public consultation processes.

It is worth noting that ENEA provides detailed information on the status and nature of policy instruments in force across all the Italian regions¹⁰⁴. In addition, within the ENEA’s website regional administrations can access the “Regional Energy Information System” through which it is possible to collect energy-economy data at regional and sub-regional level useful for urban planning.

¹⁰³ <http://www.regionieambiente.it/energia/efficienza/2121-pubblicati-i-decreti-di-completamento-del-quadro-normativo-sullefficienza-energetica-degli-edifici.html>

¹⁰⁴ Detailed information on each region are available on line at: <http://www.energiaenergetica.enea.it/l-efficienza-energetica-nelle-regioni/>

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HERON (No: 649690): Deliverable D.1.1

LANDSCAPE OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICY PACKAGES IN A MULTI-LEVEL GOVERNMENT SYSTEM

PART OF WORK PACKAGE 1: MAPPING OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICY INSTRUMENTS AND
AVAILABLE TECHNOLOGIES IN BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT

NATIONAL REPORT FOR SERBIA

30.07.2015.

Partner: Centre for Energy, University of Belgrade – Faculty of Mining and Geology

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HERON: Forward – looking socio-economic research on Energy Efficiency in EU countries

this project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649690. The content of this document reflects only the authors' views and the EASME is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Contents

ACRONYMS	4
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	5
1. THE ROLE OF GOVERNANCE AND ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICY PACKAGES ON THE NATIONAL LEVEL.....	8
1.1 POLICY PACKAGES AND POLICY GOVERNANCE IN SERBIA.....	8
1.2 NATIONAL PROGRAMMES AND INITIATIVES	22
1.3 CONCLUSIONS AND LESSONS LEARNED OF OTHER PROJECTS ABOUT THE PERFORMANCE OF THE NATIONAL POLICY PACKAGES FOR ENERGY EFFICIENCY	25
2. INTERACTION BETWEEN THE NATIONAL AND THE SUB-NATIONAL LEVELS	27
REFERENCES	29

List of Tables

Table 1: List of national documents concerning Serbian energy efficiency packages	9
Table 2: Summary of proposed measures and expected savings in the Buildings Sector	13
Table 3: Measures for energy efficiency in Buildings Sector and instruments for their achievement	14
Table 4: List of institutions active in the buildings sector	16
Table 5: Summary of proposed measures and expected savings in the Transport Sector	18
Table 6: Measures for energy efficiency in the Transport Sector and instruments for their achievement	18
Table 7: List of institutions that have an active role in the transport sector	20

ACRONYMS

DHS	District Heating System
EE	Energy Efficiency
EEAP	Energy Efficiency Action Plan
EPBD	Energy Performance Building Directive
EUE	Efficient Use of Energy
HVAC	Heating, Ventilating, Air Conditioning
Mtoe	Million tons of oil equivalent
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
SEAP	Sustainable Energy Action Plan

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Republic of Serbia officially applied for European Union membership in 2009, and received full candidate status in 2012. However, the Republic of Serbia is contracting party of the Energy Community Treaty since 2006. Recently, the Republic of Serbia adopted a new Energy Law (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2014a) that transposes the EU's Third Energy Package. Basic EU documents that defines energy efficiency policy packages in Serbia are, as follows:

- Directive 2006/32/E3 on energy end-use efficiency and energy services¹,
- Directive 2010/30/EU on the indication by labeling and standard product information of the consumption of energy and other resources by energy-related products, and
- Directive 2010/31/EU on energy performance of buildings.

In 2015, Serbian Government adopted **Energy Sector Development Strategy of Republic of Serbia up to 2025 with projections to 2030** (Government of Serbia, 2015). Energy efficiency is further promoted in this document as "new energy source", while a scenario of energy sector development assuming wider implementation of energy efficiency measures was developed. Increase of energy efficiency in all sectors of consumption is established as strategic goal. This goal should be achieved by implementation of provisions of the Law on Efficient Use of Energy (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013a) and actions defined in the national Action Plans for Energy Efficiency (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013b).

The Second Energy Efficiency Action Plan of the Republic of Serbia for the period from 2013 to 2015 (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013b) has been prepared at the request of Directive 2006/32/E3 on energy end-use efficiency and energy services, and in accordance with the model developed by the Working Group on Energy Efficiency established in the Energy Community Secretariat.

The Second EEAP is related to the period from 2013 to 2015. This strategic document defines specific quantitative targets for energy savings in line with the general objectives of other policy documents in this area. The average indicative target for saving for the period from 2013 to 2015 was defined at the level of 3.5% of the final energy consumption in 2008 (0.2952 Mtoe). The overall saving in the period from 2010 to 2015 should be 0.3975 Mtoe (4.7%). The total target of at least 9% of the final energy consumption in the ninth year (2018) of implementation remains the same as in the First EEAP (0.7524 Mtoe). The final energy savings during the period 2013-2015 should be achieved by the implementation of energy efficiency improvement measures in the household sector (0.0693 Mtoe or 23.4%), the public/commercial sector (0.0499 Mtoe or 16.8%), the industry sector (0.081 Mtoe or 27.7%) and the transport sector (0.095 Mtoe or 32.1%).

The buildings sector has not been analyzed as a specific sector in the Second EEAP. However, the most of the measures for energy efficiency improvement and related calculations are provided for the household sector and the public/commercial sector. Using provided data for these two sub-sectors in the Second EEAP, total planned savings in 2015 in the buildings sector amounts 0.1374 Mtoe, while planned savings in 2018 amounts 0.2666 Mtoe. The Second EEAP for the buildings sector targets both supply and demand side. Demand side is dominant for the residential sub-sector, while for the public/commercial sub-sector besides similar measures on demand side, supply side is considered by promotion of incentive rates for highly efficient coupled/combined heat and power generation, and by mandatory regular control of the combustion facilities, as well as air conditioning sys-

¹ Directive 2012/27/EU on energy efficiency is not binding yet on the Parties to the EC Treaty.

tems. Also, in the public/commercial sub-sector specific organizational measures target energy efficiency at both demand and supply side.

Planned savings in the Transport sector according to the Second EEAP amounts 0.1032 Mtoe in 2015, and 0.2107 Mtoe in 2018. Policy package defined by the second EEAP is mostly directed to vehicle efficiency. Out of five proposed measures, four is directed to vehicle efficiency. Only one measure (Promotion of eco-driving and car sharing scheme) is directed to travel efficiency and in less extent to system efficiency.

At a national level, energy efficiency is generally under the authority of the Ministry of Mining and Energy – Department for Energy Efficiency and Renewable Energy and this institution is recognized as the key player for implementation of all measures and instruments quoted in the second EEAP related to the buildings sector. Besides this Ministry, the Ministry of Construction, Transport and Infrastructure, the Standing Conference of Towns and Municipalities and other relevant institutions at the level of the autonomous province and local self-government are appointed as institutions in charge for the implementation of activities under specified measures.

Responsibility for implementation of measures in the transport Sector is split between different ministries and governmental institutions. The most of responsible institutions (Road Traffic Safety Agency, Ministry of Construction, Transport and Infrastructure, Ministry of Interior, etc.) are only indirectly connected to energy issues and energy efficiency improvement. A favorable circumstance is that actions primary directed to improve safety and efficiency of transport, or to diminish environmental and impact on climate, have positive effects on energy efficiency. Unfortunately, there are no official coordination mechanisms in place for the national energy efficiency policy in the Transport sector. As the public transport is within the responsibility of local self-governments, under their responsibility are all activities, necessary for introduction of energy efficiency as a criterion for fleet modernization with an assignment of improvement of public transport service performance.

The budget Fund for Energy Efficiency is planned to be national program, comprehensive mechanism for financing different measures and activities aimed to improve energy efficiency. Activities and projects that are appropriate for financing are: different technical measures for improvement of energy efficiency in the private, public, commercial sectors, development of energy management system for entities that are not designated organizations, promotion and implementation of energy audits of facilities, production processes and services, introduction of systems for combined heat and power generation for investors that use thermal and electrical energy exclusively for own use, development of energy services market in the Republic of Serbia, use of renewable energy sources for electricity and heat generation for individual usage, and all other activities aimed to the improvement of efficiency of energy use. According to the experience from 2014, one of the priorities of this program is directed to improvement of energy efficiency in the buildings sector.

Serbia is not the full member of EU and it's participation in EU projects is limited. However, as a contracting party of the **Energy Community Treaty**, performances of national policy packages for energy efficiency are regularly evaluated by Secretariat of this institution. It was concluded that with the adoption of the Law on Efficient Use of Energy, the second EEAP and Labeling Regulation, Serbia achieved a significant step forward towards the transposition of the energy efficiency acquis (Energy Community, 2015). State and possibilities for Serbian buildings sector were only partly analysed in **ENTRANZE Project**. An overview of Serbian building stock until 2010 based on literature review, as well analysis of energy balance for 2008 were done. Also, expected final energy demand for space heating and hot water in Serbia in 2020 and 2030 for three different policy scenarios was presented. However, in-depth policy discussion wasn't carried out, as well as thorough analysis of the current state of policies in Serbia. The **IEE Project TABULA**² was aimed at defining common principles for the

² <http://www.building-typology.eu>

creation of national typologies of residential buildings. In 2013, the project "Tabula" was completed, and for the first time in the Republic of Serbia provided classification of buildings in family and multi-family housing. Results of the Tabula project (Jovanovic Popovic et al., 2013) were used during development of the second EEAP. **IEA Energy Efficiency Policy and Measures Database**³ includes some indicators and information on energy efficiency policy in Serbia. Although elaborated decrees can be, in wider context, put in relation with energy efficiency, they are primarily directed to RES promotion and feed-in tariff system implementation.

Although national level's authority is dominant in conducting energy efficiency programs and initiatives, regional (Autonomous Province of Vojvodina) and local authorities have important roles in these activities too. Responsibility for implementation of the second Energy Efficiency Action Plan (EEAP) is also attributed to provincial or local governments, within their respective jurisdictions.

Some of local authorities in Serbia are very active in different energy efficiency initiatives on national, regional and international level. Concerning the **Covenant of Mayors**, interest in Serbian municipalities is still very modest compared to other European countries. Currently, 12 Serbian municipalities are signatories, but six of them are on hold, as they have not submitted their SEAPs before the deadline. Only one Serbian city, the City of Niš, has submitted the SEAP⁴.

³ <http://www.iea.org/policiesandmeasures/energyefficiency/?country=Serbia>

⁴ <http://www.ni.rs/wp-content/uploads/141224-seap.pdf>

1. THE ROLE OF GOVERNANCE AND ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICY PACKAGES ON THE NATIONAL LEVEL

1.1 POLICY PACKAGES AND POLICY GOVERNANCE IN SERBIA

Modern strategic and regulatory framework in Serbian energy sector was established after 2000. The first adopted energy sector development strategy (Government of Serbia, 2005) promoted energy efficiency (in the production, distribution and utilization of energy by end consumers of energy-related services) as the second directed priority of energy sector development. Additionally, more energy efficient and environmentally acceptable energy technologies and installations/equipment for energy utilization are promoted as the third, special priority of this document. This document does not have specified quantitative energy efficiency target.

The Republic of Serbia officially applied for European Union membership in 2009, and received full candidate status in 2012. However, Serbia particularly is contracting party of the Energy Community Treaty since 2006. This was the first contract signed between the Republic of Serbia and EU. By this document the Republic of Serbia assumed obligation of implementation of European Union regulations (Acquis Communautaire on Energy, Environment, Competition and Renewables) (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2006). Significance of the Energy Community Treaty is confirmed by ratification of Stabilization and Association Agreement in 2008. In this Agreement the necessity of cooperation of the Republic of Serbia and European Union, for the development of Community acquis and integration of the Republic of Serbia into energy market of the European Union is emphasized. Recently, the Republic of Serbia adopted a new Energy Law (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2014a) that transposes the EU's Third Energy Package. Basic EU documents that defined energy efficiency policy packages in Serbia are, as follows:

- Directive 2006/32/E3 on energy end-use efficiency and energy services⁵,
- Directive 2010/30/EU on the indication by labeling and standard product information of the consumption of energy and other resources by energy-related products, and
- Directive 2010/31/EU on energy performance of buildings.

In 2015, Serbian Government adopted the **Energy Sector Development Strategy of Republic of Serbia up to 2025 with projections to 2030** (Government of Serbia, 2015) and sent it to the National Assembly for approval. Energy efficiency is further promoted in this document as a “new energy source” and complete scenario of energy sector development assuming wider implementation of energy efficiency measures was developed. Increase of energy efficiency in all sectors of consumption is established as strategic goal. This goal should be achieved by implementation of provisions of the Law on Efficient Use of Energy (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013a) and actions defined in the national Action Plans for Energy Efficiency (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013b). Further this document insists on defining the national saving goals (in total and per sectors) and monitoring of effects of implementation of energy efficiency measures (with emphasized need for capacity building of energy statistic). Significance of non-technical measures is recognized and promoted, and as priorities introduction of energy management systems and informing and education of the public are appointed. As this document was prepared after the adoption of the Second Energy Efficiency Action Plan, national energy efficiency targets in both documents are the same. Also, in the Energy Sector Development Strategy, significance of energy efficiency for overall social and economic

⁵ Directive 2012/27/EU on energy efficiency is not binding yet on the Parties to the EC Treaty.

development of the country was emphasized. It is stated that investments required for transition of the Republic of Serbia towards more energy efficient energy use are very high for its economic state, but that they are justified, because they shall reduce import dependency, contribute to competitiveness of the economy, reduce costs of environmental protection and directly and indirectly contribute to better living standard of the citizens.

The Second Energy Efficiency Action Plan of the Republic of Serbia for the period from 2013 to 2015 (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013b) has been prepared at the request of Directive 2006/32/E3 on energy end-use efficiency and energy services, and in accordance with the model developed by the Working Group on Energy Efficiency established in the Energy Community Secretariat.

In the First Energy Efficiency Action Plan (EEAP) of the Republic of Serbia for the period from 2010 to 2012, an average indicative saving target for 2010-2012 period was defined as 9% of the final domestic energy consumption in 2008 (0.1254 Mtoe), (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2010). Also, the total target of at least 9% of the final energy consumption in the ninth year (2018) of application was also calculated with regard to the final energy consumption in 2008. This specific year was selected for calculation, because data about energy consumption in the Republic of Serbia for 2008 were the most reliable at the time of adoption of the First EEAP.

The Second EEAP is related to the period from 2013 to 2015. This strategic document defines specific quantitative targets for energy savings in line with the general objectives of other policy documents in this area. The Second EEAP contains analysis and performance evaluation of the implementation of the First EEAP, presents the key parameters of the Second EEAP and proposes measures to increase energy efficiency. Measures for the reduction of final energy consumption are followed by sets of indicative targets for the second reporting period 2013-2015. A review of horizontal measures, as well as institutional and financial framework for the implementation of energy efficiency measures are also included in the second EEAP. They are aimed to improve the implementation, monitoring and evaluation of achieved savings. The average indicative target for savings for the period from 2013 to 2015 was defined at the level of 3.5% of the final energy consumption in 2008 (0.2952 Mtoe). Therefore, the overall savings in the period from 2010 to 2015 should be 0.3975 Mtoe (4.7%). The total target of at least 9% of the final energy consumption in the ninth year (2018) of implementation remains the same as in the First EEAP (0.7524 Mtoe). Final energy savings over a period 2013-2015 should be achieved by the implementation of energy efficiency improvement measures in the household sector (0.0693 Mtoe or 23.4%), public/commercial sector (0.0499 Mtoe or 16.8%), industry sector (0.081 Mtoe or 27.7%) and transport sector (0.095 Mtoe or 32.1%).

For achieving the goals set out in the EEAP, different policy instruments (described in detail in D 1.2) are developed by adoption sets of laws, regulations and rulebooks. Main official national documents that provide information about national energy efficiency packages in the buildings and the transport sector are listed in Table 1. This table contains exact title, date, institution that is responsible for respective document, main information of the document and internet link.

Table 1: List of national documents concerning Serbian energy efficiency packages

Name of the document	Institution and the date of adoption	Main information and internet link
General documents		
Energy Sector Development Strategy of Republic of Serbia up to 2025 with projections to 2030,	Government of the Republic of Serbia, 29.05.2015 ⁶	Energy efficiency is promoted as "new energy source" and complete scenario of energy sector development assuming wider implementation of energy efficiency measures was developed. Increase of energy effi-

⁶ This document is in National Assembly of the Republic of Serbia for final adoption.

Name of the document	Institution and the date of adoption	Main information and internet link
		ciency in all sectors of consumption is established as strategic goal. http://www.srbija.gov.rs/vesti/dokumenti_sekcija.php?id=45678
The First Energy Efficiency Action Plan of the Republic of Serbia for the Period from 2010 to 2012	Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2010	Document presents the key parameters and proposes measures to increase energy efficiency. Measures for the reduction of final energy consumption are followed by sets of indicative targets for the reporting period 2010-2012. http://mre.gov.rs/doc/efikasnost-izvori/Prvi_akcioni_plan_za_energetsku_efikasnost.pdf?uri=CELEX:32009L0028
The Second Energy Efficiency Action Plan of the Republic of Serbia for the Period from 2013 to 2015	Government of the Republic of Serbia, 21.10.2013	Document defines specific quantitative targets for energy savings. It contains analysis and performance evaluation of the implementation of the First EEAP, presents the key parameters and proposes measures to increase energy efficiency. Measures for the reduction of final energy consumption are followed by sets of indicative targets for the second reporting period. A review of horizontal measures, as well as institutional and financial framework for the implementation of energy efficiency measures are also included. http://www.mre.gov.rs/doc/efikasnost-izvori/efikasnost/B_01_Drugi_akcioni_plan_za_energetsku_efikasnost_za_Republiku_Srbiju_za_period_od_2013_do_2015_godine.pdf?uri=CELEX:32009L0028
Law on Efficient Use of Energy	Government of the Republic of Serbia, 15.03.2013.	This Law regulates the conditions and ways of efficient use of energy and energy sources in the production, transmission, distribution and consumption of energy; policy of efficient use of energy; energy management system; energy labeling; minimum energy efficiency requirements in production, transmission and distribution of electricity and heat, as well as natural gas distribution; funding, incentives and other measures in this area, as well as other issues of importance to the rights and obligations of natural and legal persons in connection with the efficient use of energy. http://www.mre.gov.rs/doc/efikasnost-izvori/efikasnost/A_01_Zakon_o_efikasnom_koriscenju_energije.pdf
Buildings Sector		
Law on Construction and Planning,	Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2014	This Law regulates: conditions and manner of spatial planning, regulation and use of land and construction of buildings; monitor the implementation of the provisions of this law and inspection; other issues of importance for spatial planning, regulation and use of land and building construction. Energy efficiency improvement in buildings sector is one of the objectives of this Law. http://www.ingkomora.org.rs/zakoni/zakon_o_planiranju_i_izgradnji2014.pdf
Regulation on types of products that affect the consumption of energy and require labelling of consumption of energy and other resources	Government of the Republic of Serbia, 21.10. 2013	Regulation prescribes types of products for energy labeling, as well as the dynamics of the compulsory introduction of energy efficiency labels for different product types. http://www.mre.gov.rs/doc/efikasnost-izvori/efikasnost/D_01_Uredba_o_vrstama_proizvoda_koji_uticu_na_potrosnju_energije_za_koje_je_neophodno_oznacavanje_potrosnje_energije_i_drugih_resursa.pdf
Regulation on Programme of financing activities and measures for improvement efficient energy use in 2014	Government of the Republic of Serbia, 17.01.2014.	Regulation prescribes program of financing activities and measures for improvement efficient energy use in 2014. http://www.mre.gov.rs/doc/efikasnost-izvori/efikasnost/C_01_Uredba_o_utvrđivanju_programa_finansiranja_aktivnosti_i_mera_unapredjenja_efikasnog_koriscenja_energije_u_2014_godini.pdf
Regulation on determination of methodology for determination of price for supply of end user by heat energy	Government of the Republic of Serbia, 10.07.2015.	Regulation prescribes methodology for determination of price for supply of end user by heat energy. http://www.mre.gov.rs/doc/efikasnost-izvori/uredba_metodologija_toplotna_energija0138_cyr.pdf
Rulebook on licensing exams in the field of spatial and urban planning, preparation of technical documentation, construction and energy efficiency and on issuing and revocation of licenses for the	Ministry of Construction, Transport and Infrastructure, 16.03.2015.	Document prescribes rules for licensing exams in the field of spatial and urban planning, preparation of technical documentation, construction and energy efficiency and on issuing and revocation of licenses for the authorized urban planner, designer, contractor and responsible planner. http://www.ingkomora.rs/zakoni/pravilnici/59713_Pravilnik_o_polaganj

Name of the document	Institution and the date of adoption	Main information and internet link
authorized urban planner, designer, contractor and responsible planner		u_strucnog_ispita.pdf
Rulebook on the labelling of energy efficiency of household refrigerating appliances	Ministry of Energy, Development and Environment, 20.01.2014.	Document prescribes rules for labeling of energy efficiency of household refrigerating appliances with volume between 10 and 1500 liters. http://www.mre.gov.rs/doc/efikasnost-izvori/efikasnost/D_06_Pravilnik_o_ozacavanju_energetske_efikasnosti_rashladnih_uredjaja_za_domacinstvo.pdf
Rulebook on the labelling of energy efficiency of household washing machines	Ministry of Energy, Development and Environment, 21.02.2014.	Document prescribes rules for labeling of energy efficiency of household washing machines. http://www.mre.gov.rs/doc/efikasnost-izvori/efikasnost/D_02_Pravilnik_o_ozacavanju_energetske_efikasnosti_masina_za_pranje_vesa_u_domacinstvu.pdf
Rulebook on the labelling of energy efficiency of household dishwashers	Ministry of Energy, Development and Environment, 21.02.2014.	Document prescribes rules for labeling of energy efficiency of household dishwashers. http://www.mre.gov.rs/doc/efikasnost-izvori/efikasnost/D_03_Pravilnik_o_ozacavanju_energetske_efikasnosti_masina_za_pranje_sudova_u_domacinstvu.pdf
Rulebook on the labelling of energy efficiency of electric ovens	Ministry of Energy, Development and Environment, 24.02.2014.	Document prescribes rules for labeling of energy efficiency of electric ovens. http://www.mre.gov.rs/doc/efikasnost-izvori/efikasnost/D_04_Pravilnik_o_ozacavanju_energetske_efikasnosti_elektricnih_pecnica.pdf
Rulebook on the labelling of energy efficiency of electric bulbs and lamps	Ministry of Energy, Development and Environment, 21.02.2014.	Document prescribes rules for labeling of energy efficiency of electric bulbs and lamps. http://www.mre.gov.rs/doc/efikasnost-izvori/efikasnost/D_05_Pravilnik_o_ozacavanju_energetske_efikasnosti_elektricnih%20sijalica_i_svetiljki.pdf
Rulebook on the labelling of energy efficiency of TVs	Ministry of Energy, Development and Environment, 20.02.2014.	Document prescribes rules for labeling of energy efficiency of TVs. http://www.mre.gov.rs/doc/efikasnost-izvori/efikasnost/D_07_Pravilnik_o_ozacavanju_energetske_efikasnosti_televizora.pdf
Rulebook on the labelling of energy efficiency of air-conditioning devices	Ministry of Energy, Development and Environment, 28.02.2014.	Document prescribes rules for labeling of energy efficiency of air-conditioning devices. http://www.mre.gov.rs/doc/efikasnost-izvori/efikasnost/D_08_Pravilnik_o_ozacavanju_energetske_efikasnosti_uredjaja_za_klimatizaciju.pdf
Rulebook on Conditions, Content and Manner of Issuance of Certificates of Energy Performance of Buildings	Ministry of Environment, Mining and Spatial Planning, N/A	Document prescribes rules for conditions, content and manner of issuance of certificates of energy performance of buildings. http://www.kombeg.org.rs/Slike/UdrGradjevinarstvo/Statika/Informacij_e-zakoni/EnergetskaEfik.pdf
Rulebook on Energy Efficiency of Buildings	Ministry of Environment, Mining and Spatial Planning, 5.8.2011.	Document prescribes energy properties and method of calculating the thermal properties of buildings, as well as energy requirements for new and existing buildings. http://www.ingkomora.org.rs/strucniispiti/download/ee/PRAVILNIK_O_EEZ_za%20obuku.pdf
Rulebook on Model Energy Service Contracts for the Implementation of Energy Efficiency when Users are from Public Sector	Ministry of Mining and Energy, 16.4.2015.	Document prescribes model energy service contracts for the implementation of energy efficiency when users are from public sector. http://www.mre.gov.rs/doc/efikasnost-izvori/00%20-%20Pravilnik.pdf
Rulebook on the manner of implementation and content of training program for energy managers, expenditures for attending the training courses, and detailed conditions, curriculum, and taking of the examination for energy managers	Ministry of Mining and Energy, 22.1.2015.	Document prescribes the manner of implementation and content of training program for energy managers, expenditures for attending the training courses, and detailed conditions, curriculum, and taking of the examination for energy managers. http://www.mre.gov.rs/doc/efikasnost-izvori/Pravilnik%20o%20nacinu%20sprovodjenja%20obuke.pdf?uri=CELEX:32009L0028
Rulebook on conditions in terms of personnel, equipment and facilities of the organization that conducted the training for energy managers and authorized energy advisors	Ministry of Mining and Energy, 22.1.2015.	Document prescribes conditions in terms of personnel, equipment and facilities of the organization that conducted the training for energy managers and authorized energy advisors. http://www.mre.gov.rs/doc/efikasnost-izvori/Pravilnik%20o%20uslovima%20u%20pogledu%20kadrova.pdf?uri=CELEX:32009L0028
Rulebook on the conditions for allocation and use of the Budget Fund for improving energy efficiency of the Republic of Serbia and criteria for exemption from the	Ministry of Energy, Development and Environment 27.1.2014.	Document prescribes the conditions for allocation and use of the Budget Fund for improving energy efficiency of the Republic of Serbia and criteria for exemption from the obligation of performing an energy audit. http://www.mre.gov.rs/doc/efikasnost-

Name of the document	Institution and the date of adoption	Main information and internet link
obligation of performing an energy audit		izvori/efikasnost/C_02_Pravilnik_o_uslovima_za_raspodelu_i_koriscenje_sredstava_Budzetskog_fonda_za_unapredenje_energetske_efikasnosti.pdf
Transport Sector		
Law on Efficient Use of Energy	Government of the Republic of Serbia, 15.03.2013.	The Law prescribes that competent authority of local self-government with more than 20,000 inhabitants is obliged to adopt a program to improve energy efficiency in the transport within period of three years. Legal persons performing compulsory technical inspection of motor vehicles accordance with the Law are obliged to provide data that enable identification and tracking Indicators of energy consumption in road transport. http://www.mre.gov.rs/doc/efikasnost-izvori/efikasnost/A_01_Zakon_o_efikasnom_koriscenju_energije.pdf
Strategy of the Railway, Road, Inland Waterway, Air and Intermodal Transport Development in the Republic of Serbia (2008-2015)	Government of the Republic of Serbia 27.12.2007.	Strategy proposes a concept of development of infrastructure and transport, defines goals and objectives of transport system development and action plan for their implementation until 2015. http://www.putevi-srbije.rs/strategijapdf/Strategijatransport_eng.pdf
Law on Road Traffic Safety	Government of the Republic of Serbia, 6.8.2010.	This Law regulates the rules of traffic, conduct of traffic participants, traffic restrictions, traffic signals, signs and instructions to which all traffic participants shall adhere, the conditions which drivers shall meet in order to drive a vehicle, driver's education, passing driving tests, right to drive a vehicle, issuing of driving licenses, issuing of the labels for disabled persons' vehicles, the demands vehicles shall meet, technical examinations, inspections and vehicle registration, special measures and powers applied to road traffic, as well as other issues related to road traffic safety. http://en.abs.gov.rs/regulations
Regulation on motor vehicle import	Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2010	Document prescribes specific conditions for vehicle import in the Republic of Serbia. http://www.abs.gov.rs/odluke-i-uredbe
Regulation on marking of oil products	Government of the Republic of Serbia, 20.5.2013.	Document closely regulates the conditions, manner and procedure of marking (labeling) refined petroleum products placed on the market. http://www.mre.gov.rs/doc/nafta-i-gas/B02%20Uredba%20o%20obelezavanju%20(markiranju)%20derivata%20nafte.pdf
Law on Ratification of the Agreement on the adoption of unified technical regulations for wheeled vehicles, equipment and parts which can be fitted and/or used on vehicles with wheels and conditions for reciprocal recognition of approvals awarded in line with these regulations	National Assembly of the Republic of Serbia, 2011	Document prescribes unified technical regulations for wheeled vehicles, equipment and parts which can be fitted and/or used on vehicles with wheels and conditions for reciprocal recognition of approvals awarded in line with these regulations. Approval of vehicles according to United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE) regulations include determination and verification that vehicle's characteristics meet the requirements related to the active safety, passive safety, environmental protection and energy saving (fuel consumption), control of the conformity of series production, a unique method of application and acceptance by all contracting parties. http://demo.paragraf.rs/combined/Old/t/t2011_12/t12_0360.htm
Rulebook of the technical measures for slowing road traffic	Ministry of Transport, 17.1.2014.	Document prescribes technical measures for slowing road traffic. http://slglasnik.info/sr/9-30-01-2014/22305-pravilnik-o-tehnickim-sredstvima-za-usporavanje-saobracaja-na-putu.html
Rulebook on technical and other requirements for petroleum-derived liquid fuels	Ministry of Energy, Development and Environment, 27.12.2012.	This document prescribes technical and other requirements for petroleum-derived liquid fuels. http://www.mre.gov.rs/doc/nafta-i-gas/izmena/C12%20Pravilnik%20o%20tehnickim%20i%20drugim%20zah-tevima%20za%20tecna%20goriva%20naftnog%20porekla.pdf

1) Buildings Sector

Objectives

The buildings sector has not been analyzed as a specific sector in the Second EEAP. However, the most of the measures for energy efficiency improvement and related calculations are provided for

household sector and public/commercial sector. Using provided data for these two sub-sectors in the Second EEAP, total planned savings in 2015 in the buildings sector amounts 0.1374 Mtoe, while planned savings in 2018 amounts 0.2666 Mtoe. These **energy efficiency targets for the buildings sector** represent 1.5% and 2.9% respectively of total final energy consumption in 2013 in Serbia (Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, 2014).

The buildings sector had share of 38.5% in final energy consumption in the base year 2008. According to a new energy balances after 2010, this share raised to 49.16% in 2011 (Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, 2012). Share of the buildings sector in the final energy savings according to the Second EEAP should be 36.55% in 2018.

Summary of proposed measures and expected savings in the Second EEAP is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Summary of proposed measures and expected savings in the Buildings Sector

Name of measure in the Second EEAP	Expected savings in 2015 [Mtoe]	Expected savings in 2018 [Mtoe]
Energy efficiency improvement measures in residential buildings	0.0218	0.0436
New rules for the design and construction of buildings, the minimum requirements in terms of energy performance of buildings and their certification in accordance with the revised EPBD	0.0418	0.0848
Promotion of the use of energy-efficient household appliances	0.005762	0.01194
Energy efficiency improvement measures in public/commercial buildings	0.00691	0.0170
New rules for the design and construction of buildings, the minimum requirements in terms of energy performance of buildings and their certification in accordance with the revised EPBD	0.02676	0.05352
Introduction of Energy Management Systems in the public and commercial sector	0.008141	0.04477
Determination of energy efficiency as one of the criteria for the most economically advantageous tender in public procurement	Not estimated	Not estimated
Incentive rates for highly efficient coupled/combined heat and power generation	0.00431	0.00862
Mandatory regular control of the combustion process of boilers and other combustion chambers with the capacity over 20 kW, as well as air conditioning systems	0.00242	0.00242

The second EEAP has not further elaborated significance of energy efficiency for economic development (employment, energy costs), fuel poverty reduction, etc. Such elaboration (for all sectors) is presented in the Energy Sector Development Strategy of Republic of Serbia up to 2025 with projections to 2030.

Synthesis of policy packages

The Second EEAP, as comprehensive policy package, in the buildings sector targets both supply and demand side. Demand side is dominant in residential sub-sector (energy efficiency improvement measures in residential buildings, new rules for the design and construction of buildings, promotion of the use of energy-efficient household appliances), while for the public/commercial sub-sector besides similar measures on demand side, supply side is considered by promotion of incentive rates for highly efficient coupled/combined heat and power generation, and by mandatory regular control of

the combustion process of boilers and other combustion chambers with the capacity over 20 kW, as well as air conditioning systems. Also, in the public/commercial sub-sector specific organizational measures (Introduction of Energy Management Systems and determination of energy efficiency as one of the criteria for the most economically advantageous tender in public procurement) target energy efficiency at both demand and supply side.

Also, some of horizontal measures proposed by this document (Billing based on actual consumption of heat energy for the consumers connected to district heating system, Promotion of ESCO model for energy efficiency projects financing) have influence both on demand and supply side in the buildings sector, while horizontal measure Raising awareness about the energy efficiency importance is mostly directed to demand side.

List of measures, their short description and proposed instruments for their achievement is presented in Table 3. Instruments are quoted as they are written in the Second EEAP. Only some of them are completely developed and covered by appropriate regulations.

Table 3: Measures for energy efficiency in Buildings Sector and instruments for their achievement

Name and description of measure in the Second EEAP	Proposed instruments
<i>Residential Sub-sector</i>	
<p>H1 Energy efficiency improvement measures in residential buildings Measure includes energy savings for heating and cooling through the intervention on building envelope (improvement or replacement of external windows and doors, installation or improvement of existing thermal insulation of walls, roofs, ceilings over open passages, walls and floors on the ground, and the other walls to unheated spaces) and reducing the energy consumption of HVAC system (better HVAC equipment with automatic control systems, more efficient equipment for biomass combustion, thermal solar collectors use, more effective heating devices - heat pumps, etc.).</p>	<p>Financial instrument (credit line, subsidy, loan) Energy audit</p>
<p>H2 New rules for the design and construction of buildings, the minimum requirements in terms of energy performance of buildings and their certification in accordance with the revised EPBD Measure includes savings based on the new regulations in the construction industry. New regulations on energy performance of buildings prescribe mandatory use of the relevant ISO/EN standards for the energy performance of buildings, and include standards for thermal performance of buildings and other standards relating to the design of buildings and their HVAC systems. Measure also insists on energy certification of buildings.</p>	<p>Provisions (standards and norms)</p>
<p>H3 Promotion of the use of energy-efficient household appliances Measure includes reducing of electricity consumption by introducing energy-efficient household appliances (refrigerators, stoves, washing machines, dishwashers, air conditioners, light bulbs, etc.).</p>	<p>Public information campaigns (information) Energy labeling (mandatory information measures) Financial instruments (subsidies, credit lines)</p>
<i>Public/commercial sub-sector</i>	
<p>PC1 Energy efficiency improvement measures in public/commercial buildings Measure includes energy savings for heating and cooling through the intervention on building envelope (improvement or replacement of external windows and doors, installation or improvement of existing thermal insulation of walls, roofs, ceilings over open passages, walls and floors on the ground, and the other walls to unheated spaces), reducing the energy consumption of HVAC system (better HVAC equipment with automatic control systems, more efficient equipment for biomass combustion, thermal solar collectors use, more effective heating devices - heat pumps, etc.) and reduction of electricity use for lighting (using more energy efficient bulbs, and implementation of other measures for improving the lighting system).</p>	<p>Financial instrument (credit line, subsidy, loan) Energy audit</p>
<p>PC2 New rules for the design and construction of buildings, the minimum re-</p>	<p>Provisions (standards and norms)</p>

Name and description of measure in the Second EEAP	Proposed instruments
<p>Requirements in terms of energy performance of buildings and their certification in accordance with the revised EPBD</p> <p>Measure includes savings based on the new regulations in the construction industry. New regulations on energy performance of buildings prescribe mandatory use of the relevant ISO/EN standards for the energy performance of buildings, and include standards for thermal performance of buildings and other standards related to the design of buildings and their HVAC systems. Measure also insists on energy certification of buildings.</p>	
<p>PC3 Introduction of Energy Management Systems in the public and commercial sector</p> <p>This measure is based on the Law on Efficient Use of Energy. Energy manager who possesses the appropriate license in accordance with the same Law implements this measure. Measure includes:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Collecting and analysing data on energy consumption, proposing measures and activities aimed at increasing energy efficiency, 2) Developing programmes and plans for efficient energy use, 3) Implementing proposed measures and activities, 4) Communication with the Ministry in charge for energy issues, 5) Implementing mandatory periodic energy audits. 	Command and control instrument
<p>PC4 Determination of energy efficiency as one of the criteria for the most economically advantageous tender in public procurement</p> <p>Measure includes energy savings resulting from the procurement of energy-efficient equipment and appliances.</p>	Regulations (Information and mandatory information measures)
<p>PC5 Incentive rates for highly efficient coupled/combined heat and power generation</p> <p>Measure envisages the increasing of energy efficiency in public and commercial buildings through the implementation of projects of combined heat and power generation.</p>	Financial instruments
<p>PC6 Mandatory regular control of the combustion process of boilers and other combustion chambers with the capacity over 20 kW, as well as air conditioning systems</p> <p>This measure includes energy saving achieved by applying periodic control of boilers and other combustion plants, better regulation of the combustion process, and control of heating and air conditioning systems.</p>	Information and mandatory information measures. Regulations

Target groups

The buildings Sector is considered in the second EEAP through the residential and commercial/public sectors. The second EEAP is written without specifying measures that should be directed to specific region or municipality. Measures that target residential or public/commercial sectors are directed to province or local self-governments (municipalities), in the sense that the province or local self-governments (municipalities) are fully or partly responsible for conducting of measures in buildings in their ownership. Except Introduction of Energy Management Systems in the public and commercial sector that is foreseen to municipalities with more than 20,000 inhabitants, all other measures are general and they are related to (national, regional, local) target groups as follows:

- Final energy consumers or end-use technologies in the buildings
 - Existing buildings, lighting systems in existing buildings, HVAC systems in existing buildings (H1, PC1)
 - Reconstructed buildings and new buildings (H2, PC2)
 - Households (H3)
 - Local self-governments with more than 20,000 inhabitants, facilities which are the property of public administration bodies, autonomous province and commercial sector, with energy consumption exceeding the prescribed limits (PC3)
 - Facilities and equipment which are the public sector property (PC4),

- Supply side actors
 - Public and commercial companies, owners of CHP facilities (PC5)
 - Public and commercial companies, owners of boilers and other combustion plants, and air conditioning systems (boilers and other combustion chambers with the capacity over 20 kW, as well as air conditioning systems with the capacity over 12 kW).

Governance framework

At national level, energy efficiency is under the authority of the Ministry of Mining and Energy – Department of Energy Efficiency and Renewable Energy, and this institution is recognized as the key player for implementation of all measures and instruments quoted in the second EEAP related to the buildings sector. Besides this Ministry, the Ministry of Construction and Urban Planning, the Standing Conference of Towns and Municipalities and other relevant institutions at the level of the autonomous province and local self-government are appointed as institutions in charge for implementation of activities related to different measures. Also, for promotion of energy-efficient household appliances the role of market inspection, electricity suppliers, NGOs and consumers associations were emphasized.

A list of all institutions that have an active role in the implementation of the national policy for energy efficiency in the buildings sector is presented in Table 4. Table contains institutions, their main activities/responsibilities, as well as the relevant internet link where additional information can be found.

Table 4: List of institutions active in the buildings sector

Institution	Activities/Responsibilities	Link
Ministry of Mining and Energy- Department for Energy efficiency and Renewable Energy	Preparation of expert basis for drafting laws, proposals of regulations and rulebooks, and harmonization of legislation with EU regulations; development of technical regulations in this area, as well as analysis of the effects of application of those regulations. This department is responsible for carrying out public call procedures and selecting projects that shall be financed from the Budget Fund.	http://mre.gov.rs/energetska-efikasnost.php
Ministry of Construction, Transport and Infrastructure- Department for Construction- Section for energy efficiency and construction products	Main actions or this section related to energy efficiency in the buildings sector are as follows: maintaining register of issued certificates on energy performance of buildings; monitoring the area of energy efficiency and building products in the EU, the world and the Republic of Serbia; drafting technical regulations in the field of construction products and energy efficiency of buildings; improving energy efficiency and building products in the Republic of Serbia.	http://www.mgsi.gov.rs/cir/odsek/odsek-za-energetska-efikasnost-i-gradjevske-proizvode
Ministry of Trade, Tourism and Telecommunications –Sector for Market Inspection	Sector for market inspection deals with affairs regarding inspection surveillance of application of laws and other regulations which govern: trade, online trade, conditions for trade of goods and provision of services, prices of goods and services, coordination and safety of non-food products in production and trade (technical supervision).	http://mtt.gov.rs/en/
Ministry of Education and Science - Department for Science,	These departments are in charge for selecting and monitoring projects funded or co-funded	http://www.mpn.gov.rs/nauka/teh-noloski-razvoj

Department for Technological Development, Technology Transfer and System Innovation	by the state, within the topic energy, mining and energy efficiency.	http://www.mpn.gov.rs/nauka/integralna-i-interdisciplinarna-istrazivanja
Serbian Chamber of Engineers	Main duties of the Serbian Chamber of Engineers concerning energy efficiency in the buildings sector are education of engineers in the field of energy efficiency in buildings, organization of licensing exams, and issuing appropriate licenses.	http://www.ingkomora.org.rs/strucniispiti/?stranica=obukeEE
Standing Conference of Cities and Municipalities - Committee for Communal Services, Urban Planning and Environment	<p>Committee for Communal Services and Energy is a permanent working body of the Conference which consider issues in the field of municipal energy sector from legal, organizational, economic and technical aspects.</p> <p>The Committee monitors, analyzes and discusses issues and problems. In particular it monitors and analyzes the state of the legal framework that regulates issues related to energy efficiency, and municipal energy.</p> <p>The Committee is a forum for exchanging of inter-municipal experience and good practice and to encourage cooperation of cities and municipalities in the area municipal energy and energy efficiency. The Committee provides expert support, suggestions and initiatives for formulation of project activities and directly involved in project development and project activities aimed at capacity building.</p>	http://www.skgo.org/pages/display/103
Provincial Secretariat of Energy and Mineral Resources	Performs complex analytical tasks related to the heat energy in municipal and industrial energy sectors; performs tasks related to the development and implementation of programs to increase energy efficiency in municipal and industrial energy sectors; monitor district heating in autonomous province Vojvodina; proposes measures to encourage more efficient use of energy; prepares analyzes, reports and information, opinions and other materials from the scope of the Sector; develops proposals material work program of the Secretariat in these areas; participates in drafting laws and other regulations in these areas.	http://www.psemr.vojvodina.gov.rs/
Local self-governments	<p>Local self-governments are responsible (with national and other institutions) for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Introduction of energy management systems in the public sector, - Energy efficiency improvement measures in public buildings, - Determination of energy efficiency as one of the criteria for the most economically advantageous tender in public procurement, - Promotion of ESCO model for EE projects financing, - Raising awareness about the energy efficiency importance. 	

2) Transport Sector

Objectives

The transport sector had share of 27.63% in final energy consumption in the basic 2008 (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013). According to new energy balances after 2010, this share decreased to 21.43% in 2011 (Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, 2012). Share of transport sector in the final energy savings according to the Second EEAP should be 28% in 2018.

Planned savings in transport sector according to the Second EEAP should be 0.1032 Mtoe in 2015, and 0.2107 Mtoe in 2018. These **energy efficiency targets for transport sector** represent 1.1% and 2.3%, respectively, of total final energy consumption in 2013 in Serbia (Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, 2014).

Summary of proposed measures and expected savings in the transport sector, in the Second EEAP is presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Summary of proposed measures and expected savings in the Transport Sector

Name of measure in the Second EEAP	Expected savings in 2015 [Mtoe]	Expected savings in 2018 [Mtoe]
Introduction of the EU Regulation EC 443/2009 for energy efficiency in the transport sector	0.0225	0.058
Promotion of eco-driving and car sharing scheme	0.0099	0.0198
Introduction of incentive mechanisms for replacement of the existing vehicles	0.0132	0.0340
Modernization of fleet in order to meet technical requirements for the performance of domestic and international transportation	0.0198	0.0396
Determination of energy efficiency as a criterion for fleet modernization and the assignment of public transport service performance	0.0296	0.0593

The second EEAP does not make further elaboration of significance of energy efficiency for economic development (employment, energy costs), fuel poverty reduction, etc.

Synthesis of policy packages

Policy package defined by the second EEAP is mostly directed to vehicle efficiency. Out of five proposed measures (listed in Table 5), four are related to vehicle efficiency. Only one measure (Promotion of eco-driving and car sharing scheme) is directed to travel efficiency and in less extent to system efficiency.

List of measures, their short description and proposed instruments for their implementation are presented in Table 6. Instruments are quoted as they are proposed in the Second EEAP. Just some of them are completely developed and covered by appropriate regulations.

Table 6: Measures for energy efficiency in the Transport Sector and instruments for their achievement

Name and description of measure in the Second EEAP	Proposed instruments
T1 Introduction of the EU Regulation EC 443/2009 for energy efficiency in the transport sector Measure includes further implementation of the Law on Ratification of the	Provisions (standards and norms)

Name and description of measure in the Second EEAP	Proposed instruments
Agreement on the adoption of unified technical regulations for wheeled vehicles, equipment and parts which can be fitted and/or used on vehicles with wheels and conditions for reciprocal recognition of approvals awarded in line with these regulations ("Official Gazette of the RS - International agreements", No. 11/11)(Government of the Republic of Serbia 2011)	
T2 Promotion of eco-driving and car sharing scheme Changing driving habits and vehicle maintenance, and use of alternative modes of transportation is the main aim of this measure.	Targeted public information campaigns Training and Education
T3 Introduction of incentive mechanisms for replacement of the existing vehicles This measure includes the reduction of energy consumption (as well as CO ₂ emissions) through procurement of vehicles that meet the latest regulations and standards.	Financial instruments (credit line, subsidy, loan)
T4 Modernization of the fleet in order to meet technical requirements for the performance of domestic and international transportation Measure includes regulations for purchasing of new vehicles that meet the latest exhaust emissions standards, or that have low fuel consumption and low CO ₂ emissions for new buses and new commercial vehicles.	Regulations
T5 Determination of energy efficiency as a criterion for fleet modernization and the assignment of public transport service performance This measure envisages setting the requirements for companies which are entrusted with the performance of utilities of public transport to use vehicles that meet the latest regulations on exhaust emissions and have low fuel consumption/CO ₂ emissions (taxis, buses, vans, etc.). Also, measure include purchasing of new vehicles that meet the latest exhaust emissions standards, or that have low fuel (energy) consumption and low CO ₂ emissions.	Voluntary agreements and cooperation instruments (procurement, energy-efficient public procurement technology, commercial and institutional voluntary agreement)

Target groups

The transport Sector was considered in the second EEAP as a whole, but all listed measures are directed to road transport. The second EEAP has not quoted some specific measures directed to specific region or municipality. All measures are directed to (national) target groups, as follows:

- Supply side actors
 - o Importers and car dealers (T1, T3)
- Final energy consumers or end-use technologies
 - o Drivers of passenger vehicles, bus drivers and commercial vehicles drivers; driving instructors, intermediary organisations (fleet managers, driving schools, sectoral organisations, etc.); general public (T2)
 - o Users and/or purchasers of vehicles - both legal and natural persons (T3)
 - o Companies engaged in international road passenger and freight transport (T4)

Government bodies, the autonomous province and local self-government are responsible for Determination of energy efficiency as a criterion for fleet modernization and the assignment of public transport service performance, i.e. implementation of T5 measure.

Governance framework

According to the second EEAP responsibility for implementation of measures in Transport Sector is split between different ministries and governmental institutions. The most of responsible institutions are only indirectly connected to energy related issues and energy efficiency improvement. A favorable circumstance is that actions primary directed to improve safety and efficiency of transport, or to diminish environmental and climate impact, have positive effects from the aspect of energy efficiency. Unfortunately, there are no official coordination mechanisms in place for a national energy efficiency policy in the transport Sector.

Introduction of the EU Regulation EC 443/2009 for energy efficiency in the transport sector is under responsibility of the Road Traffic Safety Agency, the Ministry of Mining and Energy and the Ministry of Interior. This measure is financed from the funding of the Road Traffic Safety Agency, and the Budget of the Republic of Serbia. The Road Traffic Safety Agency and local self-governments should undertake activities for introduction and promotion of eco driving and cars sharing system. Financing of related activities is envisaged from the Road Traffic Safety Agency funds and donations. The Ministry of Transport and the Ministry of Interior are responsible for modernization of the fleet in order to meet technical requirements for the performance of domestic and international transportation. Costs of modernization are responsibility of companies engaged in transportation. As the public transport is the responsibility of local self-governments, they should carry out all activities (including financing) for introduction energy efficiency as a criterion for fleet modernization and the assignment of public transport service performance.

A list of all institutions that have an active role in the implementation of the national policy for energy efficiency in the transport sector is presented in Table 7. Table contains institutions, their main activities/responsibilities, as well as the relevant internet links where additional information can be found.

Table 7: List of institutions that have an active role in the transport sector

Institution	Activities/Responsibilities	Link
Ministry of Mining and Energy- Department for Energy efficiency and Renewable Energy	Preparation of expert basis for drafting laws, proposals of regulations and rulebooks, and harmonization of legislation with EU regulations; development of technical regulations, as well as analysis of the effects of application of those regulations. This department is responsible for carrying out public procurement procedures and selecting projects that shall be financed from the Budget Fund. Program for energy efficiency improvement in the transport within period of three years that shall be prepared by local authorities shall be submitted to the Ministry as well as a report on the implementation of the program.	http://mre.gov.rs/energetska-efikasnost.php
Ministry of Construction, Transport and Infrastructure- De- partment for Transport –Group for Improving roads` traffic safety	Participation in preparation of expert basis for strategies, plans, laws and other regulations in the field of road safety, participation in preparation of plans for financing measures in traffic safety, promotion of traffic safety measures, monitoring and participation in drafting technical requirements of other technical regulations, norms and standards in the field of road safety, defining traffic signalization equipment, devices and systems for regulation and control of traffic.	http://www.mgsi.gov.rs/cir/odsek/grupa-za-unapredjenje-bezbednosti-saobracaja-na-putevima
Ministry of Construction, Transport and Infrastructure- De- partment for Transport –Group for intelligent transport systems	Participation in preparation of expert basis for strategies, plans, laws and other regulations in the field of intelligent transport systems; participation in preparation of plans and funding for intelligent transportation systems; participation in drafting of technical requirements, norms and standards in the field of intelligent transport systems; monitoring and assessment of the implementation of strategies, plans, laws and other regulations and initiates amendments to laws and regulations in the relevant field; preparation of regulations regarding technical require-	http://www.mgsi.gov.rs/cir/odsek/grupa-za-inteligentne-transportne-sisteme

Institution	Activities/Responsibilities	Link
	ments for intelligent systems; improving and defining traffic signals, equipment, devices and systems for traffic management and control.	
Ministry of Construction, Transport and Infrastructure - Department for Transport – Section for rail and intermodal transport	Development of logistics centers and services; making analysis of the situation and problems in the transport of goods and passengers by rail; monitoring the development of modern transport technologies and proposing measures for their encouragement; following up of international regulations in the field of rail and intermodal transport; proposing measures for the development of logistics centers and services; cooperation with other state institutions in order to create a basis for developing a network of intermodal transport terminals.	http://www.mgsi.gov.rs/cir/odsek/odsek-za-zeleznicki-i-intermodalni-transport
Ministry of Interior-Sector for traffic police	Managing traffic safety and monitoring, and improvement of legislation in the field of road safety	http://prezentacije.mup.gov.rs/usp/Organizacija/Odeljenje%20za%20KIRS.html
Road Traffic Safety Agency	Coordinating and performing different tasks: cooperation and coordination with regional and local road traffic safety bodies, offering professional help to the bodies in order to improve traffic safety, creating professional instructions, manuals and guides for improving the work of the local bodies, following international experiences and accomplishments in the field of road traffic safety	http://www.abs.gov.rs/
Ministry of Construction transport and Infrastructure-Department for construction-Section for urban planning	Approval of the general urban plan, general regulation plan of local government and urban development plan; providing technical assistance in the preparation and adoption of urban plans	http://www.mgsi.gov.rs/cir/odsek/oddeljenje-za-planiranje-urbanog-razvoja
Ministry of Trade, Tourism and Telecommunications –Sector for Market Inspection	Coordination of activities of monitoring and improving interdepartmental and regional cooperation in the area of market supervision, making and coordinating of operational interdepartmental plans, market supervision and merging of reports on coordinated market supervision for the Serbian Government, inspection surveillance of application of laws and other regulations which govern: trade, conditions for trade of goods and provision of services, coordination and safety of non-food products in production and trade (technical supervision).	http://mtt.gov.rs/en/sectors-of-the-ministry/sector-for-market-inspection/
Local self-governments	Competent authority of local government with more than 20,000 inhabitants is obliged to adopt a program to improve energy efficiency in the transport within the period of three years. The program shall be submitted to the Ministry as well as the report on the implementation of the program no later than 30 days after the expiry of the period for which the program is adopted. Drafting and adopting Rulebooks on the criteria for the installation of technical traffic calming tools Drafting and adopting urban plans and plans of general regulation Promotion of eco-driving and car sharing scheme	

Institution	Activities/Responsibilities	Link
	Determination of energy efficiency as a criterion for fleet modernization and the assignment of public transport service performance Promotion of ESCO model for EE projects financing Raising awareness about the energy efficiency importance	
Public enterprise Roads of Serbia, Sector for Strategy, Designing and Development	Technical preparation, strategic planning, development research, designing, planning documentation related to traffic safety and environment protection, preparation and record keeping. Definition of policy and strategy for the development of traffic safety on state roads on midterm basis and definition of annual activity plans; Regular follow up and directing of all activities related to traffic safety; Preparation of technical instructions.	http://www.putevi-srbi-je.rs/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=1220&Itemid=555&lang=en
Standing Conference of Cities and Municipalities-Committee for Communal Services, Urban Planning and Environment	The Committee monitors, analyzes and discusses issues and problems and informs Presidency and members of the Conference, agencies, institutions and organizations of the Republic of Serbia and the Autonomous Province and local and international partners of the Conference. In particular it monitors and analyzes the state of the legal framework that regulates issues related to energy efficiency. The Committee provides expert support, suggestions and initiatives for the formulation of project activities and capacity building.	http://www.skgo.org/

1.2 NATIONAL PROGRAMMES AND INITIATIVES

The Republic of Serbia has adopted the Law on Efficient Use of Energy (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013a) and the second EEAP (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013b) in 2013, making a significant step forward towards the transposition of the energy efficiency acquis. However, more should be done in the near future for full implementation of the energy efficiency acquis (Energy Community, 2015). Adoption of the comprehensive set of secondary legislation based on the Law on Efficient Use of Energy is necessary precondition for establishment and implementation of national programs and initiatives aimed to support measures and activities in this field.

The only activity that can be, in some wider context, recognized as national program is **the budget Fund for Energy Efficiency**, as it is planned to be comprehensive mechanism for financing different measures and activities aimed to improve energy efficiency. According to the experience from 2014, one of the priorities of this program is increasing energy efficiency in the buildings sector.

a) General information

The Law on Efficient Use of Energy stipulated the Budget Fund for Energy Efficiency. According to the Law the use of funds from the Budget Fund for Energy Efficiency shall be carried out in accordance with the annual program for funding, adopted by the Government, while the amount of funds allocated to the Fund shall be set out within the Budget of the Republic of Serbia for each year in accordance with the state and possibilities for that year. The Energy Efficiency Fund was established in 2014, when necessary secondary legislatives have been adopted: the Regulation on Program of financing activities and measures for improvement efficient energy use in 2014 (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2014b) and the Rulebook on conditions for allocation and use of the Budget fund

of the Republic of Serbia for improvement energy efficiency and criteria for exemption from energy audit obligation (Ministry of Energy, Development and Environment, 2014a). The first call for funding was announced in 2014. The 11 projects past complete procedure and were selected for funding.

b) Type of program/initiative

The operation of the budget Fund for Energy Efficiency includes economic, regulative and informational aspects.

c) Objectives

The Budget Fund for Energy Efficiency was established with an aim to provide resources for financing activities and projects related to energy efficiency improvement in the Republic of Serbia. The activities and projects that are appropriate for financing are: implementation of different technical measures for improvement of energy efficiency in private, public, commercial, and other facilities, development of energy management system for entities that are not designated organizations, promotion and implementation of energy audits of facilities, production processes and services, introduction of systems for combined heat and power generation for investors that use heat and electrical energy exclusively for own use, development of energy services market in the Republic of Serbia, use of renewable energy sources for electricity and heat generation for individual usage, and all other activities aimed to the improvement of efficiency of energy use.

d) Target group

Target group are natural and legal persons established at the territory of the Republic of Serbia, who are eligible for grants on the basis of open competition. The first open call in 2014 was restricted only to units of self-government (Ministry of Energy, Development and Environment, 2014b). In the buildings sector activities appropriate for financing included: improvement of envelopes of buildings, improvements of heating system and system of internal lighting, or combined activities.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

Funds from the budget Energy Efficiency Fund are available to natural and legal persons established at the territory of the Republic of Serbia who are eligible for grants on the basis of open competition. The Minister in charge of Energy (Ministry of Mining and Energy) prescribes the requirements for the allocation and use of funds from Energy Efficiency Budget Fund, the method of allocation of these funds, as well as the method of monitoring the use of funds and contractual rights and obligations.

f) Implementation network

According to the Law on Efficient Use of Energy and Rulebook on conditions for allocation and use of the Budget fund of Republic of Serbia for improvement energy efficiency and criteria for exemption from energy audit obligation (Ministry of Energy, Development and Environment, 2014h) the most significant role in operation of the budget Energy Efficiency Fund has got the Ministry for Mining and Energy. This Ministry is obliged for selection of projects for funding, as well as for monitoring and verification of project results. In cases where banks co-finance projects, they are also included in processes of selecting and monitoring.

g) Outcomes

During the first call in 2014, 11 municipalities were selected for funding. Total of 98.7 million of dinars (app. 816,000 euro) was allocated. Three municipalities got 100% financing, while the rest got financing up to 70% of total project value (Ministry of Energy, Development and Environment, 2014j). There are no publicly available data about effects of funded projects to energy savings and energy efficiency improvement.

Horizontal measures are proposed in the second EEAP for dealing with institutional, regulatory, and financial and information mechanisms and measures. They are addressing several sectors including

the buildings and transport sectors. Level of implementation of horizontal measures, up to now differs, and there are no specific data about achieved savings. Horizontal measures are listed and their short description is given, as follows:

Billing based on actual (measured) consumption of thermal energy for the consumers connected to district heating system; the Law on the Efficient Use of Energy prescribes this horizontal measure and transition to billing based on heat energy consumption instead of a common practice of billing based on a flat rate. The Law also prescribes an obligation for local district heating companies and local governments to adopt municipal decision in each municipality or city, which has a district heating system, to introduce a new tariff system for billing. Currently only few municipalities (Niš, Šabac, Pančevo,...), of 57 municipalities with DHS, adopted such decision (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2015a). As the support for more efficient implementation of this measure the Methodology for determination of heat energy price was officially prescribed (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2015b).

Promotion of ESCO model for EE projects financing; The Law on the Efficient Use of Energy introduced energy services and energy performance contracting in Serbian energy sector. The ESCO By-Law (Ministry of Mining and Energy, 2015) sets out two models of ESCO agreements, one for public buildings and another one for public lighting, and generally allows public private partnerships to be established between the relevant public partner (e.g. a municipality, a public company, the State) and the relevant private partner (i.e. ESCO company) on a long-term period. Implementation and management of energy efficiency measures by a private partner should be financed from the savings achieved. Still, there is no active ESCO project in Serbia, but there are some projects in a preparation phase.

Obligation to comply with eco-design requirements for products that affect energy consumption; The Law on Efficient Use of Energy envisages that a product shall be placed on the market if it meets the requirements of eco-design. Based on the Law, the Government adopted the adequate Regulation (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013c) and in line with the Regulation, the rulebooks on labeling of energy efficiency of different household appliances were adopted (Ministry of Energy, Development and Environment, 2014 c-g).

Raising awareness about the energy efficiency importance and education; In the period from 2002 to 2012, relevant activities were conducted by the Energy Efficiency Agency. In 2012 the Energy Efficiency Agency ceased to exist, assuming that activities further should be conducted by Ministry of Mining and Energy. Also, significant activities related to this horizontal measure have been undertaken by provincial (Provincial Secretariat for Energy and Mineral Resources, 2015) and local self-governments (Gajic, 2013).

Mandatory dissemination of information to energy consumers on the monthly consumption of electricity and heat, or natural gas; In accordance with the Law on Efficient Use of Energy, public companies and other companies engaged in the distribution and supply of electricity and heat, as well as in distribution and supply of natural gas are obliged to inform the customer, once a month, on the energy bill or along with it, inter alia, on the amount of energy consumed by the customer during the previous month, the average price of energy for the customer in that month, as well as the manners of providing information to the customers about measures for energy efficiency improvement that may be taken, and other relevant data. Information dissemination to the heat customers is applied only during the heating season. Up to now this measure was implemented in electricity sector only (EPS Snabdevanje, 2015).

1.3 CONCLUSIONS AND LESSONS LEARNED OF OTHER PROJECTS ABOUT THE PERFORMANCE OF THE NATIONAL POLICY PACKAGES FOR ENERGY EFFICIENCY

Serbia is not the full member of EU and its participation in EU projects is limited. Still, as a contracting party of the **Energy Community Treaty** performance of national policy packages for energy efficiency are regularly evaluated by the Secretariat of this institution. It was concluded that with the adoption of the Law on Efficient Use of Energy, the second EEAP and the Labeling Regulation, Serbia achieved a significant step forward towards the transposition of the energy efficiency acquis (Energy Community, 2015). But also, it was emphasized what need to be done in the near future for full implementation: "The first priority for Serbia is the finalization and adoption of the comprehensive set of secondary legislation based on the Law on Efficient Use of Energy. The timely adoption of the secondary legislation will also support the implementation of the second EEAP and the achievement of the energy savings target. The second priority is the establishment of a stable and sustainable financing mechanism or mechanisms for effective implementation of the second EEAP. The establishment of the Budgetary Fund for Energy Efficiency is a significant step forward, but the Secretariat is concerned about the sustainability and the limitations posed by the earmarked public budget funds, as well as the possibility to attract other funds and blend these with the public ones in the current legal set up of the Fund. In order to achieve the indicative energy savings target, significant financial resources should be mobilized, in addition to public budget financing. It is necessary to further develop models for public private partnerships in the field of energy efficiency (including ESCOs). The capacities in Serbia should be strengthened in the area of policy-making in the Ministry of Mining and Energy and at the implementation (local) level and in other institutions involved in the second EEAP." (Energy Community, 2015).

State and possibilities of the Serbian buildings sector were only partly analysed in **ENTRANZE Project**. Document "The challenges, dynamics and activities in the building sector and its energy demand in the Republic of Serbia" (Entranze, 2014a) gives an overview of the Serbian building stock until 2010 based on literature review, as well as analysis of energy balance for 2008. In the document "Policy pathways for reducing energy demand and carbon emissions of the EU building stock until 2030" (Entranze, 2014b) expected final energy demand for space heating and preparation of hot water in Serbia in 2008 (base year), 2020, 2030 for three different policy scenarios is given. Scenario 1 refers to a moderate ambitious scenario according to current national and EU legislation, Scenario 2 and 3 are developed assuming more ambitious, innovative and stringent policy packages. However, some in-depth policy discussion wasn't carried out, as well as thorough analysis of the current state of policies in Serbia.

The **IEE Project TABULA**⁷ was aimed at defining common principles for the creation of national typologies of residential buildings. In 2013, the project "Tabula" was finalized, and for the first time the Republic of Serbia provided the classification of buildings in family and multi-family housing. Results of the Tabula project (Jovanovic Popovic et al., 2013) were used during the development of the second EEAP. Development of the National typology of residential buildings in Serbia was the result of the three-year research of the group of professors and researchers from the University of Belgrade - Faculty of Architecture. For the purpose of this project, data of the Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia were partly used, and extensive field research was conducted, including an inventory of approximately 6,000 buildings in 2011, and approximately 13,000 buildings in 2012. Although the "Tabula" defined four basic types of buildings, based on the principle of recognizing specific features of particular countries, in the case of the Republic of Serbia six types of buildings have been defined.

⁷ <http://www.building-typology.eu>

Within the family housing free-standing houses and row houses were defined, and within the multi-family housing, the categories of free-standing building, lamella, buildings in a row and high-rise were defined.

For the each type of buildings, typical elements of a thermal envelope were defined, followed with the calculated heat transfer coefficient. Characteristics of heating and hot water systems, incidence of types in the overall national housing fund, and improvement possibilities were identified. In accordance with the Rulebook on energy efficiency in buildings, for the each building type, annual energy required for heating per m² of heated area, final energy, total energy required for heating the entire heated area of the building, primary energy and carbon dioxide emissions were calculated. For the each building type the energy class was defined. The above data were provided for estimation of potential of energy efficiency improvement of buildings.

Potential energy efficiency improvements in the residential buildings include construction measures to intervene on the thermal envelope of building, as well as improvement of the heating system and domestic hot water system. Possible measures were considered at two levels of improvement: at the first level could be achieved improvement of a minimum one energy class of the building, and at second the maximum range of energy recovery in accordance with the specific characteristics of the building could be expected. Conducted calculations show that the first level of energy recovery could provide savings of a minimum 25% of the energy needed for heating, while the second level of energy recovery could enable savings of almost 70% of the energy needed for heating. In certain cases, by the application of these rehabilitation measures the energy required for heating could be reduced to only 5% of the energy currently used for heating.

IEA Energy Efficiency Policy and Measures Database⁸ includes some indicators and information on energy efficiency policy in Serbia. Although elaborated legislations can be, in wider context, put in relation with energy efficiency, they are primarily directed to RES promotion and feed-in tariff system implementation.

⁸ <http://www.iea.org/policiesandmeasures/energyefficiency/?country=Serbia>

2. INTERACTION BETWEEN THE NATIONAL AND THE SUB-NATIONAL LEVELS

Although national level's authority is dominant in conducting energy efficiency programs and initiatives, regional (Autonomous Province of Vojvodina) and local authorities have important roles in these activities too. Responsibility for implementation of the second Energy Efficiency Action Plan (EEAP) is also attributed to provincial or local governments, within their respective jurisdictions. According to this document local self-governments are responsible (with national and other institutions) for following measures:

- Introduction of energy management systems in the public sector,
- Energy efficiency improvement measures in public buildings,
- Modernization of public lighting system in towns and municipalities,
- Determination of energy efficiency as one of the criteria for the most economically advantageous tender in public procurement,
- Promotion of eco-driving and car sharing scheme,
- Determination of energy efficiency as a criterion for fleet modernization and the assignment of public transport service performance,
- Promotion of ESCO model for EE projects financing,
- Raising awareness about the energy efficiency importance.

In addition, in accordance with the Law on Efficient Use of Energy, both the autonomous province and local self-governments are entitled to establish incentive energy efficiency funds, which are stated as important sources for financing different measures listed in the second EEAP. The provincial Government of Vojvodina set up the Fund for Energy Efficiency and in 2014 and 2015 announced several calls for financing and co-financing energy efficiency projects for local governments, civic society sector and farms (Provincial Government, 2015). At the local level, apart from few initiatives aimed to establishment of energy efficiency funds, (eg. City of Zrejanin) there are still no funds established mostly due to lack of financial resources.

The second EEAP recognizes the need to engage local self-governments in planning, implementation and reporting on energy efficiency measures, and also to strengthen capacities of the local administration.

Operative system of energy management at regional and local level is recognized both in the Law on Efficient Use of Energy and the second EEAP as the precondition for adoption and implementation of energy efficiency programs. The Law on Efficient Use of Energy has defined the framework of local energy management. Autonomous Province and all municipalities with more than 20,000 inhabitants are obliged to establish such system. However, the secondary legislative needed for setting the energy management in place has not been developed yet. As a result, only several municipalities has introduced energy management system and appointed responsible persons. Necessary framework, for successful implementation of the most of measures from national EEAP attributed to provincial or local governments, is still not established.

However, although the role of local authorities in implementing national energy efficiency policy and measures is very important, actually they don't have significant influence on their development.

Some municipalities are not interested to be involved in policy development as they don't recognize the importance of it, or don't have the capacities and knowledge to be involved as they should be. Also, Ministries don't have the appropriate mechanisms to involve municipalities in the development phase. Not being involved in policy development later causes no recognizing numerous obstacles for implementation of the policy instruments (Gajic, 2012). Unlike mentioned absence of communication in developing legislation, communications between the Ministry and local level's authorities in projects concerning infrastructure development in municipalities (kfw project "Rehabilitation of district heating systems in Serbia", World Bank project "Energy Efficiency project in Serbia"...) were more successful.

Currently, the most significant mechanisms for the municipalities to be involved in national activities are public hearings in the biggest municipalities, and activities of the Standing Conference of Towns and Municipalities⁹. This association of Serbian towns and municipalities, through its Committee for Communal Services and Energy, as well as related networks of local professionals, shows significant results in representing municipalities. Representatives of the Association have good relation to line ministries and are regularly invited to working groups that develop different policy documents including national EEAPs.

Also, some of the local authorities in Serbia are very active in different energy efficiency initiatives on national, regional and international level. Concerning the biggest European initiative related to energy and aimed to local authorities, the **Covenant of Mayors**, interest in Serbian municipalities is still very modest compared to other European countries. Currently, 12 Serbian municipalities are signatories, but six of them are on hold, as they have not submitted their SEAPs before the deadline. Only one Serbian city, the City of Niš, has submitted the SEAP¹⁰ to the Covenant of Mayors, which was developed in line with European Commission methodology for the development of Sustainable Energy Action Plan (SEAP). Recognizing the failure of Covenant of Mayors initiative in Serbia, the most active municipalities have gathered around, and formed the Serbian Covenant of Mayors Club¹¹, as their own initiative, looking up to the many national Covenant of Mayors clubs from Europe.

⁹ <http://www.skgo.org>

¹⁰ <http://www.ni.rs/wp-content/uploads/141224-seap.pdf>

¹¹ <http://www.networkingcovenantofmayors.eu/Serbia.html>

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HERON (No: 649690): Deliverable D.1.1

LANDSCAPE OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICY PACKAGES IN A MULTI-LEVEL GOVERNMENT SYSTEM – NATIONAL REPORT FOR UK

DATE 05 AUGUST 2015

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HERON: Forward – looking socio-economic research on Energy Efficiency in EU countries

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649690. The content of this document reflects only the authors' views and the EASME is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Contents

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	4
ACRONYMS	5
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	7
CHAPTER 1: THE ROLE OF GOVERNANCE AND ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICY PACKAGES ON THE NATIONAL LEVEL	8
1.1 POLICY PACKAGES AND POLICY GOVERNANCE IN EUROPEAN MEMBER STATES	8
1.2 NATIONAL PROGRAMMES AND INITIATIVES	21
1.3 CONCLUSIONS AND LESSONS LEARNED OF OTHER PROJECTS ABOUT THE PERFORMANCE OF THE NATIONAL POLICY PACKAGES FOR ENERGY EFFICIENCY	68
CHAPTER 2: INTERACTION BETWEEN THE NATIONAL AND THE SUB-NATIONAL LEVELS	70
REFERENCES	73

Table of Figures

No table of figures entries found.

Table of Tables

Table 1. Policy programmes and initiatives addressing energy efficiency in the UK (in relation to system, travel and vehicle efficiency)	17
Table 2 National programmes and initiatives in buildings	21
Table 3 National programmes and initiatives in transport	50
Table 4 Horizontal policy measures	66

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 649690. The content of this document reflects only the authors' views and the EASME is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

ACRONYMS

BAT	Best available technologies
BESN	Big Energy Saving Network
BIS	Department for Business Innovation and Skills
CARES	Community Renewable Energy Scheme
CCA	Climate Change Agreements
CCL	Climate Change Levy
CCS	Carbon Capture and Storage
CERT	Carbon Emission Reduction Target
CESP	Community Energy Saving Programme
CHP	Combined Heat and Power
CSCO	Carbon Saving Community Obligation
CSE	Centre for Sustainable Energy
CSH	Code for Sustainable Homes
CO ₂	Carbon Dioxide
DCLG	Department for Communities and Local Government
DEC	Display Energy Certificates
DECC	Department of Energy and Climate Change
Defra	Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs
DfT	Department for Transport
DH	Department of Health
DNO	District network operators
ECA	Enhanced Capital Allowances
ECO	Energy Company Obligation
EDR	Electricity Demand Reduction
EE	Energy Efficiency
EED	Energy Efficiency Directive
EPBD	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
EPC	Energy Performance Certificate
EPSRC	Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council
ESCO	Energy service company
ESME	Energy system modelling environment
ESOS	Energy Savings Opportunity Scheme
EST	Energy Saving Trust
ETI	Energy Technology Institute
EU	European Union
EV	Electric Vehicles
FIT	Feed-in Tariff
GD ORB	Green Deal Oversight and Registration Body
GGC	Greening Government Commitments
GHG	Green House Gas
HEaT	Household Efficiency and Thermal improvement Programme (NI)
HEEPS	Home Energy Efficiency Programmes for Scotland
HGV	heavy goods vehicles
HNDU	Heat Networks Delivery Unit

ICE	Incentive on Connections Engagement
IEA	International Energy Agency
IPEEC	International Partnership for Energy Efficiency Cooperation
ITOs	instructor training organisations
LEBS	Low Emission Bus Scheme
LESA	Landlords Energy Saving Allowance
MEPS	Minimum energy performance standards
NI	Northern Ireland
NIEA	Northern Ireland Environment Agency
NISEP	Northern Ireland Sustainable Energy Programme
NRMM	Non-road mobile machinery
NRW	Natural Resources Wales
Ofgem	Office of Gas and Electricity Markets
OLEV	Office for Low Emission Vehicles
PHEV	Plug-in hybrid electric vehicles
PICG	Plug-In Car Grant
PiP	Plugged-In Places programme
RCEF	Rural Community Energy Fund
RCEP	Research Councils Energy Programme
RHI	Renewable Heat Incentive
RTFO	Renewable Transport Fuel Obligation
SAFED	Safe and Fuel Efficient Driving
SBRI	Small Business Research Initiative
SEPA	Scottish Environment Protection Agency
SME	Small Medium Enterprises
SOGE	Sustainable Operations on the Government Estate
TSB	Technology Strategy Board
TWh	terawatt-hours
UK	United Kingdom
ULEV	Ultra-Low Emissions Vehicles
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
UREF	Urban Community Energy Fund
VED	Vehicle Excise Duty
VERA	Vehicle and Registration Act
VCA	Vehicle Certification Agency
ZCH	Zero Carbon Hub

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This paper presents the United Kingdom's policy packages, programmes and initiatives (with horizontal policy measure analysis) for increasing the take-up of energy efficiency in the building and transport sectors; and information on policy governance and the interaction between national and sub-national levels in the UK.

The first chapter of this paper presents an overview of the policy packages and policy governance in the UK, descriptions of approximately 18 building sector policy programmes and initiatives and 15 transport sector policy programmes and initiatives with information for each covering: type of policy instrument, objectives, target groups, rules and influencing mechanisms, and implementation network. The first chapter closes with a tabular presentation of policy measures with horizontal application, followed by a section on conclusions and lessons learned from other projects about the performance of the UK's policy packages and energy efficiency approach.

The second (and final) chapter provides an explanation of the relationship and interaction between the national and sub-national levels with regard to energy efficiency policy and meeting EU requirements.

CHAPTER 1: THE ROLE OF GOVERNANCE AND ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICY PACKAGES ON THE NATIONAL LEVEL

1.1 POLICY PACKAGES AND POLICY GOVERNANCE IN THE UK

Here is the **list of main national official documents** describing policy packages for energy efficiency:

- UK National Energy Efficiency Action Plan. It was prepared by the Department of Energy and Climate Change in April 2014. The document details the progress the UK has made on energy efficiency and the further action being taken to further realise the ambition of achieving the 2020 energy efficiency target.
https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/307993/uk_national_energy_efficiency_action_plan.pdf (DECC, 2014c)
- The UK's Sixth National Communication and First Biennial Report under the UNFCCC. This document was prepared by the Department of Energy and Climate Change in December 2013. The document documents a comprehensive overview of climate change related activity in the UK including the progress made to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and to adapt to the effects of a changing climate.
[https://unfccc.int/files/national_reports/annex_i_natcom/submitted_natcom/application/pdf/uk_6nc_and_br1_2013_final_web-access\[1\].pdf](https://unfccc.int/files/national_reports/annex_i_natcom/submitted_natcom/application/pdf/uk_6nc_and_br1_2013_final_web-access[1].pdf) (HM Government, 2013)
- The Energy Efficiency Strategy: The Energy Efficiency Opportunity in the UK. This document was prepared by the Department of Energy and Climate Change in November 2012. The document provided the strategy which set the direction for energy efficiency policy for the future, giving details of the ambition, the barriers and the further steps needed to stimulate the energy efficiency market.
https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/65602/6927-energy-efficiency-strategy--the-energy-efficiency.pdf (DECC, 2012a)
- The Carbon Plan: Delivering our Low Carbon Future. This document was prepared by the Department of Energy and Climate Change in December 2011. The document presents the plan for how the UK will achieve decarbonisation within the framework of the country's energy policy.
https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/47613/3702-the-carbon-plan-delivering-our-low-carbon-future.pdf (DECC, 2011a)
- Low Carbon Transport: A Greener Future – A Carbon Reduction Strategy For transport. This document was prepared by the Department for Transport in July 2009. The document presents a strategy that is intended to enable the UK to meet the requirements of the carbon budgets set under the Climate Change Act 2008 by reducing greenhouse gas emissions from transport systems.
https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/228897/7682.pdf (Department for Transport, 2009)

- Low Carbon Transport Innovation Strategy. This document was prepared by the Department for Transport in May 2007. It sets out a framework through which the UK Government will encourage innovation and technology development in lower carbon transport technologies. <http://webarchive.nationalarchives.gov.uk/20081022212629/http://www.dft.gov.uk/pgr/scienceresearch/technology/lctis/lctisdocpdf> (Department for Transport, 2007)

1) Buildings Sector

Objectives

- The 2011 Carbon Plan sets out scenarios through which the UK could meet its legally binding target to reduce greenhouse gas emissions (GHG) by 80% between 1990 and 2050 (DECC, 2011a). The Carbon Plan 2050 scenarios require energy efficiency to contribute a reduction in final energy consumption per capita between 2007 and 2050 of 31-54% (Scenario 4: High energy efficiency and higher renewables (54% energy per capita saving from 2007 baseline)). After moving to a 2011 baseline, these Carbon Plan Scenarios now require per capita savings of between 21% and 47% between 2011 and 2050 (House of Commons, 2013).
- **Economic development:** The Government has investigated the links between energy efficiency and business productivity, and the evidence demonstrates that improvements in energy efficiency drive productivity gains for businesses. Beyond energy savings delivered through energy efficiency investment, businesses stand to benefit from reduced maintenance costs, improved working conditions, and potential for expanded markets. As firms benefit from higher productivity, this contributes to higher economic growth. Policies such as the Green Deal and Energy Company Obligation (ECO), smart meters, and the Renewable Heat Incentive (RHI) are spurring the development of new markets and technologies, and are there to help consumers cut the cost of their energy bills (DECC, 2013). Government policies are designed to play an important role in driving economic growth, by supporting jobs, driving cost-effective energy savings, and improving health outcomes. By 2014 the energy efficiency market employed around 136,000 people in the UK, is worth more than £18 billion annually, and delivers exports valued at nearly £1.9 billion per year (DECC, 2014d). Installing energy efficiency measures often requires local labour, and the investment has the potential to boost employment and economic growth. The business community see this as important. There are also long-term growth benefits. For example, lower domestic energy bills can lead to higher disposable incomes that can be spent elsewhere in the economy, while businesses can see a reduction in running costs and so an increase in productivity. Simple changes in energy use behaviour can deliver some of these benefits with little up-front cost (DECC, 2012a). Deployment of low carbon energy technologies and increased energy efficiency are key to economic development. Energy efficiency improvements can reduce **fuel poverty** and promote economic growth. Despite pressure on public spending, funding for science and research programmes has been protected in cash terms, demonstrating the government's commitment to rebalancing the economy and promoting economic growth. For the first time, Higher Education

research funding in England has been included within this ring-fence, providing stability and certainty to both parts of the dual support system of research funding (HM Government, 2013).

- **Legal provisions:** The Government wants to help businesses cut the cost of their energy bills, and reduce their energy consumption and carbon emissions, through improved energy efficiency. To complement existing schemes, such as the non-domestic RHI and the CRC Energy Efficiency Scheme, the Government enacted the legal framework for the non-domestic Green Deal in January 2013 (DECC, 2013b). The UK Government introduced the Energy Savings Opportunity Scheme (ESOS) which places a new legal requirement on large enterprises to conduct energy audits which meet the requirements of Article 8(4) and Annex VI of the Directive. This scheme will be mandatory for all large UK undertakings (of which there is estimated to be around 7,300 in the UK). Ensuring that energy customers receive frequent, accurate bills is a priority for Government. That is why the Government has placed legal obligations upon suppliers to roll out smart meters to all domestic premises and smart or advanced meters to smaller non-domestic sites by 2020. In addition to this, the government has a number of measures in place to ensure that bills are frequent, accurate and clear. The Government is committed to supporting a competitive energy services market. The UK has long-established routes for dispute resolution and a comprehensive legal framework which prohibits anti-competitive practices (DECC, 2014d).
- **Fuel poverty:** Under the proposed new measurement approach, a household is fuel poor if it is low income and has high energy costs relative to all other households. A key factor driving energy costs is energy efficiency. As such, the Government's new strategy will set out how energy efficiency improvements can be made in such households, to provide a sustainable means of reducing costs (DECC, 2012a). Working hand in hand with the Green Deal, the current ECO has been providing support to tackle 'hard to treat' properties, like those with non-standard cavity or solid walls, and supporting installations in the homes of low income and vulnerable people. ECO is an essential part of the Government's package to tackle fuel poverty (DECC, 2013b).

Synthesis of policy packages

- **Targeting supply and demand:** Comprehensive policy packages such as the Green Deal (packaged with ECO, RHI, Feed in Tariffs (FiTs)) target energy demand and supply in the building sector.
- **The Green Deal:** provides loans to improve the energy efficiency and energy generation of dwellings or small commercial buildings. The Green Deal qualifies under *economic, capacity building and networking, and best available technology promotion policy instruments*.
- **ECO:** Legally requires energy providers to improve the energy efficiency of vulnerable, fuel poor, and hard to treat homes. The ECO qualifies under *regulatory instruments*.
- **RHI and FiT:** Are subsidies to promote the uptake of renewable heat technologies and renewable electricity technologies respectively. The RHI and FiT qualify under *economic, capacity building and networking, and best available technology promotion policy instruments* (DECC, 2014d).

Target Groups

GHG emissions reductions policies cover the following sectors: *Energy supply, Industry, Transport, Building (business, domestic, public sector), Agriculture, forestry and land management, and Waste.*

- **National target groups:** Government departments, industry and business, and individuals.
- **Regional division of policy focus:** England, Wales, Scotland, Northern Ireland
- **Local target groups:** Following the government's prioritisation of local control, Local Authorities are the target groups with regard to locally focussed implementation of policy.

Governance framework

The following governmental actors are active in the field of energy efficiency (national governance level):

1. Department of Energy and Climate Change (DECC)

DECC is the UK's government ministerial department responsible for the functions related to energy and climate change. Their work is to make sure the UK has secure, clean, affordable energy supplies and promote international action to mitigate climate change. There are 13 policies from DECC and these are:

- Business and the environment
- Climate change impact in developing countries
- Climate change international action
- Energy and climate change: evidence and analysis
- Energy demand reduction in industry, business and the public sector
- Energy industry and infrastructure licensing and regulation
- Export controls
- Greenhouse gas emissions
- Household energy
- Low carbon technologies
- Radioactive and nuclear substances and waste
- UK energy security
- Weapons proliferation

The responsibilities of DECC¹ are:

- Energy security – making sure UK businesses and household have secure supplies and energy
- Action on climate change – leading government efforts to mitigate climate change and achieve the UK target of 80% reduction in emissions by 2050
- Renewable energy – sourcing at least 15% of the UK's energy from renewable sources by 2020
- Affordability – delivering secure, low carbon energy at the least cost
- Fairness – ensuring that the cost and benefits of their policies are distributed fairly

¹ <https://www.gov.uk/government/organisations/department-of-energy-climate-change>

- Supporting growth – delivering policies in a way that maximises the benefits to the economy
- Managing UK's energy legacy fairly, securely and cost effectively

2. Department for Communities and Local Government (DCLG)

DCLG is the UK's governmental ministerial department responsible for creating great places to live, work and give more power to local people to shape what happens in their area. This department is supported by 10 policies which include:

- Building regulation
- Energy efficiency in buildings
- House building
- Rented housing sector
- Emergency planning

The responsibilities of the DCLG² are:

- Supporting local government by giving them power to act for their community
- Helping communities and neighbours to solve their own problems
- Working with local enterprise partnerships to help the private sector grow
- Making the planning system work more efficiently and effectively
- Supporting local fire and rescue authorities

3. Local Councils / Local Government Association³

Local councils are responsible for services which include housing and most of the local councils have an aim to explore how they can help their residents reduce their energy bills as well as unlocking the full potential of energy efficiency schemes. The local councils have experience in areas that are developing and/or delivering energy efficiency schemes using a range of funding options and working with a range of partners. The local government association is a politically-led organisation that works on behalf of the local councils. From the case studies, the LGA have shown that locally-led schemes are often the most effective as the councils have first-hand knowledge about their communities and so are able to tailor schemes which target specific factors such as housing type and density and income and deprivation.

The following non-governmental and sub-national actors are active in the field of energy efficiency:

1. Energy Saving Trust⁴ (charity)

The Energy Saving Trust is a leading and trusted independent national organisation committed to promoting energy efficiency, energy conservation and a move to sustainable, low carbon lifestyles.

²<https://www.gov.uk/government/organisations/department-for-communities-and-local-government>

³ <http://www.local.gov.uk/home>

⁴ <http://www.energysavingtrust.org.uk/>

Their main goals are to achieve sustainable use of energy and cut carbon emissions in order to help the UK achieve its commitment to reduce carbon emissions by 80% by 2050. The services and activities provided by the Energy Saving Trust include:

- Free advice and action plans for energy saving to a range of customers (individuals through to organisations both in the private and public sectors)
- Testing of low carbon technology and energy-saving certification and accreditation services
- Management or delivery of government programmes
- Development of energy-efficient models and tools.

These services and activities are achieved through the following:

- Research and reports – the work of the Energy Saving Trust is underpinned by pioneering world-renowned research and they are committed to discovering novel ways of accelerating a move to a sustainable future
- Partners and supporters – the Energy Saving Trust works in partnership with a wide range of UK based and international organisations in order to achieve, far more than they could on their own, their commitment to help people save energy daily
- Foundation – they have set up the first energy research foundation in the UK to drive research, knowledge and insight into community energy
- Corporate social responsibility and sustainability – to manage their impact on the environment (e.g. energy efficiency, waste management, water efficiency)

2. Carbon Trust⁵

The Carbon Trust is an independent UK company that helps organisations reduce their carbon emissions and increase their resource efficiency. Their mission is to accelerate the move to a sustainable, low carbon economy. The services provided by the Carbon Trust include:

- Business advice – they provide advice to businesses, the government and the public sector on their opportunities to develop sustainable strategies to deliver savings. These are based on current and future sustainability challenges
- Carbon footprinting – they measure, verify and certify the environmental footprint of organisations, products and services.
- Developing clean technology – they work with partners such as the Government and innovators to develop and deploy low carbon technologies

3. Building Research Establishment⁶ (private research)

The Building Research Establishment (BRE) is a multidisciplinary building science centre with a mission to improve buildings through research, consultancy and testing. The BRE's work also includes participation in the preparation of the UK Building Regulations and other international building standards and codes. The main roles and responsibilities of the BRE are:

⁵ <http://www.carbontrust.com/client-services/advice/policy-markets/>

⁶ <https://www.bre.co.uk/index.jsp>

- Research and innovation – to generate and apply advanced knowledge through a diverse set of built environment projects including sustainable building design and innovative construction materials
- Sustainability – through the development and implementation of sustainable standards such as BREEAM (Building Research Establishment Assessment Methodology) to ensure a reduction in the environmental impact of the built environment (from design through to use of buildings).
- Consultancy – providing expert advice on every aspect of the built environment for both new and retrofitted buildings
- Testing – providing a unique range of test facilities to test building systems and materials against published standards
- Certification – providing certification for environmental products and services. BRE's certification provides confidence about the performance of the product and the service as well as distinguishing them from their competitors

4. Association for Environment Conscious Building (AECB)⁷ (not-for profit network, independent certification)

The AECB is a network of individuals and companies (e.g. builders, architects, students, local authorities, etc.) with a common aim of promoting sustainable building. The mission of the association is to increase awareness within the construction industry of the need to protect, preserve and enhance the environment and to develop and promote best practice in environmentally sustainable building. The AECB is focussed on helping to reduce the UK carbon emission related to both domestic and non-domestic buildings. They have therefore developed two advanced standards to promote low-carbon buildings.

5. Salix Finance⁸ (Financial)

Salix Finance enables public sector organisations across the UK to take a lead in tackling climate change by increasing their energy efficiency. They provide 100% interest-free capital for the public sector to reduce their energy cost through installation of modern and improved energy efficient technologies.

6. The Low Carbon Communities Network⁹

The Low Carbon Communities Network was formed to link, network and support the growing movement of climate change groups that are forming at local and community levels. They work with communities (households, schools, businesses) to find climate change and sustainable energy solutions which includes both technical and behavioural measures. Their roles and responsibilities include:

⁷ <https://www.aecb.net/>

⁸ <http://salixfinance.co.uk/>

⁹ <http://www.lowcarboncommunities.org/>

- Working alongside national and international communities and organisations to reduce the impact of global warming
- Encouraging the adoption of low and zero carbon technologies
Offering support in the identification of high impact, positive and achievable local solutions to tackling climate change
Enabling local level influence on local and national government policy and practice

7. Westminster Sustainable Business Forum (WSBF)¹⁰

The WSBF is an independent, not-for-profit high-level coalition of UK businesses, parliamentarians, civil servants and other organisations seeking to promote effective sustainability policy in order to maximise opportunities in the transition to a low carbon economy. The WSBF campaigns in various policy areas and this includes areas of sustainable construction and sustainable infrastructure.

2) Transport Sector

Objectives

- Through the Climate Change Act 2008, the UK is committed to reducing GHG emissions across the economy by at least 34% by 2020 and by at least 80% in comparison to 1990 levels by 2050 (refer to building sector above for more detail on carbon budgets). The transport sector in the UK will contribute to national long-term energy efficiency targets by:
 - Sourcing 10% of transport's energy from sustainably produced renewables by 2020.
 - 16% reduction from 2005 levels in GHG by 2020 for domestic transport.
 - Though international aviation and shipping are not part of the UK's domestic targets, aviation is bound into the 2020 EU level targets; furthermore, the UK government expects the air transport industry to bring emissions from UK aviation below 2005 levels by 2050 (DCLG, 2010b).
- **Economic development:** The Local Transport White Paper Creating Growth, Cutting Carbon – Making Local Sustainable Transport Happen (January 2011) represented a significant step towards meeting two key Coalition government objectives: helping to create economic growth by making sure people can get to work, to the shops or their local amenities; and tackling climate change by cutting transport carbon emissions through encouraging more low-carbon journeys. In addition, the government is committed to cutting red tape that can stifle cycle-friendly road design and to encourage changes to the way roads are built or altered. Councils will be expected to deliver infrastructure that takes cycling into account from the design stage. DfT will publish a Cycle Delivery Plan in coming months and will continue to work with other departments, local authorities and stakeholders to increase cycling as a means to reduce transport emissions and improve economic growth (HM Government, 2013).

¹⁰ <http://www.policyconnect.org.uk/wsbf/about>

- **Equality of opportunity** benefits are expected to result from the provision of accessible public transport, and broadening the range of transport choices available are important tools for delivering a fairer society (DfT, 2009).
- **Multiple benefits** of transport changes proposed:
 - Overall the transport strategy has the benefit of reducing reliance on oil and import requirements
 - Ultra low emission vehicles and low carbon buses reduce carbon emissions and air pollutants.
 - Cycling and walking as means of travel reduces emissions and is beneficial for health, reduction in obesity, improvement in performance, reducing congestion and improving local air quality.
 - Electric trains can reduce emissions (depending on electricity source) and can increase capacity and reliability, as well as offering a more comfortable passenger experience. In addition, electric trains are significantly cheaper to buy, maintain and operate than diesels which can help to reduce the overall cost of running the railway.
 - Shifting freight movements from road to rail or water brings benefits such as reducing both congestion and improving local air quality.
 - Quality of life benefits are expected from the development of sustainable travel solutions, particularly in urban areas – by reducing traffic volumes and noise (DfT, 2009).

Synthesis of policy packages

- **Comprehensive policy packages:**
 - To further progress in the transport sector the Government has implemented a long-term comprehensive package of support for the Ultra-Low Emissions Vehicle (ULEV) sector. In 2013 £500m was invested to support the development of the ULEV market from 2015-2020, which builds on the £400m previously committed. The package covers R&D and supply chain support (supply) and cleaner fuel (for HGVs) or electric charging station infrastructure (demand). The expectation is that by 2050 almost every car and van in the UK will be an ULEV. Toward this goal, in 2013 the Government announced a £37m package of measures including grants for the installation of home, on-street and train station charging points. Additionally, the uptake of ultra-low emission cars is promoted through the provision of consumer grants. By the end of the calendar year 2013, 6709 claims have been made through the Plug-in Car Grant scheme and 404 claims have been made through the Plug-in Van Grant scheme (DECC, 2014d; OLEV, 2014).
 - Previous package: Green Bus Fund (affecting both supply and demand) and the Safe and Fuel Efficient Driving (SAFED) training for bus drivers (demand) finished funding in 2009.
- **Policy components:**

The UK's energy efficiency transport policy has several components, including regulatory, planning, economic and awareness policy instruments; which are described in further detail in section 1.2. These policy instruments address all three dimensions of transport and are based on

the National Infrastructure Plan¹¹. Table 1 outlines the policy programmes and initiatives addressing energy efficiency in the transport sector.

The UK policy uses EU legislation as the basis for their transport-related energy efficiency policy; examples of this are the Renewable Energy Directive (Directive 2009/28/EC)¹² and the Fuel Quality Directive (Directive 2009/30/EC)¹³ which has led to financial incentive policy instruments such as the Renewable Transport Fuel Obligation. Part of the UK's transport energy efficiency policy packages include the funding of research and development through research councils such as the Technology Strategy Board (TSB) and the Research Council Energy Programme (RCEP). Such research and development programmes cover all aspects of improving transport efficiency; system, travel and vehicle. An example of this is that currently there is a significant drive in terms of developing ultra-low emissions vehicles (ULEVs) through TSB/Innovate UK's Low Carbon Vehicle Innovation Platform¹⁴. The main goals of this research platform is to contribute to the growth of the UK automotive sector, increase and speed the introduction of vehicle-centric technologies to the low carbon vehicles market and to help the UK reduce greenhouse gas emissions caused by road transport. In 2014-15, the government invested over £45 million in transport in order to provide consistent and long-term support for the transport sector in order to achieve the goals of the research platform.

The UK's energy efficiency policy is also supported by policies that do not directly have energy efficiency as their primary goal. Examples of these are the road transport codes and the congestion charges. Whilst the aims of these are to relieve traffic congestion in urban areas such as London (congestion charges), improve air quality (congestion charges) and road safety (road transport codes), they also positively impact the energy efficiency of the transport sector through encouraging the improvement of vehicle efficiency, shifting to more energy efficient modes of travel (travel efficiency) and reducing the number of private cars on the roads (system efficiency).

Table 1. Policy programmes and initiatives addressing energy efficiency in the UK's transport sector

Policy component	System efficiency	Travel efficiency	Vehicle efficiency
Policy programmes and initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Eco-towns: A supplement to Planning Policy Statement 1 • (Ultra-) Low Carbon Emissions Zones at local authority/regional level e.g. London 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Eco Driving training (included in national driving tests and beyond national driving test / Fuel Good Driver Training for business fleets) • Cycle to Work Scheme 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HGV policies (low rolling resistance tyres and industry-led action to improve efficiencies) • Vehicle Excise Duty (VED): fuel type and CO2 emission vehicle bands

¹¹https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/381884/2902895_NationalInfrastructurePlan2014_acc.pdf

¹² <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32009L0028>

¹³ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32009L0030>

¹⁴https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/458740/CO089__LCV_IP_S EP15_Brochure_FINAL.pdf

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Renewable Energy Directive • Fuel Quality Directive • Energy Savings Opportunity Scheme (ESOS) • Research and Development Funding e.g. Research Council Energy Programme (RCEP) and Technology Strategy Board (TSB) / Innovate UK 	<p>(Green Transport Plan)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The National Standard for cycle training • Road transport codes (speed limits etc.) • Plugged-in Places (The Plug-In Vehicle Infrastructure Strategy) • Rail Electrification • Plug-in car and van grants (including Electric Vehicle Home charge Scheme) • Low Emission Bus Scheme (LEBS) (successor scheme to the Green Bus Fund) • Research and Development Funding e.g. Research Council Energy Programme (RCEP) and Technology Strategy Board (TSB) / Innovate UK 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Renewable Transport Fuel Obligation (RTFO) / Fuel Quality Directive • Fuel Economy labels for cars • Research and Development Funding e.g. Research Council Energy Programme (RCEP) and Technology Strategy Board (TSB) / Innovate UK
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Target groups

- **National target groups:** Government departments, industry and business (for example, Freight Transport Association Logistics Carbon Reduction Scheme, UK Government funding for advanced biofuel research, and Energy Savings Opportunity Scheme (ESOS)), and individuals (Eco Driving training included in national driving tests).
- **Regional division of policy focus:** England, Wales, Scotland, Northern Ireland
- **Local target groups:** Following the government’s prioritisation of local control, Local Authorities are the target groups with regard to locally focussed implementation of policy (for example, Local Sustainable Transport Fund).

Governance framework

The following are actors active in the field of energy efficiency in the transport sector:

Energy efficient infrastructures:

- **Department for Transport (DfT)**¹⁵ is the primary Government department responsible for the Carbon Reduction Strategy for Transport. Their main roles are to support the transport network and to plan and invest in transport infrastructure to keep the UK on the move. Their responsibilities include:
 - Providing policy, guidance and funding to local authorities to run, maintain and develop their transport schemes

¹⁵ <https://www.gov.uk/government/policies?organisations%5B%5D=department-for-transport>

- Encouraging the use of new technology such as low carbon vehicles
- Promoting low carbon transport to reduce congestion and pollution
- Maintaining high standards of safety and security
- Improving the English bus service through funding and regulation

The DfT have also set aside their priorities and these include tackling congestion and improving road safety. Promoting lower carbon transport and introducing more environmentally-friendly buses and trains and supporting the development of the market for electric and other ultra-low emission vehicles and one of the policies from the DfT is transport emissions.

- **Scottish Government – Transport Scotland**¹⁶ is the Scottish transport agency and has responsibility for all transport related issues across Scotland and delivers the Scottish Government’s vision for transport. The Scottish Government’s transport responsibilities include:
 - Commitment to almost complete decarbonisation of the road transport sector by 2050
 - Improve accessibility for people with mobility difficulties about road, rail, public transport and other modes of travel
 - Using the latest technology to deliver up to date travel information for Scotland
 - Prioritising and maintaining Scotland’s trunk road network
- **Welsh Government**¹⁷ – **Transport** is the government sector responsible for all transport related issues across Wales. They have a transport planning and strategy which aims to improve transport in order to keep Wales connected, improve the economy and safeguard the environment. This strategy is implemented through policies and programmes and it is delivered through the National Transport Finance Plan. They also provide guidance for local authorities to deliver their individual local transport plans.
- **The Office for Low Emission Vehicles (OLEV)**¹⁸ is a team that works across Government departments (DfT, Department for Business Innovation and Skills (BIS), and DECC) to support the market for ULEVs. They are providing funding over £900 million to position the UK at the global forefront ultra-low emission vehicle development, manufacture and use which will help to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and air pollution on the roads. The policy from OLEV is transport emissions and they are responsible for:
 - Grants to reduce the upfront cost of new ULEVs
 - Raising awareness, developing and strengthen the capability of ULEV manufacturing, demonstration and the associated UK supply chain
 - A nationwide recharging infrastructure strategy
 - Contributing to the development of new carbon dioxide emissions standards

¹⁶ <http://www.transportscotland.gov.uk/>

¹⁷ <http://gov.wales/topics/transport/?lang=en>

¹⁸ <https://www.gov.uk/government/organisations/office-for-low-emission-vehicles>

- A programme of research and support of wider green growth opportunities

Their priorities include developing new initiatives to overcome barriers to uptake ULEVs, providing grants to reduce the upfront cost of new ULEVs, work with industry in the next phase of the joint industry-government project on hydrogen for transport and support research and development and the ULEV supply chain.

- **Energy Saving Trust – Improving my travel¹⁹** – The Energy Saving Trust provides information and valuable advice to help drivers improve their travel and achieve a greener journey. This includes information and advice on driving smarter, electric vehicles and planning journeys.

Funding resources:

- OLEV – £500m investment for all things ULEV, e.g. £20m of this amount, supplemented by up to a further £10m from the Low Carbon Strategic Investment Fund, was made available for electric vehicle charging infrastructure.
- Big Lottery Fund - £50m to Connect2, a nationwide project aimed at creating dedicated, high quality local walking and cycling networks, benefiting an estimated 6m people across the UK (the UK public voted the scheme the winner of the People's Millions Lottery contest).
- DfT - £50m of cycling funding over three years in 18 towns and cities across England (investment is matched by the local authorities).
- DfT - £140m to the Technology Strategy Board's 'Low Carbon Vehicle Innovation Platform'.
- DfT - £30m over 2009/10 and 2010/11 for low carbon bus technology. Bus operators could apply for grants to contribute towards the additional up-front cost of buying a low carbon bus.
- DfT funds EST to deliver consumer transport advice directly to the public through their network of fourteen regional advice centres in England (DfT, 2009).

Policies in a number of government departments have synergistic relationships with the reduction of GHG from the transport sector.

- With the Department of Health (DH) and the Department for Children, Schools and Families, the DfT are encouraging children to walk or cycle to school which not only brings transport benefits such as reduction of congestion and emissions, but health benefits, reduction in obesity and improved school performance.
- DfT are also working with DH to promote cycling more broadly in funding Cycling England and Bike4Life.
- DfT are working with the BIS to maximise the benefits for the UK of the transition to ULEVs.
- DfT are working with DCLG to align both planning and the performance framework for local authorities with transportation goals.

¹⁹ <http://www.energysavingtrust.org.uk/domestic/improving-my-travel-0>

- DfT are working with DECC to promote increasing fuel efficient and diversification of transport energy sources (DfT, 2009).

1.2 NATIONAL PROGRAMMES AND INITIATIVES

Table 2 National programmes and initiatives in buildings

1. Regulatory policy instruments
1.1 Building regulations Part L (conservation of fuel and power)
<p>a. General information: The legislative framework of the Building Regulations is principally made up of The Building (Approved Inspectors etc) Regulations 2010 (SI 2010/2215) and the Building Regulations Legislation 2010 (SI 2010/2214)²⁰. ‘Approved Documents’ support the fourteen technical ‘Parts’ of the Building Regulations, and Regulation 7 (workmanship and materials) and aim to provide supporting guidance to show builders how compliance with building regulations may be achieved. First implemented in the 1980s, fabric energy efficiency is enforced through Approved Document Part L of the UK Building Regulations²¹ and has been progressively tightening over time to make buildings more energy efficient, e.g. towards the approach of the Zero Carbon Homes Standard in 2016 (DECC, 2014c). As of this year however, progression toward the 2016 Standard is no longer part of the Government’s plan (HM Treasury, 2015). Building Regulations are devolved across the four UK administrations but energy standards are broadly comparable in content, scope and in the levels of improvement delivered (DECC, 2014c). Amendments are too numerous to list here but most notably the Part L split into four Approved Documents from 2006 to encompass New dwellings (L1A), Existing Dwellings (L1B), New Buildings other than Dwellings (L2A) and Existing Buildings other than dwellings (L2B) (BRAC & DCLG, 2015).</p> <p>b. Type of policy instrument: Regulatory, it is required that all new buildings and additions meet or exceed specified fabric energy efficiency target.</p> <p>c. Objectives: The primary objective of Part L of the Building Regulations is to guide the design process to arrive at or progress beyond a required fabric energy efficiency target.</p> <p>d. Target groups: Anyone responsible for dwelling and non-dwelling building work (e.g., designer, builder, installer) must ensure that the construction and design work complies with all applicable requirements of the Building Regulations. The Building Regulations are made up of procedural and technical provisions. Some works are exempt from the whole of the Regulations, whilst others are only exempt from certain aspects. In relation to technical requirements, exemptions are judged by two approaches (depending on which Approved Document):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Parts A to K, M, N and P are judged against seven classes set out in Schedule 2 of the Building Regulations²²; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Class 1 (Buildings controlled under other legislation) e.g. building in which explosives are manufactured or stored under a licence granted through the Manufacture and Storage of Explosives Regulation 2005.

²⁰<http://www.planningportal.gov.uk/buildingregulations/buildingpolicyandlegislation/currentlegislation/buildingregulations/>

²¹ <http://www.planningportal.gov.uk/buildingregulations/approveddocuments/partl/>

²²

<http://www.planningportal.gov.uk/permission/responsibilities/buildingregulations/approvalneeded/exemptions>

- Class 2 (Buildings not frequented by people)
- Class 3 (Greenhouses)
- Class 3 (Agricultural buildings)
- Class 4 (Temporary buildings)
- Class 5 (Ancillary buildings)
- Class 6 (Small detached buildings) e.g. detached, single storey building, with floor area less than 30m², with no sleeping accommodation and has no point less than one metre from the boundary of its curtilage or, which is constructed substantially of non-combustible material
- Class 7 (Extensions) e.g. ground level conservatory, porch, covered yard/way or carport (open on at least two sides) where the floor area does not exceed 30m², provided that, where applicable, the glazing satisfies the requirements of Part N of Schedule 1.
- Part L is judged against criteria set out in Regulation 21[a1] of the Building Regulations. Regulation 9²³ provides further detail on exemptions.

Generally, the Part L requirements apply to buildings, or extensions of such buildings (except Class 7: extensions type), or the carrying out of any work to, or in connection of any such building or extension where the building is a) a roofed construction with walls, and uses energy to condition the indoor climate. Part L requirements do not apply to buildings that fall into the following categories:

- Certain buildings which are listed, in conservation areas or are included in the Schedule of Monuments; where compliance with the energy efficiency requirements would unacceptably alter their character or appearance.
- Buildings which are used primarily or solely as places of worship.
- Temporary buildings with a planned time of use of 2 years or less, with low energy demand.
- Industrial sites, workshops and non-residential agricultural buildings with low energy demand.
- Stand-alone buildings other than dwellings with a total useful floor area of less than 50m².

e. Rules and influencing mechanisms: Prosecution and enforcement notices are applicable if there is a failure to comply with the Building Regulations²⁴, in terms of:

- Not following the building control procedures set out for handling building work, or;
- Building work is carried out which does not comply with the requirements contained in the Building Regulations.

In terms of prosecution, the local authority (LA) has a general duty to enforce Building Regulations in its area. If informal enforcement does not achieve compliance, the LA has two formal enforcement powers:

- **Prosecution:** if a person carrying out building work contravenes the Building Regulations, the LA may prosecute them in the Magistrate's Court. An unlimited fine may be imposed (sections 35 and 35A of the Building Act 1984). Prosecution is possible for up to two years after the completion of the offending work, and will usually be taken against the person carrying out the work (builder, installer, main contractor).
- **Enforcement notice:** the LA may serve an enforcement notice instead of, or in addition to prosecution. The notice is served on the building owner and requires the alteration or removal of

²³<http://www.planningportal.gov.uk/permission/responsibilities/buildingregulations/approvalneeded/exemptions/bcexemptreg9>

²⁴ <http://www.planningportal.gov.uk/permission/responsibilities/buildingregulations/failure>

work which contravenes the regulations (section 36 of the 1984 Act). If the owner does not comply with the notice, the LA can undertake the work itself and recover the costs from the owner. A Section 36 enforcement notice must be served after the expiration of 12 months from the date of completion of the building work. An LA cannot take enforcement action under section 36 if the work is carried out in accordance with the full plans application which the LA either approved, or failed to reject.

Where an approved inspector is providing the Building Control Service, the responsibility for checking that the Building Regulations are complied with during the building works lies with that inspector. However, approved inspectors do not have formal enforcement powers. If the building work is considered, by the Building Inspector, to not comply with Building Regulations and there is a refusal to bring it into compliance, the inspector will cancel the initial notice. If no other approved inspector takes on the work, the building control function will be taken on automatically by the LA.

- f. Implementation network:** The Secretary of State approves any amendments to the Building Regulations 2010 (SI 2010/2214), following guidance from relevant Government departments such as the Department for Communities and Local Government (DCLG) and advisory non-departmental public bodies such as the Building Regulations Advisory Committee (BRAC), as well as industry members. The DCLG provide ongoing practical actions and support to provide effective building regulations including publishing supporting guidance known as Approved Documents, overseeing and supporting building control organizations, publishing research to provide a scientific basis to underpin regulations and providing the secretariat for the Building Regulations Advisory Committee for England (BRAC), which advises the Secretary of State. In terms of ensuring the Building Regulations are enforced, the LAs are responsible for building works (except those which are exempt) in their local area, and for ensuring compliance. All building works subject to Building Regulations are checked by Local Authority Building Control or a private Approved Inspector, or carried out by a 'Competent Person', and with Local Authorities enforcing compliance. In Scotland, where such work requires a building warrant, verification of building work is the responsibility of local authorities alone. (DECC, 2014c; BRAC & DCLG, 2015).
- g. Outcomes:** (i) Estimate of observed and projected energy savings (dwellings and non-dwellings) up to end of 2012: 13.3 TWh; Estimated energy consumption savings (dwellings and non-dwellings): 7.1 TWh in 2014; 14.2 TWh in 2015 (DECC, 2014c); beyond 2015 estimates are no longer relevant following the recent policy shift away from Zero Carbon Standards (HM Treasury, 2015). (ii) Changes to Part L, 2013: best estimate total cost £1,109m (DCLG, 2013).

1.2 Energy Company Obligation (ECO)

- a. General information:** The legislative framework for the Energy Company Obligation is the Energy Act 2011 and the Electricity and Gas (Energy Companies Obligation) Order 2014 (2012 No.3219)²⁵ and the following subsequent amendments:
- The Electricity and Gas (Energy Companies Obligation) (Amendment) Order 2014 (2014 No. 1131)²⁶
 - The Electricity and Gas (Energy Companies Obligation) (Determination of Savings) (Amendment) Order 2014 (2014 No. 2897)²⁷

²⁵ http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2014/3219/pdfs/uksi_20143219_en.pdf

²⁶ http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2014/1131/pdfs/uksi_20141131_en.pdf

²⁷ http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2014/2897/pdfs/uksi_20142897_en.pdf

- The Electricity and Gas (Energy Companies Obligation) (Amendment) (No. 2) Order 2014 (2014 No. 3231)²⁸

Previously, it was covered by the Electricity and Gas (Energy Companies Obligation) Order 2012 (2012 No. 3018)²⁹. Under the Energy Act 2011³⁰, the ‘energy company obligations provisions’ means:

- sections 33BC and 33BD of the Gas Act 1986 and sections 41A and 41B of the Electricity Act 1989 (promotion of reductions in carbon emissions and home-heating costs),
- sections 103 and 103A of the Utilities Act 2000 (overall carbon emissions and home-heating cost reduction targets), and
- section 103B of the Utilities Act 2000 (Secretary of State’s power to require information about carbon emissions and home-heating cost reduction targets).

The latest Energy Company Obligation (ECO2) was launched on 1st April 2015 (running until 31st March 2017) to reduce the UK’s energy consumption and support people living in fuel poverty by funding energy efficiency improvements in homes. It extended the original scheme, which ended on 31st March 2015. The larger energy companies are set obligations to install insulation and heating measures in order to achieve reductions in energy usage and heating costs. ECO works alongside the Green Deal as a way of supporting the installation of energy efficiency measures in low-income households and areas, and in properties that are harder to treat. The ECO replaced two previous schemes, the Carbon Emissions Reduction Target (CERT) and the Community Energy Saving Programme (CESP). There are 3 obligations under the ECO. *Carbon Emissions Reduction Obligation*: provides solid wall, cavity wall and loft insulation measures, and connections to district heating systems, alongside secondary measures including double glazing and draught proofing. *Carbon Saving Community Obligation (CSCO)*: provides insulation measures and connections to district heating systems to households in specified low income areas. Suppliers must meet 15% of their obligation by installing measures in rural areas. Ofgem has published a tool to assist installers and customers to identify eligible CSCO and CSCO rural areas. *Affordable Warmth Obligation*: provides heating and insulation measures to consumers living in private tenure properties that receive particular means-tested benefits. This obligation supports low income consumers that are vulnerable to the impact of living in cold homes (DECC, 2012c).

- Type of policy instrument:** Regulatory: ECO places legal obligations on the larger energy suppliers to deliver energy efficiency measures to domestic energy users (DECC, 2012c).
- Objectives:** ECO and Green Deal aim to help reduce carbon emissions from Britain’s domestic building stock, which is an essential part of the UK’s plan to meet its statutory domestic carbon emission reduction targets by 2050 (DECC, 2012c).
- Target groups:** Energy suppliers in relation to their end-users, particularly low income, fuel poor, hard to treat homes. The Green Deal and ECO do not cover Northern Ireland. (DECC, 2012c).
- Rules and influencing mechanisms:** Suppliers with a customer base of less than 250,000 customer accounts will be exempt from the ECO (DECC, 2012c). Penalty for non-compliance: unspecified financial penalty, if financial penalty is not paid, licenses may be revoked (Ofgem, 2014).
- Implementation network:** ECO is administered by the Office for Gas and Electricity Markets (Ofgem) (DECC, 2012c), alongside the Warm Home Discount (WHD), through the Energy Efficiency and Social Programmes team, that is part of Ofgem’s Environmental Programmes team. Until March 2015, Ofgem E-Serve (on behalf of the Gas and Electricity Markets Authority) was the Administrator for ECO.
- Outcomes:** (i) The actual total carbon target runs between January 2013 to March 2015 and is 27.8MtCO₂

²⁸ http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukxi/2014/3231/pdfs/ukxi_20143231_en.pdf

²⁹ http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukxi/2012/3018/pdfs/ukxi_20123018_en.pdf

³⁰ http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2011/16/pdfs/ukpga_20110016_en.pdf

(DECC, 2012a). Estimated energy consumption savings: 0.7 TWh in 2013; 1.4 TWh in 2014; 2.1 TWh in 2015 (DECC, 2014c). (ii) Best estimate total cost £17.3bn (ECO and Green Deal combined) (iii) Expected benefits to wider society from improved air quality (£1.2bn to £1.6bn), non-traded carbon savings (£3.0bn to £4.8bn) and traded carbon allowance savings (£1.4bn to £1.5bn). Jobs are likely to be created in the solid wall insulation market where demand is expected to rise steeply. Industry responses to the consultation have suggested that the reduction in basic insulation measures (CWI and LI) may induce loss of jobs and closure of manufacturing capacity, given that skills and resources could not be expected to be redeployed in the SWI sector. However, support for hard to treat CWI and SWI which are more labour intensive than easy to treat CWI and LI, is expected to compensate for any reductions in capacity and to increase the number of jobs in the insulation sector to around 39,000-60,000 by 2015 (DECC, 2012c). ECO measures – provisional figures show there were 1,456,891 measures installed under ECO up to the end of April 2015 (DECC, 2015a).

1.3 Energy Savings Opportunity Scheme (ESOS)

- a. **General information:** Introduced June 2014, ESOS is a mandatory energy assessment scheme for large organisations in the UK. It was established by the UK Government in order to implement Article 8 (4-6) of the EU Energy Efficiency Directive (2012/27/EU)³¹. The ESOS Regulations 2014³² give effect to the scheme. Organisations that qualify for ESOS must carry out ESOS assessments every 4 years. These assessments are audits of the energy used by their buildings, industrial processes and transport to identify cost-effective energy saving measures (Environment Agency, 2015).
- b. **Type of policy instrument:** Regulatory; ESOS is a mandatory scheme (Environment Agency, 2015).
- c. **Objectives:** To target a gap in the existing policy landscape and help them to cut their energy costs, by providing targeted cost-effective recommendations to improve their energy efficiency. It will stimulate demand amongst UK businesses for energy efficiency measures, by making clear in the assessments what savings could be made. The assessments will review the organisations' entire energy consumption including buildings, industrial processes and transport activities (DECC, 2014c).
- d. **Target groups:** ESOS applies to large UK undertakings (UK company that either employs 250 or more people, or has an annual turnover in excess of 50m euro, and an annual balance sheet total in excess of 43m euro; or an overseas company with a UK registered establishment which has 250 or more employees paying income tax to the UK) and their corporate groups. It mainly affects businesses but can also apply to not-for-profit bodies and any other non-public sector undertakings that are large enough to meet the qualification criteria. Corporate groups qualify if at least one UK group member meets the ESOS definition of a large undertaking (Environment Agency, 2015).
- e. **Rules and influencing mechanisms:** The environmental regulator is responsible for compliance and enforcement activities. The regulator may issue civil sanctions including financial penalties (ranging from £5k-50k if an organisation does not meet the scheme's obligations (Environment Agency, 2015).
- f. **Implementation network:** Overall, the Environment Agency is responsible for administering the scheme across the UK, and holding the UK register. A registered office or principal place of activity (in the absence of a registered office) determines the regulator, in terms of compliance and enforcement activities (Environment Agency, 2015):
 - The Environment Agency (England)
 - Northern Ireland Environment Agency (Northern Ireland)

³¹ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2012:315:0001:0056:EN:PDF>

³² http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukxi/2014/1643/pdfs/ukxi_20141643_en.pdf

- Scottish Environment Protection Agency (Scotland)
- Natural Resources Wales (Wales)
- DECC Offshore Oil & Gas Environment and Decommissioning (offshore).

In relation to undertaking an ESOS assessment, a corporate group demonstrates compliance using either:

- An ISO 50001 energy management system certified by an accredited certification body (United Kingdom Accreditation Service (UKAS) accredited, a body accredited by another EU member state's national accreditation body or a body accredited by a body which is a member of the International Accreditation Forum), and covers all their energy use (for the whole corporate group in the UK),
- Display Energy Certificates (DECs), which are defined by the Energy Performance of Buildings Regulations 2008 (Northern Ireland) and the Energy Performance of Buildings Regulations 2012 (as amended) (England and Wales). DECs form part of the implementation in England and Wales of the European Directives 2002/91/EC and 2010/31/EU on the energy performance of buildings. DECs are undertaken by qualified assessors.
- Green Deal Assessments (GDAs), can be part of an ESOS compliant energy assessment for the types of energy consumption they cover, if they qualify as per regulation 7 of the Green Deal Framework Regulations 2012³³
- ESOS compliant energy audits. All such energy audits must be reviewed by an ESOS lead assessor. A register of approved lead assessors is available online via the UK Government's ESOS webpage³⁴. An assessor can be an employee of the business, or a third party. The assessor is not held responsible for compliance by the regulators; therefore it is recommended that a member of the corporate group/organisation who understands the ESOS requirements, and works with the lead assessor to ensure the overall approach taken is compliant with ESOS.

The Environment Agency, and the other regulators do not provide standard templates for ESOS related data/activities and/or presentation of findings. Only the data to evidence that 90% of the total energy consumption is compliant via ESOS audits or other alternative routes to compliance, is required to be undertaken and recorded. This is to reduce the administrative burden on organisations that have existing data management procedures and tools.

- g. Outcomes:** (i) Assumptions suggest that ESOS could generate annual savings of around 3.0 TWh per year, of which 2.3TWh from buildings and industrial processes (DECC, 2014b). Current analysis suggests that ESOS has the potential to deliver £1.9 billion of net benefits to the UK and reduce business energy bills by £300 million in its first year (DECC, 2014c). (ii) Best estimate total cost £1,178m (iii) The process of conducting the ESOS assessments themselves will provide employment for auditors and auditing companies. A range of other energy efficiency product and service businesses may also benefit from supporting large enterprises in implementing ESOS assessors' recommendations. The growth in the sector will help the supply side of the market mature, and enable the sector to promote the contribution it can make to a range of enterprises more effectively (DECC, 2014b).

³³ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2012/2079/contents/made>

³⁴ <https://www.gov.uk/guidance/energy-savings-opportunity-scheme-esos>

2. Dissemination and awareness instruments/Informative policy instruments

2.1 Smart Metering Implementation Programme (including in-home displays)

a. General information: The Smart Metering Implementation Programme began its foundation stage in March 2011. The Government's vision is for every home and small business in Great Britain to have smart electricity and gas meters. The programme aims to replace 53 million meters with smart electricity and gas meters in domestic properties and smart or advanced meters in smaller non-domestic sites, benefitting approximately 30 million premises (DECC, 2014d). Most households will have smart meters installed between 2015 and 2020 (DECC, 2012b).

The energy sector in Great Britain is regulated primarily through the Electricity Act 1989³⁵ and the Gas Act 1986³⁶, both of which have amended several times to reflect government policy developments. These Acts ensure the supply of gas and electricity under licence; licence-holders are then required to comply with relevant conditions contained within the licence. Below the licence conditions, a number of industry codes are applicable, and which contain the technical and commercial obligations that govern participation in licensed activities. Changes to the above regulatory framework have been, and are being undertaken to ensure every home, and smaller non-domestic premises have smart metering equipment. These changes include:

- Amendments to existing energy licences and industry codes (e.g. the requirement of suppliers to roll out smart meters), and the consequential changes to legislation, licences and codes,
- The introduction of a new licensable activity relating to communications between suppliers and other parties and smart meters in consumer premises, as well as the appointment of a Data and Communications Company (DCC) to carry out this licensed activity.
- The introduction of a new Smart Energy Code, which sets out the rules, rights and obligations for all parties for the new long-term metering arrangements in Great Britain.

The amendments to the regulatory framework, in relation to smart metering include³⁷:

- **Tranche 1**³⁸ (came into effect on 30 Nov 2012): mandated the roll-out of smart meters by energy suppliers and the establishment of a code of practice for the installation of Smart Meters.
- **Tranche 2**³⁹ (came into effect on 4 March 2013): set out energy supplier and energy network licence modifications in relation to consumer engagement, data access, reporting and security risk assessments and audits in the period before DCC provides services.
- **Tranche 3**⁴⁰ (came into effect on 14 July 2013): introduced energy supplier and energy network licence conditions to support the creation of a new industry code called the Smart Energy Code

³⁵ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/1989/29/contents>

³⁶ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/1986/44>

³⁷ <https://www.gov.uk/guidance/smart-meters-information-for-industry-and-other-stakeholders#regulatory-framework-for-smart-metering>

³⁸ https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/65646/7107-smart-meters-mod-elc-gas-licences.pdf

³⁹ https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/128747/Tranche_2_licence_conditions_Ministerial_sign_off.pdf

(SEC); placed requirements on energy suppliers to ensure that smart meters make key data available to domestic and micro-business consumers, and that key smart meter functions are switched on.

The introduction of these first three tranches supported the establishment of the enduring commercial and regulatory framework for smart metering. In September 2013 Smart DCC Ltd, a wholly owned subsidiary of Capita PLC, was awarded the licence to provide smart metering communication services (the 'DCC Licence'). This award and commencement of the DCC Licence introduced a new licensed entity into the energy market.

Following the award of the DCC Licence, the Government designated the first stage of the SEC. SEC content is being introduced in stages, so that it is in place when the DCC and users of its services need it. The designated version of the SEC was introduced to deal with matters that were required to support the initial operations of the DCC. Further stages have been introduced together with amendments to industry licences where appropriate.

- **Tranches 4 and 5⁴¹** (various dates for coming into effect, starting on 31 March 2014): included new supply licence conditions to ensure consumer access to data as required by the Energy Efficiency Directive (2012/27/EU) and to support 'Smart Change of Supplier'. They also contained changes to energy supply licence conditions related to the mandated roll-out of smart metering. These tranches also introduced further content to the SEC and amendments to the DCC Licence principally concerning the development and financing of DCC services.
- **Tranche 6⁴²** (came into effect 31 July 2014): included arrangements for the testing regime that will allow the DCC to demonstrate that all the DCC developed systems work prior to its operational service becoming available, introduces the Smart Meter Key Infrastructure (SMKI) and sets out amendments relating to smart metering system requirements, as well as some minor modifications to the DCC Licences identified which are required to ensure that the original policy and regulatory intent is achieved.
- **Tranches 7 and 8 (not yet introduced)**: predominately includes content that is required in advance of User Integration Testing (UIT) and User Entry.

Secondary Legislation: As part of the tranches of regulation changes described above DECC, using their powers under the Energy Act 2008, made amendments to the Electricity Act 1989 and Gas Act 1986 (the 'Acts') to make two new statutory instruments that supported the establishment of the DCC:

- **The Electricity and Gas (Smart Meters Licensable Activity) Order 2012 (SI 2012/2400)⁴³**: this Order introduced a new licensable activity into each of the Electricity Act 1989 and the Gas Act

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https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/211216/SMMModifications.pdf

⁴¹https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/297873/ModificationsSmartEnergyCode26March14.pdf

⁴² <https://www.gov.uk/government/consultations/new-smart-energy-code-content-stage-3>

⁴³ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukdsi/2012/9780111526545/contents>

1986. It is unlawful to undertake that activity without holding a licence. The new activity relates to the provision of a service of communicating with smart energy meters on behalf of all licensed energy suppliers.

- **The Electricity and Gas (Competitive Tenders for Smart Meter Communication Licences) Regulations 2012 (SI 2012/2414)⁴⁴ (DCC Licence Application Regulations):** these set out the competitive application process to award licences for the provision of a service of communicating with smart energy meters on behalf of all licensed energy suppliers. The process under the Regulations allows for a single person to be granted licences for this activity in respect of both electricity and gas smart meters after competition and to become a monopoly provider of communication services in Great Britain.

The UK Government also introduced a new statutory instrument to support the implementation of the *Smart Energy Code, The Electricity and Gas Appeals (Designation and Exclusion) Order 2013 (SI 2013/2429)*⁴⁵, which extends the right of appeal to the Competition Commission against certain decisions of the Gas and Energy Markets Authority (GEMA) to include decisions in relation to the Smart Energy Code. This right of appeal is in line with other industry codes.

Smart Metering Equipment Technical Specifications

In addition to the regulatory framework outlined above, energy suppliers are also required to take all reasonable steps to install smart metering equipment which meets the requirements of the smart metering equipment technical specifications (SMETS):

- SMETS 1⁴⁶ was designated by the Secretary of State in December 2012, with minor amendments made to the specification in March 2014. Equipment installed now must be compliant with SMETS 1 if it is to count towards suppliers' roll-out obligations.
- The UK Government has developed drafts of SMETS 2, the Communications Hub Technical Specification (CHTS), the Great Britain Companion Specification (GBCS) and the Security Characteristics for GB Smart Metering, which set out the requirements for the next generation of metering equipment to be installed. These documents and the associated regulatory requirements were notified to the European Commission, as required by the Technical Standards and Regulations Directive, in July 2014.

- b. Type of policy instrument:** Awareness instrument, regulatory: Installers must provide energy efficiency advice as part of the visit to install smart meters and in-home displays (DECC, 2012b).
- c. Objectives:** Through the In-home Display offered by energy suppliers as part of the rollout, consumers will have near-real time information on their energy consumption to help them control energy use, and avoid wasting energy and money. Smart meters will bring an end to estimated billing, help consumers to budget better, make switching between energy suppliers smoother and faster, and help restore trust in the energy market. New products and services will be supported in a vibrant, competitive, more efficient market in energy and energy management. Energy suppliers will have access to accurate data for billing and to improve their customer service. They will also be able to reduce costs, for example by reducing call centre traffic, removing the need for a site visits to read meters (DECC, 2014d).
- d. Target groups:** The Government is requiring energy companies to install 53 million gas and electricity

⁴⁴ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukxi/2012/2414/introduction/made>

⁴⁵ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukxi/2013/2429/contents/made>

⁴⁶ <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/smart-metering-implementation-programme-technical-specifications>

meters at 30 million domestic and smaller non-domestic properties (DECC, 2012b).

- e. Rules and influencing mechanisms:** Smart meters will be rolled out as standard across the country by 2020, but there will not be a legal obligation on individuals to have one. Energy companies will be required to install smart meters and take all reasonable steps to reach everyone. However, energy companies are not expected to take legal action to fit a smart meter if they cannot get the householder's co-operation (DECC, 2012b).
- f. Implementation network:** The programme is led by the DECC, with co-operation from interested parties such as the energy industry, Ofgem and consumer groups. DECC is responsible for driving delivery and providing active oversight of progress by all delivery parties. During 2014, industry partners including the Data and Communications Company and its contractors, energy suppliers, network operators and manufacturers have continued to develop the systems that will deliver smart meters to consumers when the main installation phase begins (DECC, 2012b). Ofgem, as electricity and gas industry regulator, will be responsible for ensuring compliance with smart metering rules. DECC's aim is to leave the management and evolution of smart metering to energy industry participants, which will then be governed through the arrangements in the Smart Energy Code, and subject to regulatory oversight by Ofgem. DECC will remain responsible for the Government's 'retail energy policy and for the realisation of the benefits set out in the Programme's business case', and if required, 'will introduce further regulation to protect these benefits, using its powers in the Energy Acts 2008 and 2011'⁴⁷. DECC has worked with industry to develop a Smart Metering Implementation Programme (SMIP) Transition Governance Model; the role of such groups is to support DECC decision-making through advice and recommendations on a variety of issues including planning, risk and issue management, and change control for design and regulatory documents. The key groups are:
- **Smart Metering Steering Group (SMSG):** a strategic level forum to review overall progress of the GB smart metering programme, discuss key challenges and resolve significant escalated issues. Members include: large energy suppliers; smaller energy suppliers; Energy UK; Energy Networks Association; Citizens Advice; Ofgem; Data and Communications Company Licensee; Smart Energy Code Panel; Smart Energy GB; Critical Friend; DECC Senior Responsibility Owner and DECC Minister.
 - **Smart Metering Delivery Group (SMDG):** a senior operational level forum through which DECC can work together with key industry and other delivery partners to monitor and drive the delivery of the overall portfolio of GB smart metering programmes, and agree actions required to mitigate key risks and resolve issues that could impact the delivery of the joint programme plan and planned benefits. Members include: large energy suppliers; smaller energy suppliers; Energy UK; Smart Energy GB; ENA; DCC Licensee; Ofgem; SEC Panel; metering equipment manufacturers (trade association level). In addition Consumer Futures and the DECC SRO will have a standing invitation to attend.
 - **Technical and Business Design Group (TBDG):** A working level forum through which DECC can work together with key industry and other delivery partners to pro-actively manage changes to the baseline technical and business design products prior to their inclusion in the SEC, thereby ensuring that the integrity of the end-to-end solution is maintained during transition. Members are expected to be Design Lead/Lead Technical Architect level from their respective organisations, and have a detailed understanding of the technical and business design baseline and the impact of changes. Members include: large energy suppliers; smaller energy suppliers; electricity and gas

4747

https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/386482/DECC_Ofgem_open_letter_on_smart_metering.pdf

network operators; Energy UK; DCC Licensee; Ofgem; Smart Energy Code Administrative Secretariat; energy services providers; metering equipment manufacturers; Meter Asset Providers and meter operators (trade association level).

- **Implementation Managers Forum (IMF):** a working level forum through which DECC can work together with key industry and other delivery partners to review progress of the portfolio of individual contributor projects and programmes towards the delivery of planned milestones and benefits. Members are expected to be Programme Manager/Implementation Manager level from their respective organisations, and have a detailed understanding of both their own programme and how it fits into the overall portfolio of smart metering programmes. Members include: large energy suppliers; smaller energy suppliers; Energy UK; Smart Energy GB; electricity and gas network operators; DCC Licensee; Ofgem; SECAS; metering equipment manufacturers (trade association level).
- **Regulatory Group (RG):** a working level forum through which key industry and other delivery partners can pro-actively provide advice and support to DECC with its on-going work on the smart metering regulatory framework. Members are expected to have a detailed understanding of the regulatory framework of the energy market.
- **Transitional Security Expert Group (TSEG):** a working level expert forum through which DECC can work together with key industry and other security experts to pro-actively manage security risks, amend security requirements and to oversee security assurance, thereby ensuring that the security of the end-to-end solution is maintained during transition until the relevant SEC security governance is in place. TSEG members are expected to have a detailed understanding of the smart metering security architecture, security requirements, be experienced in security risk management and have the ability to analyse and impact potential new or changed risks. Initial members include: large energy suppliers; smaller energy suppliers; Energy UK; electricity and gas network operators; DCC Licensee; Ofgem; SECAS; metering equipment manufacturers (trade association level) with representation from the government's security and intelligence services.
- **Transitional SMKI Policy Management Authority Group (TPMAG):** a senior, DECC led, operational level group focused on managing and governing aspects of the Smart Metering Key Infrastructure (SMKI) until SMKI obligations are implemented into the Smart Energy Code (SEC). The long term governance for SMKI is through the SMKI Policy Management Authority (PMA) which was established as a sub-committee of the SEC Panel from 31 July 2014 with its membership, role and powers defined in SEC Section L. However, the TPMAG will continue to provide governance alongside the PMA for the Subsidiary SMKI Documents that are subject to further consultation before they are implemented into the SEC after which the PMA will become responsible for their governance and TPMAG will be closed. The membership and meetings of TPMAG are aligned with the PMA membership and meetings to ensure consistency in the advice provided by the PMA and by TPMAG to the SEC Panel and the Secretary of State in support of:
 - Directive 1999/93/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 December 1999 on a Community framework for electronic signatures that was published on 19 January 2000; and the subsequent
 - UK Electronic Communications Act 2000
 TPMAG and PMA members include: two large energy suppliers; one smaller energy supplier; one Network Operator; and one independent PKI Specialist with representatives from the DCC Licensee; Ofgem; DECC; and SECAS.
- **Benefits Monitoring and Review Group (BMRG):** a forum for representatives of all delivery partners and the wider stakeholder group to review evidence provided by DECC and by group members on the performance of the smart metering rollout and the benefits realised. The BMRG has a key role in advising on the quality of the rollout, the optimisation of benefits realised,

reviewing research and evaluation outputs, managing threats and exploiting opportunities for benefit realisation, identifying new benefits, sharing lessons learned, and reviewing and responding to the broadest range of evidence available. The BMRG has an overview and advisory role to DECC on benefits realisation, which will include continued engagement in developing the reporting framework for monitoring the progress and benefits of the rollout. Core membership of the BMRG comprises representatives from the following organisations: Age UK, Association of Meter Operators, British Electrotechnical and Allied Manufacturers Association, large energy suppliers, small energy suppliers, District Network Operators, Citizens Advice, Ofgem, Energy UK, Smart Energy GB, Energy Networks Association and Energy Savings Trust. Additional participants will include those who are considered benefit enablers and those who receive benefits of Smart Metering.

- g. Outcomes:** (i) Estimated energy saving potential to 2020: 8TWh (DECC, 2014c). (ii) This national infrastructure programme is expected to deliver £17.1b of benefits at a cost of £10.9b. (iii) Smart meters are expected to have a positive net impact on consumers' bills (DECC, 2012b).

2.2 Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs)

a. General information: The EU Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (2002/91/EC) and the recast Directive, Energy Performance of Buildings (recast) Directive 2010/31/EU⁴⁸ require that all properties (homes, commercial and public buildings) must have an Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) when sold, built or rented and larger public buildings over 500m² must display a Display Energy Certificate (DEC). This legislation has been transposed into legislation in England and Wales through the Housing Act 2004, the Energy Performance of Buildings (Certificates and inspections) (England and Wales) Regulations 2007 (SI 2007/991)⁴⁹, and subsequently the Energy Performance of Buildings (England and Wales) Regulations 2012 (SI 2012/3118)⁵⁰. In Scotland, the EU EPBD has been transposed through Building Standards legislation (EPCs for new buildings and inspection of air-conditioning systems) and the Energy Performance of Buildings (Scotland) Regulations 2008 (EPCs for existing buildings)⁵¹. In Northern Ireland, the Energy Performance of Buildings (Certificates and Inspection) (Amendment) Regulations 2014 were published in response to outstanding requirements of the (recast) EU Directive 2010/31/EU. This is due to Scotland and Northern Ireland having separate building standards to England and Wales.

EPCs are produced by accredited energy assessors using standard methods and assumptions about energy usage (IEA, 2015). An EPC contains: information about a property's energy use and typical energy costs recommendations about how to reduce energy use and save money. An EPC gives a property an energy efficiency rating from A (most efficient) to G (least efficient) and is valid for 10 years (DECC, 2014c). A DEC must clearly show the actual energy use of a building, the Operational Rating (information gathered through the EPC), in order to help the public see the energy efficiency of a building. The requirement for DEC came into effect from 1st October 2008. DEC are valid for 10 years, in buildings with a total useful floor area of 500-1,000m²; but only valid for 12months if the building is over 1,000m².

b. Type of policy instrument: Dissemination and awareness instruments: The person selling the house, the

⁴⁸ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2010:153:0013:0035:EN:PDF>

⁴⁹ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukxi/2007/991/contents/made>

⁵⁰ http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukxi/2012/3118/pdfs/ukxi_20123118_en.pdf

⁵¹ http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ssi/2008/309/pdfs/ssi_20080309_en.pdf

landlord or the letting agent must show you the EPC if you're buying or renting - An EPC includes a recommendation report that lists cost-effective and other measures to improve the building's energy rating. DCLG has also developed an EPC Adviser tool to help people assess how much money they can save and carbon they can reduce by making their homes more energy efficient; required domestic energy assessors to increase their skills so that they can provide a more effective service; improved the training for domestic energy assessors to help them provide an effective service; and opened up access to the EPC register of more than 11 million domestic EPCs by providing online access to individual EPCs and making all EPC data held on the register publicly available. / Regulatory: You can be fined if you don't get an EPC when you need one (DECC, 2014c; GOV.UK, 2015a).

- c. **Objectives:** This means that the energy efficiency of one building can easily be compared with another building of the same type. This allows prospective buyers, tenants, owners, occupiers and purchasers to see information on the energy efficiency and carbon emissions from their building so they can consider energy efficiency and fuel costs as part of their investment (DECC, 2014c).
- d. **Target groups:** Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) are needed whenever a property is: built, sold, or rented (with the exception of: places of worship, temporary buildings that will be used for less than 2 years, stand-alone buildings with total useful floor space of less than 50 square metres, industrial sites, workshops and non-residential agricultural buildings that don't use a lot of energy, some buildings that are due to be demolished, holiday accommodation that's rented out for less than 4 months a year or is let under a licence to occupy, listed buildings, residential buildings intended to be used less than 4 months a year) (GOV.UK, 2015a).
- e. **Rules and influencing mechanisms:** The current owner can be fined if an EPC is not in place as required (GOV.UK, 2015a). The enforcement of the regulations is the responsibility of local weights and measures authorities i.e. trading standards. The fine is 12.5% of the rateable value of the building, capped at £5,000 (£6,890) and with a default penalty of £750 where the calculation is not possible. A further fine of £200 (£275) can be issued for failure to provide a copy of the EPC, when requested by an enforcement authority officer within seven days. In terms of DECs, the penalties are; a £500 (£690) fine for failure to display a DEC at all times in a prominent place, and a £1,000 (£1,380) fine for failure to possess a valid advisory report (GVA, unknown).
- f. **Implementation network:** The Domestic and Non-Domestic Energy Performance Certificate Registers are operated by Landmark Information Group on behalf of the Secretary of State for Communities and Local Government (DCLG); DCLG is responsible for making sure buildings in the UK meet the standards required by the EU Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (DCLG, 2015).
- g. **Outcomes:** (i) Energy savings due to EPCs unknown (ii) Best estimate total cost £13.44m (DCLG, 2015). (iii) A Government study has shown that the benefits of energy efficiency extend beyond lowering the cost of bills and cutting carbon emissions. The study found that having a more energy efficient rating can increase a property's value, demonstrating that house buyers and estate agents are beginning to recognise the value of energy efficiency measures. For an average home in England, improving its Energy Performance Certificate rating from band G to E, or from band D to B, could add more than £16,000 to the sale price of the property. This represents a significant development, particularly in the context of the misaligned financial incentives barrier (DECC, 2014c).

2.3 Green Open Homes (complementary to the Green Deal)

- a. **General information:** In 2013, the Department for Energy and Climate Change (DECC) awarded funding to

the Centre for Sustainable Energy (CSE), working in partnership with Bristol Green Doors (a national leader in running local low carbon open homes events) to set up a national Green Open Homes network⁵² to stimulate more activity and provide support for low carbon open homes events across the country (CSE, 2014).

- b. Type of policy instrument:** Dissemination and awareness instruments: approach includes a number of sources and methods for dissemination and outreach: website – searchable directory of open home events; 18 guidance notes for event organisers with free marketing graphics, photos, and templates; roadshow events to share experience and advice and networking opportunities for organisers; network newsletter; funding and expert support – grants worth £500 – 20k (total £180k) (CSE, 2014).
- c. Objectives:** The aim was to help new open homes events and networks get off the ground all around the country, to increase people’s feeling that making energy saving improvements is ‘normal in my neighbourhood’. For groups who already ran small open homes events, our goal was to help them flourish, to make the events bigger, easier to deliver, and have more impact (CSE, 2014).
- d. Target groups:** Homeowners seeking more information on energy efficiency upgrades, e.g. those with further questions regarding the Green Deal (CSE, 2014).
- e. Rules and influencing mechanisms:** Grants cannot be used directly for private profit and a budget breakdown must be provided as part of the application; Grant awards of greater than £1,000 can only be made to legally incorporated organisations; Grants cannot be used directly for private profit and a budget breakdown must be provided as part of the application. Public liability insurance is also required (CSE, 2013).
- f. Implementation network:** DECC funded, delivered by the Centre for Sustainable Energy and Bristol Green Doors (CSE, 2014).
- g. Outcomes:** (i) Energy savings due to Green Open Homes unknown (ii) Total funding for events from CSE: £180k (CSE, 2014). Most events cost up to £1,000, with some of the larger events costing up to £10,000. However, size of event didn’t necessarily equate with greater cost. Unpaid volunteer time was unquantified.
(iii) Between September 2013 and September 2014, Green Open Homes Network supported 49 organisations with the running of their events, with an average of 16 homes opening at each event (Newbury et al., 2014).

3. Economic policy instruments

3.1 The Green Deal programme (complementary to ECO, Green Open Homes, domestic RHI)

- a. General information:** Launched in January 2013, the Green Deal was expected to be the UK Government’s ‘flagship piece of legislation, which will deliver energy efficiency to homes and buildings across the land.’⁵³ Legislation for the programme was first provided in the Energy Act 2011⁵⁴ and the implementing Regulations are:
- The Green Deal Framework (Disclosure, Acknowledgment, Redress etc.) Regulations 2012 SI 2012 No. 2079⁵⁵

⁵² <http://www.greenopenhomes.net/>

⁵³ HC Deb 19 May 2011 c491

⁵⁴ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2011/16/enacted>

⁵⁵ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2012/2079/contents/made>

- The Green Deal (Energy Efficiency Improvements) Order 2012 SI 2012 No. 2106⁵⁶
- The Green Deal (Qualifying Energy Improvements) Order 2012 SI 2012 No. 2105⁵⁷
- The Green Deal (Acknowledgment) Regulations 2012 SI 2012 No. 1660⁵⁸
- The Green Deal (Disclosure) Regulations 2012 SI 2012 No. 1660⁵⁹

It aimed to provide a framework of accredited market participants, through which people pay for some of the cost of improving their homes and businesses using a type of loan that is paid back with the savings they can expect to make on their fuel bills; a pay-as-you-save scheme. The Green Deal process begins with a household employing a Green Deal assessor to provide an energy efficiency rating as well as recommend improvements that are appropriate for the property and indicate whether they can be expected to pay for themselves through reduced energy bills (IEA, 2015). Householders receive a Green Deal assessment and energy performance certificate (EPC). The customer can then take the assessment to a Green Deal provider, for a quote for the finance and installation of one or more of the recommended measures. The provider and customer then agree a Green Deal Plan, to set out the agreed amount and terms of repayment. One main aim of the Green Deal was to encourage the uptake of energy efficiency measures in buildings through reducing the capital costs required by customers and support households to install energy efficiency measures, including: insulation (loft, cavity or solid wall); draught-proofing; improved heating controls; double glazing; and renewable energy technologies (e.g. solar panels) (DECC, 2014c). Therefore, the financing of the Green Deal was critical. The Green Deal Finance Company (GDFC) was a not-for-profit organisation including local authorities and companies whose role was to set-up, finance and administer Green Deal Plans, as part of the overall Green Deal Programme. The GDFC financed the Green Deal by purchasing Green Deal Plans from Green Deal Providers, once the agreed Green Deal measures had been installed and accepted by the consumer. In addition to the GDFC, the UK Government also provided financial incentives directly to consumers through the Green Deal Cashback and Green Deal Home Improvement Fund.

From July 2015, the UK Government stopped funding the Green Deal Finance Company (GDFC) and future funding releases of the Green Deal Home Improvement Fund (GDHIF) due to concerns around low take-up, industry standards and the administrative complexities of the programme.

- b. Type of policy instrument:** Economic: loan system; dissemination and awareness: The Green Deal has a central role to play in raising consumer awareness of the benefits of installing energy efficiency measures; the Green Deal assessment provides the perfect opportunity for targeted advice to be given to consumers, as required by Article 17(2) (DECC, 2014c).
- c. Objectives:** The objective is to help households and small businesses improve energy efficiency or reduce carbon emissions and ensure that they have access to trusted information about energy efficiency. The Green Deal is intended to encourage undertaking of energy assessments. It offers energy efficiency assessments, financing and the installation of energy efficiency measures through a network of Green Deal approved assessors, installers and providers (DECC, 2014c).
- d. Target groups:** Households (owner-occupied and private rented tenants and landlords) in existing dwellings as well as the owners, landlords and tenants of small non-dwellings. The Green Deal and ECO do not cover Northern Ireland (DECC, 2014c).
- e. Rules and influencing mechanisms:** The Green Deal, although legislated through DECC, is based in the

⁵⁶ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2012/2106/contents/made>

⁵⁷ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2012/2105/contents/made>

⁵⁸ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2012/1661/contents/made>

⁵⁹ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2012/1660/contents/made>

private sector and seeks to enhance the uptake of physical energy efficiency measures as well as increase assessments and awareness of energy use and efficiency in domestic and small non-domestic properties. The Green Deal framework regulations provide a Code of Practice as well as assessor and provider certification in order to ensure consumer protection. The overall authorisation body is the Green Deal Oversight and Registration Body (GD ORB). In addition, a Green Deal Ombudsman and Investigation Service, run by the Ombudsman Services, has been established. The Ombudsman Services provide independent, impartial and cost-effective dispute resolution outside the courts, and operate under appropriate UK legal and regulatory authority. The Green Deal also sought to positively influence the conflicting interests of tenants and landlords, and is supported by the first tenants' energy efficiency improvements regulations coming into force by 1 April 2016, and the legislation surrounding EPCs ensuring that by 2018, it will be illegal to rent a property with an EPC rating of E or below. Because it is the bill payer in rented dwellings that benefits from energy efficiency improvements, the Landlords Energy Saving Allowance, a financial incentive, allows landlords of domestic rented property to claim tax relief of up to £1,500 per property for the costs of buying and installing energy-saving products (DECC, 2014c).

- f. Implementation network:** The Green Deal Oversight and Registration Body (GD ORB), on behalf of the Secretary of State, manages the authorisation scheme for participants in the Green Deal and is responsible for a number of functions aimed at providing effective administration and oversight of the scheme. The GD ORB is responsible for maintaining a register of all authorised Green Deal Providers, Certification Bodies, Assessors and Installers; maintaining the Green Deal Code of Practice and controlling the use of the Quality Mark; ongoing monitoring of Green Deal Participants against the Code of Practice; producing an annual Green Deal report; and gathering evidence of non-compliance and referring participants to the Ombudsman or the Secretary of State where appropriate and imposing sanctions when directed (DCLG, DWP & DECC, 2015).
- g. Outcomes:** (i) Estimated energy consumption savings (dwelling and non-dwelling): 0.4 TWh in 2014; 0.7 TWh in 2015 (DECC, 2014c). (ii) Best estimate total cost £17.3bn (Green Deal and ECO combined) (DECC, 2012c). (iii) The Green Deal programme will support the creation of up to 60,000 jobs in the insulation sector alone by 2015. Heating and insulation measures will benefit around 230,000 low-income households each year. By 2020 the Green Deal could reduce UK household and business carbon emissions by 4.5 million tonnes per year (DCLG, DWP & DECC, 2015).

3.2 The Salix Finance public sector energy efficiency loan scheme

- a. General information:** The EU Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (2002/91/EC) and the subsequent recast Directive (2010/31/EU) sought to ensure the public sector was given a leading role in promoting energy efficiency. Due to this, UK Government created means of funding energy efficiency measures in buildings in the public sector. One such initiative was the funding of the Salix scheme. In 2004 the Salix Finance public sector energy efficiency loan scheme was established to provide public sector organisations with interest free loans for energy efficiency projects (DECC, 2014c). Salix is an independent, not-for-profit organisation that is publicly funded by the DECC, the Department for Education (DoE), the Welsh Government, the Scottish Government and Higher Education Funding Council for England (HEFCE) and provides two types of funding programmes; the Salix Energy Efficiency Loans Scheme (savings from measures installed due to loan are used to pay back the interest-free loan, and once the loan has been repaid, the continued savings are used within the specific public sector organisation that installed the measures) and the Recycling Fund (a ring-fenced fund managed by the public sector organisation. In this case, the loan is repaid, through the financial savings delivered by the projects, into the fund and is effectively self-sustaining and enables further funding of other energy efficiency projects).
- b. Type of policy instrument:** Economic and dissemination/awareness: interest free loans for energy efficiency improvements in the public sector (DECC, 2014c). Salix also facilitates knowledge sharing

through quarterly regional meetings, technical workshops and project case studies. This enables the sharing of this knowledge between organisations helps support Salix clients in delivering long term, cost effective savings (Salix, 2014).

- c. **Objectives:** To provide interest free loans to improve the energy efficiency of hospitals, schools and other public sector buildings (DECC, 2014c) in order to ensure the UK's public sector leads by example in terms of achieving a low-carbon economy.
- d. **Target groups:** *'Any public sector body who receive the majority of their income directly from the public sector can apply. Only those projects where the resultant energy savings, over the lifetime of the project, go directly back to the public sector and the public sector gains a direct financial benefit are eligible. An example of an ineligible project would be an outsourced estate management contract in which the outsource supplier paid the energy bills and benefitted from any savings achieved from the project. However, if the energy bill was a pass through under the contract and the public sector benefitted from the energy savings, then the project would be eligible'* (Salix, 2014). All public sector organisations (across their whole estates) in England, Wales and Scotland are eligible to apply for funding. Such organisations include schools, higher and further educational institutions, emergency services, hospitals, leisure centres, local authorities, the NHS. Eligibility is dependent on the installation of technologies on the Salix list of eligible technologies, and the completion of the Salix Programme Compliance Tools (Salix, 2014).
- e. **Rules and influencing mechanisms:** Recipients of funding must apply the basic rules of procurement whenever they spend public money. These rules look to make sure that public funds are spent openly and fairly, and make the most of every budget, while protecting against legal challenges, financial penalties and damage to a recipient's reputation (Salix, 2014). In total, over 120 technologies (e.g. boilers, combined heat and power, LED and lighting upgrades, and heat recovery) fit the Salix funding criteria, and as such can be funded through the Salix finance schemes. However, the list of supported technologies is evolving and public sector organisations can discuss the addition of technologies they feel fit the Salix criteria for funding.
- f. **Implementation network:** Salix Finance Ltd is grant funded by DECC, with contributions from the Department for Education (DfE), The Higher Education Funding Council for England (HEFCE) and the Welsh and Scottish governments (Salix, 2014). Salix Finance Ltd ensure the participating public sector organisations provide data to ensure cost-effective and energy/carbon savings are achieved.
- g. **Outcomes:** (i) Estimated energy consumption savings (dwelling and non-dwelling): 0.2 TWh in 2015; 0.5 TWh in 2016 (DECC, 2014c). All projects are forecast to save 538,146 tonnes of CO₂ annually and 7,422,659 tonnes over the projects' lifetime. This represents £98.5 million of annual financial savings to Salix clients' energy bills and £1.395 billion over the projects' lifetime. The average financial payback from all projects is 3.8 years, based on the value of projects in relation to the forecast annual financial savings from these projects. (ii) Total funding to Salix to date: £198.7m; The cost of generating 1 tonne of lifetime CO₂ saving across all projects is £50.64 per tonne (Salix, 2014). (iii) Salix has funded over 11,000 projects with 794 public sector bodies, valued at £272.8 million. An additional £18 million was provided for Salix loans in 2012-13, £8m of which was ring-fenced for schools. In December 2013 the Government announced a further £90 million for Salix over the next three years to provide loans to improve the energy efficiency of hospitals, schools, and other public sector buildings, building on the Salix scheme (DECC, 2014c).

3.3 Electricity Demand Reduction (EDR) scheme

- a. **General information:** The Energy Act 2013⁶⁰ contained provisions for a financial incentive to encourage lasting reductions in electricity demand that can be delivered through the Capacity Market⁶¹; part of the

⁶⁰ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2013/32/contents/enacted/data.htm>

UK Government's electricity market reform package which seeks to ensure security of electricity supply, encourage investment required to replace older power stations and provide backup for more intermittent and inflexible low carbon generation sources. The Capacity Market was also designed to support the development of more active demand management in the electricity market. Further regulations relating to the Capacity Market include; Electricity Capacity Regulations (2014)⁶², the Electricity Capacity (supplier payment etc.) regulations 2014⁶³, the Electricity Capacity (amending) Regulations 2015⁶⁴.

"A Capacity Market is being introduced in Great Britain to ensure that consumers continue to receive reliable electricity supplies at an affordable cost at times of very high electricity demand. It will provide regular monthly payments to capacity providers during the delivery year. In return, they must be available to produce electricity or shift demand when demand is close to exceeding supply, or face penalties if they fail to deliver the capacity. At present, the Capacity Market will be open to capacity providers in the form of new and existing power stations, electricity storage providers and those who can shift or switch demand to other times (demand side response). EDR could reduce the level of demand placed on the system and, in turn, lower the amount of other types of capacity that need to be provided. The diagram below illustrates how different types of resources (electricity generators, electricity demand reduction and demand side response) could provide capacity.

The Capacity Market will operate as an auction, with participants bidding in the amount of capacity they are able to offer and a price at which they are willing to provide it. The first capacity auction will take place in December 2014 for delivery four years ahead. In addition, the Government will run transitional arrangements for demand side response capacity in 2015 and 2016." (DECC, 2014e)

The Electricity Demand Reduction Scheme (EDR) was used to test this approach. The EDR is a Government pilot providing the chance to be paid for delivering electricity savings at peak times from certain types of efficiency projects in Great Britain. Currently the scheme is in Phase II of the pilot. The EDR Pilot is based around a competitive auction (like the Capacity Market is); the first auction was held on 12th January 2015 for a total of around £10million, the second is scheduled for the following year, and the total budget for the EDR pilot is at least £20million. The EDR Pilot process is as follows:

"The EDR Pilot auction process will first invite participants to submit an Expression of Interest Form, and to subsequently submit an application to qualify for the auction. Expression of Interest and Application Forms will be assessed to ensure that they meet the requirements of the EDR Pilot and are for projects that we expect should be able to deliver the expected capacity savings. If successful, participants will then be invited to submit a bid into the auction on a £.pence per kW basis for the average amount of capacity reduction their project is expected to deliver in the specified winter peak period. A maximum price will be set at £300 per kW. Winning bids will be selected on a £/kW ranking up to the total budget available in the auction.

Winners will be required to sign a Participant Agreement, which will commit the participant to a number of obligations, including installing and reporting Operational Verification for the measures they bid into the auction, measuring and reporting the capacity savings delivered and participating in the evaluation of the EDR Pilot. In exchange for full compliance, DECC will pay participants their winning bid price multiplied by the average capacity savings committed to in their successful application.

The evaluation of the EDR Pilot is intended to provide a robust evidence base so that the Government is

⁶¹ <https://www.gov.uk/government/collections/electricity-market-reform-capacity-market>

⁶² <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2014/2043/contents/made>

⁶³ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2014/3354/contents/made>

⁶⁴ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2015/875/contents/made>

able to make such decisions on EDR in the longer term. Learning from the evaluation will underpin the design of any enduring scheme therefore participation in evaluation activities is essential. The evaluation will also be used to fulfil the Department's obligation to report the outcomes of the EDR Pilot to Parliament." (DECC, 2014e)

All bids for the Pilot Scheme Phase I had to be received before 10am on 12th January 2015. Following this time, the bids were opened and ranked in merit (price) order from low to high, up to the available budget. This ranking meant that the cheapest projects (on a £/kW basis) were selected first. The auction was run as a 'pay-as-bid' auction; the bidders were paid the price they bid, if they were successful. Bids were selected up until the point where the budget was exhausted, and an independent observer oversaw the auction.

Following lessons learnt from Phase I, eligibility has been broadened to explicitly include: the installation of insulation or other thermal envelope improvements in buildings that are electrically heated and the installation of Building Energy Management Systems (including energy IT/software where these actively control electricity use); and bidders can protect from risk of under-delivery of savings by bidding into the Auction a lower level of savings than are recognised in measurement and verification Documents (DECC, 2015b).

- b. Type of policy instrument:** Economic: grant provided for reduction of electricity demand (DECC, 2015b).
- c. Objectives:** To evaluate and report on an exemplar case of electricity demand reduction during peak times, most likely through the replacement of less efficient equipment with a more efficient version (DECC, 2015b). The EDR pilot has two objectives:
 - To examine the viability of electricity demand reduction in the Capacity Market; and
 - To learn lessons for Government and wider stakeholders on the delivery of EDR schemes.
- d. Target groups:** Organisations from all sectors (private, public and voluntary/third-sector) are invited to participate in the EDR Pilot (DECC, 2013a). DECC is excluded. Participants from all geographic locations may apply, as long as they are able to enter into contract with the UK Government. However, project sites must be located within Great Britain and be connected to the Great Britain Electricity Grid (England, Wales and Scotland only; sites in Northern Ireland are excluded as they are connected to the Irish Single Electricity Market).
- e. Rules and influencing mechanisms:** There are eligibility rules in place (some described above in target groups) (DECC, 2014e):
 - All measures included in an application must deliver reductions in electricity demand through the installation of equipment, including replacement of less efficient measures. Behavioural, new build, generation, load shifting and expansion projects are excluded.
 - The 'payback' of measures included at any single site in a project must have a payback period of two years or more.
 - Measures which are already benefitting or will benefit from specified incentives are not eligible.
 - Measures must deliver capacity savings across the winter peak period (the 83 business days from 1 November 2015 to 29 February 2016).
 - Measures must not have a short replacement cycle (an expected lifespan of less than 16,000 hours), unless included as a component in the installation of an eligible EDR measure.
 - Measures included as part of any one application (one project) must result in an average of at least 100kW of savings throughout the winter peak period (4pm-8pm, business days, 1 November 2015 to 29 February 2016).
 - Measures must be able to be installed and provide Operational Verification by 15 October 2015.
 - Measures must be electricity Grid connected and based in Great Britain (if the site is partially self-supplied, then any onsite generation must be declared).

In addition, there are also eligibility criteria relating to the participant's history of convictions, insolvency, misconduct and/or tax offences (DECC, 2015b).

- f. Implementation network:** Funded, approved, and evaluated by DECC as part of their Energy demand

reduction in industry, business and the public sector policy framework (DECC, 2015b). There is a specific EDR project team overseeing and providing administrative and evaluation duties in relation to the pilot scheme.

- g. Outcomes:** (i) Total Potential for EDR in 2030 (after impact of existing policy) is 32.2TWh. (ii) Best estimate total cost £0.34bn (DECC, 2013). (iii) In addition to being paid per kW, projects will also benefit from the ongoing reduction in electricity bills, which includes savings made outside the winter peak period (DECC, 2015b).

3.4 Feed-in Tariffs (FiTs)

- a. General information:** In the UK, the feed-in-tariffs were announced in October 2008 and introduced on 1 April 2010. The legislative framework for the tariffs was laid down in the 2008 Energy Act.
- b. Type of policy instrument:** Economic: The Feed-in-tariff is a scheme that pays people for generating their own electricity from renewable or low carbon sources.
- c. Objectives:** The tariffs were introduced by the Government with the aim to increase the uptake of renewable electricity-generating technologies in the UK and to help the UK reduce its carbon emissions.
- d. Target groups:** domestic and non-domestic building owners (e.g. households, landlords, business, school etc.)
- e. Rules and influencing mechanism:** The tariffs are based on the electricity generated by a renewable source which is used at the point of generation and exported to the grid (i.e. surplus electricity). They therefore give three financial benefits. These are cash back for all electricity generated (generation tariff), cash back for electricity exported to the grid (export tariff) and a reduction in the electricity bill due to reduced grid electricity supply (energy bill savings). The energy supplier pays a set rate for each unit of electricity generated and exported to the grid. Renewable technologies up to 5 megawatts and supported by the Renewable Obligation qualify for the scheme. These include technologies such as Solar PVs, wind turbines, hydroelectricity, anaerobic digesters (AD) and micro combined heat and power (CHP). To be eligible for FiTs, the installer of the renewable energy system and the products used must be certified under the Microgeneration Certification Scheme (with the exception of AD and hydro plants). The tariffs received depend on the eligibility date (the date the energy/FiT supplier receives a valid application for FiT) and for Solar PV systems, the property's Energy Performance Certificate (EPC). Evidence of the property's EPC rating is required when applying for FiTs and a rating of D or above will earn a higher rate compared to a rating not D or above. The tariff period or lifetime is 20 years for solar PVs, hydro and wind energy systems and 10 years for micro CHP systems. In the UK FiTs are tax free.
- f. Implementation network:** The Department for Energy and Climate Change (DECC) makes key decisions on FiTs in terms of government policy. The UK energy regulator, the Office of Gas and Electricity Markets, administers the scheme and the energy suppliers make the FiT payments to their customers. There are inter-relationships between the FiTs and other regulatory measures such as the Renewable Obligation and the Carbon Reduction Commitment.
- g. Outcomes:** The government estimated that FiTs to support small scale low-carbon electricity generation would cost £8.6 billion up to 2030 and produce monetised carbon savings worth £0.42 billion (DECC, 2010). An assessment of the first year of the FiT scheme conducted by the University of London showed that installations of solar and wind power increased (Mendonca, 2011).

3.5 Renewable Heat Incentive (RHI)

- a. General information:** The Renewable Heat Incentive (RHI) was introduced on 28 November 2011 and was introduced through the Energy Act 2008. It is the world's first long-term financial support programme for renewable heat.
- b. Type of policy instrument:** Economic: The RHI is a scheme that pays people for generating their own heat from renewable or low carbon sources. The scheme was designed to bridge the gap between the cost of

fossil fuel heat installations and renewable heat alternatives through financial support for owners.

- c. **Objectives:** The tariffs were introduced by the Government with the aim to increase the uptake of renewable heat-generating technologies in UK households, communities and businesses.
- d. **Target groups:** domestic and non-domestic building owners (e.g. households, landlords, businesses, schools etc.) and communities
- e. **Rules and influencing mechanism:** The RHI was introduced in two phases: the Non-Domestic RHI which provides payments to industry, businesses and public sector organisations and the domestic RHI which provide payments to homeowners, private landlords, social landlords and self-builders. The domestic RHI which was introduced on 9 April 2014 is not open to new build properties other than self-build. The renewable energy technologies eligible for RHI are flat plate or evacuated tube solar thermal panels, air-source heat pumps, ground and water-source heat pumps and biomass-only boilers and biomass pellet stoves with integrated boilers. Different tariffs are paid for different technologies and the level of the tariff have been set to reflect the expected cost of renewable heat generation over 20 years for non-domestic and over seven years for domestic RHI. Payments are made on quarterly basis. The RHI provides support for community and district heating schemes where a single renewable heat system provides heat or hot water to a number of households or properties. Similar to the FiT, the installed renewable heating system must be MCS certified. All RHI applications for domestic RHI must be accompanied by a Green Deal Advice report and must have a domestic EPC.
- f. **Implementation network:** The RHI schemes were introduced by the Department for Energy and Climate Change. It is delivered by the Office of Gas and Electricity Markets and paid for by the UK Treasury
- g. **Outcomes:** Since the introduction of the Domestic RHI, 25,000 renewable heating systems have been accredited to receive the payments. From these accreditations, it is estimated that approximately 1.4MT of CO₂ will be saved (Ofgem, 2015)

4. Capacity building and networking

4.1 Big Energy Saving Network (BESN)

- a. **General information:** The Big Energy Saving Network (BESN)⁶⁵ is a £900,000 programme established in 2014 to support eligible third sector organisations and community groups to deliver an extensive programme of outreach to vulnerable consumers, focussed on helping them to reduce their energy costs through assisted action on tariffs, switching and take-up of energy efficiency offers. Additional funding of £1m will allow us to continue supporting and growing BESN in 2015/16.
- b. **Type of policy instrument:** Capacity building and networking: building capacity in the most vulnerable areas to reduce energy consumption and resultant bills. Also building capacity in community groups in order to reach out to these vulnerable groups.
- c. **Objectives:** Outreach to vulnerable consumers, focussed on helping them to reduce their energy costs through assisted action on tariffs, switching and take-up of energy efficiency offers.
- d. **Target groups:** Third sector organisations and community groups that focus on helping vulnerable energy consumers i.e. those significantly less able than a typical consumer to protect or represent his or her interests in the energy market; and/or; significantly more likely than a typical consumer to suffer detriment, or that detriment is likely to be more substantial.
- e. **Rules and influencing mechanisms:** Mainly socio-economic influences and potential to 'up-skill'. No exemptions, penalties or sanctions.

⁶⁵ <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/big-energy-saving-network-grant-offer-fund>

- f. Implementation network:** BESN is funded by the Department of Energy and Climate Change (DECC), and there is a specific team within DECC that provide an over-seeing role. DECC were successful in appointing a range of delivery organisations that reflected the diverse characteristics of vulnerable consumers that BESN was intended to reach.
- g. Outcomes:** (i) Energy impact data is not available. (ii) Based on the £900k allocated to Phase I, the following unit costs were calculated: customers engaged through workshops: £56.25; customers engaged overall: £9.57; customers achieving 'key' outcomes (workshops only): £193.97. (iii) BESN workshops were successful in reaching a range of vulnerable groups including: those aged over 65; households with dependent children, those without access to gas and those without internet access. BESN is estimated to have reached around 16,000 participants via workshops (exceeding the target of 15,000) and a further 78,000 through frontline workers (falling within the target range of 60-90,000). BESN workshops were particularly successful at empowering consumers to get the best energy deal. The majority of those who responded to the survey reported feeling more informed and empowered as a result of their participation (73 per cent) and many went on to take subsequent action - from small-scale changes such as installing new light bulbs (32 per cent) to larger actions; nearly a third of participants (29 per cent) contacted their energy supplier about their tariff, 11 per cent switched supplier, and 5 per cent applied for an ECO assessment following BESN (DECC, 2015c).

4.2 Energy Management for Non-specialists training programme

- a. General information:** GAIA Active⁶⁶, funded by the UK Government as part of the UK's 'improving the skills base and supporting take up policy in the UK National Energy Efficiency Strategy (DECC, 2013b) created the 'Energy Management for Non-specialists' training programme in 2013. The programme was created for individuals that have energy management as part of their remit, but are not energy managers. The programme consisted of a one-day workshop and five subject-oriented webinars, as well as homework designed to ensure participants put the learning into practice. Topics covered included understanding energy data and bills, company engagement, and choosing and presenting capital investments. On successful completion of the programme, participants were awarded an EMA Level II certification.
- b. Type of policy instrument:** Capacity building and networking: support from Government to enable energy management skills. / Financial: Grant.
- c. Objectives:** To equip non-specialists with the skills of energy management.
- d. Target groups:** Any individual with the capacity to put into practice energy management; those who are not energy specialists but have (or will have) energy reduction as part of their role.
- e. Rules and influencing mechanisms:** Information on rules and influencing mechanisms not available. Mainly socio-economic influences and potential to 'up-skill'. No exemptions, penalties or sanctions.
- f. Implementation network:** GAIA Active⁶⁷, a private company of sustainability specialists was responsible for the design and implementation of the training programme, and the programme itself was funded through the DECC. GAIA now continue to run the programme without funding from DECC.
- g. Outcomes:** (i) Energy impact data is not available. (ii) No cost details available. (iii) The programme was attended by facilities, property, health and safety, environment, and energy managers. The training was successful in raising the profile of energy management within participants business, and speeding up energy reduction initiatives. Participants reported undertaking new projects in employee engagement, investment in new technologies, and engaging the boardroom to back tough reduction targets. Two

⁶⁶ <http://gaiaactive.com/energy-management-ema-stage-ii-and-beyond-online/>

⁶⁷ <http://gaiaactive.com/>

participants actually changed jobs to become full time energy reduction specialists. Following success of the first round, GAIA secured funding to offer the programme again the following year (DECC, 2013b).

4.3 Community Energy Peer Mentoring Fund

- a. General information:** The Community Energy Peer Mentoring Fund (CEPMF)⁶⁸ (ran from November 2013 – March 2015) supported community energy projects with grants to receive support and advice to get started with community energy projects. 12 community energy projects received grants totalling £500,000 to help fund projects including a community forum that provides workshops and assistance to communities to generate power using hydro energy and a social enterprise that sets up study visits and seminars for local community groups to help reduce their fossil fuel energy. Currently, community energy groups work on a variety of different projects such as raising funds for solar panels on community buildings to installing energy efficiency measures to help communities save money on their energy bills (SIB, n.d.). The CEPMF was developed in the context of the publication of the UK's first ever Community Energy Strategy⁶⁹ (2014), which highlighted a number of barriers, including the difficulties facing community groups in relation to accessing the right skills and expertise.
- b. Type of policy instrument:** Capacity building and networking: support from Government to enable community energy projects. / Financial: Grant.
- c. Objectives:** The funding was designed to help new groups working in the area of energy efficiency and carbon reduction to get off the ground so they can start saving money and generating energy in their community. It also helped existing groups to professionalise, develop business plans and scale up their work and to show how social action can help people reduce their energy bills.
- d. Target groups:** Community-level organisations and groups (both existing and new) who undertake energy-related projects and activities.
- e. Rules and influencing mechanisms:** Information on rules and influencing mechanisms not available. Mainly socio-economic influences and potential to 'up-skill'. No exemptions, penalties or sanctions.
- f. Implementation network:** The Community Energy Peer Mentoring Fund was funded by Cabinet Office's Centre for Social Action and the Department of Energy and Climate Change (DECC). EDF Energy were also part of the CEPMF through pro bono supporting to the 12 grant recipients; senior staff from EDF Energy volunteered to act as mentors, depending on the expertise and their geographical locations, and provided ongoing business support as and where needed.
- g. Outcomes:** (i) Energy impact data is not available. (ii) £500k total in grants awarded. (iii) Examples of projects developed with funding: Training volunteers to carry out home energy audits and simple energy saving installations such as draught proofing for Sutton's vulnerable and low income households; Marches Energy Agency, Beat the Cold, Keele University and

⁶⁸https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/449831/CEPMF_learning_doc_Final_corrected.pdf

⁶⁹ <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/community-energy-strategy>

Middleport Environment Centre are working together to support volunteers in designing and delivering activities and events to raise awareness about energy efficiency in the home. Based in Shrewsbury and Silverdale (Newcastle under Lyme), the project will run until March 2015 (SIB, n.d.)

5. Policy instruments for the promotion of energy services

5.1 Licence Lite (Supports Community Energy Strategy)

- a. General information:** In 2009 the UK Government recognised the importance of encouraging smaller-scale, distributed generation. The Electricity Act 1989⁷⁰ provides the overall regulatory framework for the supply of electricity in the UK. The Act provides Ofgem, as the regulator of the gas and electricity industries in Great Britain powers and duties relating to the protection of the interests of existing and future consumers, by *“promoting effective competition between persons engaged in, or in commercial activities connected with...the generation, transmission, distribution or supply of electricity or the provision or use of electricity interconnectors.”*⁷¹ As part of this Act, certain activities concerning electricity may only be carried out with a licence (or under a relevant exemption or exception). Ofgem published licence modification proposals and guidance which allows for exemption from certain licence conditions as long as alternative arrangements are made with another fully licensed supplier. Licence Lite⁷² (or Standard Licence Condition (SLC) 11.3) is a Licence Condition implemented in 2009, with associated guidance that helps new suppliers to enter the electricity supply market by providing a way to apply for a licence to supply electricity and get a direction that will relieve the obligation to directly fulfil the Standard Licence Condition (SLC) 11.2⁷³. If Licence Lite is proven to operate successfully, the UK Government would be supportive of greater levels of uptake amongst community energy projects and low- and zero-carbon decentralised energy projects generally, including for the electricity element of heat networks supplied by combined heat and power (CHP) systems (DECC, 2014a).
- b. Type of policy instrument:** Promotion of energy services: providing an easier way to licence small scale energy suppliers (DECC, 2014a).
- c. Objectives:** To enable communities to sell electricity locally, at a ‘local price’ as a way for all members of the community to benefit from a community energy project. Further community energy projects may wish to sell electricity beyond their local community, which ultimately has the potential to increase competition in the retail market and increase access for consumers to the sector (DECC, 2014a).
- d. Target groups:** Owners and operators of distributed energy schemes, electricity suppliers, distribution network operators, consumer groups, local authorities, property developers, and manufacturers and any other interested parties, in particular, small scale energy suppliers and community energy organisations (DECC, 2014a).
- e. Rules and influencing mechanisms:** Licence Lite relieves the applicant of their obligation to be a direct party to a number of industry codes. The regulatory costs incurred by complying with these codes are

⁷⁰ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/1989/29/contents>

⁷¹ <https://www.ofgem.gov.uk/ofgem-publications/58104/definalproposals.pdf>

⁷² https://www.ofgem.gov.uk/sites/default/files/docs/2009/02/de_final_proposals_0.pdf

⁷³ <https://epr.ofgem.gov.uk/Content/Documents/Electricity%20Supply%20Standard%20Licence%20Conditions%20Consolidated%20-%20Current%20Version.pdf>

disproportionately high for smaller suppliers. Licence Lite lets a new supplier partner with an existing supplier (third party fully licensed supplier (TPLS)) to be responsible for some of the more costly and technically challenging parts of a supply licence. License suppliers that handle domestic and/or small-business customers are required to be members of the Ombudsman scheme, and comply with complaints handling regulations. Customers have the right to take certain complaints to the Energy Ombudsman, if the supplier fails to resolve the problem. If either the Licence Lite supplier or the TPLS does not meet its commercial obligations as set out in the supplier services agreement, it is expected that parties seek redress via the commercial agreement. If a Licence Lite supplier is found to have breached its licence conditions there are a number of enforcement actions Ofgem may take, including imposition of penalties, consumer redress, and orders (Ofgem, 2015). In terms of setting the amount of any financial penalty and/or payment under a consumer redress order, the amount in each case must not exceed 10% of the regulated person's turnover. Ofgem have enforcement powers under the following legislation:

- the Gas Act 1986 (the Gas Act)
- the Electricity Act 1989 (the Electricity Act)
- the Utilities Act 2000
- the Competition Act 1998 (the Competition Act)
- the Enterprise Act 2002 (the Enterprise Act)
- the Unfair Terms in Consumer Contracts Regulations 1999 (UTCCRs)
- the Business Protection from Misleading Marketing Regulations 2008 (the BPMMRs).

f. Implementation network: Ofgem; The UK Government wants to see Licence Lite work for community groups and will actively work with Ofgem to support this (DECC, 2014a).

g. Outcomes: (i) Energy impact data is not available. (ii) No cost details available. (iii) This arrangement, which has become known as 'Licence Lite', has been taken forward by the Greater London Authority (GLA) which has made application for a Licence Lite licence on behalf of the Mayor of London. The GLA application is a welcome development which will help clarify the need for any further guidance in this area. Clearly this would be an important step for Licence Lite, and would provide others with a route to learn from (DECC, 2014).

5.2 Heat Networks Delivery Unit (HNDU)

a. General information: Recognising the capacity and capability challenges which local authorities identified as barriers to heat network deployment in the UK, the Heat Network Delivery Unit (HNDU)⁷⁴ was established by the Department of Energy and Climate Change in September 2013 to provide grant funding and guidance to local authorities in England and Wales (the Scottish Parliament has set its own Heat Map and Vision for Heat). This honoured a commitment in 'The future of heating: meeting the challenge' (published in March 2013) to support local authorities exploring heat network opportunities. In the first round of the programme, 31 local authorities will be receiving £1.95m.

b. Type of policy instrument: Promotion of energy services: the intent is to support heat network programmes / Capacity building: the purpose is to provide support and guidance for capacity building with regard to heat networks / Financial: funding is allotted to local authorities

c. Objectives: HNDU aims to transform district heating in the UK, providing financial support, guidance and expertise for local authorities, especially in the crucial early stage of developing a heat network.

d. Target groups: Local authorities

⁷⁴https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/394509/DECC_Energy_Investment_Report_WEB.pdf

- e. Rules and influencing mechanisms:** Local authorities apply for HNDU support through bidding rounds. Successful applicants are published on the Heat Network Delivery Funding page. All bids are reviewed by a panel of engineering, financial and commercial experts with significant experience in heat networks development. Grant funding of no more than 67% of eligible costs is provided to successful local authorities under section 31 of the Local Government Act. Eligible costs are defined as externally commissioned consultancy costs for heat network development work. If successful, each local authority is assigned an HNDU staff member as 'Project Lead' and their work together is supported through an online collaboration site and face to face meetings.
- f. Implementation network:** HNDU is a unit within DECC and is staffed by experts, who have gained experience developing heat networks outside the civil service working on technical or commercial aspects of heat networks for consultancies or local authorities.
- g. Outcomes:** (i) Energy impact data is not available. (ii) Budget of £6.9m (iii) Since inception the Unit has awarded support to 180 unique projects across 115 local authorities including £9.7 million of grant funding. The Unit is currently scheduled to run until March 2016. As set out in Delivering UK Energy Investment: Networks released in January 2015, DECC analysis suggests the portfolio of HNDU projects alone could represent between £400 million to £800 million of capital investment opportunity over the next 10 years (on an assumption of 25% to 50% of current projects coming to fruition) (GOV.UK, 2015b).

5.3 Rural Community Energy Fund (RCEF) & Urban Community Energy Fund (UCEF)

- a. General information:** In June 2013 DECC and Defra launched the £15m Rural Community Energy Fund (RCEF) to provide finance for rural communities in England to explore the feasibility of, and planning for, electricity and heat projects. This fund was also complemented by the £10m Urban Community Energy Fund (UCEF). Communities in Wales can already access similar financial support through the Ynni'r Fro scheme, while in Scotland the Community and Renewable Energy Scheme (CARES) includes a preplanning loan scheme. Evaluation of the schemes will look at the impact of community energy group involvement in Green Deal Communities schemes (DECC, 2014a). A legal structure is needed in order for applications for the majority of grants and loans, such as; community benefit society, co-operative society, community interest companies (supervised by the CIC Regulator), charities (regulated by the Charity Commission), joint ventures.
- b. Type of policy instrument:** Promotion of energy services: the intent is to support community energy programmes / Capacity building: the purpose is to provide support and guidance for capacity building with regard to community energy projects / Financial: funding is allotted to community groups
- c. Objectives:** RCEF and UCEF funds are offered to be used as source of early stage finance for community heat projects. Through these funds, community groups can receive grants for technical feasibility studies, and loans for the later, more complex stages of project development. This funding will help groups overcome the riskier stages of renewable development and attract commercial finance, or raise money through a community share offer. The RCEF and UCEF aim to contribute to the UK Government's target for renewable energy and community-owned renewable schemes (DECC, 2014a).
- d. Target groups:** Rural and urban communities interested in renewable energy and community-owned renewable schemes. Local authorities become eligible for RCEF and UCEF if working with an applicant community group. (DECC, 2014a).
- e. Rules and influencing mechanisms:** Local authorities become eligible for RCEF and UCEF if working with an applicant community group. Loans issued to groups are repaid, enabling the fund to self-sustain, recycling funds to support more community groups (DECC, 2014a). The Rural Community Energy Fund (RCEF) is available to rural communities in England that:
- represent a rural community of:

- fewer than 10,000 residents; or
- more than 10,000 residents but within a local authority area which is classified by the Office of National Statistics as 'predominantly rural'.
- form a legal entity in order to receive public funds
- demonstrate the support of the wider community

and are planning a renewable energy project which:

- will provide a legacy for the future benefit of the community
- use a proven renewable technology

In terms of the UCEF, the following are eligible to apply:

- Groups that:
 - are developing a project in an urban area
 - incorporated as a legal form that we can give money to
 - answer a series of other eligibility criteria
- In addition, any of the following groups are eligible to apply for the fund:
 - Registered Company (including CICs)
 - Charitable Incorporated Organisation
 - Registered Societies (formerly known as IPS)
 - Parish and Town Councils
 - Local Authorities, businesses and Housing Associations can apply in partnership with the local community.

f. Implementation network: DECC/DEFRA-funded; monitoring and evaluation will be carried out on the UCEF and RCEF by DECC Community Energy Unit (DECC, 2015d). Waste and Resources Action Programme (WRAP) and Centre for Sustainable Energy (CSE) provide advice and support relating to the application and undertaking of RCEF and UCEF-funded projects. WRAP⁷⁵ are the UCEF scheme administrators and CSE⁷⁶ have been contracted the management of the UCEF fund, in partnership with Pure Leapfrog, a business-led charity⁷⁷.

g. Outcomes: (i) The potential generation of all the approved RCEF and UCEF projects is already up to 60MW and growing (DECC, 2015d). (ii) £15m total funds to distributed under RCEF / £10m total funds to distributed under UCEF (iii) RCEF distributed £450k to 25 electricity generation projects in 2014. RCEF passes £1m distributed to 48 projects in February 2015 and projecting £800k for 25 electricity generation projects over the course of the year (DECC, 2015d).

6. Policy instruments for R&D and best available technologies (BAT) promotion

6.1 Technology Strategy Board (TSB) / Innovate UK

a. General information: The Technology Strategy Board was first established in 2004 as an advisory body

⁷⁵ <http://www.wrap.org.uk/content/rural-community-energy-fund>

⁷⁶ <https://www.cse.org.uk/>

⁷⁷ <http://www.pureleapfrog.org/page.jsp?id=2>

within the former UK Department of Trade and Industry (DTI). As the primary channel through which the Government encourages innovation, the Technology Strategy Board (TSB), now called Innovate UK, is the UK's innovation agency. Many of the priority areas Innovate UK focus on are also reflected in the 'Eight Great Technologies' identified by Science and Universities Minister David Willetts. One of Innovate UK's main tools is collaborative R&D funding; running competitions in a broad range of growth creating areas, from transport to biosciences and from construction to nanoscale technologies. Innovate UK have developed Catalysts are run in partnership with the research councils, offering businesses and researchers a clear and progressive route for development, so that successful early-stage projects can easily find support for the next stage on their innovation journey; and Catapult centres: A Catapult is a technology and innovation centre where the very best of the UK's businesses, scientists and engineers can work side by side on research and development – transforming ideas into new products and services to generate economic growth. Catapults add an important new dimension to complement our existing research and development programmes, helping businesses to adopt, develop and exploit innovative products and technologies. They offer concentrated expertise in areas such as manufacturing processes, test facilities, type approval and accreditation or supply chain development. Many provide access to cutting-edge equipment and specialist facilities to develop and test ideas in reality (TSB, 2014). Previous TSB projects funded include: Retrofit for the Future: funding innovate technology and methods in retrofitted dwellings; Building Performance Evaluation: funding two year evaluation of sustainable new build dwellings and non-dwellings; and Design for Future Climate: funding research of the impact of climate change on energy efficiency and technology in buildings and innovative responses to the problem (Innovate UK, 2015).

- b. Type of policy instrument:** Policy instruments for R&D and best available technologies (BAT) promotion.
- c. Objectives:** The focus of Innovate UK is on innovation, working with business to stimulate and support innovation and accelerate economic growth
- d. Target groups:** Business and research
- e. Rules and influencing mechanisms:** The responsibilities of Innovate UK are to: provide new support for innovative small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) with high-growth potential; make sure that government initiatives such as SBRI (Small Business Research Initiative) attract innovative UK businesses and give companies access to important customers in the public sector; identify and invest in the sectors that have the greatest potential for innovation to speed up economic growth; and help innovative companies work with their backers so their ideas can be developed commercially
- f. Implementation network:** Innovate UK is an executive non-departmental public body, sponsored by the Department for Business, Innovation & Skills.
- g. Outcomes:** (i) Energy impact data is not available. (ii) Gross grant expenditure for built environment 2012-2013: £15m; 2013-2014: £32.7m (iii) Aside from job creation as a result of funding Innovate UK has increased full-time employment from 196 to 257 employees from 2013-2014. Millions of £ invested in R&D resulting in numerous outcomes directly befitting business and the public.

6.2 Code for Sustainable Homes (CSH)

- a. General information:** The code for sustainable homes is the national standard for the sustainable design and construction of new homes. The Code was launched by the Department for Communities and Local Government (DCLG) in December 2006. The CSH technical guidance came into effect in April 2007, and it became possible to assess new homes built in England from this date. It can take, on average, 18 months to two years to design and build a Code home. As a result the first homes built to the Code standard were not awarded a certificate until 2008. The code provides nine measures of sustainable design: energy/CO₂; water; materials; surface water runoff (flooding and flood prevention); waste; pollution; health and well-being; management; and ecology. It uses a 1 to 6 star system to rate the overall sustainability performance of a new home against these nine categories (DCLG, 2010a). Following the December 2009 consultation, a

number of revisions were made to the Code in 2010 (DCLG, 2010b).

- b. Type of policy instrument:** Policy instruments for R&D and best available technologies (BAT) promotion: As a result of pushing the limit on new home design to meet more stringent standards the CSH inspires R&D and promotes and demonstrates the integration of BAT.
- c. Objectives:** The Code for Sustainable Homes is a vital tool for improving environmental performance and reducing CO₂ emissions from new homes. The extensive framework provided by the Code sets challenging targets in a range of categories; from energy use and CO₂ emissions, to water consumption, to site ecology. It aims to reduce carbon emissions and promote higher standards of sustainable design above the current minimum standards set out by the building regulations.
- d. Target groups:** Designers, builders and owners of new dwellings.
- e. Rules and influencing mechanisms:** The code is voluntary and should not be confused with zero-carbon policy or the 2016 zero-carbon target. The only circumstances where the code can be enforced are where: local councils require developers to comply with the code by including a requirement in their planning policy; affordable housing is funded by the Homes and Community Agency that requires homes to be built to code level 3; the level 3 energy standard is now incorporated in the building regulations. The code applies in England, Wales and Northern Ireland. Within England it replaces the EcoHomes scheme, developed by the Building Research Establishment. Assessments are carried out in two phases: An initial assessment is carried out at the design stage. This is based on detailed documentary evidence and commitments which results in an interim certificate of compliance. Final assessment and certification is carried out at the post construction stage. Based on the design stage review, this includes a confirmation of compliance, including site records and visual inspection, and results in a final certificate of compliance.
- f. Implementation network:** Launched and managed by DCLG.
- g. Outcomes:** (i) Energy impact data is not available. (ii) Best estimate total cost £67.6m (DCLG, 2010b) (iii) Between April 2007 and the end of December 2014, 151,262 dwellings have received a three star rating at post-construction stage and 42,017 dwellings have received a four star rating. A total of 76% of those at post-construction stage have been awarded at Code level 3 since April 2007 (DCLG, 2015).

6.3 Energy Technology Institute (ETI)

- a. General information:** The ETI is a public-private partnership between global energy and engineering companies and the UK government established by the UK government in 2007. ETI makes targeted commercial investments in nine technology programmes across heat, power, transport and the infrastructure that links them. Investment must meet UK 2020 and 2050 energy climate change targets cost effectively (ETI, 2015). Example project: £100 million, 5 year Smart Systems and Heat Programme to investigate what drives heat demand and the potential for technical innovations to meet this demand more efficiently (DECC, 2014c).
- b. Type of policy instrument:** Policy instruments for R&D and best available technologies (BAT) promotion: ETI brings together engineering projects that develop affordable, secure and sustainable technologies to help the UK address its long term emissions reductions targets as well as delivering nearer term benefits (ETI, 2015).
- c. Objectives:** The primary objective is to act as a conduit between academia, industry and the government to accelerate the development of low carbon technologies. ETI brings together engineering projects that develop affordable, secure and sustainable technologies to help the UK address its long term emissions reductions targets as well as delivering nearer term benefits (ETI, 2015).
- d. Target groups:** Academia and industry as well as government bodies and departments with energy efficiency-related policies within their remit (ETI, 2015).
- e. Rules and influencing mechanisms:** All officers and employees of the ETI must avoid conflicts of interest with their ETI responsibilities. Any such conflict, actual or potential, must be declared immediately as it arises to enable the ETI to take appropriate action. ETI establishes processes that identify, assess and

manage risks and carries out regular internal audits to ensure full compliance throughout. All business transactions on behalf of the ETI will be reflected accurately and fairly in the accounts, in accordance with established procedures, and will be subject to audit and disclosure. ETI respects the strict need for confidentiality when dealing with the intellectual property assets of both member organisations and other organisations with ETI conducts business. ETI respects all applicable laws and regulations of the countries in which ETI operates and shall seek to operate within the framework of applicable competition laws including any EC rules and regulations relating to State Aid. ETI expressly forbids the direct or indirect offer, payment, solicitation or acceptance of bribes or any form of payments which seek to create an unfair advantage or exert undue influence over an individual or organisation. Gifts and hospitality in excess of £30 will be declared (ETI, 2015).

- f. Implementation network:** The ETI is a public-private partnership between global energy and engineering companies and the UK government.
- g. Outcomes:** (i) Energy impact data is not available. (ii) No cost details available. (iii) No other impact details available.

Table 3 National programmes and initiatives in transport

1. Planning instruments
1.1 Plugged-in Places (The Plug-In Vehicle Infrastructure Strategy)
<p>a. General information: The Plugged-In Places (PiP) programme is the key mechanism for commencing the roll-out of recharging infrastructure in the UK and providing learning to inform the future development of a national network. The PiP is part of the key transport actions held within the UK Governments Carbon Plan 2011⁷⁸. The Government provided up to £30m in matched funding in 2010-2013 to support the installation and trialling of recharging infrastructure in eight places across the country (8,500 charge points). These are led by local consortia including private and public sector organisations, local utilities and businesses to secure investment in plug-in vehicle infrastructure for their areas (OLEV, 2011). The PiP programme is supported by a legislative framework based on European new car CO₂ targets (Regulation (EC) No. 443/2009⁷⁹), EU Framework Directive 2007/46/EC⁸⁰ as well as the Renewable Energy Directive (RED) 2009/28/EC⁸¹ as well as the UK's National Planning Policy Framework (DCLG, 2012).</p> <p>b. Type of policy instrument: Planning instrument: The Strategy is focused on improving the infrastructure for electric vehicle ownership through planning.</p> <p>c. Objectives: In addition to making plug-in vehicles more affordable and stimulating technological innovation, having the right infrastructure in place to support plug-in vehicle owners is the other critical component in maintaining the UK's favourable market position. By providing clarity of approach and</p>

⁷⁸ https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/47613/3702-the-carbon-plan-delivering-our-low-carbon-future.pdf

⁷⁹ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:32009R0443>

⁸⁰ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32007L0046>

⁸¹ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2009:140:0016:0062:EN:PDF>

removing barriers for those wishing to invest in, provide or benefit from such infrastructure, the Strategy aims to stimulate and accommodate the growth in the plug-in vehicle market that we expect to see up to 2020.

- d. Target groups:** The PiP aims to encourage local authorities to adopt plug-in vehicle recharging infrastructure within their local planning policies, as well as encourage research and development in electric vehicles within the transport industry, and improve the economic viability of plug-in vehicle infrastructure for installation contractors, charge-point manufacturers and operators as well as local authorities and owners of publicly accessible car parks. In addition, a secondary target group is the end user/consumer (both domestic and business).
- e. Rules and influencing mechanisms:** As a strategy, there are no specific rules. However, it is combined with numerous policies and financial incentives in relation to increasing the uptake of plug-in vehicles (hybrid and/or full electric) such as the Plug-in Car and Van Grant incentives, favourable tax regimes (plug-in vehicles receive VED and Company Car Tax exemptions, as well as Enhanced Capital Allowances). Furthermore, businesses monitored under the Carbon Reduction Commitment (CRC) are able to discount electricity used to charge plug-in vehicles from their total electricity consumption. Planning-related incentives include the establishment of a Permitted Development Right for landowners to install charge-points without the need for planning permission.
- f. Implementation network:** Office for Low Emission Vehicles (OLEV). Implementation strategy includes: using the Plugged-In Places trials as a central mechanism to inform the development of commercial models for plug-in vehicle infrastructure; removing barriers to the market, such as the requirement for planning permission for public recharging infrastructure, and working to enable charge point operators to charge the market rate for electricity; producing a conducive environment for private investment, by encouraging infrastructure through planning policies, supporting the move to standardisation and, if raising finance proves a barrier, the potential for targeted financial solutions through the Green Investment Bank; and helping the consumer by enabling all public infrastructure to be interoperable and improving the provision of information about public charge points (OLEV, 2011).
- g. Outcomes:** (i) Energy impact data is not available. (ii) Total grant funding £30m. (iii) Following a qualitative research review of the PiP programme, public charging infrastructure was considered to be important by 40% of respondents in influencing their decision to purchase EVs. Though EV drivers used the charge points there was very little awareness of the PiP programme provided the infrastructure. Lack of compatibility between different charge point providers was confusing and frustrating for EV purchasers and users (TRL, 2013).

1.2 Eco-towns: A supplement to Planning Policy Statement 1

- a. General information:** In 2009 DCLG set out how eco-towns should be defined as part of the overall planning policy. Among many issues such as setting out that dwellings should be zero carbon and planning for biodiversity. With regard to transportation specifically: It is important to ensure that eco-towns are genuine mixed-use communities and that unsustainable commuter trips are kept to a minimum. Travel in eco-towns should support people's desire for mobility whilst achieving the goal of low carbon living. The town should be designed so that access to it and through it gives priority to options such as walking, cycling, public transport and other sustainable options, thereby reducing residents' reliance on private cars, including techniques such as filtered permeability. To achieve this, homes should be within ten minutes' walk of (a) frequent public transport and (b) neighbourhood services. The provision of services within the eco-town may be co-located to reduce the need for individuals to travel by private car and encourage the efficient use of the sustainable transport options available (DCLG, 2009b). *The eco-towns planning policy supplement was cancelled in its current form from 5th March 2015.*
- b. Type of policy instrument:** Planning instrument: sets out planning rules for eco-towns

- c. Objectives:** To minimize energy consumption and to make healthy living easier.
- d. Target groups:** Developers, designers, infrastructure and building industries.
- e. Rules and influencing mechanisms:** Planning applications should include travel plans which demonstrate: (a) how the town's design will enable at least 50 per cent of trips originating in eco-towns to be made by non-car means, with the potential for this to increase over time to at least 60 per cent (b) good design principles, drawing from Manual for Streets, Building for Life, and community travel planning principles (c) how transport choice messages, infrastructure and services will be provided from 'day one' of residential occupation, and (d) how the carbon impact of transport in the eco-town will be monitored, as part of embedding a long term low-carbon approach to travel within plans for community governance. Where eco-town plans intend to incorporate ultra-low carbon vehicle options, including electric car schemes to help achieve a sustainable transport system, planning applications should demonstrate that: (a) there will be sufficient energy headroom to meet the higher demand for electricity, and (b) the scheme will not add so many additional private vehicles to the local road network that these will cause congestion. The policies set out in the Planning Policy Strategy should be taken into account by regional planning bodies in the preparation of revisions to regional spatial strategies, by the Mayor of London in relation to the spatial development strategy for London, and by local planning authorities in the preparation of local development documents (DCLG, 2009b).
- f. Implementation network:** The UK Government ministerial department, DCLG,⁸² sets out national planning policy guidance, strategy and rules. The DCLG has the following responsibilities:
- supporting local government by giving them the power to act for their community - without interference from central government.
 - helping communities and neighbourhoods to solve their own problems so neighbourhoods are strong, attractive and thriving.
 - working with local enterprise partnerships and enterprise zones to help the private sector grow.
 - making the planning system work more efficiently and effectively.
 - supporting local fire and rescue authorities so that they're able to respond to emergencies and reduce the number and impact of fires.
- There are corresponding departments in the Welsh Government, Scottish Government and the Northern Ireland Executive, and which are responsible for policy relating to communities and local government within their localities. In terms of planning, England and Wales follow the same planning policies, whilst Scotland and Northern Ireland have their own separate local planning policy frameworks. Within the DCLG, the executive agency, the Planning Inspectorate, deals with "planning appeals, national infrastructure planning applications, examinations of local plans and other planning-related and specialist casework in England and Wales."⁸³ Eco-towns will need to be monitored through regional and local monitoring frameworks. Regional Planning Bodies and Local Planning Authorities will be required to monitor the implementation of their spatial policies as set out in the RSS and in development plan documents at the local level. Regional Planning Bodies and Local Planning Authorities should set out in their Annual Monitoring Reports indicators for monitoring the sustainability of eco-towns in their region/district. Arrangements should be put in place for the long-term monitoring of the standards set out for eco-towns as part of the requirements for community governance.
- g. Outcomes:** (i) Energy impact data is not available. (ii) Total estimated implementation cost £700-1400m (DCLG, 2009a) (iii) Three Ecotowns have progressed since 2007: Cornwall (St. Austell), Oxfordshire (Bicester) and Hampshire (Bordon). The UK government appears to have misunderstood both how long it

⁸² <https://www.gov.uk/government/organisations/department-for-communities-and-local-government>

⁸³ <https://www.gov.uk/government/organisations/planning-inspectorate>

takes to bring such large schemes together from scratch (and ignoring a lengthy recession) and what institutional support is needed to ensure delivery. Spring 2015 the UK Government indicated that it would remove the policy guidance (PPS1 supplement) involving eco-towns from the National Planning Policy Framework (along with requirements for zero carbon homes by 2016) (Parker, 2015).

1.3 Rail electrification

- a. **General information:** Railway electrification in the UK has been going on since the 19th century and the electrified network is to continue expanding. Electrifying the rail network will mean greener and more reliable journeys for passengers. In 2006, 40% of the UK rail network was electrified.
- b. **Type of policy instrument:** Planning instrument: The Government is committed to investing in a programme of electrification to transform the railway and have confirmed funding for investment in electrification projects such as the North West Electrification project and the Western Main Line.
- c. **Objectives:** To improve the rail network in order to improve services, support economic growth across cities and towns, increase number of seats on the trains and improve the reliability of the train service.
- d. **Targets groups:** All rail passengers, train companies, business.
- e. **Rules and influencing mechanisms:** The electrification programmes will be managed and delivered by Network Rail and the Rail Industry Association and the Department for Transport will be working with Network Rail to deliver the programmes
- f. **Implementation network:** Network Rail owns and operates the UK's rail infrastructure and are responsible for the railway network. They work closely with the Department for Transport, train companies and other stakeholders to deliver the plans for electrifying the rail network
- g. **Outcomes:** Electric trains do not produce emissions at the point of use and are estimated to reduce carbon emissions by 20-30% compared to diesel trains. This in turn improves air quality and quality of life with the added benefits of reduced noise pollution.

2. Regulatory policy instruments

2.1 Vehicle Excise Duty (VED): fuel type and CO2 emission vehicle bands

- a. **General information:** Section 1 of the Vehicle and Registration Act (VERA) 1994 provides for the charging of VED. Section 2 of VERA provides that VED in respect of a vehicle of any description is chargeable by reference to the applicable rate specified in schedule 1 of VERA. Part 1A of Schedule 1 to VERA sets out the VED rates for cars registered on or after 1 March 2001, as amended by successive Finance Acts (HM R&C, 2015).
Policy set forth in the 2015 Summer Budget (July): Vehicle Excise Duty (VED) for cars first registered from 1 April 2017 onwards. First Year Rates (FYRs) of VED will vary according to the carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions of the vehicle. A flat Standard Rate (SR) of £140 will apply in all subsequent years, except for zero-emission cars for which the SR will be £0. Cars with a list price above £40,000 will attract a supplement of £310 on their SR for the first 5 years in which a SR is paid. All cars first registered before 1 April 2017 will remain in the current VED system, which will not change (HM R&C, 2015).
- b. **Type of policy instrument:** Regulatory: VED and SR are required by all vehicle owners.
- c. **Objectives:** The reformed VED system retains and strengthens the CO₂-based FYRs to incentivise uptake of the very cleanest cars whilst moving to a flat SR in order to make the tax fairer, simpler and sustainable (HM R&C, 2015).
- d. **Target groups:** All vehicle owners.
- e. **Rules and influencing mechanisms:** To ensure those who can afford the most expensive cars make a fair contribution, a supplement of £310 will be applied to the SR of cars with a list price (not including VED)

over £40,000, for the first 5 years in which a SR is paid. Section 1 of the Vehicle and Registration Act (VERA) 1994 provides for the charging of VED. Section 2 of VERA provides that VED in respect of a vehicle of any description is chargeable by reference to the applicable rate specified in schedule 1 of VERA. Part 1A of Schedule 1 to VERA sets out the VED rates for cars registered on or after 1 March 2001, as amended by successive Finance Acts (HM R&C, 2015).

- f. Implementation network:** Tax set forth by HM Revenue & Customs. The measure is monitored through the DVLA vehicle licensing data (HM R&C, 2015).
- g. Outcomes:** (i) This measure supports the development and manufacture of zero and Ultra Low Emission Vehicles (ULEVs) in the United Kingdom by providing preferential tax treatment of these cars over conventionally fuelled cars. The very cleanest zero-emission vehicles are particularly incentivised as they continue to be pay a £0 of VED. - Carbon emissions: by strengthening the incentive to purchase zero-emission cars and ULEVs over conventionally fuelled cars this measure is expected to contribute to the UK's carbon emissions targets. (ii) No cost details available. (iii) The current VED structure based on CO₂ bands was introduced in 2001 when average UK new car emissions were 178 gCO₂/km. The Band A threshold of 100 gCO₂/km below which cars pay no VED was introduced in 2003 when average new car emissions were 173 gCO₂/km. Since then, to meet EU emissions targets average new car emissions have fallen to 125 gCO₂/km. This means that an increasingly large number of ordinary cars now fall into the zero- or lower-rated VED bands, creating a sustainability challenge and weakening the environmental signal in VED. This is set to continue as manufacturers meet further EU targets of 95 gCO₂/km set for 2020. Additionally, the system results in significant unfairness as owners of newer cars pay little or no VED while owners of older cars generally pay higher rates. This measure is expected to have a small positive effect on inflation but is not expected to have any significant macroeconomic impacts. The costing includes a behavioural response to account for an increase in vehicle purchases in the period between the measure being announced and it being implemented (HM R&C, 2015).

2.2 Renewable Transport Fuel Obligation (RTFO)

- a. General information:** The Renewable Transport Fuel Obligation (RTFO)⁸⁴ supports the government's policy on reducing greenhouse gas emissions (GHG) from vehicles by encouraging the production of biofuels that don't damage the environment. Under the RTFO suppliers of transport and non-road mobile machinery (NRMM) fuel in the UK must be able to show that a percentage of the fuel they supply comes from renewable and sustainable sources. Fuel suppliers who supply at least 450,000 litres of fuel a year are affected. This includes suppliers of biofuels as well as suppliers of fossil fuel. The RTFO only covers biofuels used in the transport and NRMM sectors (DfT, 2012).
- The Renewable Transport Fuel Obligation Order 2007⁸⁵ was amended in December 2011⁸⁶ to transpose the transport elements of the EU Renewable Energy Directive (RED) 2009/28/EC, and was amended again in 2013⁸⁷ to implement the closely related requirements of articles 7a-e of the EU Fuel Quality Directive 2009/30/EC⁸⁸. It has also undergone amendments in 2009⁸⁹ and 2015⁹⁰. The RTFO scheme is closely

⁸⁴ <https://www.gov.uk/guidance/renewable-transport-fuels-obligation>

⁸⁵ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2007/3072/contents/made>

⁸⁶ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2011/2937/contents/made>

⁸⁷ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2013/816/contents/made>

⁸⁸ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2009:140:0088:0113:EN:PDF>

aligned to reporting requirements placed on suppliers under the Motor Fuel (Road Vehicle and Mobile Machinery) Greenhouse Gas Emissions Regulations 2012⁹¹, which also form part of the UK's transposition of the EU Fuel Quality Directive 2009/30/EC.

Other related UK legislation includes:

- The Energy Act 2004 (Part 2, Chapter 5 outlines)⁹²
- The Climate Change Act 2008⁹³
- The Biodiesel Duty Regulations 2010⁹⁴
- HM Revenue and Customs note on the extension of the duty differential for biodiesel from used cooking oil⁹⁵
- The Biodiesel and Bioblend Regulations 2002⁹⁶
- The Hydrocarbon Oil Duties Act 1979⁹⁷

Relevant EU legislation about biofuels includes:

- The Renewable Energy Directive (RED)⁹⁸
- The Fuel Quality Directive (FQD)⁹⁹
- Regulation 510/2011 of the European Parliament and of the council of 11 May 2011 setting emission performance standards for new light commercial vehicles as part of the Union's integrated approach to reduce CO₂ emissions from light-duty vehicles.¹⁰⁰

b. Type of policy instrument: Regulatory: suppliers of transport and non-road mobile machinery (NRMM) fuel in the UK must be able to show that a percentage of the fuel they supply comes from renewable and sustainable sources.

c. Objectives: Reducing transport related GHG while supporting production of biofuels.

d. Target groups: Obligatory for companies own and supply 450,000 litres or more of any road transport or NRMM fuel for use in the UK. Open to any company.

⁸⁹ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2009/843/contents/made>

⁹⁰ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2015/534/contents/made>

⁹¹ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2012/3030/contents/made>

⁹² <http://webarchive.nationalarchives.gov.uk/+http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2004/20/contents>

⁹³ <http://webarchive.nationalarchives.gov.uk/20120202155346/http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2008/27/contents>

⁹⁴ <http://webarchive.nationalarchives.gov.uk/20110131070443/http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2010/984/contents/made>

⁹⁵ <http://webarchive.nationalarchives.gov.uk/20110202215457/http://www.hmrc.gov.uk/pbr2009/pbrn31.htm>

⁹⁶ <http://webarchive.nationalarchives.gov.uk/20101218152931/http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2002/1928/contents/made>

⁹⁷ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/1979/5/contents>

⁹⁸ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2009:140:0016:0062:EN:PDF>

⁹⁹ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2009:140:0088:0113:EN:PDF>

¹⁰⁰ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=CONSLEG:2011R0510:20120313:EN:PDF>

- e. Rules and influencing mechanisms:** A company must register under the RTFO if it owns and supplies 450,000 litres or more of any road transport or NRMM fuel for use in the UK during the course of an obligation year (15 April to 14 April). The 450,000 litre figure includes all fossil fuels and biofuels. If a company supplies less than 450,000 litres a year in the UK, it can still register to claim Renewable Transport Fuel Certificates (RTFCs). Any company that supplies sustainable biofuel for use in road transport or NRMM in the UK can claim RTFCs. Companies can trade RTFCs or sell them to companies that need them to meet their obligations under the RTFO. Suppliers covered by the RTFO must provide data on the volumes and source of biofuel brought to market in the UK (DfT, 2012). In terms of non-compliance; *“The Administrator has powers to impose civil penalties in certain cases of non-compliance with the requirements of the RTFO including: failure to register with the Administrator if obligated; failure to meet the obligation through either the redemption of RTFCs or the payment of the buy-out price; or the fraudulent application for, or gaining of RTFCs. The Administrator may also apply interest to, and will collect, overdue civil penalties and buy-out payments”* (DfT, 2014b).
- f. Implementation network:** The Administrator of the RTFO is the Secretary of State; however, the daily administration including registration and compliance of the RTFO is managed by the RTFO Unit in the Department for Transport (DfT). In addition to the practical administration of the RTFO, the RTFO Unit run regular stakeholder events, publish a monthly newsletter with updates on important developments and has developed guidance to help suppliers and verifiers meet the requirements in the RTFO legislation. The unit also has an expert advisory group which provides technical advice, input and expertise on issues around carbon and sustainability of biofuel.
- g. Outcomes:** (i) Estimated total net GHG savings in mtCO₂e/yr (not including indirect land use change effects): 1.6 in year 1; 2.0 in year 2; 2.1 in year 3; 2.4 in year 4; 2.0 in year 5. (ii) Best estimate total cost £2,215m (iii) Benefits which have not explicitly monetised in this cost benefit analysis include development of a UK biofuels industry (capital investment and jobs), increased agricultural production, diversification of the fuel supply, increased production of protein rich animal feed (as a co-product of bioethanol production). It was estimated that a 100 million litre biodiesel processing plant would create/sustain 200 jobs in farming and 62 jobs at the plant itself. If the plants were supplied entirely by feedstock produced in the UK, this would equate to 2,200 farming jobs and 682 jobs at the plants (DfT, 2014a).

2.3 Energy Savings Opportunity Scheme (ESOS)

- a. General information:** Introduced June 2014, ESOS is a mandatory energy assessment scheme for large organisations in the UK. It was established by the UK Government in order to implement Article 8 (4-6) of the EU Energy Efficiency Directive (2012/27/EU)¹⁰¹. The ESOS Regulations 2014¹⁰² give effect to the scheme. Organisations that qualify for ESOS must carry out ESOS assessments every 4 years. These assessments are audits of the energy used by their buildings, industrial processes and transport to identify cost-effective energy saving measures (Environment Agency, 2015).
- b. Type of policy instrument:** Regulatory; ESOS is a mandatory scheme (Environment Agency, 2015).
- c. Objectives:** To target a gap in the existing policy landscape and help them to cut their energy costs, by providing targeted cost-effective recommendations to improve their energy efficiency. It will stimulate demand amongst UK businesses for energy efficiency measures, by making clear in the assessments what savings could be made. The assessments will review the organisations’ entire energy consumption including buildings, industrial processes and transport activities (DECC, 2014c).

¹⁰¹ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2012:315:0001:0056:EN:PDF>

¹⁰² http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukxi/2014/1643/pdfs/ukxi_20141643_en.pdf

- d. Target groups:** ESOS applies to large UK undertakings (UK company that either employs 250 or more people, or has an annual turnover in excess of 50m euro, and an annual balance sheet total in excess of 43m euro; or an overseas company with a UK registered establishment which has 250 or more employees paying income tax to the UK) and their corporate groups. It mainly affects businesses but can also apply to not-for-profit bodies and any other non-public sector undertakings that are large enough to meet the qualification criteria. Corporate groups qualify if at least one UK group member meets the ESOS definition of a large undertaking (Environment Agency, 2015).
- e. Rules and influencing mechanisms:** The environmental regulator is responsible for compliance and enforcement activities. The regulator may issue civil sanctions including financial penalties (ranging from £5k-50k if an organisation does not meet the scheme's obligations (Environment Agency, 2015).
- f. Implementation network:** Overall, the Environment Agency is responsible for administering the scheme across the UK, and holding the UK register. A registered office or principal place of activity (in the absence of a registered office) determines the regulator, in terms of compliance and enforcement activities (Environment Agency, 2015):
- The Environment Agency (England)
 - Northern Ireland Environment Agency (Northern Ireland)
 - Scottish Environment Protection Agency (Scotland)
 - Natural Resources Wales (Wales)
 - DECC Offshore Oil & Gas Environment and Decommissioning (offshore).

In relation to undertaking an ESOS assessment, a corporate group demonstrates compliance using either:

- An ISO 50001 energy management system certified by an accredited certification body (United Kingdom Accreditation Service (UKAS) accredited, a body accredited by another EU member state's national accreditation body or a body accredited by a body which is a member of the International Accreditation Forum), and covers all their energy use (for the whole corporate group in the UK),
- Display Energy Certificates (DECs), which are defined by the Energy Performance of Buildings Regulations 2008 (Northern Ireland) and the Energy Performance of Buildings Regulations 2012 (as amended) (England and Wales). DECs form part of the implementation in England and Wales of the European Directives 2002/91/EC and 2010/31/EU on the energy performance of buildings. DECs are undertaken by qualified assessors.
- Green Deal Assessments (GDAs), can be part of an ESOS compliant energy assessment for the types of energy consumption they cover, if they qualify as per regulation 7 of the Green Deal Framework Regulations 2012¹⁰³
- ESOS compliant energy audits. All such energy audits must be reviewed by an ESOS lead assessor. An register of approved lead assessors is available online via the UK Government's ESOS webpage¹⁰⁴. An assessor can be an employee of the business, or a third party. The assessor is not held responsible for compliance by the regulators; therefore it is recommended that a member of the corporate group/organisation who understands the ESOS requirements, and works with the lead assessor to ensure the overall approach taken is compliant with ESOS.

The Environment Agency, and the other regulators do not provide standard templates for ESOS related data/activities and/or presentation of findings. Only the data to evidence that 90% of the total energy

¹⁰³ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2012/2079/contents/made>

¹⁰⁴ <https://www.gov.uk/guidance/energy-savings-opportunity-scheme-esos>

consumption is compliant via ESOS audits or other alternative routes to compliance, is required to be undertaken and recorded. This is to reduce the administrative burden on organisations that have existing data management procedures and tools.

- g. Outcomes:** (i) Assumptions suggest that ESOS could generate annual savings of around 3.0 TWh per year, of which 0.7TWh from transport (DECC, 2014b). Current analysis suggests that ESOS has the potential to deliver £1.9 billion of net benefits to the UK and reduce business energy bills by £300 million in its first year (DECC, 2014c). (ii) Best estimate total cost £1,178m (iii) The process of conducting the ESOS assessments themselves will provide employment for auditors and auditing companies. A range of other energy efficiency product and service businesses may also benefit from supporting large enterprises in implementing ESOS assessors' recommendations. The growth in the sector will help the supply side of the market mature, and enable the sector to promote the contribution it can make to a range of enterprises more effectively (DECC, 2014b).

2.4 (Ultra-) Low Carbon Emissions Zones (LEZ)

- a. General information:** The Low Carbon Emissions Zones started operating on 4 February 2008 with a phased introduction of an increasing stricter regime until 3 January 2012. Plans for an Ultra low emission zone, to be implemented in 2020, are under consideration.
- b. Type of policy instrument:** Regulatory: the primary purpose is to encourage the most polluting vehicles to become cleaner in order to reduce traffic pollution and improve air quality, health and quality of life of residents, workers and visitors in London.
- c. Objectives:** To reduce the tailpipe emissions of diesel-powered commercial vehicles in London
- d. Target groups:** Commercial companies that own diesel-powered vehicles (diesel lorries, buses, coaches, motor caravans, larger vans and minibuses)
- e. Rules and influencing mechanisms:** The low carbon emission zone operates 24 hours a day, every day of the year including weekends and public and bank holidays. Vehicles that do not conform to higher emission standards are charged a fee for driving within the specified zone which are marked by signs. The LEZ emission standards are based on European emission standards relating to particulate matter emitted by vehicles and which have an effect on health. The zone is monitored using Automatic Number Plate Reading Cameras (ANPR) to record vehicle number plates. These number plates are checked against the UK Driver and Vehicle Licensing Agency (DVLA) and Transport for London (TfL) pursues owners of vehicles for which the charge has not been paid. The daily charge is £100 per day for large vans and £200 for heavy vehicles. All non-GB vehicles that drive through the LEZ should be registered with TfL in order to avoid paying the charge if it meets the standards. The LEZ scheme is supported by the British Lung Foundation and the British Heart Foundation. For the Ultra-Low Emission Zone, stricter and high emission standards will be implemented, targeting more diesel vehicles as they produce relatively higher levels of particulates
- f. Implementation network:** Managed by Transport for London and administered by the TfL executive agency with the Greater London Authority.
- g. Outcomes:** Significant fleet turnover and vehicle use in London and a reduction vehicle use within the zone reduced. Air quality measurements for PM10 reduced between within the LEZ, improving air quality.

2.5. HGV Policies (low rolling resistance tyres and industry-led action to improve efficiencies)

- a. General information:** The government is committed to helping the freight industry cut cost and reduce greenhouse gas emissions as well as ensure safety in the movement of goods through effective regulation.
- b. Type of policy:** Regulatory policy: The main purpose is to help boost the economy through efficient movement of goods at a reasonable cost and with minimum impact on the environment and on communities.

- c. Objectives:** As well as reducing the environmental impact of the freight industry, one of the objective of the government policies relating to HGVs is to ensure that both foreign and UK hauliers make a contribution when using UK roads. Longer HGV semi-trailers have also been trialled in order to assess whether their use reduces greenghouse gas emissions. The Low Emission, Fuel Efficient HGV Task Force was also esblished with the objective of identifying and promoting measures to reduce emissions from HGVs.
- d. Target groups:** Hauliers, road users, local councils
- e. Rules and influencing mechanisms:** The Government's Department for Transport and Driver and Vehicle Standards Agency are responsible for delivering the HGV policies. The Department for Transport works with the Driver and Vehicle Licensing Agency (DVLA) to implement the HGV road user levy where HGVs of 12 tonnes and more are required to make a contribution to the wear and tear of the road network. Automatic number plate recognition cameras and other checks are used to alert the DVLA of unpaid vehicles. The Low Emission HGV Task Force set out a series of recommendations to support the early adoption of gas HGVs in the short term and inform on the development of medium and long term strategies for the role of methane in HGVs. DfT started the trial of longer semi-trailers in January 2011 to test its impact on efficiency, emissions and safety.
- f. Implementation network:** Overseen by the Department for Transport and different policies are administered by different agencies such as DVLA
- g. Outcomes:** reccommendations have been made from the findings of the task force to enable the uptake of low emission, fuel efficient HGVs (DfT, 2015b). The trail of the longer semi-trialers is expected to save 3,000 tonnes of CO2 over 10 years, benefits which are estimated at £33 million over the 10 year. The reduction in emissions is expected from the increased trailer capacity which should allow the same quantity of goods to be transported in fewer journeys. In the interim report published in 2014, the new estimate of 'journeys saved' (used as a proxy for carbon savings) was in the range of 1.2-1.4 million vehicle km. (DfT, 2015c)

3. Financial policy instruments

3.1 Cycle to Work Scheme (Green Transport Plan)

- a. General information:** To promote healthier journeys to work and to reduce environmental pollution, the 1999 Finance Act¹⁰⁵ introduced an annual tax exemption, which allows employers to loan cycles and cyclists' safety equipment to employees as a tax-free benefit. The exemption was one of a series of measures introduced under the Government's Green Transport Plan (DfT, 2011).
- b. Type of policy instrument:** Financial: tax-free benefit.
- c. Objectives:** The Cycle to Work tax efficient scheme is a part of a series of measures to promote healthier journeys to work and to reduce environmental pollution by making cycling more attractive.
- d. Target groups:** Employers of all sizes across the public, private and voluntary sectors can implement a tax exempt loan scheme for their employees.
- e. Rules and influencing mechanisms:** To qualify for the tax exemption, the cycles and cyclists' safety equipment loaned by the employer under the scheme must be available to employees generally with no groups of employees excluded. There is no limit on the total value of the equipment including the cycle, e.g. it is possible to loan two cycles to one employee. The tax exemption only applies when an employee mainly uses the cycle and cyclists' safety equipment for qualifying journeys. A qualifying journey for an employee means a journey, or part of a journey; between his or her home and workplace, or between one workplace and another, in connection with the performance of their duties of employment. So, for

¹⁰⁵ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/1999/16/contents>

example, cycling to and from the station to get to work would qualify. In this case, 'mainly' means that more than 50% of use of the cycle and safety equipment must involve a qualifying journey. Employees are not expected to keep mileage logs but employers should make clear to them that if they do not use the cycle mainly for qualifying journeys, they may lose the benefit of the tax exemption. In that event the employer would have to report the benefit in kind on form P11D, and account for Class 1A NICs, in the normal way. The employee would be liable for the tax due on the benefit in kind.

- f. Implementation network:** Scheme was first put forth by the DfT and is implemented by employers, under the guidance and regulation of HMRC, OFT/FCA and through approved cycle to work scheme providers. In addition, in order to gain the tax exemption, bicycles must be purchased through a retailer that is affiliated to a cycle to work scheme. The HMRC have published guidance and clarifications relating to the scheme; in 2010 the HMRC clarified that the bicycles needed to be sold at fair market value, to prevent the scheme becoming a tax loophole. Until March 2014, the scheme was regulated by the Office of Fair Trading (OFT; now no longer in existence), after which the Financial Conduct Agency (FCA) provided regulation relating to the Cycle to Work scheme as it regulates the consumer credit market, overall, and other regulated financial services activities. Within the FCA Handbook, PERG 2.11.3¹⁰⁶ outlines the specific exemption for Cycle to Work schemes. In terms of how the scheme is implemented in practice; *“Normally, hire payments are sacrificed from your employees' gross monthly salary, these payments are not subject to income tax and National Insurance Contributions (NICs). At the end of the hire period, as the employer, you may choose to give employees the option to purchase the equipment. If your employee chooses to purchase your bike the cycle to work scheme provider will put in place a transfer of ownership process based on a Market Value payment set by HMRC. The scheme operates under a group consumer credit licence, which has an upper limit of £1,000. This allows employees to obtain cycles and related cycling safety equipment up to the limit of £1,000 including VAT. The Office of Fair Trading has agreed to adjust the consumer credit licence limit of £1,000 per person in the event someone has a specific need such as a disability. A higher limit can be applied if an employer has a separate company specific consumer credit licence thereby enabling employees to obtain cycles and equipment for an amount above the £1,000 limit covered by the group licence.”* (Cycletoworkalliance.org.uk, 2015)
- g. Outcomes:** (i) Scheme users are cycling a total of 13.2m miles per week. 67% of participants would commute to work by car if they did not cycle to work. These commuters are saving 112,210 tonnes of CO2 per annum in reduced carbon emissions. (ii) No cost details available. (iii) Employees who participate in schemes run by Alliance members save up to 40% of the total cost of a new bike. To date over 550,000 people have taken advantage of the scheme, which involves over 2,220 bike retailers and 32,000 employers. There is a direct health benefit from the scheme, with 87% of participants noticing their health improving, 84% of users rating the scheme as an important and easy way to keep fit and 97% of businesses thinking the scheme is an important way to encourage a healthy workforce. The scheme plays an important role in helping new cyclists get started. 54% of people did not cycle to work before joining the scheme. Furthermore, 40% of those who classed themselves as novice cyclists before joining the scheme, now class themselves as enthusiast cyclists – demonstrating the role of the scheme in delivering behavioural change and driving cycling up-take (CtWA, n.d.).

3.2 Plug-in car and van grants (including Electric Vehicle Home charge Scheme)

- a. General information:** The Plug-In Car Grant¹⁰⁷ (PICG) and the Plug-in Van Grant¹⁰⁸ (PiVG) were launched in January 2011 and reduce the cost of plugin vehicles for consumers by cutting the cost of eligible vehicles

¹⁰⁶ <https://www.handbook.fca.org.uk/handbook/PERG/2/11.html>

¹⁰⁷ <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/plug-in-car-grant/plug-in-car-grant-eligibility-guidance>

by 25% up to £5,000 and 20% off the cost of a van, up to a maximum of £8,000. A consumer can get a grant towards the cost of each new electric (plug-in) car or van if it meets certain conditions (OLEV, 2011). The Home charge point grant is set as a 75% contribution to the cost of one charge point and its installation and the grant cap is set at £700 (including VAT) per eligible vehicle (OLEV, 2015a). The grants, offered by the UK Government, aim to encourage more consumers to purchase and drive ultra-low emission vehicles, as part of the UK's Carbon Plan 2011 and the framework and targets established in through the Climate Change Act 2008¹⁰⁹. The grants use EU Directives ((EC) 2007/46/EC) to specify eligible vehicles.

- b. Type of policy instrument:** Financial: grants.
- c. Objectives:** To encourage uptake of electric (plug-in) vehicles. Combined with tax benefits (such as VED and Company Car Tax exemptions) and selected local benefits, these measures aim to make ultra-low emission vehicles a more attractive proposition to consumers in terms of cost – one of the key barriers to the uptake of new technology (OLEV, 2011).
- d. Target groups:** Auto consumers
- e. Rules and influencing mechanisms:** A new vehicle is likely to be eligible if it is one of the following: electric vehicles (EVs) – these run completely on batteries and are plugged into the mains to be recharged plug-in hybrid electric vehicles (PHEVs) – these use a petrol or diesel engine combined with a battery that plugs into the mains hydrogen fuel cell vehicles and other technologies. Vehicles must emit less than 75 grams of carbon dioxide (CO₂) per kilometre driven. Electric vehicles must be able to travel a minimum of 70 miles between charges. Plug-in hybrid electric vehicles must have a minimum electric range of 10 miles. Vehicles must be able to reach a speed of 60 miles per hour or more (OLEV, 2011). Customers must provide evidence of keepership, lease, or be named as the primary user of an eligible electric vehicle in order to be able to qualify for the home charge grant (OLEV, 2015a).
- f. Implementation network:** DfT through OLEV supplies the grants. Auto dealerships will manage all paperwork with regard to the grants. It is a requirement of the Plug-In Car Grant that manufacturers of eligible vehicles set out how they will engage with purchasers to ensure safe recharging of their vehicles; and the Institution of Engineering and Technology, the standards body responsible for electrical safety, is producing a Code of Practice to advise electricians how to ensure safe plug-in vehicle recharging installations (OLEV, 2011).
- g. Outcomes:** (i) Energy impact data is not available. (ii) The Spending Review made provision of over £300m over the life of this Parliament for the Plug-In Car Grant to reduce the upfront cost of eligible vehicles to consumers and businesses (OLEV, 2011). (iii) A total of 9,046 ultra-low emission vehicles were registered in the first quarter of 2015 – a rise of 366% from the same period in 2014. As announced in the 2015 Summer Budget the government is investing £500 million over the next 5 years in making ULEVs more accessible to families and businesses across the country (DfT, 2015).

3.3 Low Emission Bus Scheme (LEBS) (successor scheme to the Green Bus Fund)

- a. General information:** The LEBS was announced by OLEV in 2015 as a low emissions vehicle impact for local areas. The scheme will be run as a competition, with £30m made available for local authorities and operators in England and Wales through a competitive bidding process for the purchase of low mission buses and the infrastructure to support them between April 2016 and March 2019. The scheme builds on the success of the Green Bus Fund which ran from 2009-2013 (OLEV, 2015b). The grants, offered by the UK

¹⁰⁸ <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/plug-in-van-grant/plug-in-van-grant-vehicles-list-and-eligibility-guidance>

¹⁰⁹ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2008/27/contents>

Government, aim to encourage more consumers to purchase and drive ultra-low emission vehicles, as part of the UK's Carbon Plan 2011 and the framework and targets established in through the Climate Change Act 2008¹¹⁰.

- b. **Type of policy instrument:** Financial: Central government funding for local authorities.
- c. **Objectives:** Increase the uptake of low and ultralow emission buses, speeding up the full transition to an ultralow emission bus fleet in England and Wales, and reducing the need for subsidy support; support the improvement of local air quality; and support OLEV's commitment of attracting investment to the UK (OLEV, 2015b).
- d. **Target groups:** Any English or Welsh local authority or bus operator can apply for funding.
- e. **Rules and influencing mechanisms:** The Department will contribute a maximum of 90% of the cost difference between the low emission bus and the standard diesel equivalent of the same total passenger capacity. Under the new testing procedure, in order to qualify as a LEB, a bus will need to: produce at least 15% less greenhouse gas emissions than the average conventional Euro V equivalent diesel bus of the same total passenger capacity; and meet or exceed Euro VI emissions regulations (OLEV, 2015b).
- f. **Implementation network:** This is an OLEV funded scheme which will be administered by the Department for Transport. The Office for Low Emission Vehicles (OLEV) is a cross Government, industry endorsed team combining policy and funding streams to simplify policy development and delivery for ultra low emission vehicles. OLEV currently comprises people and funding from the Departments for Transport (DfT), Business, Innovation and Skills (BIS), and Energy and Climate Change (DECC). Its core purpose is to support the early market for electric and other ultra low emission vehicles (ULEVs).
- g. **Outcomes:** (i) Energy impact data is not available. (ii) Total of £30m available in funds. (iii) The Green Bus Fund delivered around 1,250 low emission buses onto England's roads (OLEV, 2015b).

4. Dissemination and awareness instruments

4.1 Fuel Economy labels for cars

- a. **General information:** Regulations came into force on 21 November 2001¹¹¹. These regulations were further amended by Statutory Instrument 2013 No 65¹¹², which took effect 11 February 2013 (VCA, 2013).
- b. **Type of policy instrument:** Dissemination and awareness instruments: the primary purpose is to create more awareness with regard to emissions. / Regulatory: the labels are required for all vehicles.
- c. **Objectives:** To give consumers more information about the fuel consumption and CO2 emissions characteristics of new cars (VCA, 2013).
- d. **Target groups:** Dealers, suppliers and manufacturers of vehicles that are displayed for sale or lease.
- e. **Rules and influencing mechanisms:** The Regulations specify the Secretary of State as an enforcement authority (England, Wales and Scotland). The Vehicle Certification Agency (VCA) are officials of the Secretary of State for Transport and have responsibility for reviewing the content of promotional literature to ensure that the mandatory data is included and accurate. Local weights and measures authorities will enforce all other aspects of the regulations in England, Wales, and Scotland e.g. checking posters, labels, and availability of guidebooks. Since weights and measures authorities will be visiting dealers' premises to conduct their enforcement duties, they also have responsibility for checking that promotional literature available on site contains fuel consumption and CO2 data. However, if there are queries regarding the accuracy of the data in the literature, the matter should be referred to the VCA. As part of their

¹¹⁰ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2008/27/contents>

¹¹¹ <http://www.dft.gov.uk/vca/additional/files/fcb--co2/enforcement-on-advertising/vca061.pdf>

¹¹² http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2013/65/pdfs/uksiem_20130065_en.pdf

enforcement responsibility, weights and measures authorities have the authority to take action against dealers and suppliers if information is incorrect or not supplied to dealers. In Northern Ireland the Department of Enterprise, Trade and Investment will hold enforcement responsibility for all aspects of the Regulations. Enforcement action should be in the form of helping and encouraging dealers and manufacturers to comply with the requirements of the Regulations, and prosecutions only to be brought in cases of persistent non-compliance (VCA, 2013).

- f. **Implementation network:** Overseen by the Department for Transport, and administered by the VCA, with local weights and measures authorities enforcing all aspects of the regulations, except for the review of promotional literature content, which is the responsibility of the VCA.
- g. **Outcomes:** (i) Energy impact data is not available. (ii) No cost details available. (iii) No other impact details available.

4.2 The National Standard for cycle training

- a. **General information:** The National Standard for cycle training is built upon similar principles to training for motorcycle riders and car drivers, teaching the importance of assessing the likely risks faced by road users. Launched in 2005, the National Standard was developed by over 20 organisations and is maintained by the Department for Transport (DfT). There are three levels and a series of progressive outcomes within each level which can be used in training to take the complete beginner all the way to being able to ride on any road where cycling is permitted. In 2012, following consultation with stakeholders, the National Standard was revised and re-launched alongside a new quality assurance framework (DfT, 2015).
- b. **Type of policy instrument:** Dissemination and awareness instruments: the primary purpose of the scheme is to equip people with cycling skills.
- c. **Objectives:** The primary purpose of the National Standard is to get more people cycling, more often and with less risk. It helps break down some of the biggest barriers to cycling, opening up opportunities for people to get on their bikes and enabling cycling to become a normal everyday activity.
- d. **Target groups:** The National Standard for cycling is designed to encourage and empower people of all ages to make independent cycle journeys in a wide range of road conditions.
- e. **Rules and influencing mechanisms:** National Standard/Bikeability training may only be delivered by National Standard Instructors (NSIs), who have successfully completed a DfT recognised instructor training course. From 1 January 2011, instructor training organisations (ITOs) are the only bodies recognised by government as providers of training for National Standard instructor trainers, instructors and assistant instructors. All NSIs are issued with an NSI number. The National Standard instructor database contains a record of every instructor holding an NSI number.
- f. **Implementation network:** The DfT promotes the National Standard through the Bikeability award scheme in England. Any cycle training organisation wishing to use the Bikeability branding and issue the Bikeability award materials to trainees must first register a scheme. Bikeability is organised and delivered locally by registered bikeability providers. Scheme registration is part of a quality assurance process to help ensure organisations are delivering good practice cycle training. The NSI database is managed by Steer Davies Gleave on behalf of the Department for Transport.
- g. **Outcomes:** (i) Energy impact data is not available. (ii) No cost details available. (iii) Bikeability training addresses cycling safety concerns, equipping children with the necessary skills to respond to these dangers. Children who have taken part in the scheme feel safer and more confident when riding on the road (86%) and their parents feel more confident in allowing them to do so (87%). Children who have participated also feel more confident about riding their bike more often (87%) and, attested to by their parents, report an increased frequency in cycling having taken part in Bikeability (51% of children say they ride more having taken part in Bikeability and 49% of parents report an increase in the frequency with which their child rides). Participation also seems to encourage children to make new types of journeys using their bike, with children who have taken part more likely to cycle to get to places and more likely to say that they always or sometimes

cycle on the road than those who have not. In light of these positive outcomes, it is perhaps unsurprising that Bikeability training itself is rated very highly by both parents (97% say that they are very/quite satisfied with the training) and children (95% describe it as fairly/very good), and children who have taken part say that they would recommend it to friends (91%). Indeed, children who have not yet participated (and their parents) are keen that they should do so, indicating a high level of latent demand for the scheme (DfT, 2015).

4.3 Eco-driving training / FuelGood driver training

- a. **General information:** Eco-driving training as offered through the FuelGood driver training from Energy Saving Trust (EST) trains employees to be more fuel efficient. Training is free and is also offered for electricity vehicles (EST, 2014).
- b. **Type of policy instrument:** Dissemination and awareness instruments: the primary purpose of the scheme is to equip people with efficient driving skills.
- c. **Objectives:** To increase the efficiency of driving; reducing emissions.
- d. **Target groups:** Employees who drive for companies.
- e. **Rules and influencing mechanisms:** Mainly socio-economic influences and potential to 'up-skill'. No exemptions, penalties or sanctions.
- f. **Implementation network:** Delivered by the Energy Saving Trust (EST); training is delivered in 2-hour, one-to-one driving sessions.
- g. **Outcomes:** (i) Energy impact data is not available. (ii) No cost details available. (iii) Based on 8,700 miles per year, typical annual savings of up to £235 per car driver (more for van drivers) should all the tips given in the training be followed. Other expected benefits include: reduced wear and tear on tyres, brakes and clutches; reduced carbon footprint; and less accidents. Over 200 organisations have trained in the Energy Saving Trust's driver training programme including FTSE 100 companies Carillion and Mitie as well as 25 Scottish Local Authorities, five NHS Trusts and more than 10 universities and colleges. The training is projected to increase a driver's MPG by up to 15%, helping organisations save on fuel costs and carbon emissions. 15% is the average MPG improvement seen on the day of training. Studies suggest that a typical driver will maintain savings of 1-6%, or £20-£120, across the entire year.

5. Dissemination and awareness instruments

5.1 Research Councils Energy Programme (RCEP)

- a. **General information:** Led by the Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC), the Energy Programme brings together the work of EPSRC and that of the Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council (BBSRC), the Economic and Social Research Council (ESRC), the Natural Environment Research Council (NERC), and the Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC). The Energy Programme is investing more than £625 million in research and skills to pioneer a low carbon future. This builds on an investment of £839 million over the past eight years (RCUK, 2014).
- b. **Type of policy instrument:** Dissemination and awareness instrument: The research Councils Energy Programme focusses on R&D and prioritises dissemination of findings.
- c. **Objectives:** The Research Councils UK Energy Programme aims to position the UK to meet its energy and environmental targets and policy goals through world-class research and training. The objectives are to support a full spectrum of energy research to help the UK meet the objectives and targets set out in the 2007 Energy White Paper; to work in partnership to contribute to the research and postgraduate training needs of energy-related businesses and other key stakeholders; to increase the international visibility and level of international collaboration within the UK energy research portfolio; and to expand UK research capacity in energy-related areas (RCUK, 2014).
- d. **Target groups:** Academia, business, government.

- e. Rules and influencing mechanisms:** Priorities for the Energy Programme include continuing support for a broad research portfolio in power generation and supply and to grow the portfolio in demand reduction, transport, security of supply, research capacity building and international engagement. It includes investments in large research consortia, “whole-system” research, strategic partnerships with leading companies and support for the UK Energy Research Centre (UKERC), as well as support for fundamental science based energy research through investigator-led projects (HM Government, 2013).
- f. Implementation network:** RCEP is the largest public funder of the Energy Technologies Institute (ETI) – a public-private partnership of up to £1 billion to accelerate the deployment of new energy technologies. RCEP is also working with the Living with Environmental Change Programme (LWEC) to ensure a whole systems response to climate change (RCUK, 2014).
- g. Outcomes:** (i) Energy impact data is not available. (ii) Over the period 2011-15 expenditure under the Programme will exceed £540 million (HM Government, 2013). (iii) Funding has led to breakthroughs in hydrogen use for the future of car fuels and a second generation in biofuels (RCUK, 2014).

5.2 Technology Strategy Board (TSB) / Innovate UK

- a. General information:** The Technology Strategy Board was first established in 2004 as an advisory body within the former UK Department of Trade and Industry (DTI). As the primary channel through which the Government encourages innovation, the Technology Strategy Board (TSB), now called Innovate UK, is the UK’s innovation agency. Many of the priority areas Innovate UK focus on are also reflected in the ‘Eight Great Technologies’ identified by Science and Universities Minister David Willetts. One of Innovate UK’s main tools is collaborative R&D funding; running competitions in a broad range of growth creating areas, from transport to biosciences and from construction to nanoscale technologies. Innovate UK have developed Catalysts are run in partnership with the research councils, offering businesses and researchers a clear and progressive route for development, so that successful early-stage projects can easily find support for the next stage on their innovation journey; and Catapult centres: A Catapult is a technology and innovation centre where the very best of the UK’s businesses, scientists and engineers can work side by side on research and development – transforming ideas into new products and services to generate economic growth. Catapults add an important new dimension to complement our existing research and development programmes, helping businesses to adopt, develop and exploit innovative products and technologies. They offer concentrated expertise in areas such as manufacturing processes, test facilities, type approval and accreditation or supply chain development. Many provide access to cutting-edge equipment and specialist facilities to develop and test ideas in reality (TSB, 2014). Previous TSB projects funded include: Low carbon truck trial; Batteries for Low Carbon Vehicles: Recycling and Re-Use; Marine Vessel Efficiency (Innovate UK, 2015).
- b. Type of policy instrument:** Policy instruments for R&D and best available technologies (BAT) promotion
- c. Objectives:** The focus of Innovate UK is on innovation, working with business to stimulate and support innovation and accelerate economic growth
- d. Target groups:** Business and research
- e. Rules and influencing mechanisms:** The responsibilities of Innovate UK are to: provide new support for innovative small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) with high-growth potential; make sure that government initiatives such as SBRI (Small Business Research Initiative) attract innovative UK businesses and give companies access to important customers in the public sector; identify and invest in the sectors that have the greatest potential for innovation to speed up economic growth; and help innovative companies work with their backers so their ideas can be developed commercially
- f. Implementation network:** Innovate UK is an executive non-departmental public body, sponsored by the Department for Business, Innovation & Skills. Innovate UK’s responsibilities are to:
- determine which science and technology developments will drive future economic growth

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • meet UK innovators with great ideas in the fields we're focused on • fund the strongest opportunities • connect innovators with the right partners they need to succeed • help our innovators launch, build and grow successful businesses <p>g. Outcomes: (i) Energy impact data is not available. (ii) Gross grant expenditure for transport sector 2012-2013: £23.3m; 2013-2014: £30.8m (iii) Aside from job creation as a result of funding Innovate UK has increased full-time employment from 196 to 257 employees from 2013-2014. Millions of £ invested in R&D resulting in numerous outcomes directly befitting business and the public.</p>

Table 4 Horizontal policy measures

Horizontal policy measure	Buildings	Transport	Industry/ energy supply	Ag, forestry & land mgmt.	Waste
Energy Saving Opportunity Scheme: targeted cost-effective recommendations to improve energy efficiency. The assessments review the organisations' entire energy consumption including buildings, industrial processes and transport activities (DECC, 2014c).	ü	ü	ü		
Green Investment Bank: The UK Green Investment Bank was created by the UK Government, which has committed to provide £3.8bn of capital to invest. GIB uses this to back green projects, on commercial terms, across the UK and mobilise other private sector capital into the UK's green economy (DECC, 2014c).	ü	ü	ü		ü
Sustainable procurement: the Government Buying Standards (GBS): All central government departments and their related organisations must ensure that they meet the GBS when buying goods and services for those product groups covered. The mandatory standards are encouraged for the wider public sector to specify in tenders (DEFRA, 2012).	ü	ü	ü	ü	ü
Sustainable Operations on the Government Estate (SOGE) (2009-2011) / Greening Government Commitments (2011 –): targets on sustainable operations, mandated mechanisms, and sustainable procurement (DECC, 2011b).	ü	ü			ü
Renewable Transport Fuel Obligation: The Renewable Transport Fuel Obligation (RTFO) supports the government's policy on reducing greenhouse gas emissions from vehicles by encouraging the production of biofuels that don't damage the environment (DfT, 2012)		ü	ü	ü	
Energy Saving Trust: advice on energy saving in buildings and transport	ü	ü			
Technology Strategy Board / Innovation UK: One of Innovate UK's main tools is collaborative R&D funding; running competitions in a broad range of growth creating areas, from transport to biosciences and from construction to nanoscale technologies (Entranze, 2013).	ü	ü	ü		ü

1.3 CONCLUSIONS AND LESSONS LEARNED OF OTHER PROJECTS ABOUT THE PERFORMANCE OF THE NATIONAL POLICY PACKAGES FOR ENERGY EFFICIENCY

Energy Efficiency Watch:

The Energy Efficiency Watch (EEW) (Energy Efficiency Watch, 2013) assessed the UK as *comparatively ambitious* with its EE strategy. However, a majority of domestic experts assess the progress made by the UK from 2010-13 as low to moderate. 60% of the experts believe that only a few additional policies have been set up. The experts were divided with half considering the UK's ambition to be *rather low* and the other half considering it *relatively high*. 49% of the experts expect that national energy savings targets will not be achieved.

The UK has successfully established a good public sector policy framework that can serve as a good practice example. This includes clear rules and standards for public procurement, good activities to establish a role model and good programmes for public buildings. The **building sector** showed mixed results. Demonstration projects and education & training measures were found to be lacking. Critical issues raised by the survey of experts include ageing housing stock with low renovation rates and lack of awareness raising activities for households and SMEs.

Recommendations include:

- Though the residential sector is believed to hold the largest potential for improvement, the Green Deal was seen as a failure risk and experts were uncertain of the actual impact.
- As the UK's EE policy for appliances is largely based on EU legislation, the UK should complement current legislation with stronger incentives, education and training measures.
- Suggestion to impose 40% reduction in capital funding to universities that do not develop a carbon management plan and make reductions.
- Establish carbon reduction commitments for large energy-intensive organisations not covered by EU emission trading system.

ODYSSEE-MURE:

ODYSSEE-MURE's analysis (Odyssee-Mure, 2012) shows that in the **domestic sector** household EE has improved by around 23% over the period 1990-2010. Most of this improvement was however seen in the early 1990s, though overall efficiency has again increased gradually since 2005 due to continued efficiency improvements for space heating. Recent improvement in insulation and heating efficiency has been offset by an increase in electrical appliances per household; consumption for large electrical appliances continued to increase since 2004 due to an increase in TV appliances per household. Climate corrected fuel consumption per dwelling has also risen by approximately 8% over the period. Exemplary policy measure plans included the Green Deal (no longer in place, 2015) with ECO and the planned roll-out of Smart Meters, and Government confirmation for all new homes to be zero carbon from 2016 (no longer in place, 2015).

In the **transport sector** EE has improved steadily by 23% over the period from 1990-2008. This improvement is due to gradual improvement in car efficiency which dominates consumer transport energy in the UK. Some improvement in car and air transport has been counterbalanced by a

decrease in road freight efficiency. Exemplary policy measures included Government support for market growth for ultra-low emission vehicles (including technologies such as electric batteries, hydrogen fuel cells and plug-in hybrid technology), providing £300 million in consumer incentives and the Renewable Transport Fuel Obligation (RTFO) obligates fossil fuel suppliers to produce evidence that a percentage of fuels for road transport supplied in the UK come from renewable sources and are sustainable.

Entranze:

According to the Entranze (Entranze, 2013) policy analysis, the UK has a strong focus on carbon neutral rather than nearly zero energy buildings (nZEB). It was also explained that there was no official plan and the necessary provisions for gradually tightening of buildings requirements. The UK (and Belgium) was found to have the greatest number of financial instruments in place in 2010-2011. There is little subjective analysis on the UK in the Entranze project as the UK was not a 'target country' for the Entranze project.

Request 2 Action:

The UK pilot project identified new ways to deliver face to face advice in a highly cost effective manner where pilot builders were trained on low carbon theory and practices, and given additional technical guidance (in the form of a brochure) on how to incorporate energy efficiency into typical renovation projects. A version of the information brochure was also provided for their customers. Everything was backed by an impartial and trusted organisation (EST). The project proved to be effective at equipping builders to convince their clients to incorporate low carbon measures into their renovation plans.

IEA:

According to a review by the IEA, from 2006-2012 the UK's strategy to move to a low carbon economy and tackle climate change has a remarkable sense of coherence, commitment and communication (IEA, 2012). A part of the UK's strategy includes ambitious legislative and operational frameworks including: the Climate Change Act, carbon budgets and a Carbon Plan. The government has demonstrated a high level of willingness to take action and was willing to propose new market-based regulations that are adapted to a changing context where security of supply and transition to a low carbon energy future play a major role. **Transport sector** EE is mainly promoted through the need to reduce GHG emissions. Indirect reduction is implemented through transport fuel taxes which are comparatively high by international standards.

It was recommended that:

- From 2012 to 2015, more work would need to be done to re-establish trust in energy markets, drive demand (through awareness campaigns) for Green Deal (**building sector**) energy efficiency measures and encourage active engagement with smart meters.
- The government strengthen the coordinating role of DECC with other government departments such as the DfT.
- Empower local governments and communities to effectively find innovative solutions to local energy challenges.

- Pay close attention to cost-effectiveness of relevant policies in the **transport sector**.

Concerted Action Energy Efficiency Directive (CA EED):

The Concerted Action for the Energy Efficiency was launched in order to support the effective implementation of the Directive on Energy Efficiency in all EU member states. According to the EED implementation in the UK report published in 2014, the Directive will be implemented on a UK-wide basis. The UK is currently in the process of implementing the Directive through the transposition of the requirements into the UK law and where additional action is needed to meet the requirements of the Directive, consultation is underway with stakeholders on relevant options and provisions (ca-eed, 2014).

<http://www.esd-ca.eu/>

MOSIAC – Mobility Management Applications in the Community

The MOSIAC project was funded by the European Commission Transport Directorate and had three main objectives: to improve the understanding of mobility management, to demonstrate mobility management concepts in different countries and to disseminate the findings to help in the development of effective mobility management strategies. In the UK, it was concluded that current UK transport policy aims to improve the integration of different transport modes and encourage people to use alternatives to cars. However, for mobility centres to be introduced, a re-regulation of the UK public transport will be required. Another major barrier to expanding on the few existing centres into a more comprehensive mobility centre would funding for set up and other aspects such as gathering information on transport services. An alternative approach which is being tried in the UK is 'virtual' mobility centres which provide information on various different services through the internet. This could offer an opportunity for introducing physical, more accessible mobility centres.

<http://www.transport-research.info/Upload/Documents/200310/mosaic.pdf2>:

CHAPTER 2: INTERACTION BETWEEN THE NATIONAL AND THE SUB-NATIONAL LEVELS

The UK consists of four countries: England, Scotland, Wales and Northern Ireland. 'UK policy' always refers to England. In Scotland and Wales, the encouragement of energy efficiency is devolved, while the regulation of energy efficiency is reserved, and the promotion and regulation of energy efficiency is devolved to Northern Ireland. Scotland, Wales and Northern Ireland have a separate fuel poverty strategy and fuel poverty programmes (DECC, 2012a). DECC is, in partnership with the Devolved Administrations (Scotland, Wales and Northern Ireland), the government policy lead. The Environment Agency is the UK Scheme Administrator and responsible for auditing and enforcement of the scheme in England. The devolved administrations' regulators, the Scottish Environment Protection Agency (SEPA), Natural Resources Wales (NRW) and Northern Ireland Environment Agency (NIEA), are responsible for auditing and enforcement in their countries. The UK Treasury (HMT) is responsible for setting the allowance price for the scheme (HM Government, 2013).

Northern Ireland

Northern Ireland's (NI) Strategic Energy Framework (2010), sets out the NI Executive's vision for sustainable energy, including contribute to the UK's energy saving target set by Article 7 of the Energy Efficiency Directive. **The Green Deal and ECO do not cover Northern Ireland.** The Northern Ireland Government is examining the possibility of an energy efficiency supplier obligation from 2016. A Green Deal-style loan and grant support mechanism for energy efficiency improvements, the Household Efficiency and Thermal improvement Programme (HEaT), has been piloted.

Policies distinct from those in the rest of the UK include the Warm Homes Scheme supporting EE improvements for fuel poor private sector households, the Northern Ireland Sustainable Energy Programme (NISEP) provides grant funding for energy efficiency and renewable energy schemes for both domestic and non-domestic buildings and the Northern Ireland Renewable Heat Incentive (RHI) provides financial support to non-domestic renewable heat generators and producers of bio methane. A Renewable Heat Premium Payment is available for the domestic market.

Scotland

In addition to UK Government goals, the Scottish Government aims to reduce final energy consumption across all sectors by 12% in 2020 against a baseline averaged over the years 2005 – 2007. This target was set out in the Energy Efficiency Action Plan for Scotland (EEAP) in October 2010 and sits alongside and supports the government's GHG emissions reduction targets. Scotland is on track to meet this target with a 6.2% fall by 2010 against the baseline.

Building regulations are devolved across the four UK administrations. Regulations in Scotland are broadly comparable to those elsewhere in the UK in content, scope and in the levels of improvement delivered over the past decades. Since 2007, reviews of energy standards in Scotland have been informed by the recommendations of the Sullivan Report Panel. The panel met in 2013 and made recommendations for post 2015 regulations which are being considered by Scottish Ministers. Directive 2010/31/EU, the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD), applies to the UK as a Member State but is implemented in Scotland by the Scottish Government, with transposition of the Articles of the Directive achieving the same effect as in the rest of the UK.

The Scottish Sustainable Housing Strategy (2013) sets out the route map and vision to 2030 for high-quality, affordable, warm, low-carbon homes. It includes current policies and proposals for future action under four headings: Home Energy Efficiency Programmes for Scotland (HEEPS); the role of Standards; New Build Market Transformation; and Financial Market Transformation. The role of

HEEPS is to maximise opportunities to effectively insulate homes, to help leverage additional funding through the ECO, and to take on the challenge of tackling hard to treat homes which require, for example, solid wall insulation. This programme has shifted the focus to area-based schemes to tackle fuel poverty along with national schemes to provide for the most vulnerable households (DECC, 2014c)

In Scotland and Wales 10% more government funding is available per domestic electricity consumer to improve domestic EE than England (Read, 2014).

Wales

The Welsh Government's Climate Change Strategy (2010) set a 3% per annum target reduction in GHG emissions in areas of devolved competency, leading to a total reduction of 40% in GHG emissions by 2020 against a 1990 baseline. The strategy specified target emissions reduction 'ranges' for each sector to which the target applied (transport, domestic, business, agriculture, public sector and waste). Building regulations were devolved in 2011, enabling the Welsh Government to consult on and amend Part L. These amendments set a higher level of energy performance for new and existing buildings from 2014, with a review in 2016. **This continues a pre-devolution policy trend which set more stringent buildings regulations for energy performance in Wales than those in England or Scotland.**

The Welsh Government has introduced a suite of policies and programmes to meet these targets, notably the National Energy Efficiency and Savings Plan (2011) and the Fuel Poverty Strategy (2010). The policy focus of the Welsh Government is primarily on expenditure on retrofit programmes to address fuel poverty, enhanced planning policy/building regulations and support for the supply chain. Its programme includes Nest, a fuel poverty programme that provides energy efficiency advice and income maximisation advice, alongside installation of 'whole house' measures. Alongside Nest, Arbed is the area-based 'whole house' retrofit programme, with Arbed Phase 2 retrofitting over 4,500 homes across Wales in 2012-15. The Welsh Government has also made available an additional £80m to leverage investment from the ECO (DECC, 2014c).

Municipalities

There are a total of 33 local authorities in the UK (8%) with Sustainable Energy Action Plans with the Covenant of Mayors (29 in England, 3 in Scotland, 1 in Wales) (CoM, 2015;HM Government, 2013).

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